

**Electrochemical processes of bio-analytical
importance at micro- and nano-liquid | liquid
interfaces**

by

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Declaration

Micheál D. Scanlon declares that this is his own work, fulfilling the requirements of the Doctor of Philosophy degree, PhD. This work was based on research carried out in the Tyndall National Institute (Molecular Microsystems Group), University College Cork, between October 2005 and May 2009.

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Dr. Damien W. M. Arrigan, supervisor

**To the memory of my mother, Ann, and to my
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Glossary of major symbols

Subscripts

Symbol	Meaning	Symbol	Meaning
<i>a</i>	(a) anodic (b) array	<i>i</i>	initial
<i>bg</i>	background subtracted	λ	switching time in cyclic voltammetry
<i>c</i>	(a) cathodic (b) charging	lim	limiting
<i>D</i>	disc	O	denotes species O in $O + ne^- \rightleftharpoons R$
<i>d</i>	diffusion	o	organic phase
<i>dl</i>	double-layer	<i>P</i>	(a) peak (b) pores
<i>eq</i>	equilibrium	R	denotes species R in $O + ne^- \rightleftharpoons R$
<i>f</i>	(a) faradaic (b) forward (c) final	<i>r</i>	reverse
		<i>sub</i>	subtractive background subtraction
		<i>ss</i>	steady-state
		w	aqueous phase

Units

Symbol	Meaning	Symbol	meaning
A	Ampere	mM	Millimolar
Å	Angstrom	min	Minute
C	(a) Celsius (b) Coulomb	mol	Mole
cm	Centimetre	μA	Microamp
dm	Decimetre	μM	Micromolar
F	Farad	μm	Micrometer
J	Joule	nA	Nanoamp
K	Kelvin	nM	Nanomolar
L	Litre	nm	Nanometre
M	Molar	Ω	Ohm
mA	Milliamp	S	Siemens
mL	Millilitre	s	Second
		V	Volt

Roman symbols

Symbol	Meaning	Usual units
A	area	cm^2
a_j^α	activity of substance j in a phase α	none
C	capacitance	F
C_{dl}	differential capacitance of the double layer	F, F cm^{-2}
C_j	concentration of species j	M, mol cm^{-3}
C_j^*	bulk concentration of species j	M, mol cm^{-3}
$C_j(x=0)$	concentration of species j at the electrode surface	M, mol cm^{-3}
C_p	circumference of a circular electrode or pore	cm
$\frac{\partial C_j(x,t)}{\partial x}$	concentration gradient of species j at a distance x from the electrode at time t	none
D_j	diffusion coefficient of species j	$\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
d	dimensionless depth of the liquid-liquid interface in a μ - or nanoITIES	none
E	potential of an electrode versus a reference	V
E^0	standard potential of an electrode or a redox couple	V
$E^{0'}$	formal potential of an electrode	V
E_{eq}	equilibrium potential of an electrode	V
$E_{p,w \rightarrow o}$	peak potential for ion transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase (usually the forward sweep in cyclic voltammetry)	V

$E_{p,o \rightarrow w}$	peak potential for ion transfer from the organic to the aqueous phase (usually the reverse sweep in cyclic voltammetry)	V
$E^{1/2}$	measured or expected half-wave potential in voltammetry	V
ΔE_j	peak-to-peak separation of the forward and reverse peaks on a cyclic voltammogram for species j	V
e	elementary charge	C
F	the Faraday constant, charge on one mole of electrons	C
$\Delta G_{transfer,j}^{o,\alpha \rightarrow \beta}$	standard Gibbs free energy of transfer for species j from phase α into phase β	kJ mol ⁻¹
I_c	ionic strength	mol dm ⁻³
i	current	A
i_c	charging (or non-faradaic) current	A
i_d	diffusion limited current	A
i_f	faradaic current	A
i_{lim}	limiting current	A
$i_{p,w \rightarrow o}$	peak current for ion transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase (usually the forward sweep in cyclic voltammetry)	A
$i_{p,o \rightarrow w}$	peak current for ion transfer from the organic to the aqueous phase (usually the reverse sweep in cyclic voltammetry)	A
i_{ss}	steady-state current	A
J	current density	A cm ⁻²
$J_j(x,t)$	flux of a species j at location x at time t	mol cm ⁻² s ⁻¹
k^o	standard heterogeneous rate constant	cm s ⁻¹
k_B	Boltzmann's constant	J K ⁻¹
L	recess depth of a microelectrode or the recessed depth of a liquid-liquid interface in a μ - or nano-ITIES from the aqueous side	cm
l	membrane or pore depth	cm
N	number of analytical measurements taken within the dynamic range of a calibration plot	none
N_A	Avagadro's constant	mol ⁻¹
N_j	total number of moles of species j in a system	mol
N_p	total number of pores in an array	none
n	stoichiometric number of electrons involved in an electrode reaction	none
O	oxidised form of the standard system $O + ne^- \rightleftharpoons R$; often used as a subscript to denote a quantity associated to species O	none

Q	charge	C
q^j	excess surface charge on phase j	C
R	(a) reduced form of the standard system $O + ne^- \rightleftharpoons R$; often used as a subscript to denote a quantity associated to species R	none
	(b) correlation coefficient	none
R	gas constant	$J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$
R_a	array resistance	Ω
R_p	pore resistance	Ω
r_a	electrode or pore radius	cm
r_c	electrode or pore centre-centre separation	cm
r_r	distance between two consecutive rows of electrodes or pores in an hexagonally close packed array	cm
S_j^α	the solubility of a species j in a phase α	none
T	absolute temperature	K
t	time	s
V_{av}	volumetric flow rate	$mL min^{-1}$
$v(x)$	linear velocity of solution flow, as a function of the x-axis	$cm s^{-1}$
x	distance, often from a planar electrode	cm
x_1	distance of the IHP from the electrode surface	cm
x_2	distance of the OHP from the electrode surface	cm
z_j	charge on species j in signed units of electronic charge	none

Greek symbols

Symbol	Meaning	Usual units
α	denotes the aqueous phase of a liquid-liquid electrochemical setup	none
β	denotes the organic phase of a liquid-liquid electrochemical setup	none
δ	(a) diffusion zone extension around an electrode that exhibits spherical diffusion (b) “diffusion” layer thickness for species j at an electrode fed by convective transfer	none
δ_N	Nernst diffusion layer thickness	none
δ_H	hydrodynamic boundary layer thickness	none
ϵ_o	dielectric constant of free space	$F m^{-1}$
ϵ_r	relative dielectric constant of a solvent	none
γ_j^α	activity coefficient for species j in phase α	none

η	overpotential, $E - E_{eq}$	V
κ	conductivity of a solution	S cm^{-1} or $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
λ_D	Debye length of an electrolyte solution	cm
$\bar{\mu}_j^{-\alpha}$	electrochemical potential of species j in phase α	kJ mol^{-1}
μ_j^α	chemical potential of species j in phase α	kJ mol^{-1}
$\mu_j^{\alpha,o}$	standard chemical potential of species j in phase α	kJ mol^{-1}
ν	scan rate of a voltammetric scan	V s^{-1}
ϕ^j	absolute electrostatic (Galvani or inner) potential of phase j	V
ϕ_1	Galvani potential at the IHP with respect to the bulk solution	V
ϕ_2	Galvani potential at the OHP with respect to the bulk solution	V
$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$	Galvani interfacial potential difference at a liquid-liquid interface	V
$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^o$	standard Galvani potential of ion transfer for species j from phase α to phase β	V
$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$	formal Galvani potential of ion transfer for species j from phase α to phase β	V
$\frac{\partial\phi(x)}{\partial x}$	potential gradient	none
∇	Laplacian operator	none
∞	an infinitely large distance from a planar electrode	cm

Standard abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACT	aqueous complexation followed by transfer
ALD	atomic layer deposition
BS	background subtraction
CV	cyclic voltammetry
CVD	chemical vapour deposition
DI	de-ionised
DPV	differential pulse voltammetry
DRIE	deep reactive ion etching
e-beam	electron beam
EDL	electrical double layer
ET	electron transfer
FESEM	field emission scanning electron microscopy
FIA	flow injection analysis
FIB	focussed ion beam

FIT	facilitated ion transfer
HCP	hexagonally close packed
HDV	hydrodynamic voltammetry
HOMO	highest occupied molecular orbital
ICP	inductively coupled plasma
IHP	inner Helmholtz plane
IT	ion transfer
IPE	ideally polarisable electrode
ITIES	interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions
LOD	limit of detection
LPCVD	low pressure chemical vapour deposition
LSV	linear sweep voltammetry
LUMO	lowest unoccupied molecular orbital
MVN	modified Verwey-Niessen
OCP	open circuit potential
OHP	outer Helmholtz plane
PECVD	plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition
pI	isoelectric point
RSD	relative standard deviation
SCE	saturated calomel electrode
SECM	scanning electrochemical microscopy
SEM	scanning electron microscopy
SV	stripping voltammetry
STEM	scanning transmission electron microscopy
TEM	transmission electron microscopy
TIC	transfer by interfacial complexation
TID	transfer by interfacial dissociation
TOC	transfer followed by organic complexation
UV	ultra-violet

Chemical abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
(BTPPA)(Cl)	bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene) chloride
DAB-AM-4	polypropyleneimine tetraamine dendrimer
DB18C6	dibenzo-18-crown-6 ether
1,2-DCE	1,2-dichloroethane
1,4-DCB	1,4-dichlorobutane
1,6-DCH	1,6-dichlorohexane
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
ETH-500	commercial trade name of tetradodecylammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate
FNDPE	2-fluorophenyl 2-nitrophenylether
HEWL	hen-egg-white lysozyme
PEEK TM	polyetheretherketone
PTFE	poly(tetrafluoroethylene) or Teflon
PVC	poly(vinyl chloride)
(K)(TPB)	potassium tetraphenylborate
(K)(TFPB)	potassium tetrakis(4-fluorophenyl)borate

(K)(TPBCl)	potassium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate
(Na)(4-OBSA)	sodium 4-ocylbenzenesulfonate
NB	nitrobenzene
o-NPOE	o-nitrophenyl octyl ether
(TBA)(Cl)	tetrabutylammonium chloride
(TEA)(Cl)	tetraethylammonium chloride
(TOA)(Cl)	tetraocylamminum chloride
TTCD	1,4,7,10-tetrathiacyclododecane

Abstract

The work presented herein describes the voltammetric characterisation of arrays of miniaturised (either to the micro- or nano-scale) interfaces between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES), by ion transfer (IT) electrochemistry of the model tetraethylammonium cation (TEA^+) via cyclic voltammetry, and the use of macro- and micro-scale ITIES as a novel approach to study the behaviour of, and improve the analytical sensitivity to, analytes of biological importance.

The organic phase was gellified with poly (vinyl chloride) to increase the mechanical stability of the μITIES arrays (confined within 100 μm deep silicon pores). IT of TEA^+ revealed the liquid-organogel interface as essentially inlaid on the aqueous side of the micropore channel, the TEA^+ diffusion coefficient reduced 9-fold in the organogel, and only μITIES array designs with sufficiently large pore-to-pore separations achieved steady-state behaviour. The μITIES arrays were characterised

with TEA⁺ under hydrodynamic conditions and hydrodynamic voltammograms created for a mixture of oligopeptides. Using an organogel allowed implementation of voltammetric stripping techniques at the μ ITIES arrays greatly improving the detection limits and sensitivities for a selection of oligopeptides compared with those attained at the macroITIES.

The first reported use of geometrically regular solid-state nanopore arrays, fabricated in 100 nm thick Si₃N₄ membranes, to support nanoscale ITIES is presented. IT of TEA⁺ for a variety of nanoITIES array designs (in terms of pore radii, pore-to-pore separation, and array pore numbers) is outlined. The results suggest that nanoITIES arrays exhibiting overlapping diffusion zones behave as one μ ITIES.

The electrochemical response of hen-egg-white lysozyme at the macroITIES was dominated by the charge of lysozyme in the aqueous phase and the nature of the organic phase anion. It is proposed that lysozyme does not transfer across the ITIES itself but absorbs on the aqueous side of the ITIES facilitating the transfer of the organic anion.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 The fundamental concepts of electrochemistry

1.1.1 Electrochemical systems

Electrochemistry is a specific branch of chemistry that can be divided into two types: (a) the chemistry of ionic conducting solutions and (b) the chemistry of electrically charged interfaces. Both types are strongly connected.¹

1.1.2 Solid-electrode electrochemistry

Solid-electrode electrochemistry is a heterogeneous chemical process that entails electron transfer between a conductor or semiconductor (the electrode) and an electro-active chemical species in solution.²⁻⁴

1.1.3 Electron transfer

Electron transfer causes oxidation and reduction to occur at the electrode surface. Oxidation is an anodic process involving the loss of electrons from the chemical species in solution to the electrode (Equation 1.1.1) and reduction is a cathodic process where the species gains electrons from the electrode (Equation 1.1.2).

These reactions at the electrodes are driven on application of a voltage (or potential) (volt, V). A volt is defined as the energy (joule, J) required to move charge (coulomb, C). Since electrons possess charge, if a voltage is applied to the electrode the “energy” of the electrons within the metal will be altered. To understand the behaviour of electrons in an electrode we need to introduce the concept of the *Fermi-level*. A metal consists of tightly packed atoms with extensively overlapping atomic orbitals. As a result a piece of metal possesses a continuum of levels, as distinct from individual well defined electron energy levels found in a single atom of the same material. Electrons fill these levels from the bottom up and the Fermi-level corresponds to the energy at which the “top” electrons sit.³

The Fermi-level is raised in the metal by applying a more negative potential to the electrode than that of zero current. If these electrons are promoted to a level higher in energy relative to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) of the electroactive species then they may transfer into this vacant electronic orbital. Current now flows from the electrode to the solution and reduction takes place (see Figure 1.1.1(B)). Correspondingly, decreasing the energy of the Fermi level relative to the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) of the electrolyte species, by applying a

more positive potential to the electrode, results in current flowing from the species at the electrode-solution interface to the electrode and oxidation takes place (see Figure 1.1.1(C)). By convention,⁵ a current generated by an anodic process (oxidation) is designated as a positive quantity or by a cathodic process (reduction) a negative quantity.

Figure 1.1.1: Schematic of electron transfer during an electrochemical process at the electrode-solution interface. **(A)** Situation where no electron transfer is possible, **(B)** reduction of electrolyte species and **(C)** oxidation of electrolyte species. LUMO: lowest unoccupied molecular orbital. HOMO: highest occupied molecular orbital.

The potential of the working electrode (where the electron transfer takes place, see section 2.1.2) is observed with respect to a reference electrode (an electrode of constant composition with fixed potential, see section 2.1.4). The critical potentials at which the reduction and oxidation processes occur in Figure 1.1.1 are related to the standard potentials, E° , for the specific redox couple under study. If we consider the cathodic reaction, an applied potential more negative than E° for the redox couple $O + ne^- \rightarrow R$ leads to reduction, as observed in Figure 1.1.1(B). The kinetics of electron transfer are dependent on the standard heterogenous rate constant, k° .^{3, 4, 6} A system with a large k° value will achieve equilibrium swiftly; whereas, a system with a small k° will be sluggish. In the instance where k° is swift both on the forward and reverse reactions the concentrations of O and R at the electrode surface, $C_o(x=0)$ and

$C_R(x=0)$, respectively, are assumed to be at equilibrium from a thermodynamic point of view. For the half reaction $O + ne^- \rightarrow R$ the equilibrium electrode potential (E_{eq}) is governed by the *Nernst equation* under these conditions,^{3, 4, 6} as detailed in Equation 1.1.3.

$$E_{eq} = E^{o'} + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{C_O(x=0)}{C_R(x=0)} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.3})$$

Where $E^{o'}$ is the formal potential of the redox couple (V), R is the molar gas constant ($8.314 \text{ JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$), T is the Kelvin temperature, n is the number of electrons transferred in the reaction, and F is the Faraday constant ($96,487 \text{ C}$).

1.1.4 Faradaic and non-faradaic processes

Reduction-oxidation reactions are known as *faradaic processes* since they are governed by Faraday's law.^{3, 4, 6} This law states that the amount of chemical change (i.e. the number of moles of species O that undergo reduction) is proportional to the quantity of electricity passed (i.e. the total charge, Q , consumed in the process). The relationship is summarised in Equation 1.1.4.

$$Q = \int_0^t i dt = nN_j F \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.4})$$

where Q is the charge (coulombs, C), i is the faradaic current (amperes, A) and N_j is the number of moles (mol) of species j in the system.

The presence of an electrode in solution, and the resulting electrode-solution interface, inevitably disrupts the electrolyte solution since metal-electrolyte interactions are considerably different from those in solution. In addition, the electrode is held under potentiostatic control causing charge to build up at the interface. The resultant interactions that occur between ions or molecules in solution and the electrode

surface, leading to an accumulation of charges and dipole charges at the interface, are known as *non-faradaic processes*, examples being adsorption and desorption. The structure formed in this process is known as the *electrical double layer*.^{2-4, 6}

1.1.5 Polarisable and non-polarisable electrodes

When an electrode departs from its equilibrium potential (E_{eq} , defined in Equation 1.1.3) upon the passage of a faradaic current this process is termed *polarisation*. The magnitude of polarisation is measured as the *overpotential*, η .

$$\eta = E - E_{eq} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.5})$$

An *ideally polarisable electrode* (IPE) will in theory allow no-charge transfer across the solid electrode-solution interface, regardless of the extent of an applied voltage by an external element. This type of electrode will show a very large change in potential on application of an infinitesimal current. As illustrated in Figure 1.1.2(A), the IPE is characterised by a horizontal region of an i - E curve. Alternatively an *ideally non-polarisable electrode* is one whose potential does not change on passage of a current, in essence this electrode is of a fixed potential and characterised by a vertical region on the i - E curve, see Figure 1.1.2(B).³

Figure 1.1.2: Current-potential behaviour of **(A)** an ideally polarisable electrode and **(B)** an ideally non-polarisable electrode. The dashed lines represent the behaviour of electrode-solution systems that approach ideal situations.

1.1.6 The electrical double layer

When an electrode reaction takes place both faradaic and non-faradaic processes occur simultaneously. Thus, in order to study faradaic processes, any contributions to the electrochemical data by non-faradaic processes need to be taken into consideration and an in-depth knowledge of the electrical double layer is required. The concept of the electrical double layer was first introduced by Helmholtz and has been modified and improved consistently since, notably by Gouy, Chapman, Stern and Grahame.^{2-4, 6}

In Helmholtz's model the surface of the electrode is electrostatic in nature with a charge density (q^M) that is present due to an excess or deficiency of electrons in a very thin layer ($< 0.1 \text{ \AA}$) within the metal surface. Helmholtz assumed that in order to maintain electro-neutrality at the interface the counter-charge in solution must also reside at the metal surface. Two layers of charge of opposite polarity (double-layer) face each other and are separated by a distance on the molecular order. The electrode-solution interface is analogous to that of a capacitor, see Figure 1.1.3. A capacitor is an electrical component consisting of a pair of metal conductors facing each other and separated by a dielectric material.³

Figure 1.1.3: *The Helmholtz model of the electrical double layer. The electrode-electrolyte solution interface is essentially analogous to that of a capacitor.*

When a potential is applied to a capacitor, charge will accumulate on its metal plates according to Equation 1.1.6.

$$\frac{Q}{E} = C \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.6})$$

where E is the potential across the capacitor, and C is the capacitance (in farads, F). Charge will accumulate until Q is satisfied in Equation 1.1.6, and during this process a charging (or non-faradaic) current will flow. The electrode-solution interface is characterised by a double-layer capacitance, C_{dl} , which is dependent on the applied potential.³

Gouy and Chapman modified Helmholtz's model by introducing the concept of the *diffuse layer*, depicted in Figure 1.1.4. Gouy-Chapman theory explains that the counter-charge in solution is not confined to the metallic surface. In particular, electrolyte solutions with low charge carrier densities require a "thicker" diffuse layer to neutralise the charge on the electrode surface. The greatest concentration of counter-ions will be found close to the electrode surface where attractive electrostatic forces are strongest. On moving away from the electrode surface the counter-ion concentration decreases with weakening electrostatic force. Besides electrolyte concentration, potential also has a large effect on the thickness of the diffuse layer. Higher applied potentials to the electrode mean greater electrostatic forces and reduced diffuse layer thicknesses.^{2,3}

Figure 1.1.4: Scheme of the proposed model of the electrical double-layer. The potential profile across the double-layer region has been illustrated in the absence of specific adsorption of ions. IHP: inner Helmholtz plane at a distance x_1 from the electrode surface. OHP: outer Helmholtz plane at a distance x_2 from the electrode surface. ϕ^m , ϕ_2 , and ϕ^s are the Galvani (or inner) potentials of the metal surface, the solvated cation and the electrolyte solution, respectively.

Helmholtz, Gouy and Chapman considered the ions in solution as point-charges that can approach the surface arbitrarily closely. This is an unrealistic assumption. Stern's modification defines a *plane of closest approach* for the centres of the ions, known as the outer Helmholtz plane (OHP), at some distance, x_2 , from the electrode surface, as illustrated in Figure 1.1.4. The distance is determined by the ionic radius of the ion and further increased if the ion is either solvated and/or separated from the electrode surface by a layer of adsorbed electrolyte. The concept of the OHP becomes important

in systems with large applied potentials and high electrolyte concentrations where all the charge in solution is compressed at this boundary.^{2,3}

Ions are held in place at the OHP by long range electrostatic forces that are essentially only dependent on the charge and radius of the ion. These ions are said to be non-specifically adsorbed, although adsorption is a misleading term in this case as no short range or chemical interaction occurs between the ions and the metal surface. Grahame noted that very short range interactions affect the interfacial structure. *Specifically adsorbed species* may be tightly bound to the surface, displacing solvent molecules. The inner Helmholtz plane (IHP) is defined as the distance, x_I , between the adsorbed species centre and the electrode surface, as illustrated in Figure 1.1.4.^{2,3}

The Debye length (λ_D) corresponds to the distance from the electrode where the surplus charge at the surface no longer has an affect on a particle in proximity to the electrode (i.e. in the diffuse layer). The Debye length in an electrolyte solution is determined by the ionic strength of the electrolyte, the dielectric constant of the solvent, and the temperature.⁷

In principle we can see that all species in solution (electrolyte molecules, specifically adsorbed species, etc.) affect the structure of the double layer and thus the double-layer capacitance, C_{dl} . Therefore the non-faradaic currents are non-specific in nature and rarely used to provide voltammetric information. They will; however, contribute to the background noise.³ The analytical signal is provided in the main by the faradaic current which arises due to electron transfer between the species in solution and the

electrode. Since electron transfer occurs over distances < 1 nm species in the bulk solution must be brought to the electrode surface via a *mass transport process*.^{3, 4, 6, 8}

1.1.7 Mass transport

Mass transport, formally defined as the flux ($J_i(x)$) of the electro-active species to the surface of an electrode, is established by a combination of diffusion, migration and convection as described by the Nernst-Planck equation (Equation 1.1.7).^{3, 6} This equation assumes that the electrode is perfectly flat and of infinite dimensions, such that one-dimensional diffusion to the electrode need only be considered.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 J_i(x) = -D_i \frac{\partial C_i(x)}{\partial x} - \frac{z_i F}{RT} D_i C_i \frac{\partial \phi(x)}{\partial x} + C_i v(x) \\
 \underbrace{\hspace{1.5cm}} \quad \underbrace{\hspace{2.5cm}} \quad \underbrace{\hspace{3.5cm}} \quad \underbrace{\hspace{1.5cm}} \\
 \text{Total flux} = \text{diffusion} + \text{migration} + \text{convection}
 \end{array}
 \tag{Eq. 1.1.7}$$

where $J_i(x)$ is the flux of species i ($\text{mol cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) at a distance x from the surface, D_i , z_i , and C_i are the diffusion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), charge (dimensionless), and concentration (mol cm^{-3}) of species i , respectively, $\partial C_i(x)/\partial(x)$ is the concentration gradient at distance x , $\partial \phi(x)/\partial x$ is the potential gradient, and $v(x)$ is the velocity (cm s^{-1}). Migration is the movement of an ion under the influence of an electric field, i.e. an electrical potential gradient. Addition of an inert electrolyte, known as the supporting electrolyte, at a concentration far in excess of that of the electro-active species reduces the migrational influence on $J_i(x)$ to negligible levels. Convection, due to stirring or hydrodynamic transport, is minimised by removing all stirring or vibrational movement in the electrochemical cell and performing experiments on a time scale such that natural convection does not have a significant influence. Thus, electrochemical cells can be designed such that diffusion, transport of molecules in

solution due to the presence of a concentration gradient, is the sole contributor to mass transport. In this case, the faradaic current, i , measured is directly proportional to the flux of the species i in the oxidised state (O) from the bulk solution to the electrode surface, $J_o(x, t)$, at a location x and time t (Equation 1.1.8).^{3,4}

$$i = nFAJ_o(x, t) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.8})$$

Where A is the area of the working electrode (cm^2 , see definition in section 2.1.2).

Fick's laws of diffusion describe the flux and concentration as a function of time, t , and position, x , in the case of linear diffusion to the electrode. Fick's first law states that the flux, $J_o(x, t)$, is proportional to the concentration gradient (Equation 1.1.9).^{3,4}

$$-J_o(x, t) = D_o \frac{\partial C_o(x, t)}{\partial x} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.9})$$

where D_o is the diffusion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and $\partial C_o(x)/\partial(x)$ the concentration gradient of the oxidised species, O. Fick's second law relates the change of concentration of O with the time, t .^{3,4} The formulation of this equation specifically for linear diffusion is illustrated in Equation 1.1.10 and the general formulation for any geometry is shown in Equation 1.1.11.

$$\frac{\partial C_o(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_o \left(\frac{\partial^2 C_o(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.10})$$

$$\frac{\partial C_o}{\partial t} = D_o \nabla^2 C_o \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.11})$$

where ∇^2 is the Laplacian operator and C_o the concentration (mol cm^{-3}) of O. The Laplacian operator is available in different forms to resolve Equation 1.1.11 depending on the geometry of the electrode.^{3,4}

Solving equations 1.1.8, 1.1.9 and 1.1.10 under the following boundary conditions:^{3, 4}

(1) at $t = 0$ for all x , $C_o = C_o^*$,

(2) for $t > 0$ and $x = 0$, $C_o = 0$,

(3) at $x = \infty$, $C_o = C_o^*$.

yield's *concentration profiles* and also the *Cottrell equation*^{3, 4, 6} (Equation 1.1.12) which is used to calculate the diffusion-limited current (i_d). C_o and C_o^* are the concentrations of O at the electrode surface and in the bulk solution, respectively. A qualitative understanding of the manner in which concentration profiles (see Figures 1.1.5(B) and (C)) develop with time and vary depending on the experimental procedures implemented is crucial when interpreting experimental results. The Cottrell equation is widely reported in the literature to estimate diffusion coefficients. It describes the *cathodic current-time transit* illustrated in Figure 1.1.5(D).^{3, 4, 6}

$$i_d = \frac{nFD_o^{1/2}C_o^*}{\pi^{1/2}t^{1/2}} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1.12})$$

Figure 1.1.5: (A) The potential-time waveform (this experiment is a chronoamperometric experiment). (B) & (C) Development of the concentration profiles for the reaction $O + ne^- \rightarrow R$ with time at a potential where the process is diffusion controlled. (D) The current-time response on application of the potential step. The following boundary conditions are applied: at $t = 0$, $C_o = C_o^*$ and $C_r = 0$ at all x values; at $t > 0$, at the electrode surface, $x = 0$, $C_o = 0$ and $C_r = C_o^*$, and for the bulk condition, $x \rightarrow \infty$, $C_o = C_o^*$ and $C_r = 0$. C_o and C_r are the concentrations of O and R, respectively, at the membrane surface. C_o^* is the concentration of O in the bulk solution.

The concentration profiles outlined in Figures 1.1.5(B) & (C) are for an experiment designed in such a way that no reduced species are present in the solution initially and that the potential step applied (from E_1 , a value more positive than E° , to E_2 , a value much more negative than E° for the redox couple, as shown in Figure 1.1.5 (A)) instantly causes the concentration of the oxidised species at the membrane surface to drop from that of the bulk to zero, and vice-versa for the reduced species at the electrode surface. At short times the reduced species are only present close to the electrode surface and the concentration of oxidised species remains at C_o^* everywhere except close to the electrode, hence the steep slope at short times in the concentration profiles. However, the depletion zone of C_o extends with time into the solution leading to a decreasing concentration gradient with increasing time (Figure 1.1.5 (B)). The current is a function of the concentration gradient of O at the electrode (Equation 1.1.8). Initially the current will be high at the electrode (when the maximum concentration of O is available to the electrode for electron transfer) but tails off as the flux of O reaches a diffusion limited steady-state, as illustrated in Figure 1.1.5(D).³

In summary, electrochemistry at solid electrodes, in its simplest form, involves mass transport of a reactant to the electrode solely by diffusion, rapid heterogeneous electron transfer involving non-adsorbed species, and finally diffusion of the product

to the bulk solution. In principle, any step may be rate-determining. Additional complications such as chemical reactions before and after electron transfer, and surface reactions such as adsorption, desorption and electro-deposition may also occur. Electron transfer plays a key role in numerous chemical, physical and biological systems ensuring electrochemistry is a powerful tool in their analysis. Analytical, mechanistic and kinetic data in a system may be probed by electrochemistry.

1.2 Electrochemistry at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES)

1.2.1 Relevance and historical background of liquid-liquid electrochemistry

The interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES) is created when two bulk solvents, one an aqueous solution containing a hydrophilic electrolyte (for example, lithium chloride, LiCl) and the other an organic solution containing a hydrophobic electrolyte (for example, bis-(triphenylphosphoranylidene) ammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)-borate ((BTPPA)(TPB)Cl)), ideally of a low (theoretically zero) miscibility are brought into contact.⁹ The interface is a unique environment, both structurally and thermodynamically different from the bulk solutions.

Processes occurring at liquid-liquid interfaces are ubiquitous in nature, for example ion transfer across lipid bilayer membranes, and play a key physiological role in the body. A biological membrane can be defined as a lipid bilayer composed of a double layer of phospholipids where the polar heads face the aqueous intracellular and extracellular solutions. The lipophilic chains of the phospholipids form the oil-like

inner layer of the membrane.¹⁰ Thus, electrochemical processes at the ITIES have attracted attention due to their bio-mimetic features. This was first noted by Blank and Feig who suggested that the water-oil structure of the ITIES may be used to model interfacial mechanisms at *one-half of a biological membrane*,¹¹ as illustrated in Figure 1.2.1. To this end, adsorbed phospholipid monolayers at the ITIES have been used as simple models in fundamental physicochemical investigations of biological membranes.¹²⁻¹⁴

Figure 1.2.1: Comparison of (A) a phospholipid bilayer biological membrane and (B) a simplified schematic of a bio-membrane. The hydrophilic head of the phospholipid faces the intra- or extra-cellular fluid and the lipophilic tails form an inner hydrophobic core. The ITIES is a model of one-half of this bio-membrane structure.

Liquid-liquid electrochemistry is proving versatile in terms of potential real-world applications. The ITIES is useful in electroanalytical chemistry for the voltammetric^{15, 16} and amperometric¹⁷⁻¹⁹ detection of ions. Further applications include separation and extraction techniques,^{20, 21} phase-transfer catalysis,^{22, 23} and drug delivery in pharmacology.²⁴

The origins of this branch of electrochemistry may be traced back over 100 years to Nernst and Riesenfeld who observed the transfer of ions across the water-phenol interface using coloured inorganic electrolytes.²⁵ However, the field remained dormant until the 1960's since, from a theoretical point of view, the interfacial

structure and potential distribution across the interface were unknown and, from an experimental point-of-view, large ohmic potential drops occurred in the organic phase. Gavach et al. demonstrated that an ITIES could be polarised, and that the Galvani potential between the two phases could be used as a driving force for charge reactions.²⁶ Subsequently, Koryta et al. in the late 1970's introduced the concept of an ideally polarised ITIES²⁷ and postulated that the description of transport across the ITIES bore many parallels to the description of redox processes on solid-electrode surfaces immersed in a solution.²⁸ The invention of a 4-electrode potentiostat with ohmic drop compensation by Samec et al.²⁹ allowed the use of voltammetry (and other dynamic electrochemical techniques used at conventional solid-state electrodes) to study kinetics at the ITIES. Various reviews and books have been published detailing the state of the art in this field.³⁰ Reviewed topics include bio-analytical detection at the ITIES,³¹ miniaturisation of the ITIES,^{32, 33} and the emergence of new techniques such as scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM).^{34, 35}

1.2.2 The theory of electrochemistry at the ITIES

When two electrically conducting phases are brought into contact an interface is established, known as the ITIES. Each conducting phase has a characteristic Galvani (or inner) potential, ϕ^α or ϕ^β . When no current is passing through the conducting phase, no net movement of charge carrier occurs. Thus, the electric field at all interior points must be zero and the phase is termed an equipotential volume.³ When a solute is introduced to one of the two phases it will diffuse into the other, and over time an equilibrium is established. In reality, each of the two phases contain solutes which are charge carriers (ions) that partition between the two adjacent phases through the

interface. This partition occurs due to the Galvani interfacial potential difference established at the liquid-liquid interface, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$.⁹

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi = \phi^{\alpha} - \phi^{\beta} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.1})$$

From a thermodynamics viewpoint, the work required to transfer a mole of ions from a vacuum to a liquid phase, α , is defined as the electrochemical potential, $\bar{\mu}_j^{\alpha}$.

$$\bar{\mu}_j^{\alpha} = \mu_j^{\alpha} + z_j F \phi^{\alpha} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.2})$$

The $z_j F \phi^{\alpha}$ term is the electrical work required to transfer the charge that the ion possesses into the phase α . An ion in solution will have short-distance interactions with its environment, for example ion-dipole interactions, dispersion forces, and hydration to some extent will occur. Thus, the energy level of the ion in a phase clearly depends on its chemical environment. This is represented by μ_j^{α} , the chemical potential of the ion in phase α , in equation 1.2.2. For uncharged species the electrochemical potential is solely dependent on this chemical contribution (Equation 1.2.3).^{2, 3, 9}

$$\bar{\mu}_j^{\alpha} = \mu_j^{\alpha} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.3})$$

In an ideal solution, μ_j^{α} is represented by:

$$\mu_j^{\alpha} = \mu_j^{\alpha,o} + RT \ln a_j^{\alpha} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.4})$$

where $\mu_j^{\alpha,o}$ is the standard chemical potential and a_j^{α} is the activity of the ion j . The activity is a measure of the effective concentration of species j in solution. Activity depends on temperature, pressure and composition of the solution, among other factors. The activity can be written in terms of concentration as follows:

$$a_j^{\alpha} = \gamma_j^{\alpha} C_j^{\alpha} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.5})$$

where γ_j^α is the activity coefficient for species j in phase α .

Therefore we can now re-write Equation 1.2.2 as follows:

$$\bar{\mu}_j^\alpha = \mu_j^{\alpha,o} + RT \ln a_j^\alpha + z_j F \phi^\alpha \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.6})$$

Once the species j has established a thermodynamic equilibrium between the phases α and β , then the electrochemical potential of the species must be the same in both phases:

$$\bar{\mu}_j^\alpha = \bar{\mu}_j^\beta \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.7})$$

At this point Equations 1.2.6 and 1.2.7 can be combined and written as follows:

$$\mu_j^{\alpha,o} + RT \ln a_j^\alpha + z_j F \phi^\alpha = \mu_j^{\beta,o} + RT \ln a_j^\beta + z_j F \phi^\beta \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.8})$$

Re-organising Equation 1.2.8 leads to an equation for the Galvani potential difference established at the liquid-liquid interface, $\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi$.

$$\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi = \phi^\alpha - \phi^\beta = \frac{\mu_j^{\beta,o} - \mu_j^{\alpha,o}}{z_j F} + \frac{RT}{z_j F} \ln \left(\frac{a_j^\beta}{a_j^\alpha} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.9})$$

The difference in the standard chemical potentials is also known as the standard Gibbs energy of transfer, $\Delta G_{transfer,j}^{\alpha,\alpha \rightarrow \beta}$. This is the energy gained when a single ion is transferred from one solution to the other when both are in the standard state. Ions with a significantly positive or negative $\Delta G_{transfer,j}^{\alpha,\alpha \rightarrow \beta}$ value are designated as hydrophilic or hydrophobic ions, respectively.

$$\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi_j^o = \frac{\Delta G_{transfer,j}^{\alpha,\alpha \rightarrow \beta}}{z_j F} = \frac{\mu_j^{\beta,o} - \mu_j^{\alpha,o}}{z_j F} \quad (\text{Eq.1.2.10})$$

with $\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi_j^o$ defined as the standard Galvani ion transfer potential for species j from phase α to β . By combining Equations 1.2.9 and 1.2.10 we arrive at the *Nernst equation*:^{2, 3, 9, 31}

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi = \phi^{\alpha} - \phi^{\beta} = \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^o + \frac{RT}{z_j F} \ln \left(\frac{a_j^{\beta}}{a_j^{\alpha}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.11})$$

Equation 1.2.11 is the equivalent of the classical Nernst equation for electron transfer reactions at solid conductor-electrolyte solution interface. This expression does not involve any redox reactions and is known as the *Nernst equation for the ion transfer at the ITIES*. Since $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^o$ remains constant when the interfacial potential is changed, i.e. charge is injected on either side of the interface by an external energy source; the ratio a_j^{β}/a_j^{α} will also have to change. As a result, a quantity of the equilibrated ions will transfer to the other side of the interface, thus causing an electrical current to move across the interface. Voltammograms are attained by measuring this current as a function of the applied potential, analogous to the solid conductor-electrolyte solution setup. It should be noted that the potential difference at the ITIES may also be manipulated by changing the relative activities of a common ion on either side of the interface.³¹

The Nernst equation can be expressed in terms of the concentrations and activity coefficients of species j by combining Equations 1.2.5 and 1.2.11.

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi = \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^o + \frac{RT}{z_j F} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_j^{\beta} C_j^{\beta}}{\gamma_j^{\alpha} C_j^{\alpha}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.12})$$

Finally, this equation can be expressed solely in terms of the concentrations of species j in either phase by rearranging Equation 1.2.12, replacing the standard Galvani ion transfer potential, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^o$, and activity coefficients with a new constant known as the formal Galvani ion transfer potential, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{\prime}$.

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi = \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'} + \frac{RT}{z_j F} \ln\left(\frac{C_j^{\beta}}{C_j^{\alpha}}\right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.13})$$

with:

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'} = \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o} + \frac{RT}{z_j F} \ln\left(\frac{\gamma_j^{\beta}}{\gamma_j^{\alpha}}\right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.14})$$

1.2.3 The microscopic physical structure of the ITIES

Verwey and Niessen initially described the electrical double layer at the ITIES as two back-to-back diffuse layers, with one phase containing an excess of positive charge and the other an excess of negative charge.³⁶ The distribution of the Galvani potential difference ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$) is spread across the diffuse layers and described in terms of Gouy-Chapman theory (see section 1.1.6). Verwey and Niessen visualised the boundary between the two phases as a dimensionless geometric surface separating the two charged regions,³⁶ see Figure 1.2.2(A). This model was later modified by Gavach to include an ion-free inner layer of orientated solvent molecules separating the two charged phases.³⁷ This became known as the modified Verwey-Niessen (MVN) model, see Figure 1.2.2(B).

The nature of this inner layer is still a point of debate. Samec et al. proposed that ions can penetrate into the inner layer over a distance.³⁸ Girault and Schiffrin proposed the existence of the *mixed solvent layer*, such that the interfacial region is not molecularly sharp but has a “thickness” of constantly changing composition.³⁹ The thickness was a function of both the ionic size of aqueous electrolytes and the polarity of the organic solvent. Theoretical studies of the interfacial structure by molecular dynamic simulations suggest that the interface is only molecularly sharp on the pico-second

timescale. With time the interface becomes “rough” with protrusions of one liquid into the other up to distances of 10 \AA ,⁴⁰⁻⁴⁷ see Figure 1.2.2(C). Schmickler and co-workers suggest that the thickness of the mixed solvent region depends on the miscibility of the two solvents.^{48, 49}

Figure 1.2.2: Proposed structure of the ITIES (A) Verwey-Niessen model, (B) modified Verwey-Niessen (MVN), and (C) interfacial protrusions. The difference between (A) as opposed to (B) & (C) may be the large (i.e. longer than pico-second) time-scale of all experimental approaches.

Very few experimental techniques are capable of providing information on the microscopic structure of the interface and verifying the theoretical predictions. The structural properties of the inner layer are difficult to elucidate due its relatively small size and buried nature. Synchrotron X-ray reflectivity studies by Schlossman and co-workers⁵⁰⁻⁵⁴ and neutron reflectivity studies^{55, 56} allow the root mean square height of interfacial distortions to be measured. Neutron reflection studies by Strutwolf et al.⁵⁶ report that the 1,2-dichloroethane | aqueous potassium hydroxide interface is smooth with a root mean square roughness less than 10 \AA , in agreement with theoretical predictions. A schematic of the mixed solvent layer model, elucidated from theory and experimental data, is illustrated in Figure 1.2.3.

Figure 1.2.3: Schematic representation of the mixed solvent layer model at the ITIES. The Galvani potential difference, $(\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi)$, and the standard Gibbs energy of transfer, $\Delta G_{transfer,j}^{o,\alpha \rightarrow \beta}$, are illustrated for the transfer of species j from the aqueous phase, (α) , to the organic phase, (β) .

1.2.4 Polarisable and non-polarisable ITIES

Polarisation of the liquid-liquid interface is a purely ionic process. As discussed, the distribution of the Galvani potential difference $(\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi)$ is spread across the back-to-back diffuse layers, with one phase containing an excess of positive charge and the other an excess of negative charge. The ITIES act as the working electrode.

Polarisable interface. The term “ideally polarisable” with respect to a liquid-liquid setup refers only to the situation where the constituent ionic electrolytes in both phases have infinite Gibbs energy of transfer. Thus, no current will flow (no faradaic process will occur) irrespective of the magnitude of the applied polarisation voltage from an external source (potentiostat). Realistically, however; no such system exists as real ions have a finite solubility in any solvent. In order to achieve a polarisable interface very hydrophilic ions (A^+, B^-) are chosen for the aqueous phase and very hydrophobic ions (C^+, D^-) are chosen for the organic phase in order to maximise $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi^{o'}$ of each electrolyte ion present, see Figure 1.2.4. Under these conditions, the interface is polarised within a certain potential window, defined by the formal ion transfer potentials of the electrolyte ions.

Figure 1.2.4: Constituent electrolyte ions of a polarisable liquid-liquid interface. A^+B^- and C^+D^- are highly hydrophilic and hydrophobic ions, respectively.

Non-polarisable interface. If a binary 1:1 electrolyte (A^+B^-) is present in both the aqueous and the organic phases, as illustrated in Figure 1.2.5, then a non-polarisable interface results.

Figure 1.2.5: Constituent electrolyte ions of a non-polarisable liquid-liquid interface.

The Nernst equation (see Equation 1.2.11) can be written for the cation A^+ (with $z_{A^+} = +1$) and the anion B^- (with $z_{B^-} = -1$) as follows:

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi = \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi_{A^+}^o + \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{a_{A^+}^{\beta}}{a_{A^+}^{\alpha}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.15})$$

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi = \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi_{B^-}^o - \frac{RT}{F} \left(\frac{a_{B^-}^{\beta}}{a_{B^-}^{\alpha}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.16})$$

The following is true with regard to solubility of the cation and anion in each phase:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{A^+}^{\alpha} &\neq S_{B^-}^{\alpha}, & S_{A^+}^{\beta} &\neq S_{B^-}^{\beta}, \\ S_{A^+}^{\alpha} &\neq S_{A^+}^{\beta}, & S_{B^-}^{\alpha} &\neq S_{B^-}^{\beta}, \end{aligned}$$

where $S_{A^+}^{\alpha}$ is the solubility of the cation in the aqueous phase (α), $S_{B^-}^{\alpha}$ is the solubility of the anion in the aqueous phase, $S_{A^+}^{\beta}$ is the solubility of the cation in the organic phase (β), and $S_{B^-}^{\beta}$ is the solubility of the anion in the organic phase.

Let us say the organic phase can have a maximum solubility of 0.1 M A^+ , whereas the aqueous phase can have a maximum solubility of 1 M A^+ . Let us also imagine that the aqueous phase initially has a concentration of 1 M A^+ and the organic phase has an initial concentration of 0.09 M A^+ . When the two phases come into contact forming an ITIES an equilibration occurs across the interface. As a result, the organic phase now has a concentration of 0.1 M A^+ and the aqueous phase has a concentration of 0.99 M A^+ . This equilibration occurs by the ions distributing between the two phases across the ITIES.

Due to the different solubility of A^+ in both phases a distribution potential is established across the ITIES. This potential is said to be independent of the concentration because once an ITIES is formed, irrespective of the initial

concentration of A^+ in each phase, an equilibration based on A^+ 's solubility in either phase will be reached.

If we take into account that this occurs for both ions simultaneously then the interfacial potential difference can be re-written in terms of the activity coefficients of the ions (i.e. independent of concentration) by combining Equations 1.2.15 and 1.2.16 in this fashion:

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi = \frac{\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_{A^+}^{o'} + \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_{B^-}^{o'}}{2} + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_{A^+}^{\beta} \gamma_{B^-}^{\alpha}}{\gamma_{A^+}^{\alpha} \gamma_{B^-}^{\beta}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.17})$$

$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ is controlled by the distribution of the ions across the interface, and this is often called the *distribution potential*.

A second type of non-polarised ITIES may be formed, with both the organic and aqueous phases containing a common ion, A^+ , as illustrated in Figure 1.2.6.

Figure 1.2.6: Constituent electrolyte ions of a non-polarisable liquid-liquid interface, with one ion, A^+ , in common between the two phases, and the anions B^- and C^- are hydrophilic and hydrophobic enough to remain in aqueous and organic phases, respectively.

Under these conditions $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ is controlled by the distribution of A^+ in both phases, and is in essence a simplified version of the processes occurring in Figure 1.2.5. Once more a distribution potential will be established between the two phases, but this time solely dependent on the activity of A^+ in either phase:

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi = \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_{A^+}^{o'} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(\frac{a_{A^+}^{\beta}}{a_{A^+}^{\alpha}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.2.18})$$

1.2.5 Appropriate choices of electrolyte and solvent when preparing an ITIES

Ideally, from an electro-analytical point-of-view it is desirable to choose ionic electrolytes that (a) maximise the potential window (i.e. the polarised potential region where no faradaic processes occur) and (b) are chemically inert. In addition, when choosing a solvent desirable features are (a) again, an ability to maximise the potential window, (b) a low miscibility with the alternate phase, (c) an ability to form a stable interface, (d) polar characteristics permitting the transfer of charged species and, (e) as low a toxicity as possible.

The two most common organic solvents used historically have been 1,2-dichloroethane (1,2-DCE)^{9, 57} and nitrobenzene (NB).^{58, 59} However; in the past 30 years a multitude of different organic solvents, listed in Table 1.2.1, have been chosen that successfully form stable ITIES with an aqueous phase. 1,2-DCE and NB are very toxic chemicals. Research has been carried out into less toxic alternatives such as 2-heptanone and 2-octanone⁶⁰⁻⁶² (non-halogenated, non aromatic compounds). Although aromatic, *o*-nitrophenyl octyl ether (*o*-NPOE) is another less toxic alternative.⁶³⁻⁶⁵ Senda and co-workers investigated analogues of 1,2-DCE, namely 1,4-dichlorobutane (1,4-DCB) and 1,6-dichlorohexane (1,6-DCH).^{66, 67} Both are less toxic than 1,2-DCE, but more interestingly the polarised potential window increases in magnitude in the order 1,2-DCE < 1,4-DCB < 1,6-DCH. This may prove very useful from an analytical viewpoint as a wider potential window provides greater scope to detect ions that may normally transfer outside the detection window, possibly at similar potentials to the aqueous or organic electrolytes.

Table 1.2.1: Suitable organic solvents.

Organic solvent	References
Nitrobenzene (NB)	58, 59
1,2-dichloroethane (1,2-DCE)	9, 57
1,4-dichlorobutane (1,4-DCB)	66, 67
1,6-dichlorohexane (1,6-DCH)	66, 67
O-nitrophenyl octyl ether (o-NPOE)	63-65
2-heptanone	60-62
2-octanone	60, 61
2-fluorophenyl 2-nitrophenylether (FNDPE)	68
n-octanol	69
Acetophenone	70
Nitroethane	71
Benzonitrile	72
O-nitrotoluene	73
O-dichlorobenzene	74
Chloroform	75

Table 1.2.2: Suitable supporting organic electrolyte salts. *denotes commercial name.

Organic electrolyte salts	Acronym	References
Bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetraphenylborate	(BTPPA)(TPB)	76-79
Bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetrakis(4-fluorophenyl)borate	(BTPPA)(TFPB)	77-79
Bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate	(BTPPA)(TPBCl)	77-80
Tetrabutylammonium tetraphenylborate	(TBA)(TPB)	81
Tetradodecylammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate	(ETH 500)*	16
Tetraocylammonium tetraphenylborate	(TOA)(TPB)	80

The organic supporting electrolytes are generally some variation of a tetraphenylborate salt, as listed in Table 1.2.2. These salts have been chosen due to their high hydrophobicities (in order to maximise their $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi^{o'}$, as discussed in section 1.2.4) and relative inertness. These salts cannot be termed completely inert as TPB^{-} , for example, has been noted to react with silver ions.⁸⁰ Studies by Samec and co-workers⁷⁷ and by Arrigan and co-workers^{78, 79} suggest that the organic anions (either TPB^{-} , TFPB^{-} , or TPBCl^{-}) may influence the transfer response of certain biological macromolecules at the ITIES. This will be discussed in detail in Chapter 3 of this thesis in regard to hen-egg-white lysozyme.

The aqueous phase is prepared using ultra-pure water. The aqueous phase electrolyte ions, listed in Table 1.2.3, are highly hydrophilic (oncemore, in order to maximise $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi^{o'}$, as discussed in section 1.2.4). In the presence of an ionophore the affinity of the electrolyte ions with the ionophore is important. As will be discussed in section 1.2.8, when an ion undergoes facilitated ion transfer (FIT) across the interface by means of an ionophore then the ion's $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$ is reduced and as a consequence so is the polarisable potential window at the ITIES.

Table 1.2.3: Suitable supporting aqueous electrolyte salts.

Aqueous electrolyte salts	References
Alkali chlorides (XCl , with $\text{X}=\text{H}^{+}, \text{Li}^{+}, \text{Na}^{+}, \text{K}^{+}, \text{Rb}^{+}, \text{Cs}^{+}$)	67, 78
Alkaline earth chlorides (XCl_2 , with $\text{X}=\text{Mg}^{2+}, \text{Ca}^{2+}$)	16
Sulphates (Li_2SO_4)	66, 67

1.2.6 The voltammetric response of the background electrolytes at the ITIES

As discussed in section 1.2.2, by polarising the interface and providing sufficient Gibbs energy of transfer to an ion, such that it may transfer from one phase to the other across the interface, is a process known as *ion transfer (IT)* and described quantitatively by the Nernst equation (Equation 1.2.11). Voltammograms are attained by measuring the resultant current as a function of the applied potential, analogous to the solid conductor-electrolyte solution setup. Figure 1.2.7 illustrates a typical cyclic voltammogram (technique discussed in detail in section 2.2.2) for a liquid-liquid system composed only of aqueous and organic “background” electrolyte ions (i.e. a blank system, devoid of analyte).

Figure 1.2.7: Characteristic cyclic voltammetry (CV) response of a “blank” system. The aqueous phase electrolyte is 10 mM $\text{LiCl}_{(\text{aq})}$. The organic phase consists of 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl) dissolved in 1,2-DCE. The reference electrodes used were Ag/AgCl wires in both phases. The arrows indicate the direction of the potential scan: in a positive direction on the forward sweep and in a negative direction on the reverse sweep.

Two conventions need to be addressed: (a) the current convention and, (b) the potential convention. (a) When a cation transfers from an aqueous, w, to an organic, o, solution the current is defined as positive, and vice-versa when a cation transfers from o to w the current is defined as negative. When an anion transfers from w to o the

current is defined as negative and from o to w the current is defined as positive. (b) The aqueous phase becomes more positively charged moving from the left-hand-side to the right-hand side of the voltammogram.⁹

In Figure 1.2.7 the CV scan has been divided into three distinct regions (A) the negative potential region, (B) the intermediate (polarised) region and, (C) the positive potential region. In all experiments described in this thesis the starting potential is set at the lowest potential, in region A (as opposed to starting at the beginning of the polarised region B) and the CV will now be discussed with this in mind. The polarisation potential is scanned in the positive direction, with the following ion transfer processes occurring:

A₁: On application of the highly negative starting potential, 0.1 V, the positively charged organic cation (BTPPA⁺) is instantaneously transferred from o → w and the aqueous anion (Cl⁻) is transferred from w → o. As the scan becomes more positive, from 0.1 V to ~0.25 V BTPPA⁺ will transfer from w → o, and Cl⁻ from o → w producing the observed positive peak.

B₁: In this potential region (or window) no transfer (faradaic processes) of background electrolyte occurs. The current recorded is simply due to the charging current present at the ITIES (due to non-faradaic processes).

C₁: At the highest (most positive) potentials on the forward scan, ~0.8 V to 0.95 V, the aqueous cation, Li⁺, transfers from w → o, and the organic anion, TPBCl⁻, transfers from o → w with a positive increase in current the result.

C₂: The potential is switched at the highest potential reached, 0.95 V, and subsequently reversed. In the potential region 0.95 to ~0.8 V TPBCl⁻ and Li⁺ back transfer to the organic and aqueous phases, respectively, producing a negative peak.

B₂: As with **B₁**, this region is polarised with the current recorded due to non-faradaic processes occurring at the ITIES.

A₂: At the lowest potentials (most negative) on the reverse scan, ~ 0.25 V to 0.1 V, BTPPA^+ transfers from $\text{o} \rightarrow \text{w}$ and Cl^- transfers from $\text{w} \rightarrow \text{o}$ with a negative increase in current the result.

1.2.7 The voltammetric response of analyte ion transfer (IT) at the ITIES

Clearly, from an experimental point of view, ion transfer of a species j across the ITIES can only be observed if the species' $\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi^{\phi'}$ is such that ion transfer occurs at an applied potential in the polarised region B of Figure 1.2.7. Just such a scenario is illustrated in Figure 1.2.8 for the ion transfer (IT) of $150 \mu\text{M}$ tetraethylammonium cation (TEA^+) across an ITIES established using an identical setup to that described in section 1.2.7.

Figure 1.2.8: Characteristic cyclic voltammetry (CV) response of a system with an added transferring analyte. The aqueous phase electrolyte is $10 \text{ mM LiCl}_{(\text{aq})}$. The organic phase consists of $10 \text{ mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl)}$ dissolved in 1,2-DCE. An addition of $150 \mu\text{M}$ tetraethylammonium cation $\text{TEA}^+_{(\text{aq})}$ was made. The reference electrodes used were Ag/AgCl wires in both phases. The arrows indicate the direction of the potential scan: in a positive direction on the forward sweep and in a negative direction on the reverse sweep.

Ion transfer processes of the background electrolytes in regions A and C of figure 1.2.8 occur as previously described for Figure 1.2.7. From a phenomenological viewpoint ion transfer consists of (a) mass transport of the ion in one of the phases to the interface, (b) the ion transfer reaction and (c) mass transport of the transferred ion away from the interface in the second phase. As discussed in section 1.1.7, the flux, $J_i(x)$, of an ionic species to the interface is determined by a combination of diffusion, migration and convection. The presence of an excess concentration of supporting electrolyte in both the aqueous and organic phases minimises migratory effects. Convection is minimised by avoiding vibrations in the cell and conducting the voltammetry on a time-scale such that natural convection in the liquids is not influential. Therefore, the mass transport to the interface is predominantly diffusion controlled.

During the forward (positive) sweep, when $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ approaches a value positive of the $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi^{o'}$ of TEA^+ , the concentrations of TEA^+ on either side of the ITIES are rearranged (from equation 1.2.13) in order to retain electro-neutrality at the interface. The result is cation transfer from w \rightarrow o, with a corresponding increase in the current observed. This is a diffusion-controlled process and produces a peaked shaped response, as illustrated in region **B**₁ of Figure 1.2.8. As will be discussed in more detail in section 2.2.1, the concentration profile of TEA^+ at the interface behaves in an identical manner to the behaviour of an oxidised species undergoing reduction at a solid electrode-solution interface, see Figure 1.1.5. The TEA^+ peak current decreases in a Cottrellian manner (see Equation 1.1.12) linearly with $t^{1/2}$, as the concentration gradient in the interfacial region becomes shallower. On the reverse (negative) sweep

when $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ approaches a value negative of the $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi^{o'}$ of TEA⁺, back extraction of TEA⁺ occurs from o \rightarrow w, in a diffusion-controlled manner, producing the negative current peak illustrated in region **B**₂ of Figure 1.2.8.

The type of ion transfer observed with TEA⁺ in Figure 1.2.8 is known as *reversible ion transfer*. A detailed description of the evolution of the potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$)-current curve due to reversible IT at the ITIES for linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) and cyclic voltammetry (CV) is given in section 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. The observable characteristics of ion transfer in cyclic voltammetry are the peak currents and peak potentials produced on the forward and reverse sweeps. The significance of these characteristics when analysing a CV response will be discussed in more detail in section 2.2.3.

1.2.8 Facilitated ion transfer (FIT) at the ITIES

Alas, ion transfer of a species j across the ITIES frequently occurs at an applied potential outside the polarised region B, depicted in Figure 1.2.7. This is particularly the case for metal ions (Na⁺, K⁺, Cu²⁺, Ag⁺, Hg⁺, Pb⁺, Cd²⁺, Cr⁶⁺) and biological molecules such as dopamine^{15, 16} and a variety of oligopeptides (as will be discussed in Chapter 5 of this thesis). Each of these species are hydrophilic in nature and thus necessitate large polarisation potentials to overcome their high $\Delta G_{transfer}^{o,\alpha\rightarrow\beta}$. This limitation of the ITIES from an analytical perspective has been overcome to a degree by the introduction of ionophores to the system.^{28, 29}

An ionophore is generally a hydrophobic molecule soluble in an organic phase, capable of binding a specific hydrophilic ion, and shielding the charge of that ion

from its environment. In this manner, the ion-ionophore complex is considerably less hydrophilic, with a reduced Gibbs energy of solvation in the organic phase, compared with the uncomplexed free ion. The resultant decrease in $\Delta G_{transfer}^{o,\alpha\rightarrow\beta}$ means a lower polarisation potential is required to promote ion transfer, with the $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi^{o'}$ of the complex now at a potential within the polarised region of the voltammogram. The origin of the ionophore may be either natural^{28, 82, 83} or synthetic.⁸⁴⁻⁸⁷ This type of ion transfer is known as *facilitated (or assisted) ion transfer (FIT)*.

FIT involves the reversible transfer of an ion across the ITIES assisted by one to m ionophores. Different complex ratios, from 1:1 to 1: m , can be formed between the ion and the ionophore and all species involved (the ion, the ionophore, and the complex) may be present in both phases.⁸⁸ In order to investigate the transfer process quantitatively one of the two constituents of the complex, either the ionophore or the ion, should be in excess (usually by a factor of 20 or more). This introduces the concept of a limiting factor, where the observed current is proportional to the concentration of the lower concentration species.^{89, 90}

An ideal ionophore interacts selectively and complexes with the target ion only. Thus, by definition, no interaction of the ionophore with other electrolyte ions occurs. In reality, many commonly used ionophores in liquid-liquid electrochemistry, such as dibenzo-18-crown-6 ether (DB18C6), complex the aqueous phase cation (for example, H^+ , K^+ , Li^+), reduce the $\Delta G_{transfer}^{o,\alpha\rightarrow\beta}$ for that cation, and as a result also reduce the available polarised potential window for analyte detection.

The stability of the complex is crucial and the complexation/decomplexation reaction occurs fast and in a reversible manner. Too stable and the complexed ion will transfer irreversibly across the ITIES into the organic phase, not stable enough and no complex transfer occurs with the $\Delta G_{transfer}^{\alpha, \alpha \rightarrow \beta}$ of the ion remaining unchanged. The complex should be capable of diffusing freely and the kinetics of ion transfer across the ITIES should also be fast and reversible.

FIT is divided into four different classifications based on the mechanism of complexation and charge transfer between the ion and the ionophore. Shao et al.⁹¹ proposed a rationalisation of the nomenclature of these reaction mechanisms in the early 1990's. Schematics of these four mechanisms, transfer by interfacial complexation (TIC), transfer by interfacial dissociation (TID), aqueous complexation followed by transfer (ACT), and transfer followed by organic complexation (TOC), are illustrated in Figure 1.2.9.

Lin et al. initially suggested that perhaps ACT was the predominant mechanism.⁹² This mechanism assumes that the ionophore is capable of partitioning between both phases. Transfer occurs after the homogenous complexation of the ion and ionophore in the aqueous phase. Such a mechanism is only viable for ionophores with a high solubility in the aqueous phase. This requirement immediately eliminates most commonly used ionophores which are generally very hydrophobic in nature, for example DB18C6. Dryfe and co-workers have proposed an ACT mechanism for the facilitated transfer of Cu^{2+} with 1,4,7,10-tetrathiacyclododecane (TTCD) at a water | 1,2-DCE interface modified with a size selective membrane.⁸⁷

Figure 1.2.9: Schematic representation of the mechanisms of complex formation between an ion and an ionophore, followed by charge transfer, at the ITIES. **(TIC):** transfer by interfacial complexation. **(TID):** transfer by interfacial dissociation. **(ACT):** aqueous complexation followed by transfer. **(TOC):** transfer followed by organic complexation.

Investigations by Senda and co-workers identified the TIC-TID mechanism, where the ionophore remains in the organic phase interacting and facilitating ion transfer at the interface, as that most suited to hydrophobic ionophores.^{93, 94} The TOC mechanism, suggested by Koryta,²⁸ involves complexation and stabilisation of the ion in the organic phases after preliminary ion transfer from the aqueous phase. As a result, the

equilibrium distribution of the ions between the two phases is altered, promoting ion transfer. TOC has not been distinguished from the TIC-TID or ACT mechanisms, as the necessary kinetic data remains immeasurable. In this case, diffusion is the factor limiting the transfer and not $\Delta G_{transfer}^{o,\alpha\rightarrow\beta}$.⁸⁸

Charge transfer across the ITIES, either originating from an IT, FIT, or electron transfer (ET, this source of charge transfer will not be detailed in this thesis) process across the ITIES may be impeded by a layer of adsorbed molecules at the ITIES. Protein adsorption at the ITIES has been studied by a number of groups over the past 30 years and will be outlined in the introduction to chapter 3 of this thesis. In addition, phospholipids adsorbed at the ITIES have been widely used to investigate the behaviour of biological membranes, especially with respect to charge transfer processes.^{12, 95, 96}

1.3 Minaturisation of the ITIES: the development of micro- and nano-ITIES

1.3.1 The theory behind developing minaturised ITIES

The development of arrays of micro- and nano-scale interfaces between two immiscible electrolyte solutions, μ ITIES and nanoITIES, respectively, offers benefits at the liquid-liquid interface similar to those experienced at the solid-liquid interface on introduction of solid micro- and nano-electrode arrays.^{32, 97} From an experimental viewpoint, miniaturisation of the liquid-liquid interface minimises difficulties associated with the high iR -drop effect across the interface (owing to the use of highly

resistive non-aqueous solvents) and allows separation of the faradaic current from double-layer charging current.⁹⁸ Significantly enhanced mass transport⁹⁸ and voltammetric measurements in low polarity media or even in media with no supporting electrolytes are possible.⁹⁹⁻¹⁰¹ Additional benefits of supporting the miniaturised ITIES in a solid-state array include improved control over pore size, the geometry of the array and higher mechanical stability at the interface. Furthermore, new research avenues will become available such as integrating microelectrodes into the porous membrane, incorporating μ ITIES and nanoITIES into more complex systems, for example micro- and nano-fluidic devices, and improving the selectivity and sensitivity of nanoITIES based sensors by surface-functionalisation¹⁰² of the nanopore arrays.

1.3.2 Current methods of producing μ ITIES

Two approaches for establishing μ ITIES are available. One is based on the use of micro-pipettes, where the liquid-liquid interface is formed at the tip of a pulled glass pipette.^{76, 90, 91, 103-107} The other employs the placement of organic and aqueous phases on either sides of inert membranes possessing arrays of μm -sized holes. Girault and co-workers used laser ablation to drill holes through thin inert polymer films which were placed at the interface.^{108, 109} Dryfe and co-workers have modified the liquid-liquid interface with highly porous zeolite^{110, 111} and γ -alumina^{110, 112} membranes creating arrays of μ ITIES. Our group has introduced silicon membranes with geometrically regular micropore arrays at the interface. The preparation of these silicon membranes will be discussed in more detail in section 2.3.2.

1.3.3 Landmark papers and breakthroughs in the development of μ ITIES

1986: Girault and Taylor¹¹³ carried out the first experiments that introduced a μ ITIES at the tip of a micropipette. In their paper they outlined the transfer of tetraethylammonium cation (TEA^+) from the organic phase to the aqueous phase through a micropipette with an internal diameter of 25 micrometers. They also presented the advantages now associated with using microinterfaces, which include:

- (1) The formation of a spherical mass transfer pattern, leading to high steady-state conditions of mass transport. In essence an identical response to that expected from a solid microelectrode was observed. This advantage will be elaborated on further in section 1.3.4.
- (2) An ability to study charge transfer reactions in low polarity media due to the low value of the iR drop.¹¹³

1989: Girault and Campbell^{108, 109} produced the first μ ITIES using a methodology that did not involve micropipettes. Microholes were photoablated by an UV excimer laser in a polyester thin film substrate. Success was then achieved in establishing the first liquid-liquid microinterface formed in a microhole. This novel approach was developed in an attempt to overcome the difficulties of cyclic voltammetry analysis at fast sweep rates encountered at micropipettes (due to the large resistance of the electrolyte in the micropipette).^{108, 109}

1991: Shao *et al.*⁹¹ explained the observation of asymmetric diffusion regimes when using micropipettes.

- *Linear diffusion* is observed when the transfer process is controlled by species leaving the micropipette.
- *Spherical diffusion* is observed when the transfer process is controlled by species entering the micropipette.

These two processes are easily differentiated by the use of cyclic voltammetry. The *ingress* transfer leads to a steady-state voltammogram (spherical diffusion) whereas the *egress* transfer produces a peak-shaped current response (linear diffusion). Asymmetric diffusion regimes at singular and arrays of μ ITIES will also be discussed further in sections 1.3.4, 1.3.5, and 1.3.6. Shao *et al.* applied these observations when studying the assisted transfer of alkali metal cations from the aqueous phase to the organic phase using micropipettes.⁹¹

1995: Beattie *et al.*¹¹⁴ developed a method allowing the first reproducible tip geometries for micropipettes. Up to this point the poor reproducibility of the tip geometry of the micropipettes was the principle disadvantage when using μ ITIES. A more sophisticated pipette puller and thinner glass made this breakthrough possible.¹¹⁴

1998: Shao and Mirkin¹⁰⁴ showed that the hydrophilic nature of the glass micropipettes could be changed to hydrophobic by silanisation of either the inner or outer wall of the borosilicate glass or quartz micropipettes. Previously, due to the hydrophilic nature of the glass, the aqueous phase had to be inserted into the micropipette, whereas now the phase in the micropipette can be either aqueous or organic:

- when the aqueous phase is inside the pipette the outer walls are silanised,
- when the organic phase is inside the pipette the inner walls are silanised.

Therefore it was concluded that silanisation of micropipette-ITIES had a key role to play in controlling the mode of diffusion of μ -liquid | liquid interfaces.¹⁰⁴

1.3.4 Asymmetric diffusion regimes at singular solid-state μ ITIES

The μ ITIES arrays used for studies in this thesis are prepared in micro-machined silicon membranes. Girault and co-workers^{115, 116} have established that the

methodologies developed for solid microelectrode theory may also be applied to such solid-state μ ITIES arrays.

The key advantage solid-state microelectrodes possess is the significantly enhanced mass transport rates they exhibit. Diffusion to a single microelectrode occurs in two-dimensions at sufficiently long times: normal to the plane of the interface (linear diffusion) and radially with respect to the axis of symmetry (spherical diffusion).³ As a consequence current density is not uniform across the surface of the microelectrode but greater at the edge. This is commonly known as the “edge effect”.¹¹⁷ This effect relates to the current crowding phenomenon around the periphery of the microelectrode, the nearest part of the electrode in contact with transferring analyte in the surrounding electrolyte. Diffusion to and from the edge of the microelectrode is effectively to a point, such that the flux of ions, j , and therefore the mass transport at the edge, is enhanced resulting in spherical diffusion. At macro electrodes linear diffusion dominates the voltammetric response, completely overwhelming any contribution from spherical ion diffusion, resulting in a peak-shaped voltammogram.¹¹⁷ However, as the dimensions of the electrode are reduced spherical diffusion plays a more significant role and the rates of mass transport across the miniaturised electrode should increase correspondingly.

Solid-state microelectrodes can assume a number of different geometries, for example inlaid, hemisphere, band, ring, ring-disk, finite cone, or recessed.¹¹⁸ An inlaid microelectrode geometry, illustrated in Figure 1.3.1, is observed when the surface of the microelectrode is at the same level as the surrounding insulating inert material. With this geometry spherical diffusion dominates as the dimensions of the

microelectrode are reduced, as discussed. The steady-state current (i_{ss}) at inlaid microdisk electrodes is defined as,^{97, 118, 119}

$$i_{ss} = 4z_j F D_j C_j^* r_a \quad (\text{Eq. 1.3.1})$$

where z_j , D_j , and C_j^* are the charge (C), diffusion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), and bulk concentration (mol cm^{-3}) of the species j reacting at the microelectrode surface. r_a is the radius of the microelectrode (cm). From an experimental viewpoint, Osborne et al.¹¹⁵ suggested that a liquid-liquid interface confined within a solid-state micropore behaves in an identical manner to an inlaid microelectrode, and thus ion transfer across the μITIES from the aqueous to the organic phase can be characterised by Equation 1.3.1, provided:

- the micropore is fully filled with the organic phase,
- such that the interface is located at the end of the micropore channel, on the aqueous side, and
- the interface is planar (i.e. flat),

A recessed microelectrode geometry, illustrated in Figure 1.3.1, is observed when the microelectrode surface is at a level lower than the surrounding inert insulating material, essentially at the bottom of a pore or channel in the insulating material. The diffusion regime observed with this geometry is more complex; spherical at the opening and linear within the confines of the channel. Bond and co-workers¹²⁰ have established that, for a given diffusion coefficient, recessed microelectrodes exhibit lower steady-state currents (i_{ss}), by a factor equal to $(4L/\pi r_a) + 1$ compared with inlaid microelectrodes, as transport of the reacting species, j , is shielded by the

surrounding pore wall. The steady-state current (i_{ss}) at recessed microelectrodes is thus defined as,¹²⁰

$$i_{ss} = \frac{4\pi z_j F D_j C_j^* r_a^2}{(4L + \pi r_a)} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.3.2})$$

where L is the recess depth (cm). For a μ ITIES perfectly inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel, as discussed, the steady-state current (i_{ss}) due to the transfer of an ion initially present in the organic phase should be characterised by Equation 1.3.2 (i.e. treated as a recessed microelectrode).^{17, 116, 119, 121, 122}

Figure 1.3.1: Schematic of the geometries and diffusion regimes of inlaid and recessed microelectrodes, and the equation required to calculate the steady-state currents (i_{ss}) for each geometry type.

The position of the liquid-liquid interface within the micropore channel has a large bearing on the symmetry/asymmetry of the resulting cyclic voltammogram due to ion

transfer. Let us consider ion transfer across a μ ITIES confined within a single micropore, where the diffusion coefficients of the transferring species, j , are identical in the aqueous (α) and organic phases (β), i.e. $D_j^\alpha = D_j^\beta$, and allow the diffusion field to expand a distance equal to half the length of the pore on the timescale of the voltammetric experiment. Ion transfer under such conditions when the interface is either inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel, inlaid at the organic side of the micropore channel, or located at the centre of the micropore channel is illustrated in Figures 1.3.1(A₁ & A₂), (B₁ & B₂), and (C₁ & C₂), respectively. The main point of interest is that symmetrical CVs, due to identical diffusion patterns being established on the forward and reverse sweeps, are only possible when the ITIES is located in the centre of the micropore channel (where the shielding effect of the surrounding pore wall is identical for the initial and back-transfer of ions). Thus, the position of the liquid-liquid interface is the first possible source of asymmetry for ion transfer across a singular μ ITIES.

As discussed, when the interface is inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel (Figure 1.3.1(A₁ & A₂)) transfer from $w \rightarrow o$ is treated analogous to that at an inlaid microelectrode and the transfer from $o \rightarrow w$ is treated analogous to that at a recessed microelectrode. When the interface is inlaid at the organic side of the micropore channel (Figure 1.3.1(B₁ & B₂)) the trend is reversed, with transfer from $w \rightarrow o$ now treated analogous to that at a recessed microelectrode, and from $o \rightarrow w$ treated analogous to that at an inlaid microelectrode. In the final situation where the interface is not inlaid at either end of the micropore channel (the extreme case being in the exact centre, Figure 1.3.1(C₁ & C₂)) both transfer processes may be considered analogous to the recessed microelectrode situation.

Figure 1.3.2: Schematics of the ion transfer diffusion regimes from $w \rightarrow o$ and $o \rightarrow w$ at a μ ITIES confined within a single solid-state micropore when the interface is either (A₁ & A₂) inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel, (B₁ & B₂) inlaid at the organic side of the micropore channel, or (C₁ & C₂) located at the centre of the micropore channel. Ion transfer is observed under the condition that the diffusion coefficients of the transferring species, j , are identical in the aqueous (α) and organic phases (β), i.e. $D_j^\alpha = D_j^\beta$, and allow the diffusion field to expand a distance equal to half the length of the pore on the timescale of the cyclic voltammetric experiment.

The second source of asymmetry for ion transfer across a singular μ ITIES is the varying viscosity of the aqueous and organic phases, and the resulting differences in

the diffusion coefficient of the transferring species j in either phase, i.e. $D_j^\alpha \neq D_j^\beta$. This is of particular importance for μ ITIES setups since, as will be discussed in section 1.3.10, the organic phase is often solidified or gellified with significant reductions in D_j^β observed as a result. Just such a scenario is illustrated in Figure 1.3.3. The interface is located in the centre of the micropore channel (the only situation where symmetrical ion transfer may be observed when $D_j^\alpha = D_j^\beta$, as outlined in Figure 1.3.2(C₁ & C₂)), but now $D_j^\alpha \gg D_j^\beta$. As can be seen, for ion transfer from $w \rightarrow o$ the diffusion field can extend out of the pore and i_{ss} will be correspondingly enhanced by the resultant spherical diffusion component. On the other hand, the significant reductions in D_j^β mean the ions do not diffuse out of the pore after initial transfer from $w \rightarrow o$ on the timescale of the voltammetric experiment, and, as a result, linear diffusion only contributes to current observed on the reverse sweep.

Figure 1.3.3: Schematics of the ion transfer diffusion regimes from $w \rightarrow o$ and $o \rightarrow w$ at a μ ITIES confined within a single solid-state micropore when the interface is located at the centre of the micropore channel and the diffusion coefficient of the transferring species j is significantly larger in the aqueous phase (α) than in the organic phase (β), i.e. $D_j^\alpha \gg D_j^\beta$.

1.3.5 Diffusion zone extensions (δ) at arrays of solid-state μ ITIES

A diffusion zone is present around each individual pore in a μ ITIES array. The magnitude of the diffusion zone extension (δ), and whether overlap occurs between the individual diffusion zones (resulting in individual pores “depleting” the same areas at the μ ITIES), is dependent on:

- the geometric parameters of the solid-state micropore arrays; in particular the pore radii (r_a) (when fabricating these arrays each pore in the array will have an identical pore radius) and the pore centre-to-centre separation (r_c),
- the voltammetric timescale of the experiment; determined by the potential window used and the scan rate (ν) applied, and
- the diffusion coefficients of the transferring species in both phases.

The shape of the voltammetric responses and the size of the steady-state currents observed (i_{ss}) are dependent on the ratios of $\delta: r_a$ and $\delta: r_c$. The location of the liquid-liquid interface within the micropore channel is also important, as discussed in section 1.3.4. For simplification, the most commonly reported liquid-liquid interface location, inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel (see Figure 1.3.2(A₁ & A₂), will be the case discussed with regard to μ ITIES arrays in this section, unless otherwise stated.

The diffusion regimes established at an array of μ ITIES for the initial and back-transfer of an ion, j , across the interface during a CV experiment have been assigned to one of eight categories depending on the ratios of $\delta: r_a$ and $\delta: r_c$ (four categories for the transfer of an ion from $w \rightarrow o$, and the equivalent four categories for the back-transfer from $o \rightarrow w$), illustrated in Figure 1.3.4. This system of discussing the diffusion regimes during a CV experiment at an array of μ ITIES is analogous to the

nomenclature devised by Compton and co-workers to discuss the magnitude of the diffusion zone extensions at microelectrode arrays.^{123, 124}

Figure 1.3.4: Schematic of the eight diffusion regimes possible at an array of μ TIES, inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel, depending on the ratios of $\delta : r_a$ and $\delta : r_c$. Diffusion regimes (A), (B), (C) and (D) are specific for the transfer of an ion, j , from $w \rightarrow o$, and diffusion regimes (E), (F), (G) and (H) are the equivalent four categories for the back-transfer from $o \rightarrow w$.

When an ion is initially transferred across the μ ITIES from $w \rightarrow o$ the following situations may arise:

Category A: The extension of the diffusion zone (δ) is small compared with the radius of the pore that defines the individual μ ITIES, i.e. $\delta < r_a$, resulting in linear diffusion. The resulting $i - \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$ curve is thus a scaled down peak shaped macroITIES response. This situation will only arise if very fast scan rates are applied, and at large values of r_c .

Category B: This category represents the optimum situation when designing an array of μ ITIES. The diffusion zone extends beyond the area of the pore, $\delta > r_a$, thus ensuring spherical diffusion is established at each individual μ ITIES. The pores, however, are sufficiently separated such that no overlapping of individual diffusion fields occurs, $\delta < 0.5r_c$. This ensures the maximum faradaic steady-state current/background charging current ratio. The faradaic steady-state current (i_{ss}) observed is equivalent to the current established at individual inlaid μ ITIES multiplied by the number of pores in the array (N_p):

$$i_{ss} = (4z_j F D_j C_j * r_a) N_p \quad (\text{Eq. 1.3.3})$$

Such an array of μ ITIES will be characterised by a scan rate independent voltammogram with steady-state features. As an aside, if category B μ ITIES behaviour is observed at recessed interfaces (such as those illustrated in Figures 1.3.2 (B₁ & B₂) and (C₁ & C₂)) then the faradaic steady-state current (i_{ss}) observed is

equivalent to the current established at individual recessed μ ITIES multiplied by the number of pores in the array (N_p):

$$i_{ss} = \left(\frac{4\pi z_j F D_j C_j^* r_a^2}{(4L + \pi r_a)} \right) N_p \quad (\text{Eq. 1.3.4})$$

Category C: The diffusion zone extends beyond half the pore centre-to-centre separation, $\delta > 0.5r_c$. Now that the individual diffusion zones are no longer mutually exclusive they are competing for analyte in the same region of solution, known as the “exclusion zone”. As a result the observed current is reduced in comparison to category B. The greater the size of the exclusion zone, the greater the drop in the observed current. The resulting voltammogram may be peaked shape and show a dependence on the scan rate. The current expected at such a μ ITIES is best estimated only by a simulation incorporating all experimental parameters. It should be noted that a vital parameter is the scan rate. The distance over which the diffusion zone around each pore is allowed to extend is dependent on the timescale of the experiment. Thus at long timescales (owing to slow scan rates applied) a μ ITIES array design that normally shows category B type behaviour will now show category C type behaviour, and *vice versa* at short timescales (owing to fast scan rates applied) a μ ITIES array design in category C may revert to category B type behaviour.

Category D: The diffusion zone extends far beyond half the pore centre-to-centre separation, $\delta \gg 0.5r_c$. This situation is typical for pores separated at minimal distances. A linear diffusion field is established and the μ ITIES array essentially behaves as a macroITIES. The $i - \Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi$ curve will be peak shaped and the peak

current (i_p) described by the Randles-Sevcik equation (see section 2.2.3, Equation 2.2.1).

The current for the back transfer of an ion cannot be established using Equations 1.3.3, 1.3.4, or 2.2.1. This is because the bulk concentration of the ion (C_j^*) now present in the organic phase after the initial transfer event from $w \rightarrow o$ is unknown. Simulations are necessary to determine the expected magnitude of current on the reverse sweep. When an ion is back-transferred across the μ ITIES from $o \rightarrow w$ the following situations may arise:

Category E: After the initial transfer event the ion in the organic phase does not diffuse out of the micropore channel on the timescale of the experiment. Linear diffusion and a peak shaped voltammogram are thus observed on the reverse sweep. This situation arises either (a) due to very fast scan rates being applied or (b) the diffusion coefficient of the ion in the organic phase is so slow that diffusion out of the pore on the timescale of the experiment is not possible.

Category F: After the initial transfer event the ion diffuses out of the pore, establishing a spherical diffusion field at the opening of the pore (in addition to the linear diffusion field within the micropore channel). The pores are sufficiently separated, however, that these individual spherical diffusion fields do not overlap, analogous to the situation described for category B. The current on the reverse sweep will be enhanced due to the spherical component, but the voltammogram may remain peak-shaped due to the linear diffusion component to the back-transfer.

Category G: As with category F, after the initial transfer event the ion diffuses out of the pore, establishing a spherical diffusion field at the opening of the pore. In this case, however, the diffusion zone extends beyond half the pore centre-to-centre separation, $\delta > 0.5r_c$, creating exclusion zones where adjacent pores deplete the same region of solution. As a result the observed current on the reverse sweep is reduced in comparison to category F, and, once again, the resulting voltammogram may be peak shaped.

Category H: Similar to category G except the spherical diffusion zone at the opening of each pore now extends far beyond half the pore centre-to-centre separation, $\delta \gg 0.5r_c$. Linear diffusion dominates the back-transfer event both at the opening of and within the micropore channel, and subsequently the $i - \Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi$ curve observed will be peak shaped on the reverse sweep.

1.3.6 Methods of estimating the conditions for non-interacting diffusion zones

Davies and Compton¹²³ have proposed an equation to estimate the extension of the diffusion zone (δ) under voltammetric conditions at microelectrode arrays,

$$\delta \approx \sqrt{2D_j \frac{\Delta(\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi)}{\nu}} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.3.5})$$

where $\Delta(\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi)$ approximately matches the potential interval between the onset (faradaic) current and attainment of the peak or steady-state current (usually ~0.3 V at a microelectrode). From Equation 1.3.5 it is clear that the rate at which the diffusion zone expands depends on the time allowed via the potential scan rate, and is independent of the pore radius. This is due to equation 1.3.5 being derived with the assumption of one-dimensional diffusion.

Davies and Compton have defined a parameter, let us call it r_c^o , as a value approximately half that of r_c which results in a 2.5 % decrease in peak (or steady-state) current compared to the case where the microelectrodes are infinitely separated. This parameter indicates the value of r_c where the transition from microelectrodes exhibiting non-linear diffusion ($\delta < 0.5r_c$) to microelectrodes with overlapping diffusion zones exhibiting linear diffusion ($\delta > 0.5r_c$) occurs. In essence, the maximum diffusion zone extension (δ) without significantly overlapping diffusion zones is achieved when $\delta = r_c^o (\approx 0.5 r_c)$. Davies and Compton have shown that equation 1.3.5 provides an accurate means of calculating r_c^o when $r_a > 1 \mu\text{m}$. For $r_a < 1 \mu\text{m}$ equation 1.3.5 overestimates r_c^o , with the overestimate increasing with decreasing r_a . Thus, Davies and Compton's equation can be readily applied to all μITIES experiments described in this thesis, but will overestimate r_c^o if used when discussing overlap of diffusion zones established at nanoITIES.

Alternatively, a variety of expressions have been derived that estimate the conditions for non-interacting diffusion zones based on a linear relationship between r_a and r_c , for example that by Saito et al.¹²⁵

$$r_c > 12 r_a \quad (\text{Eq. 1.3.6})$$

The majority of these expressions were formulated based on an assumption of purely steady-state voltammetry at the microelectrodes and thus are independent of the time allowed via the potential scan rate. Using equation 1.3.6 as an example, Davies and Compton¹²³ have determined that these linear relationships significantly underestimate the value of r_c^o when $r_a < 1 \mu\text{m}$ and, thus, are also unsuitable to

calculate r_c^o with regard to a nanoITIES setup. As yet no universal “basic” equation exists that allows us to estimate with a high degree of accuracy r_c^o when $r_a < 1 \mu\text{m}$. The only viable option is to carry out simulations for each individual nanoITIES array that is to be studied.

1.3.7 The use of micropipettes and solid-state μITIES arrays to study the TIC/TID facilitated ion transfer mechanism

The concept of asymmetric diffusion regimes at the tip of a micropipette on application of a triangular waveform using cyclic voltammetry, as discussed by Girault and co-workers^{80, 126} (and mentioned in section 1.3.3), has been used as a powerful methodology to identify whether the transfer processes on the forward or reverse sweeps are due to an ion entering (ingress) or leaving (egress) the micropipette. A spherical diffusion field is indicative of the ingress of an ion controlling the transfer process, whereas, a linear diffusion field indicates that the egress of an ion controls the transfer process. Both diffusion regimes are easily distinguishable from cyclic voltammetry experiments.

Zazpe et al.¹¹⁹ have applied a silicon solid-state μITIES array, that exhibits an asymmetric diffusion regime (category B type diffusion on the forward sweep, and category E type diffusion on the reverse sweep, micropore array design 2, see table 4.2.1 in Chapter 4) for simple ion transfer, to study the facilitated ion transfer of potassium ions (K^+) across the μITIES using dibenzo-18-crown-6 ether (DB18C6) as the ionophore. The TIC/TID mechanism applies in this instance (see section 1.2.8), and the diffusion regime observed is determined by the limiting factor controlling the transfer process (in this case the analyte was in excess, and the ionophore was the

limiting factor). A summary of possible diffusion regimes for FIT across a micropipette or silicon solid-state supported μ ITIES array depending on whether the ionophore or analyte is in excess is illustrated in Figure 1.3.5.

Figure 1.3.5: Summary of possible diffusion regimes at the tip of a micropipette **(A)** & **(B)**, or at a solid-state μ ITIES array **(C)** & **(D)** when studying a TIC/TID facilitated ion transfer under experimental conditions where either the ionophore or analyte is in excess. The micropipette and micropores in the solid-state array are both filled with the organic phase.

For CV at the tip of a micropipette:

(A) The molecule in excess in this case is the ionophore, which is located in the organic phase within the micropipette. Therefore, the transfer process from $w \rightarrow o$ will be controlled by the ingress of the limiting factor, the analyte, to the ITIES and a spherical diffusion regime is established on the forward sweep. On the reverse sweep, from $o \rightarrow w$, the limiting factor is the ionophore-analyte complex formed within the micropipette. Thus, the egress of the complex to the ITIES controls the transport process, and a linear diffusion regime is observed on the reverse sweep.

(B) The molecule in excess in this case is the analyte, which is located in the aqueous phase outside the micropipette. Therefore, the transfer process from $w \rightarrow o$ will be controlled by the egress of the limiting factor, the ionophore, to the ITIES and a linear diffusion regime is established on the forward sweep. On the reverse sweep, from $o \rightarrow w$, the limiting factor is, again, the ionophore-analyte complex formed within the micropipette. Thus, the egress of the complex to the ITIES controls the transport process, and a linear diffusion regime is observed on the reverse sweep.

For CV at an array of silicon solid-state μ ITIES arrays:

(C) The molecule in excess in this case is the ionophore, which is located in the organic phase within the pores of the μ ITIES array. Therefore, the transfer process from $w \rightarrow o$ will be controlled by the diffusion of the limiting factor, the analyte, to the ITIES and a spherical diffusion regime is established on the forward sweep. On

the reverse sweep, from $o \rightarrow w$, the limiting factor is the ionophore-analyte complex formed within the pores of the μ ITIES array. Thus, the diffusion of the complex to the ITIES controls the transport process, and a linear diffusion regime is observed on the reverse sweep.

(D) The molecule in excess in this case is the analyte, which is located in the aqueous phase. Therefore, the transfer process from $w \rightarrow o$ will be controlled by the diffusion of the limiting factor, the ionophore, to the ITIES and a linear diffusion regime is established on the forward sweep. On the reverse sweep, from $o \rightarrow w$, the limiting factor is, again, the ionophore-analyte complex formed within the pores of the μ ITIES array. Thus, the diffusion of the complex to the ITIES controls the transport process, and a linear diffusion regime is observed on the reverse sweep.

1.3.8 Current methods of producing nanoITIES and their applications

Analogous to μ ITIES, to date two categories of nanoITIES have been reported, those supported at the tip of a nanopipette^{98-101, 127-133} or a double-barreled nanopipette,^{100, 134, 135} producing single or double nano-interfaces, and those created by immobilizing nanoporous materials, containing geometrically irregular pore arrays with extremely high pore densities (up to ca. 10^9 pores per cm), such as “track etched” polyester¹³⁶ and γ -alumina ultrafiltration membranes¹¹² at the ITIES.

The premise of using a nanopipette to support a liquid-liquid interface was initially introduced by Shao and Mirkin⁹⁸ in 1997. These nanopipettes are fabricated from borosilicate or quartz capillaries using standard laser heated pipette pulling techniques and nano-ITIES down to 20 nm in diameter have been reported.^{98, 130, 137} In addition to

possessing the aforementioned advantages associated with minaturising the ITIES, these very short and sharp nanopipettes produce near steady state voltammograms on both the forward and the reverse sweep, as opposed to asymmetric diffusion fields typically observed for micro-ITIES supported at pipette tips. The hemispherical diffusion fields established on both sides of the interface are due to the unique shape of the nanopipette and lend to simplification of the data analysis.^{130, 133} Indeed these nanoITIES have been extensively used to evaluate the mechanisms of simple (unassisted)^{100, 130, 133} and facilitated (assisted)^{98, 127-129, 131} ion transfer (IT) and electron transfer¹³² (ET) at the liquid-liquid interface. Charge transfer phenomena in media with low ionic strength⁹⁹⁻¹⁰¹ and previously unattainable fast heterogenous kinetics^{98, 128, 130} at the ITIES have been observed. Nanopipettes have established themselves as an important new class of scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) tips^{35, 127, 131} and have found other uses such as electrochemical attosyringes, as recently reported by Mirkin's group.¹³⁸

1.3.9 The explosion of interest in solid-state nanopore membrane structures and the opportunities they present, 1996-present

In chapter 7 of this thesis, the first arrays of geometrically regular solid-state nanopores, fabricated in 100 nm thick silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) membranes, that have been used to successfully support nanoscale liquid-liquid interfaces will be introduced. Over the past decade the fabrication methodology required to produce solid-state nanoporous membrane structures has developed at pace, with a number of recent reviews a testament to the progress being made in this field.^{102, 139-141} The impetus to create these solid-state structures with either a single or arrays of nanopores derives from the vast potential nanopores possess to sequence DNA in a

cheap, label-free and ultra-fast manner.^{102, 139-143} The initial experimental evidence supporting the idea that a DNA molecule may indeed be sequenced using a nanopore was provided by Kasianowicz et al.¹⁴⁴ in 1996. They observed a measurable decrease in the ion current passing through the biological pore α -hemolysin as single-stranded DNA translocated across it. This finding instigated a series of papers to be published on α -hemolysin based studies of DNA translocation.¹⁴² However, in order to advance their research the limitations of using biological pores, namely their fixed geometries and instability with variances in external factors such as pH, temperature, salt concentration and mechanical stress, needed to be addressed. The logical solution was the development of stable, size-tunable solid-state nanopores that possess the advantage of ease of integration into existing micro-fabricated technology.^{102, 139-142}

Nanopores are of course not limited to solely detecting DNA and can be applied to the analysis of any chemical species with dimensions that correspond to the size of the nanopore. Single molecular detection in the extremely small volume defined by the interior of the nanopore structure is a realistic goal, and to this end the sensing of unlabelled bovine serum albumin, ovalbumin and avidin proteins as well as possible protein-protein interactions has already been achieved.^{145, 146} By modifying the surface of the nanopore structures a whole host of possibilities can arise in terms of manipulating and separating chemical species.¹⁰²

The majority of solid-state nanoporous membrane structures have been fabricated in materials familiar to the microelectronics industry, that were thoroughly characterised over the last half century, such as silicon (Si),¹⁴⁷ silicon nitride (Si₃N₄),^{145, 146, 148-156} silicon dioxide (SiO₂)^{131, 155, 157-159} and silicon carbide (SiC).¹⁶⁰ A few notable

exceptions exist such as nanopores in thermoplastics^{161, 162} and track-etched polymers.¹⁶³⁻¹⁶⁵ The Si₃N₄ and SiO₂ membranes are generally ultra-thin (10-50 nm in thickness) because the smallest nanopores (ca. 1 nm in diameter) are formed most easily in the thinnest membranes.

In broad terms, when attempting to fabricate the smallest reported nanopores the strategy is to initially create a moderately “large” nanopore, between 20 and 200 nm in diameter, by using focused ion beam (FIB) drilling,^{149, 152-154, 160} e-beam lithography,^{145, 146, 156, 159} or, by using a focused electron-beam provided by a transmission electron microscope (TEM)^{150, 151} as a drill. Once this initial pore is created in the membrane it can be shrunk in two ways, the first and more obvious way is by depositing layers of material in a conformal manner in the pore using techniques such as atomic layer deposition (ALD),^{154, 166} electroless plating^{167, 168} and ion- or e-beam assisted SiO₂,^{157, 158, 169} Pt,¹⁶⁹ or carbon¹⁷⁰ deposition. Alternatively, the pore may be exposed to a beam of ions, electrons or photons. This approach is more complicated as depending on the ion rate and temperature the pores may enlarge or shrink,^{148, 152, 160} and similarly with e-beams^{151, 152, 156, 160, 171, 172} and photons¹⁶¹ the pore may actually enlarge or shrink depending on the initial geometry of the pore. When this behaviour is combined with the fact that the shrinking/expanding of the nanopore can be viewed in real-time with TEM^{151, 152, 160, 171} or FESEM^{156, 172} it becomes clear that this technique provides a method of creating truly size-tunable nanopores.

In the main, solid-state membranes with single nanopores have been reported. Since the majority of these membranes are fabricated with the express intent of only ever

being used to detect DNA related translocations, and this field is in its relative infancy, one pore is preferable to avoid any confusion due to simultaneous DNA events. Nonetheless, arrays of nanopores have been fabricated in SiO_2 and Si_3N_4 membranes by means of scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM),¹⁵¹ directly drilling each hole in the array sequentially with FIB,^{149, 153, 160} or patterning a polymer with e-beam lithography followed by pattern transfer into the underlying Si_3N_4 membrane via reactive ion etching.^{145, 146, 159}

Other alternative approaches to nanopore fabrication have been reported. White and co-workers^{173, 174} have fabricated a truncated cone-shaped nanopore electrode. This consists of a Pt disc embedded in a glass conical pore. The circular opening of the pore ranges between 5 and 100 nm in diameter. Typically, nanoporous membranes can be mounted in cells allowing the solution to be in contact with both sides of the membrane while the edges of the membrane itself are mechanically supported. In contrast, the nanopore electrode is open to the solution through a single orifice only. The Pt disc is an in-built signal transducer capable of monitoring molecular transport through the nanopore. Striemer et al.^{175, 176} have developed a novel technique of fabricating size-tunable and mechanically robust ultra-thin nanopores in nanocrystalline (pnc) Si. They have exploited the phenomenon of voids forming spontaneously as nanocrystals nucleate and grow when ultra-thin amorphous Si undergoes rapid thermal annealing forming pnc-Si, and therefore avoiding the necessity to directly etch the nanopores.

1.3.10 Gellification of the miniaturised ITIES

The mechanical instability of the liquid-liquid interface is readily solved by gellification of one of the liquids, typically the organic phase. This concept was introduced by Senda and co-workers in the 1980's.¹⁷⁷ However, gellification of the organic phase leads to an increase of resistance in the cell, which may result in distorted voltammograms, and a decrease in the diffusion coefficients of the transferring species.¹⁷⁸ The high interfacial resistance may be minimised by combining the use of a miniaturised ITIES, as detailed in section 1.3.1, with a gellified liquid phase. Gellified-ITIES have been reported with a variety of organic solvents (also containing the organic electrolyte salt), the most common organogel systems being poly(vinyl chloride)-nitrobenzene (PVC-NB),^{177, 179} PVC-NPOE,^{13, 17, 18, 180-184} PVC-FNDPE,⁶⁸ PVC-1,2-DCE^{20, 21, 185} and PVC-1,6-DCH (see Chapter 2 for organogel preparation). Alternatively, the aqueous phase can be gellified using agarose, as demonstrated by Fantini et al.¹⁸⁶ and Vanysek et al.¹⁸⁷ Rahman and co-workers have studied ion transfer at a frozen aqueous phase-1,2-DCE interface.¹⁸⁸

The presence of a gellified organic phase eliminates the necessity to have a stationary aqueous phase in order to maintain a stable interface. Flow-injection analysis (FIA) of numerous charged species using a variety of electrochemical detection techniques (eg. amperometric, voltammetric, or chronocoulometric) has thus been reported at the gellified-ITIES.^{18-21, 179, 182, 184, 189-199} Ionophores have been incorporated into the organogel to improve the sensitivity and selectivity of ion transfer, as detailed in section 1.2.8. Every ion has a unique $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{\circ'}$ allowing the Galvani potential difference across the interface, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$, to be tailored to permit the selective extraction of a particular ion from one phase to another in the presence of a mixture of ions.^{18, 20, 21,}

^{182, 185, 191} By applying this principle the selective potentiostatic extraction of ions across the interface from the flowing aqueous phase to the stationary organogel has been reported by Arrigan and co-workers.^{20, 21, 185} A gel can thus be pre-concentrated with a particular ion, increasing the sensitivity of the technique, by applying the appropriate $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ over a period of time. Greatly improved limits of detection are achieved by using stripping techniques, for example differential pulse stripping voltammetry (DPSV), to back-extract the pre-concentrated ions from the organogel to the aqueous phase, and will be further discussed in Chapter 4.

1.4 Aims of the work to be presented in this thesis

The aims of the work presented in this thesis are two-fold:

- (a) to use electrochemistry at the ITIES to investigate analytes of biological importance, such as oligopeptides and the bio-macromolecules insulin and hen-egg-white lysozyme, in a non-redox manner, and
- (b) miniaturising the ITIES to improve the mass transport rates (and thus allow the attainment of increased current densities), improve the mechanical stability at the ITIES, reduce resistance in the system, and provide a reproducible interfacial area. Once the miniaturised ITIES are characterised by ion transfer electrochemistry of the model analyte tetraethylammonium cation (TEA⁺) they may be applied to improving the detection limits and studying the behaviour of the aforementioned analytes of biological importance.

In chapter 3, cyclic voltammetry will be used to characterise the electrochemical behaviour of hen-egg-white lysozyme at the polarised aqueous | 1,2-DCE interface.

This forms a part of investigations into the electrochemical behaviour of biomolecules at liquid-liquid interfaces as a basis for their label-free detection by electrochemical methods.²⁰⁰

In chapter 4 μ ITIES confined within the walls of solid-state silicon micropore arrays, developed at the Tyndall National Institute by Arrigan and co-workers,¹¹⁹ will be electrochemically characterised by the voltammetric transfer of TEA⁺ across the interface under stationary and flowing conditions. The organic phase will be gellified to improve the stability of the liquid-liquid interface. Crucial information that may be attained from these studies are the position of the liquid-liquid interface within the micropore channel and the identification of those μ ITIES array designs that allow the ideal analytical situation of non-overlapping diffusion zones to be achieved on transfer of the analyte from the aqueous to the organic phase. The μ ITIES arrays will also be characterised under hydrodynamic conditions via amperometric detection of TEA⁺ at varying volumetric flow rates.

In chapter 5 suitable μ ITIES arrays, identified in chapter 4, will be applied to the detection of a series of oligopeptides, each with a different α -side chain, charge, relative molecular mass, and hydrophobicity under stationary and flowing conditions. The gellification of the organic phase will allow the preconcentration of the organogel with the analytes of interest and the application of stripping techniques. Both of these innovations should allow substantial improvements in the limits of detection and sensitivities of the analytical response in comparison to those achievable at the macroITIES. This is especially the case when we consider the improved current densities already present due to the beneficial effects of increased mass transport to the

μ ITIES arrays. In chapter 6 the behaviour of the bio-macromolecules insulin and hen-egg-white lysozyme will be explored at suitable μ ITIES arrays.

Chapter 7 will focus on miniaturising the ITIES to the nanoscale. This will require the fabrication of novel geometrically regular nanoporous solid-state membranes that can support the nanoITIES arrays. These arrays will be characterised with TEA^+ and the effects of pore radii, pore centre-to centre-separation, and number of pores in the array, investigated. If achieved these will be the first reported arrays of nanoITIES that have the characteristics of being both (a) in a solid-state membrane and (b) containing a regular array of pores. Once characterised these membranes will provide the basis for development of nanoanalytical detection methods, including those aimed at the detection of biochemical substances.

Chapter 2

Experimental methods and materials

2.1 The electrochemical cell

2.1.1 The four-electrode system at the ITIES

The polarisation of the ITIES, as described in section 1.2.2, is achieved by means of a four-electrode potentiostat system introduced by Samec and co-workers in the late 1970's.^{201, 202} This configuration enables the real-time monitoring (and control) of the Galvani interfacial potential difference, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$, and recording of the current. Thus, all dynamic electrochemical techniques (potential sweep or potential step) relevant to studies of electron transfer at the solid conductor-electrolyte solution interface may now also be applied to charge transfer at the ITIES.

The four-electrode system consists of two counter electrodes (one in each phase) and two reference electrodes (also, one in each phase). The denser of the two phases, the organic phase, is placed in the bottom of the electrochemical cell and the aqueous phase is on top. The current recorded is due to charge transfer (IT, FIT, ET) across the interface between these two immiscible liquids, and therefore, for electrochemistry at the ITIES the interface itself is considered the working electrode.⁹ Under certain conditions, for example when working with low electrical currents or large-area reference electrodes, three-^{108, 119, 203} or two-²⁰⁴ electrode configurations are possible. In these scenarios one or two reference electrodes, respectively, carry out the duties of both a reference and a counter electrode.

2.1.2 The working “electrode”

In a conventional solid conductor-electrolyte solution electrochemical cell the working electrode is the electrode that responds to the analyte in solution, or in other words, is the electrode where the reaction of interest takes place.⁶ A wide variety of materials may be used as the working electrode in these systems with gold, platinum, and glassy carbon being common. Requirements for successful working electrodes are reproducible electrochemical signals and low signal-to-noise ratios. Additionally, factors such as the available potential window (ideally polarised region), the reproducibility of the surface, cost, availability and toxicity need to be taken into account.⁶

As mentioned, the working “electrode” for the four-electrode ITIES setup is the interface itself, as by definition, this is where the charge transfer event (analyte response) of interest takes places. Unique advantages of a liquid interface are the

reproducibility of the interface “surface”, as no cleaning either by mechanical or electrical means is required as would be the case at solid electrodes. Factors such as cost, the available potential window and toxicity are all dependent on the choice of electrolyte salts and solvents, as described in section 1.2.5. The geometry of the working electrode has a large bearing on the electrochemical response and may be modified by immobilizing porous solid-state inert membranes at the ITIES or by using micro- and nano-pipettes, as discussed in detail in section 1.3.

2.1.3 The counter electrodes

The two counter electrodes, often referred to as auxiliary electrodes, act as a source or sink of electrons in the electrochemical circuit. The presence of these electrodes in the aqueous and organic phases allow the potentiostat to pass current through the analyte solution without passing current into or out of the reference electrode. This prevents the potential of the reference electrode from being disturbed, either by electrode polarisation or an iR drop.^{3, 6} The counter electrodes are made of an inert conductive material, in this case platinum (Pt) wire. It is important to ensure that the counter electrode surface area is relatively large, and this is achieved by spot-welding a mesh of Pt to the Pt wire. If the counter electrode surface area is too small an additional source of resistance may be introduced to the system, and thus should be avoided. The organic phase counter electrode is sheathed in a sealed glass layer from the top of the mesh to ~0.5 cm from the top of the Pt wire. This ensures that the Pt is only in contact with the organic phase (the bottom liquid), even though it has to physically pass through the aqueous phase and interface.³⁰

2.1.4 The reference electrodes

In a conventional solid conductor-electrolyte solution electrochemical cell the reference electrode provides a stable and reproducible potential, against which the potential of the working electrode is compared.⁶ Typical references include the *saturated calomel electrode (SCE)*, which is $\text{Hg}/\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{KCl}$ (saturated in water) and the *silver-silver chloride electrode*, which is $\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}/\text{KCl}$ (saturated in water). The constant composition or makeup of these electrodes ensures they operate at a constant potential.³

In the case of liquid-liquid electrochemistry the two reference electrodes are placed in two Luggin capillaries, the tips of which extend until they are ~ 1 mm away from the interface.⁹ This pair of electrodes monitors the potential of the whole cell, which includes the interface. Typically the aqueous phase reference electrode is Ag/AgCl wire, and as the aqueous phase almost always contains chloride the potential of this working electrode is maintained constant.³⁰ The organic phase reference electrode is more complicated. Again, a Ag/AgCl wire is used as the metallic input but cannot be immersed directly in the organic phase due to the absence of chloride. Instead the electrode is immersed in an aqueous solution, known as the organic phase reference solution. This solution contains a chloride anion (to maintain the potential at this electrode constant) and a cation common to the organic phase electrolyte salt.³⁰ For example, if the organic electrolyte salt is $(\text{BTPPA})(\text{TPBCl})$, then the cation in the organic phase reference solution will be BTPPA^+ . The organic phase reference solution is in contact with the organic phase in the Luggin capillary, forming the reference interface.³⁰ The common cation equilibrates between the two solutions and sets up an interfacial potential according to equation 1.2.18. In an effort to overcome

resistance in the Luggin capillary arising from the presence of this “reference interface”, Clark et al.²⁰⁵ proposed the use of a silver/silver-tetraphenylborate reference electrode. However, this electrode has not found widespread use due to problems of potential instability and irreproducibility of the preparation process.²⁰⁵

It should be noted that the potential applied by the potentiostat and observed on a cyclic voltammogram is not usually the Galvani standard ion transfer potential, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^o$, but is in fact the sum of the interfacial potential, the potential of the two reference electrodes, and the potential of the reference interface.³⁰ Since the potential of the two reference electrodes depends entirely on the nature of the electrodes, the observed potentials in a cyclic voltammogram refer only to the electrochemical cell used, and as such represent an arbitrary scale. Therefore, in any experiment where the potential of a specific analyte peak is important, a 10 to 50 μM of a suitable reference ion such as tetraethylammonium chloride (TEA)(Cl) are added to the aqueous phase at the end of the experiment in order to reference all the half-wave potentials, $E_j^{1/2}$, deduced from the voltammograms relative to $E_{TEA^+}^{1/2}$.²⁰⁶

The tetraphenylarsonium tetraphenylborate ($\text{Ph}_4\text{AsPh}_4\text{B}$) scale represents one non-thermodynamic method for the voltammetric determination of zero on the potential scale.^{9, 63} If $\text{Ph}_4\text{AsPh}_4\text{B}$ is used as the organic phase electrolyte salt then the onset of increasing current at positive and negative Galvani potential differences (as discussed in section 1.2.6 with regard to (BTPPA)(TPBCl)) is assigned to (Ph_4As^+) and (Ph_4B^-) transfer, respectively. The centre of symmetry of the current potential curves of the supporting $\text{Ph}_4\text{AsPh}_4\text{B}$ electrolyte is designated as $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi = 0$.^{9, 63} The formal Galvani

ion transfer potential of TEA^+ , $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_{\text{TEA}^+}^{o'}$, into a 1,2-DCE organic solvent is estimated on this “absolute Galvani potential scale” as 0.044 V.⁹ The potential at which $E_j^{1/2}$ of a transferring ion j is observed in a CV can be transposed to the absolute scale using the following relationship:

$$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'} = E_j^{1/2} - E_{\text{TEA}^+}^{1/2} + \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_{\text{TEA}^+}^{o'} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.1.1})$$

2.2 Electrochemical techniques

2.2.1 Potential sweep techniques: linear sweep voltammetry (LSV)

LSV may also be called linear potential sweep chronoamperometry, a less popular but more informative title.⁸ As mentioned in section 2.1.1, this technique has been applicable to studying charge transfer at the ITIES ever since the advent of the four-electrode potentiostat, and when discussing LSV in this thesis (and all other dynamic electrochemical techniques) the subject will be broached from a liquid-liquid point-of-view. Specifically, reversible ion transfer of a model cation (for example, TEA^+) across the ITIES is discussed, unless otherwise noted. For simplicity the diffusion coefficient of the transferring ion is assumed to be identical in both phases, i.e. $D_j^{\alpha} = D_j^{\beta}$. Also, the concentration of the cation at the interface in the aqueous phase, C_j^{α} , plus the concentration of the cation at the interface in the organic phase, C_j^{β} , must equal the bulk concentration of the cation in the aqueous phase, $C_j^{\alpha *}$, at all times. Therefore the following two conditions hold: (1) at $t = 0$, $C_j^{\alpha} = C_j^{\alpha *}$ and $C_j^{\beta} = 0$; and (2) at $t > 0$, $C_j^{\alpha} + C_j^{\beta} = C_j^{\alpha *}$.

With LSV the Galvani potential difference applied across the interface, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$, is scanned linearly from an initial (less positive) value, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_i$, to a final (more positive) value, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_f$, at a constant rate (this is known as the scan rate, v , with units $V s^{-1}$), as depicted in the potential-time excitation signal in Figure 2.2.1(A). A typical i - E LSV response curve for the transfer of a model cation, for example TEA⁺, from the aqueous to the organic phase in the polarised region of the potential window is illustrated in Figure 2.2.1(B).

Figure 2.2.1: (A) Potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi / V$)-time (t/s) excitation signal for linear sweep voltammetry (LSV). (B) The resulting i - E curve for the transfer of a cationic species from $w \rightarrow o$ under the following conditions: at $t = 0$, $C_j^{\alpha} = C_j^{\alpha*}$ and $C_j^{\beta} = 0$; and at $t > 0$, $C_j^{\alpha} + C_j^{\beta} = C_j^{\alpha*}$. $E_{p,w \rightarrow o}$ is the peak potential (V) and $i_{p,w \rightarrow o}$ is the peak current (A).

The concentration profiles on both the aqueous and organic side of the ITIES change in response to the applied potential across the interface, scanned linearly from $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_i$ to $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_f$. The evolution of the peak-shaped response and its relationship with the concentration profiles at the ITIES will now be explained in detail, and is illustrated in Figures 2.2.2 (A) & (B).

Figure 2.2.2: (A) The i - E curve on the transfer of a cationic species from $w \rightarrow o$ for LSV, under the conditions described in Figure 2.2.1. Five points have been highlighted and colour coded to match the corresponding concentration profile at the ITIES at that moment in the i - E curve. (B) The concentration profiles either side of the ITIES on the transfer of a cationic species from $w \rightarrow o$ for LSV, under the conditions described in Figure 2.2.1. The interface is positioned at $x = 0$.

Point 1. in the LSV scan: The scan is begun at $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_i$, an applied potential difference across the interface considerably more negative than the formal ion transfer potential of the model ion, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$. At this potential only no faradaic current flows, as shown in Figure 2.2.2(A), and at $t = 0$, $C_j^{\alpha} = C_j^{\alpha *}$ and $C_j^{\beta} = 0$, as shown in Figure 2.2.2(B).

Scanning from point 1. to point 2.: As the potential is scanned linearly in a positive direction $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ approaches the vicinity of $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$ and the concentrations of the model ion either side of the ITIES are re-arranged, as described by the Nernst equation tailored for the ITIES (equation 1.2.13). The cation transfers across the interface and a faradaic current begins to flow (Figure 2.2.2(A)). Therefore, at $t > 0$ and $x = 0$, $C_j^{\alpha} \neq C_j^{\alpha *}$ and $C_j^{\alpha} + C_j^{\beta} = C_j^{\alpha *}$ at the interface.

Scanning from point 2. to point 3.: As $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ continues to grow more positive with increasing t and more cations are transferred across the interface, then the C_j^{α} at the interface decreases and, as a result, a concentration gradient is established (see Figure 2.2.2(B)). An increase in the flux of the model cation to the ITIES is observed and, as described in Equations 1.1.8 and 1.19, the current increases correspondingly.

Point 3: This point on the i - E curve represents $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$, an applied potential at which the concentration of species j at the interface are equal, $C_j^{\alpha} = C_j^{\beta}$, clearly seen in the concentration profile (Figure 2.2.2(B)).

Scanning from point 3. to point 4: As $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ becomes more positive than $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$, C_j^{α} drops to almost zero, and the rate of mass transport reaches a maximum when the concentration gradient at the ITIES is at its steepest (see Figure 2.2.2(B)).

Scanning from point 4 to point 5: After point 4, C_j^{α} drops to zero and the depletion effect sets in (Figure 2.2.2 (B)). As a result the current decreases with a $t^{-1/2}$ dependence, as described by the Cottrell equation (Equation 1.1.12). The observation is thus a peaked-shaped current-potential curve as depicted in Figure 2.2.2(A).

2.2.2 Potential sweep techniques: cyclic voltammetry (CV)

CV is a reversal technique and essentially an extension of an LSV experiment to include a reverse sweep (from a more positive to less positive $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$) once the initial forward sweep is complete. The Galvani potential difference applied across the interface, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$, is scanned linearly from an initial (less positive) value, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_i$, to a more positive value, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_{\lambda}$, known as the switching potential. At $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_{\lambda}$ the sweep is reversed and scanned once more to a less positive final value, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_f$, at a constant rate, as illustrated in Figures 2.2.3(A) & (B). This triangular waveform can be repeated, starting again at $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_i$ (which more often than not is identical to $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_f$), any number of times and hence the technique is called *cyclic* voltammetry.

Figure 2.2.3: (A) Potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi/V$)-time (t/s) excitation signal for cyclic voltammetry (CV). (B) The resulting i - E curve for the transfer of a cationic species from $w \rightarrow o$ on the forward sweep and then the back-transfer from $o \rightarrow w$ under the following initial conditions: at $t = 0$, $C_j^{\alpha} = C_j^{\alpha*}$ and $C_j^{\beta} = 0$. $E_{p,w \rightarrow o}$ & $E_{p,o \rightarrow w}$ are the peak potentials (V) for the forward and reverse sweeps, respectively, and $i_{p,w \rightarrow o}$ & $i_{p,o \rightarrow w}$ are the peak currents (A) for the forward and reverse sweeps, respectively.

At the start of the reverse sweep there is a large concentration of the model cation on the organic side of the interface. As $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ approaches $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j'$ once more, the concentrations of the model ion on either side of the ITIES are re-arranged, the cation is back-transferred to the aqueous phase, and a current flows (by convention a

negative current for transfer of a cation from o \rightarrow w, as discussed in section 1.2.6). The reversal current has a shape much like that of the forward peak for essentially the same reasons, as depicted in Figure 2.2.3(B).

At the μ - and nano-ITIES, the LSV and CV responses are considerably different from that described here for the macroITIES. The primary reason for this is the assumption of linear diffusion to the macroITIES. This assumption does not hold at the μ - and nano-ITIES where spherical diffusion dominates mass transport. A detailed description of the resulting voltammograms is outlined in chapters 4, 5, 6, and 8.

2.2.3 LSV and CV data interpretation

Two immediately observable characteristics from an LSV experiment are the peak current ($i_{p,w \rightarrow o}$) and the peak potential ($E_{p,w \rightarrow o}$), as illustrated in Figure 2.2.1(B). The peak current is described by the *Randles-Sevcik equation*^{4, 6, 8} under the following conditions: reversible ion transfer occurs at a flat interface, under stationary conditions in the electrochemical cell, with an excess of supporting electrolytes in both phases, and one-dimensional diffusion of the ion to the interface. The Randles-Sevcik equation is,

$$i_p = (2.69 \times 10^5) z_j^{3/2} A D_j^{\alpha/2} C_j^{\alpha} * \nu^{1/2} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.2.1})$$

at 25°C where i_p is the peak current (A), z_j is the charge on the transferring species j , A is the area of the interface (cm²), D_j^{α} is the diffusion coefficient of the species j in the aqueous phase (cm² s⁻¹), $C_j^{\alpha} *$ is the concentration of the species j in the bulk aqueous phase (mol cm⁻³), and ν is the scan rate (V s⁻¹). It should be noted that the term i_p is interchangeable with i_f in this context. When accurately determining the

area of the interface the area taken up by the organic counter electrode passing through the interface in our experimental setup needs to be considered.

When measuring the peak current from a voltammogram the background or charging current, i_c , (due to non-faradaic processes occurring at the interface, see sections 1.1.4 and 1.2.6) must be taken into account. Two approaches may be taken: (a) extrapolate the base-line current that precedes the faradaic current and measure i_p by the difference, as illustrated in Figure 2.2.1(B), or (b) carry out a separate scan at the scan rate of a “blank” system containing the background electrolytes only. i_p is then taken as the difference between the peak current and background current when both are measured at the same potential and from zero current.¹

The potential difference across the ITIES is constantly changing during a potential sweep experimental, and as a result a charging current, i_c , always flows. From Equation 2.2.2 it is clear that i_c increases linearly with the scan rate (ν), as opposed to i_p which increases linearly with $\nu^{1/2}$.⁸

$$i_c = AC_{dl}\nu \quad (\text{Eq. 2.2.2})$$

where C_{dl} is the capacitance of the double-layer per square centimeter (F cm^{-2}). If

Equations 2.2.1 and 2.2.2 are combined,

$$\frac{i_c}{i_p} = \frac{C_{dl}\nu^{1/2}}{(2.69 \times 10^5) z_j^{3/2} D_j^{\alpha/2} C_j^{\alpha} *} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.2.3})$$

Finally, if we consider that D_j^{α} is typically in the order $\sim 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and C_{dl} is in the order $10\text{-}20 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$,²⁰⁷ then:

$$\frac{i_c}{i_p} \approx \frac{(2.4 \times 10^{-8}) \nu^{1/2}}{z_j^{3/2} C_j^{\alpha} *}$$
(Eq. 2.2.4)

Clearly, the relative importance of the charging current increases at fast scan rates and low bulk analyte solution concentrations. This phenomenon often sets the limits on the maximum scan rate that can be applied to a system and also the minimum bulk concentration of analyte that gives a detectable faradaic current signal. Later in section 2.2.4 minimizing the influence of i_c by implementing differential techniques at the ITIES will be discussed.

Preliminary experiments at the ITIES for a previously un-characterised ion or molecule often involve studying the dependence of the magnitude of i_p on the scan rate. When i_p increases linearly with $\nu^{1/2}$ this is indicative of a diffusion-controlled ion transfer process, as described by the Randles-Sevcik equation (Equation 2.2.1), but if i_p increases linearly with ν then this may indicate a non-faradaic process, such as adsorption, is occurring at the ITIES. An explanation of why the current increases with increasing scan rates is illustrated in Figures 2.2.4(A) & (B).

Figure 2.2.4: The concentration profiles on the aqueous side of the ITIES on the transfer of a cationic species from $w \rightarrow o$ for LSV, under the conditions described in Figure 2.2.1 and colour coded in an identical manner to Figure 2.2.2. The interface is positioned at $x = 0$. **(A)** is representative of the application of a slow scan rate and **(B)** a fast scan rate.

The concentration profiles on the aqueous side of the ITIES in Figures 2.2.4(A) & (B) for an LSV experiment, under identical conditions to those described in Figure 2.2.1, vary only in scan rate applied; (A) representing a slow scan rate and (B) a fast scan rate. Comparison reveals that $\partial C_j(x,t)/\partial x$ at the ITIES, i.e. at $x = 0$, is larger at all $\Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi$ values for the faster scan rate and as a consequence the observed current is larger. The concentration of species j at the interface is independent of scan rate, as described by the Nernst equation tailored for the ITIES (Equation 1.2.13). However, as the scan rate increases less time is available for depletion of the aqueous phase immediately adjacent the ITIES and as a result a steeper concentration gradient results.⁸

Analogous to LSV, for CV there are four parameters in the i - E curve of consequence, namely the forward and reverse sweep peak currents, $i_{p,w \rightarrow o}$ and $i_{p,o \rightarrow w}$, respectively,

and the forward and reverse sweep peak potentials, $E_{p,w \rightarrow o}$ and $E_{p,o \rightarrow w}$, respectively, as illustrated in Figure 2.2.3(B). Once more the charging current needs to be taken into account when measuring these experimental variables, again illustrated in Figure 2.2.3(B). All data interpretation applicable to an LSV scan is equally applicable to a CV scan.

CV is more versatile than LSV, however; and may be used as an indicator of whether an ion transfer event is ideally reversible, quasi-reversible, or irreversible in nature on the time-scale of the voltammetric experiment. If the reverse peak is absent (no ion transfer from $o \rightarrow w$) this may indicate irreversible IT across the ITIES. The ratio of the reverse to forward peak currents ($i_{p,o \rightarrow w} / i_{p,w \rightarrow o}$) is unity for a reversible reaction. The peak-to-peak separation, ΔE_p , of the forward and reverse sweep peak potentials is defined as follows for reversible IT:

$$\Delta E_p = E_{p,w \rightarrow o} - E_{p,o \rightarrow w} = \frac{59}{z_j} \text{ mV} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.2.5})$$

This equation may be used to determine z_j and as a criterion for Nernstian behaviour. An increase in ΔE_p beyond 59 mV may be indicative of quasi- or irreversible IT, however; whether an IT event is reversible, quasi-reversible, or irreversible is highly dependent on the specific experimental conditions employed (for example scan rate) and therefore comparison of experimental CV data with simulated data is always a useful exercise. The half-wave potential, $E_j^{1/2}$, is defined as:

$$E_j^{1/2} = \frac{E_{p,w \rightarrow o} + E_{p,o \rightarrow w}}{2} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.2.6})$$

$E_j^{1/2}$ can be transposed to the “absolute Galvani potential scale” and $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$ calculated as described in section 2.1.4 and by Equation 2.1.1.

Analogous to LSV, with increasing scan rate both $i_{p,w \rightarrow o}$ and $i_{p,o \rightarrow w}$ increase proportionally with $\nu^{1/2}$. Therefore plots of $i_{p,w \rightarrow o}$ and $i_{p,o \rightarrow w}$ versus $\nu^{1/2}$ should be linear with intercepts at the origin for reversible IT. D_j^{α} can be determined from the slope of this graph ($i_{p,w \rightarrow o} / \nu^{1/2}$) by applying the Randles-Sevcik equation (Equation 2.2.1). Note that the diffusion coefficient of species j in the organic phase, D_j^{β} , cannot be determined in this manner as the bulk concentration term, $C_j^{\beta *}$, is unknown.

2.2.4 Pulse techniques: differential pulse voltammetry (DPV)

DPV provides increased sensitivities over LSV and CV by reducing the charging current's (i_c) contribution to the analytical signal i.e. the ratio of the faradaic current (i_f) to the charging current is maximised. As depicted in Figure 2.2.5(A), i_c decays at a faster rate than i_f . Just after the application of a potential step or pulse the contribution of i_c to the measurable overall current, equal to $i_f + i_c$, is significant but decreases to almost negligible levels with time. By employing a pulsed-potential waveform, illustrated in Figure 2.2.5(B), the current is sampled before the application of a pulse (i_1) and at the end of a pulse (i_2), by which time i_c would be significantly decayed. The difference between these two current values is determined, $\Delta i = i_2 - i_1$, and plotted versus the base Galvani potential difference across the interface, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$.

Figure 2.2.5: (A) Evolution with time of the faradaic current (i_f) and the charging current (i_c) after the application of a potential step. (B) Potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi / mV$)-time (t/ms) waveform of differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). Note that $\Delta i = i_2 - i_1$. (C) The sigmoidal $i - \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ curve. The greatest values of Δi occur on the rising part of the current curve, where $\Delta(\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi)$ causes the greatest changes in i_f . (D) The resulting $\Delta i - \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ curve for the transfer of a cationic species from $w \rightarrow o$, under the experimental conditions outlined in Figure 2.2.1.

For DPV the potential changes are restricted to very small movements or pulses, $\Delta(\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi)$, as illustrated in Figure 2.2.5(C). The greatest values of Δi occur on the rising part of the current curve, where $\Delta(\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi)$ causes the greatest changes in the faradaic current. Since the potential excitation signals are short the diffusion-limited transient observed for LSV once $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi > \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{\circ}$ is not observed, and as a result the $i - \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ curve is sigmoidal in shape as illustrated in Figure 2.2.5 (C).

As mentioned, with DPV the $\Delta i - \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$ curve, which behaves like a derivative of the $i - \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$ curve, is the response reported, as illustrated in Figure 2.2.5(D). This means that the current difference, Δi is at the maximal value at the potential where current changes most rapidly with potential.²⁰⁸ At a $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$ significantly more negative than $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi^{o'}$, no faradaic processes occur and therefore Δi will be close to zero except for any contribution due to i_c (which will be small, especially if the sampling is delayed to an extent). When a potential pulse is applied at $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi > \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi_j^{o'}$ Δi is small as the $\Delta(\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi)$ applied is sufficiently positive to cause the maximum faradaic current to flow at both i_1 and i_2 .

The peak observed in between the two regions of low Δi in Figure 2.2.5 (D) is explained as follows. As $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$ continues to grow more positive with increasing t , approaching the $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi_j^{o'}$, i_f increases. Therefore in this region the current sampled at the base potential (i_1) will always be significantly smaller than the current sampled at the end of the pulse (i_2) as in the time between the two sampling events i_f increases (and therefore Δi increases), as can be seen in Figure 2.2.5(C). The rate of increase of Δi reaches a maximum at $E^{1/2}$, and this point in Figure 2.2.5(C) represents the peak of the curve seen in Figure 2.2.5(D). For potential pulses applied after $E_{1/2}$ the Δi steadily decreases.

2.2.5 Stripping voltammetry (SV)

Stripping voltammetry (SV) is also used to improve detection capability.²⁰⁹ This is a two-step method, in which the first step involves potential-controlled pre-concentration at the working electrode. As applied to voltammetry at the ITIES, the pre-concentration step involves selective extraction of the analyte from the aqueous phase into the organic phase, and the second (detection) step is the back-extraction into the aqueous phase under suitable voltammetric conditions. The peak current or charge resulting from the (back-extractive) stripping process is the analytical response and is proportional to the concentration of analyte. The most commonly used detection techniques on back-extraction are linear sweep voltammetry, known as linear sweep stripping voltammetry (LSSV) in this case, differential pulse voltammetry (DPSV), and square wave voltammetry (SWSV). The limits of detection achieved can be lowered by increasing the pre-concentration time. The sensitivity of this technique may be further improved by using background subtraction techniques, as will be discussed in detail in chapter 5. The evolution of the applied potential difference across the ITIES with time for SV is illustrated in Figure 2.2.6.

Figure 2.2.6: Evolution of the applied potential difference across the ITIES as a function of time during a stripping voltammetry experiment at the ITIES.

2.2.6 Amperometry

In amperometric detection the potential difference applied at the ITIES ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$) is maintained constant (by the potentiostat) and the current response is monitored with time. Typically, amperometry is used in conjunction with flow injection analysis (FIA), i.e. under hydrodynamic conditions.⁸ Hydrodynamic methods are those that employ convective mass transport of reactants and products. This means that the analyte is added to, for example, a flowing electrolyte solution or one disturbed by a stirring motion. On application of a specific $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$, a charging current is initially observed. This decays quickly with time to a stable charging (background) current due to non-faradaic processes. If an analyte is added (for example a plug of analyte may be injected into a flowing system), the species will be extracted from $w \rightarrow o$ (provided $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi > \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi^{\circ}$) as it flows over the ITIES, and a peak shaped current response is observed. Once the current has returned to the baseline (charging) current a new injection of analyte may be made, as illustrated in Figure 2.2.7.

Figure 2.2.7: Typical amperogram (i - t response) at a constant $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$. By convention (see section 1.2.6),⁹ if a cationic species is extracted across the ITIES from $w \rightarrow o$ a positive peak current is observed and if an anionic species is extracted across the ITIES from $w \rightarrow o$ a negative peak current is observed.

2.3 Experimental procedures

2.3.1 The macroITIES experimental setup

Voltammetry experiments at the macroscopic liquid-liquid interface were carried out using a CHI620B potentiostat (CH Instruments, Texas, USA). The electrochemical cell used to support the four-electrode configuration is illustrated in Figure 2.3.1. A customized glass liquid-liquid electrochemical cell was used, fabricated by AGB Scientific Limited (Dublin, Ireland). The geometric area of the interface was 1.1 cm^2 and flat in appearance. The interface was polarised by two Ag/AgCl reference electrodes (one in each phase) and the current monitored using two Pt mesh counter electrodes (one in each phase).

Figure 2.3.1: The 4-electrode glass electrochemical cell used to support the macroITIES.

The Ag/AgCl reference electrodes were prepared by oxidising silver wires in concentrated ferric chloride (FeCl_3) solution. The counter electrodes were prepared by spot-welding a Pt mesh onto a Pt wire. Subsequently the Pt electrodes were sheathed in a layer of glass. Prior to each experiment the glass electrochemical cell and the Pt counter electrodes were cleaned in nitric acid (69%). The electrochemical cell was

then cleaned by sonication for 5 minutes in a suitable solvent, typically acetone or 1-propanol. The cell was dried using a nitrogen gun and placed in the oven at 80°C for 5 minutes to evaporate off any remaining solvent. The counter electrodes were also cleaned with a solvent and dried using an air gun. They were then mildly “flamed” in a butane flame from a Bunsen burner. This was necessary as some analytes, in particular biomolecules such as oligopeptides or lysozyme, may not be entirely removed from the Pt mesh by chemical cleaning alone.

The protocol for setting up an electrochemical cell was as follows:

- The organic counter electrode was inserted into the glass electrochemical cell first.
- The organic phase solution (ca. 2 mL) was added to cell using a glass pipette, via the “organic” Luggin capillary, until a level mid-way between the two Luggin capillaries was attained.
- The aqueous phase (exactly 2 mL) was added slowly to the cell, using a calibrated micropipette, by dropping it along the inside of the cell wall. The total 2 mL volume was added piecemeal by 10 x 200 μ L additions. The volume of the aqueous phase had to be known exactly as this was the phase that will be spiked with a volume of standard analyte solution.
- Note that even though the organic counter electrode passes through the aqueous phase (and the interface itself) at no point did the Pt wire come in contact the aqueous phase as it is protected by a glass sheath.
- The organic phase reference solution (20-30 μ L) was then added on top of the organic phase solution in the “organic” Luggin capillary via a glass pipette.

- The electrochemical setup was completed by adding the remaining counter electrode to the aqueous phase, a reference electrode into both Luggin capillaries and connecting each electrode to the potentiostat.

A complete list of all the chemicals used during the course of these studies is available in Appendix A. Appropriate aqueous and organic phase solvents and electrolytes are outlined in section 1.2.5. During the course of the studies outlined in this thesis 10 mM HCl, 10 mM LiCl, and 10 mM LiOH were the aqueous phases utilised. The analyte under investigation was prepared in an identical aqueous phase solution to that used in the electrochemical cell. At the macroITIES, 1,2-DCE was chosen as the organic solvent with either 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl), (BTPPA)(TFPB), or (BTPPA)(TPB) acting as the organic electrolyte salt. The preparation of each of these organic electrolytes is outlined in the Appendix B. The organic phase reference solution was 10 mM (BTPPA)(Cl) dissolved in 10 mM LiCl.

2.3.2 The miniaturised ITIES experimental setup

The approach taken when setting up either a micro- or nano-ITIES experiment was identical with the exception of the membrane used to support the miniaturised ITIES. Voltammetry experiments at micro- and nano-scopic liquid-liquid interface arrays were carried out using a CHI620B potentiostat (CH Instruments, Texas, USA). The electrochemical cell used to support the three-electrode configuration is illustrated in Figure 2.3.2. The micro- or nanoporous silicon-based membrane was sealed onto the lower orifice of a borosilicate glass cylinder (6 mm external diameter, 3 mm inner diameter) using silicone rubber (RS Components, stock number 555-588). This glass cylinder contained the organic phase (20-30 μ L), present as an organogel, with the

organic phase reference solution (a further 20-30 μL) placed on top of the organogel. The aqueous phase was contained in a 10 mL beaker. The setup consisted of one Pt mesh counter electrode (in the aqueous phase) and two Ag/AgCl reference electrodes (one in each phase). As mentioned in section 2.1.1 when working with low electrical currents three-electrode^{108, 119, 203} configurations are possible. Just such a scenario arose here and the Ag/AgCl electrode in the organic phase carried out the duties of both a counter and a reference electrode. The electrochemical cell was housed in a Faraday cage for the duration of the experiments.

Figure 2.3.2: The 3-electrode electrochemical cell used to support miniaturised (micro- or nano-scale) arrays of ITIES. In the picture a nanoporous membrane is immobilised at the end of the glass cylinder.

The microporous membranes were fabricated from 525 μm thick silicon wafers, as reported by Arrigan and co-workers¹¹⁹ in 2007. Standard photolithographic were used in conjunction with KOH wet-etching, to selectively thin the wafer thickness from the back-side to 100 μm . Subsequently, deep reactive ion etching (DRIE, outlined in more detail in Appendix F, section F.1.12) was used to drill the micropores through the thinned silicon on the front side. The DRIE process is a gas-phase plasma etch of the silicon, based on the alternate introduction of SF_6 and C_4F_8 into the plasma reaction chamber. The SF_6 etches the exposed silicon, and subsequent exposure of the etched surface to C_4F_8 produces a fluorocarbon passivation coating on all exposed silicon. All non-vertical surfaces were then stripped of the fluorocarbon coating (but not the vertical surfaces) by exposure to a high-energy ion beam. As a result, the now freshly exposed silicon was then etched by SF_6 , whereas the fluorocarbon-wall will remain unchanged. This process continues until the desired pore depth has been achieved. This is known as the Bosch process,²¹⁰ and was carried out with a STS Deep Trench Etcher (Surface Technology Systems, UK). From an experimental point-of-view the micropores are hydrophobic (due to the fluorocarbon-coated pore walls) which increased the likelihood of the pores being filled with the hydrophobic organic phase. The silicon wafer was diced to produce individual microporous chips, 4 x 4 mm in diameter. A variety of micropore array designs were fabricated with variations of pore radii (r_a), in the range $\text{ca. } 2.5 \geq r_a \leq \text{ca. } 25 \mu\text{m}$, and pore centre-to-centre spacing (r_c).

Two nanopore array fabrication processes were investigated, one set of pores were fabricated in a 100 nm thick silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) membrane deposited on a 525 μm thick silicon wafer and the other set were fabricated in the silicon oxide layer of a

silicon-on-insulator (SOI) wafer. Both nanofabrication processes were achieved by combining KOH wet-etching, standard photolithographic techniques, e-beam lithography and polymer protection of the fragile membrane during dicing. All of these points are dealt with in detail in chapter 7. Pore radii (r_a) in the range $ca. 25 \geq r_a \leq ca. 250$ nm may be written by the e-beam and subsequently etched. After dicing the nanopore array chips measured 5 x 5 mm in diameter.

As mentioned, the organic phase in the miniaturised ITIES setup was present as an organogel with the inherent associated advantages and disadvantages, as discussed in section 1.3.6. Two different organogels were prepared with regard to experiments carried out in this thesis. Both are composed of an organic solvent (1,6-DCH), an organic electrolyte ((BTTPA)(TPBCl)), and the low molecular weight PVC. One of the gels (used to study facilitated ion transport (FIT)) also had an ionophore (DB18C6) present, whereas the other gel (used to study simple IT) did not contain an ionophore. The protocol when preparing an organogel was as follows:

- 1,6-DCH was purified following the published experimental procedure,⁶⁷ as outlined in the Appendix C.
- 5 ml of purified 1,6-DCH was added to a 10 ml beaker containing a pre-weighed amount of supporting electrolyte and ionophore, giving a 10 mM concentration of (BTTPA)(TPBCl) and a 10 mM concentration of DB18C6, if present.
- The electrolyte solution was warmed on a hot plate to ca. 50 °C, stirring with a magnetic stirrer throughout, until the solution went clear. 0.5 g of PVC was added in stages to give a 10 % w/v solution, resulting in a cloudy appearance.

- The temperature was increased gradually to a maximum of ca. 65 °C over a period of 30 minutes. The solution was allowed to be stirred at this temperature until a clear gel was prepared.
- The gel was then cooled to 60 °C while stirring on the hot plate. The gel was inserted into the borosilicate glass cylinder, with the micro- or nanoporous silicon-based chip attached, as a liquid at ca. 60 °C using a glass pipette.
- In the case of the micropore arrays, from extensive electrochemical characterisation outlined in Chapter 4, we know that this procedure allowed the gel to fill the hydrophobic pores rendering an interfacial geometry which is inlaid at the ITIES. This is outlined schematically in Figure 2.3.3. The organogel was allowed to cure at room temperature for 1 hour before use.

Figure 2.3.3: Schematic diagram showing the organogel-filled micropore array in contact with the aqueous phase.

2.3.3 Incorporating μ ITIES arrays into a flow-injection analysis (FIA) experimental setup

Voltammetric and flow injection amperometric experiments at the μ ITIES array were performed using a CHI620B potentiostat (CH Instruments, Texas, USA). The electrochemical cell used in these studies is fabricated from poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE, commonly known as Teflon) and is based on that employed by Berduque et al.^{20, 21, 211} to electrochemically modulate the liquid-liquid extraction of ions at a macroITIES. The present design incorporated the organogel and organic reference solution filled borosilicate glass cylinder with the microporous silicon membrane sealed onto the lower orifice detailed in section 2.3.2. This design allowed the aqueous phase to flow under the organogel supported in the silicon microporous membrane, illustrated in Figure 2.3.4. The cell consisted of two pieces that are held together using Teflon nuts and bolts and an o-ring (Viton O-ring, 25 mm approximate internal diameter and 1.8mm of thickness) to prevent leakage of the aqueous phase. The aqueous phase electrodes consisted of a platinum mesh counter electrode and a Ag/AgCl reference electrode. A Ag/AgCl electrode in the organic reference solution acted as both the organic reference electrode and the organic counter electrode.

Figure 2.3.4: Schematic diagram of the PTFE microscaled electrochemical cell. (X) Organic phase Ag/AgCl reference electrode. (X) also acts as the organic phase counter electrode. (Y) Aqueous phase Ag/AgCl reference electrode. (Z) Platinum mesh counter electrode for the aqueous phase. This figure is adapted from Alfonso Berduque's PhD thesis (2006).²¹¹

The aqueous phase was introduced into the Teflon cell by means of a syringe pump (KD Scientific KDS200 series syringe pump) with controllable flow rates. A six-port valve (C22-3186 valve, Carl Stuart Ltd.) was connected to both the pump and the electrochemical cell by means of tubing and polyetheretherketone (PEEKTM) fittings (Omnifit®, Bio-Chem Fluidics Ltd.) and used to inject samples via a 100- μ L injection loop. A schematic of this setup is illustrated in Figure 2.3.5.

Figure 2.3.5: **Top:** Schematic flow diagram of a 2-position sample injector (or switching valve). The valve is viewed from the end opposite the handle or actuator (denoted as an arrow with a shadow in the diagram). Position (A) is used to fill the 100 μL injection loop with the analyte sample from the small syringe. Position (B) is used to inject the 100 μL plug of analyte through the electrochemical cell by flowing the aqueous phase through the injection loop. **Bottom:** schematic of the flow injection system used.

Once the experimental setup was complete the electrochemical cell was filled with the desired aqueous phase by flowing the liquid at the relatively quick volumetric flow rate of 1 mL min^{-1} using the syringe pump. The cell was deemed full once drops of

aqueous phase begin to fill the waste receptacle placed under the exit tube. At this point the flow of the solution was halted, and a stationary CV of the solution run. In this manner the cell setup and parameters used were verified prior to each experiment.²⁰ Thereafter, desired flow rates were set and aliquots of target analyte solutions injected into the flowing aqueous phase.

Chapter 3

Electrochemical behaviour of hen-egg-white lysozyme at the polarised water | 1, 2-dichloroethane interface

3.1 Introduction

Lysozyme is an enzyme whose primary function is to promote the hydrolysis of polysaccharides in Gram-positive bacterial cell walls.²¹² It is present in mucosal secretions such as saliva and tears, and is abundant in hen egg white.²¹³ Hen-egg-white-lysozyme (HEWL) is a globular protein consisting of 129 amino acid residues^{214, 215} and four cysteine disulphide bridges²¹⁶ which contribute stability to the structure. An isoelectric point (pI) of 11.35²¹⁷ leads HEWL to be positively charged at physiological pH. Its hydrodynamic radius is $\sim 19 \text{ \AA}$ ²¹⁸⁻²²¹ and it possesses a molecular weight, M_w , of $\sim 14,600 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$.²¹³ Increased lysozyme concentrations or activity in bodily fluids such as urine, serum, cerebrospinal fluid and breast milk have been used as indicators for conditions such as leukemia,²²² breast cancer,^{223, 224} meningitis,²²⁵ tuberculosis,²²⁶ renal diseases,²²⁷ rheumatoid arthritis,²²⁸ and Crohn's disease.^{229, 230}

Electrochemical ion transfer at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES) offers an attractive label-free method for studying charged macromolecules, such as proteins, with a range of dynamic electrochemical techniques.³¹ As discussed in section 1.2, electrochemistry at the ITIES allows electron or non-redox charge (ion) transfers at the liquid-liquid interface to be studied.⁹ Widely applied to the study of small ionic molecules over the past 30 years, recently a series of papers focused on the behaviour of polyions such as non-redoxactive peptides and proteins at the ITIES have appeared.^{31, 200} The facilitated transfer of a range of model peptides in the presence of an organic-phase ionophore dibenzo-18-crown-6-ether (DB18C6) at both the ITIES^{231, 232} and at gellified micro-ITIES arrays (see chapter 5) is possible. Thus far, the sensing of the anticoagulant heparin (a multi-charged polysaccharide) and its antidote protamine (a charged polypeptide) at aqueous | PVC plasticized membranes via amperometric²³³⁻²³⁶ and potentiometric methods²³⁷⁻²⁴⁰ has been a main focus of interest. Amemiya and co-workers have reported the transfer of protamine at polarised water | oil microinterfaces.^{241, 242} Trojánek et al. provided evidence of ion pair formation between protamine and the anion of the organic phase at the interface, facilitating the transfer of protamine into the organic phase, by voltammetric and conductimetric methods.⁷⁷ Shinshi et al. attributed the electrochemical extraction of cytochrome c, ribonuclease and protamine across the ITIES to the formation of a protein-reverse micelle complex at the interface in the presence of an anionic surfactant in the organic phase.²⁴³ Other notable contributions to this area are further reverse micelle studies by Vagin and co-workers,^{150, 244} the observation of electron transfer between a ferrocene derivative in the organic phase and cytochrome c in the aqueous phase²⁴⁵ and the detection of synthetic macromolecules such as dendrons²⁴⁶ and dendrimers.^{247, 248}

Early studies at the water | nitrobenzene interface of protein adsorption by Vanysek et al. imply that bovine serum albumen (BSA), colicine E3 and ovalbumin adsorb at the ITIES resulting in the formation of a white layer that prevents interfacial Cs^+ transfer.⁵⁸ AC impedance measurements of the interfacial capacitance indicated that BSA continues to adsorb beyond the initial saturation of the interface.²⁴⁹ At the water | 1,2-dichloroethane (1,2-DCE) interface, second harmonic generation studies of haemoglobin and myoglobin adsorption demonstrated that interactions of neighbouring proteins occurred during adsorption at the interface.²⁵⁰ Interfacial capacitance measurements of glucose oxidase (GOx) adsorption showed that the nature and concentration of the supporting organic electrolyte affected the adsorption of the enzyme at the ITIES.²⁵¹ Interfacial capacitance measurements at the interface have also been used to study the potential- and time-dependent adsorption of insulin at the ITIES.²⁵² On-going studies of protein behaviour at the water | 1,2-DCE interface in this laboratory have revealed that both haemoglobin and insulin adsorb at the interface and that the observed electrochemical ion transfer responses for both are dependent on the aqueous phase pH and on the nature of the organic anion in the organic phase.^{78, 79}

In this study, cyclic voltammetry was used to characterise the electrochemical behaviour of HEWL at the polarised aqueous | 1,2-DCE interface. An investigation into the influence of scan rate, concentration, pH, the nature of the organic phase electrolyte anion, the ionic strength of the aqueous phase solution and time on the electrochemical ion transfer response is presented. This forms a part of investigations into the electrochemical behaviour of biomolecules at liquid-liquid interfaces as a basis for their label-free detection by electrochemical methods.²⁰⁰

3.2 Experimental details

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) experiments were used for the electrochemical characterisation of the HEWL behaviour. A stock solution of known HEWL concentration was prepared in either 10 mM HCl or 10 mM LiCl and an aliquot added to the corresponding aqueous phase. To study the influence of pH on the ion transfer process, HEWL solutions made up daily in 10 mM LiCl (pH 5.5) were adjusted to more acidic pHs (down to pH ~1) by adding aliquots of either 10 mM or 1 M stock HCl solution and to more basic pHs (up to pH ~12) by adding aliquots of either 10 mM or 1 M stock LiOH. pH measurements were made using a pH meter (Orion model 520 A). All CV experiments were carried out in triplicate. The composition of the electrochemical cells used are given in Figure 3.2.1. Tetraethylammonium (TEA^+) chloride was dissolved in the appropriate aqueous phase solution (10 mM HCl or 10 mM LiCl) and added to the electrochemical cell at the end of a series of experiments to allow the TEA^+ half-wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, to be used as a standard to adjust the experimentally determined potentials to the Galvani scale (see section 2.1.4). At the water | 1,2-DCE interface the literature value of the standard ion transfer potential ($\Delta_o^w \phi^o$) of TEA^+ on the Galvani scale is 0.044 V.⁹

Figure 3.2.1: Electrochemical cell configurations utilised in this study.

3.3 Results and discussion

3.3.1 Electroactivity of HEWL at the ITIES

3.3.1.1 Cyclic voltammetry in the range $0.9 < \text{pH} < 11.9$. The typical CV response of HEWL is highly asymmetric, consisting of distinct forward (positive) and reverse (negative) peaks, as illustrated in Figure 3.3.1(A). As mentioned in the experimental section the TEA⁺ half-wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, can be used as a standard to adjust the experimentally determined potentials to the Galvani scale (Figure 3.3.1(B)).

The influence of a full spectrum of aqueous phase pH conditions on the HEWL CV response were investigated in a systematic manner, ranging from the highly acidic (pH 0.9) to the basic (pH 11.9). The pH of the 10 mM LiCl aqueous phase was adjusted to more acidic or basic values by the addition of aliquots of HCl or LiOH respectively, as indicated in cell 1 (Figure 3.2.1). The CV response was found to be dependent on the pH conditions employed (Figure 3.3.2). These observations are similar to previous pH studies on haemoglobin,⁷⁸ insulin⁷⁹ and other macromolecules such as dendrons²⁴⁶ and dendrimers.^{247, 248}

Figure 3.3.1: Cyclic voltammetry of 10 μM HEWL **(A)** in the absence and **(B)** in the presence of 0.2 mM TEA⁺. Transfer potentials are corrected with respect to the TEA⁺ half wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, and are on the Galvani scale. Experimental setup as detailed in cell 2, with 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl) acting as the organic electrolyte salt. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

The forward (positive) scan was seen to consist of one or two peaks, depending on the pH. In the pH range of ~ 1.9 to ~ 3.3 two peaks were observed, referred to here as the main peak and the pre-peak. The pre-peak was always significantly smaller in magnitude than the main peak and occurred at a potential ~ 70 mV lower than the main peak. This feature is illustrated with the CV response of 25 μM HEWL at pH 1.9 in Figure 3.3.2(C).

Figure 3.3.2: Cyclic voltammetry of HEWL at different pH conditions: CV response of 25 μM HEWL at pH 0.9 (A), 1.3 (B), 1.9 (C), 2.6 (D), 3.3 (E), 4.3 (F), 5.9 (G), 8.5 (H), 10.1 (I) and 11.9 (J). Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} . Transfer potentials are corrected with respect to the TEA⁺ half wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, and are on the Galvani scale. Experimental setup as detailed in cell 1.

Interestingly, at all pH values irrespective of whether one or two peaks were observed on the forward (positive) sweep, only one peak was ever observed on the reverse (negative) sweep. A speculative interpretation of this observation suggests that perhaps an “*i-C-i*” mechanism (i.e. ion transfer – chemical process – ion transfer mechanism, equivalent to an ECE mechanism at solid electrodes) is responsible. The initial ion transfer event (on the forward sweep) is followed by a chemical step (perhaps the denaturing of the HEWL molecule at the ITIES) and then a second ion transfer event (on the reverse sweep). The two ion transfer events produce asymmetrical CV responses since the specie(s) involved in the ion transfer process are no longer chemically or perhaps structurally identical. This mechanism may also explain the extremely large HEWL peak-to-peak separation, $\Delta E_{(\text{HEWL})}$, typically indicative of an irreversible process, but here indicative of differing processes occurring on the forward and reverse scans: ion-transfer reaction involving HEWL and ion-transfer involving denatured HEWL. Native and denatured HEWL may be chemically identical but would be structurally different due to some unravelling of the amino acid chains to produce the denatured version.

$\Delta E_{(\text{HEWL})}$ varies with pH, increasing with decreasing acidity (Table 3.3.1). Neither the forward ($\Delta\phi_{f(\text{HEWL})}$) nor reverse ($\Delta\phi_{r(\text{HEWL})}$) HEWL transfer potentials were independent of pH, indicating that the charge on the protein influences both. Two distinct possibilities exist to explain the observation that $\Delta\phi_{f(\text{HEWL})}$ increases with

increasing pH. The net charge on HEWL decreases with increasing pH which may (a) result in an increased Gibbs energy of transfer being required to transfer the HEWL molecule across the interface or (b) a change of conformation of the HEWL molecule at more alkali pHs may reduce the ability of HEWL to complex and facilitate the transfer of the organic phase electrolyte anion.

Table 3.3.1: Observed trends in the HEWL forward and reverse transfer potentials and peak-to-peak separations at different pH conditions. $\Delta\phi_{f(HEWL)}$: HEWL forward sweep transfer potential. $\Delta\phi_{r(HEWL)}$: HEWL reverse sweep transfer potential. $\Delta\phi_{f(HEWL)}$ and $\Delta\phi_{r(HEWL)}$ are corrected with respect to the TEA⁺ half wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, and are on the Galvani scale. $\Delta E_{(HEWL)} = [\Delta\phi_{f(HEWL)} - \Delta\phi_{r(HEWL)}]$.

pH	$\Delta\phi_{f(HEWL)}$ mV	$\Delta\phi_{r(HEWL)}$ mV	$\Delta E_{(HEWL)}$ mV
0.9	416	237	179
1.3	396	219	177
1.6	409	204	205
1.9	426	183	243
2.6	425	180	245
3.3	428	177	251
4.3	431	187	244
5.9	449	192	257
8.5	459	196	263
9.1	475	182	293
10.2	485	173	312
11.1	n / a	n / a	n / a
11.9	n / a	n / a	n / a

The shape of the main HEWL peak on the forward sweep indicates that a diffusion-controlled process may be taking place at the liquid-liquid interface. This is in contrast to the reverse peak where the distinguishing features, of an extremely sharp drop off in current once the maximum peak current is attained, are highly indicative of an adsorption process.

3.3.1.2 Scan rate studies. In an effort to determine the diffusion coefficient of HEWL, $D_{(HEWL)}$, voltammetric scan rate studies were carried out on 10 μM HEWL at pH 2 (Figure 3.3.3). The experimental details are summarized in cell 2 (Figure 3.2.1), with 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl) as the organic phase electrolyte salt. As previously mentioned, at pH 2 both the main peak and the pre-peak are present on the forward (positive) sweep. The peak currents of the main peak on the forward sweep and the peak on the reverse sweep were found to increase linearly with the square root of the scan rate ($\nu^{1/2}$) (inset top, Figure 3.3.3). This indicated that these peak currents are limited by a diffusion-controlled process to the interface. At the lower scan rates the pre-peak on the forward sweep was clearly distinguishable from the main peak. However, with increasing scan rates the pre-peak merged with the main peak to a greater extent and becomes less distinct. The current of the pre-peak increases linearly with the scan rate (ν) indicating that an adsorption process was also taking place at the interface (inset bottom, Figure 3.3.3).

Figure 3.3.3: Scan rate studies of HEWL: CV response of blank (black) and 10 μM HEWL at scan rates of 5 (light grey), 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40 and 50 (black) mV s^{-1} . **Inset top:** Peak current (μA) versus square root of the scan rate ($(\text{V s}^{-1})^{1/2}$) for the forward and reverse HEWL peaks. **Inset bottom:** Peak current (μA) versus the scan rate (V s^{-1}) for the HEWL pre-peak on the forward sweep. Experimental setup as detailed in cell 2, with 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl) acting as the organic electrolyte salt.

The diffusion-controlled transfer processes on the forward sweep and on the reverse sweep were also found to be concentration dependent, increasing in a linear fashion with increasing HEWL concentration (Figure 3.3.4). The pre-peak on the forward sweep was also observed to be concentration dependent, increasing exponentially in the concentration range (5 – 40 μM HEWL) studied (inset bottom, Figure 3.3.4). Both $\Delta\phi_{f(\text{HEWL})}$ and $\Delta\phi_{r(\text{HEWL})}$ are independent of the HEWL concentration, remaining unchanged over the concentration range investigated.

Figure 3.3.4: Studies of increasing concentration HEWL: A representative CV response for blank (grey) and 25 μM HEWL (black) is shown. Dynamic range studied was 5 – 40 μM HEWL. **Inset top:** Peak current (μA) versus increasing concentration HEWL (μM) for the forward and reverse HEWL peaks respectively. **Inset bottom:** Peak current (μA) versus increasing concentration HEWL (μM) for the HEWL pre-peak on the forward sweep. Experimental setup as detailed in cell 2, with 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl) acting as the organic electrolyte salt. Scan rate used was 10 mV s^{-1} .

The dependence of the HEWL net charge, z_j , on pH has been studied previously by a number of groups either experimentally²⁵³⁻²⁵⁷ or computationally.^{258, 259} Kuehner et al.²⁵⁷ (1999), Haynes et al.²⁵⁶ (1994) and Tanford and Roxby²⁵⁴ (1972) have each prepared experimental hydrogen ion titration curves of HEWL in potassium chloride solutions at ionic strengths of 100 mM. The data of Kuehner et al. and Haynes et al. were in agreement, with only small deviations from each other over the entire pH range. The older data of Tanford and Roxby deviated more significantly from the other two data sets. Kuehner et al. attributed these deviations to the possible presence of protein impurities in Tanford and Roxby's titrations. Kuramitsu and Hamaguchi²⁵⁵ (1980) calculated a titration curve from experimental pK_as in 100 mM KCl solution. This curve was also in total agreement with and overlaid perfectly on titration curve of Kuehner et al.

$D_{(HEWL)}$ was determined from the experimental voltammetric scan rate data by using the modified Randles-Sevcik equation (Equation 3.3.1, and also see section 2.2.3).

$$i_{p,f(HEWL)} = (2.69 \times 10^5) z_j^{3/2} A D_j^{1/2} C_j * \nu^{1/2} \quad (\text{Eq. 3.3.1})$$

In this equation, $i_{p,f(HEWL)}$ is the forward peak current, z_j , D_j and C_j are the charge, diffusion coefficient, and bulk concentration of the analyte species controlling the transfer process. z_j was assumed to be the net charge of the HEWL molecule. The value of z_j varies as the HEWL molecule becomes progressively more protonated with decreasing pH. The charge on the HEWL molecule at pH 2 was estimated from the calculated titration curve of Kuramitsu and Hamaguchi to be approximately 17+.²⁵⁵ From the slope of the modified Randles-Sevcik plot (inset top, Figure 3.3.3), $i_{p,f(HEWL)} / \nu^{1/2} = 286.8 \mu\text{A V}^{-1/2} \text{s}^{1/2}$, the diffusion coefficient was calculated as $2.3 \times$

$10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ from the main peak on the forward sweep, which is in reasonable agreement with the reported HEWL diffusion coefficient of $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.²⁶⁰

3.3.1.3 Comparison of theoretical and experiment HEWL peak currents in the range $0 < \text{pH} < 14$. A theoretical peak current curve over the entire pH range was generated for the main HEWL peak on the forward sweep. This was achieved by applying the modified Randles-Sevcik equation at intervals of $\frac{1}{4}$ of a pH unit in the pH range 0-14. The values of z_j used to calculate the theoretical $i_{p,f(HEWL)}$ in this study were taken from the experimental data of Kuehner et al.²⁵⁷ (between pH 2.5-11.5) and from the calculated titration curve of Kuramitsu and Hamaguchi²⁵⁵ (in the pH ranges 0-2.5 and 11.5-14). Since the value of z_j was now known at each pH and $D_{(HEWL)}$ was determined experimentally, the theoretical peak current curve in the pH range 0-14 was generated for the forward main peak (Figure 3.3.5).

Figure 3.3.5: Comparison of the experimental (black dots) and theoretical (solid line) cyclic voltammetry peak current responses for 25 μM HEWL with varying pH. Theoretical response derived from HEWL titration curves in 100 mM potassium chloride solutions.^{255, 257} Experimental setup as detailed in cell 1.

Despite the non-reversible nature of the HEWL CV response the experimental peak current followed remarkably close to the theoretical curve for HEWL. This indicated that the current-pH behaviour of HEWL was dominated by the charge of the biomolecule at each pH. A deviation between the experimental and theory curves was seen in the acidic region between pH 1.6 and 3.3 with considerably lower peak currents than expected being observed. Additionally, no electrochemical response was observed for HEWL at pH values approaching and above the pI of HEWL (illustrated in Figure 3.3.2(J)). This trend was also observed for insulin⁷⁹ and haemoglobin⁷⁸ at

the ITIES. It seems that the net neutral and negatively charged biomolecules are either (a) incapable of transferring across the ITIES themselves or (b) incapable of facilitating the transfer of the organic anion TPBCl⁻, or other organic electrolyte species, across the ITIES.

3.3.1.4 Trends in $\Delta E_{(TEA^+)}$ in the presence and absence of HEWL. The TEA⁺ peak-to-peak separation ($\Delta E_{(TEA^+)}$) was greater in the presence of HEWL than in its absence (Figure 3.3.6). This can be explained by the adsorption of HEWL at the interface, inhibiting the transfer of TEA⁺ across the ITIES. A thick white layer is observed at the ITIES which visibly increased when carrying out experiments in the pH range 6 – 11. The increase in $\Delta E_{(TEA^+)}$ in the presence of HEWL signified that the TEA⁺ transfer became quasi-irreversible. As the pH increased to 11.3, approaching the isoelectric point (pI) of HEWL, a very large increase in $\Delta E_{(TEA^+)}$ was observed in the presence of HEWL but not in its absence. Moving to pH values in excess of the pI a subsequent decrease in $\Delta E_{(TEA^+)}$ was noted in the presence of HEWL (Figure 3.3.6).

Figure 3.3.6: Comparison of the peak-to-peak separation (ΔE) of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ in the presence (solid dots) and absence (hollow squares) of $25 \mu\text{M HEWL}$ at different pH conditions.

From the observed trends in Figure 3.3.6 it is clear that the amount of HEWL adsorbed at the ITIES decreases as the pH is moved away from the pI. Lu et al.²⁶¹ report an identical observation in relation to the adsorption of HEWL at an air-water interface at a similarly low ionic strength (0.02 mol dm^{-3}). They use neutron reflection to study the variation of the adsorbed HEWL surface excess and the thickness of the adsorbed HEWL layer at the interface with pH. In their analysis they attribute the combined effects of two distinct phenomena to produce the observed trends, namely

(a) electrostatic repulsion within the adsorbed layer and (b) solubility of the HEWL molecules in solution.

Firstly, when the electrostatic repulsion within the adsorbed layer is at a minimum the layer will be at maximum thickness. At the pI the net charge within the HEWL molecule is at a minimum, thus the electrostatic repulsive forces are at a minimum and the adsorbed layer will be at maximum thickness. On shifting the solution pH away from the pI an increase of the net charge within the HEWL molecule will occur and cause a resultant increase in lateral electrostatic repulsive forces. Secondly, the charge density of the HEWL molecule increases on shifting the solution pH away from the pI. The HEWL molecule is more hydrophilic in nature, its solubility increases in the aqueous phase solution and less lysozyme adsorbs at the ITIES.

3.3.2 Influence of aqueous phase ionic strength

The influence of the ionic strength of the aqueous phase solution on the CV response to 25 μM HEWL was investigated (Figure 3.3.7 and Table 3.3.2). The electrolyte concentration of LiCl was varied in the range 1 mM to 100 mM. The pH, as previously mentioned, has numerous effects on the CV response of HEWL. Therefore each solution was maintained at pH 2 by the addition of 10 mM HCl, as detailed in cell 3 (Figure 3.2.1). At the chosen pH of 2 the effect of ionic strength on the pre-peak and main peak of the forward sweep could be investigated. The total ionic strengths of each aqueous phase (before the addition of HEWL) were determined to be 0.011, 0.02, 0.06, and 0.11 M for electrolyte solutions of 10 mM HCl plus 1, 10, 50 and 100 mM LiCl respectively. The ionic strengths were calculated using Equation 3.3.2,

$$I_c = \frac{1}{2} \sum_j^n C_j * z_j^2 \quad (\text{Eq. 3.3.2})$$

where I_c is the total ionic strength of the electrolyte (mol dm^{-3}), $C_j *$ is the molar bulk concentration of the ion j (mol dm^{-3}), and z_j is the charge on that ion j . The sum is then taken over all ions in solution.

Table 3.3.2: Effect of the ionic strength of the aqueous phase solution on the HEWL forward and reverse transfer potentials and peak-to-peak separations. Transfer potentials are corrected with respect to the TEA⁺ half wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, are on the Galvani scale.

Ionic Strength of Aqueous Phase mol dm⁻³	$\Delta\phi_{f(\text{HEWL})}$ mV	$\Delta\phi_{r(\text{HEWL})}$ mV	$\Delta E_{(\text{HEWL})}$ mV
0.011	410	169	241
0.02	389	183	206
0.06	383	198	185
0.11	360	206	154

Increasing the ionic strength of the aqueous phase electrolyte from $0.011 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to 0.11 mol dm^{-3} caused a marked decrease in the magnitude of the pre-peak in terms of peak current and charge, ultimately causing it to disappear altogether with increased ionic strength (Figure 3.3.7). At low pHs and high ionic strengths the solubility of the HEWL molecule is expected to increase. A reduced adsorbed layer is present at the ITIES due to the association of the excess salt ions in solution with the protein molecule, lowering its tendency to adsorb.

Figure 3.3.7: The effect of the ionic strength of the aqueous phase solution on the cyclic voltammetry response of HEWL: CV response of 25 μM HEWL at aqueous solution ionic strengths of (A) 0.011 M, (B) 0.02 M, (C) 0.06 M, and (D) 0.11 M. Transfer potentials are corrected with respect to the TEA⁺ half wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, and are on the Galvani scale. Experimental setup as detailed in cell 3. Scan rate used was 5 mVs^{-1} .

The TEA⁺ adjusted peak potentials of the forward main HEWL peak ($\Delta\phi_{f(HEWL)}$) appeared at successively lower potentials while those of the reverse HEWL peak ($\Delta\phi_{r(HEWL)}$) appeared at successively higher potentials with increasing ionic strength (Table 3.3.2). Thus, the peak-to-peak separation of the HEWL forward and reverse peaks ($\Delta E_{(HEWL)}$) were seen to decrease with increasing ionic strength (Table 3.3.2). It is a well known phenomenon that as the ionic strength of a solution varies it may cause a change in the globular conformation of a protein molecule.²⁶² The conformational change of HEWL may result in the exposure of more hydrophobic pockets or fragments of the molecule. In this case the hydrophobic pockets of the HEWL molecule, necessary to facilitate the transfer of the hydrophobic TPBCl⁻ molecule across the ITIES, may be more accessible and thus result in a reduced Gibbs energy of transfer, observed in Table 3.3.2 and Figure 3.3.7, with increasing ionic strength.

3.3.3 Influence of the organic phase electrolyte anion

Previous studies indicate that the degree of hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity of the organic phase electrolyte anion influences the voltammetric response of a selection of biomolecules. This phenomenon was initially reported by Trojaneck et al.⁷⁷ who observed that the more hydrophobic organic electrolyte anions shifted the transfer peak potentials (positive and negative) of protamine (a polypeptide) at the ITIES to higher values. The three anions investigated in their study were tetrakis(4-fluorophenyl)borate, tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)-borate and tetraphenylborate (or TFPB⁻, TPBCl⁻ and TPB⁻, respectively), with the transfer peaks appearing at successively higher potentials in order of increasing hydrophobicity, $\Delta\phi_{TPB} < \Delta\phi_{TPBCl} < \Delta\phi_{TFPB}$.

More recently we have reported a similar trend with the transfer potentials of haemoglobin⁷⁸ and insulin⁷⁹ at the water | 1,2-dichloroethane interface. From a mechanistic point of view, the main HEWL peak on the forward sweep may arise due to the transfer of the organic anion from o to w. If this is indeed the case one would expect the more hydrophobic anion to require a higher Gibbs energy on transferring into the aqueous phase (and therefore appear at a higher potential).

Figure 3.3.8: The effect of the organic anion on the cyclic voltammetry response of HEWL: CV response of 10 μM HEWL with (A) TPFB⁻, (B) TPBCl⁻ and (C) TPB⁻ acting as the organic anion. Transfer potentials are corrected with respect to the TEA⁺ half wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, and are on the Galvani scale. Experimental setup as detailed in cell 2. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

Table 3.3.3: Effect of the nature of the organic anion on the HEWL forward and reverse transfer potentials and peak-to-peak separations. Transfer potentials are corrected with respect to the TEA⁺ half wave potential, $E^{1/2}$, and are on the Galvani scale.

Organic Electrolyte Salt	$\Delta\phi_{f(HEWL)}$ mV	$\Delta\phi_{r(HEWL)}$ mV	$\Delta E_{(HEWL)}$ mV
(BTPPA)(TPFB)	413	186	227
(BTPPA)(TPBCl)	408	180	228
(BTPPA)(TPB)	296	108	188

The influence of the three different electrolyte anions on the voltammetry of 10 μM HEWL at pH 2 was investigated (Figure 3.3.8). Near identical CVs were obtained in the presence of TFPB⁻ and TPBCl⁻ in terms of their shape, peak currents, charges and peak potentials of the forward and reverse peaks. A very slight increase in the peak potentials of the forward and reverse peaks was noted in the presence of the more hydrophobic TFPB⁻, and no variation in $\Delta E_{(HEWL)}$ was noted between the two anions (Table 3.3.3). However, in the presence of the least hydrophobic TPB⁻, a significantly different CV response was observed. In terms of shape no pre-peak on the forward sweep was evident at pH 2 and the main HEWL forward peak was less well defined, being significantly more obscured due to the transfer of the background electrolyte than was the case with TFPB⁻ and TPBCl⁻. The peak potentials of the forward and reverse peaks in the presence of TPB⁻ occurred at lower values than with the more hydrophobic anions, with the overall trend of $\Delta\phi_{TPB} < \Delta\phi_{TPBCl} \leq \Delta\phi_{TFPB}$ in agreement with the previous studies.⁷⁷⁻⁷⁹ A significant decrease in $\Delta E_{(HEWL)}$ was also noted with TPB⁻ (Table 3.3.3). The charge and peak current of the reverse TPB⁻ peak were also smaller, with the following overall trends observed $Q_{TPB} < Q_{TPBCl} \approx Q_{TFPB}$ and $i_{p,r(TPB)} < i_{p,r(TPBCl)} \approx i_{p,r(TFPB)}$. These trends are identical to those found with haemoglobin⁷⁸ and insulin⁷⁹ but opposite to that found with protamine.⁷⁷ The data

suggests that the interaction of HEWL with the organic electrolyte anion increases with increasing hydrophobicity of the anion, in the order $\text{TPB}^- < \text{TPBCl}^- \approx \text{TFPB}^-$.

The crystallographic structure and the distributions of the charged groups of the model globular protein HEWL have been thoroughly characterised and can be obtained from the Worldwide Protein Data Bank.²⁶³ Lu et al.²⁶¹ discuss the charge distributions and identify the most hydrophilic region of the protein being close to the C-terminus (due to the presence of a dense charge distribution) and lesser hydrophilic regions being located around the cleft of the active site and the N-terminus. A hydrophobic pocket or region will be characterised by an almost complete absence of charge residues. Lu et al. identify one such area of HEWL as the side opposite the cleft of the active site.²⁶¹ Perhaps this hydrophobic region of the HEWL molecule is in close proximity to the cationic binding sites that the organic anions interact with.

3.3.4 Influence of time

The influence of time on the voltammetric response of HEWL was investigated by means of repetitive potentiodynamic cycling of 25 μM HEWL at pH 2. The potential waveform applied is shown in Figure 3.3.9(A). The initial potential was set at 0.25 V for 20s, scanned to 0.85 V and then back to 0.25 V at a rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . Subsequently, the cell was set at open circuit potential (o. c. p.) for 180 s before the waveform was repeated. In total 100 such repetitive runs using this procedure were completed. An appropriate pH at which to carry out the experiment was deemed to be pH 2 since under these conditions the pre-peak on the forward sweep, in addition to the main HEWL forward peak and the reverse peak, may be studied.

Figure 3.3.9: Repetitive CVs of HEWL at the ITIES. CV response, at 5 mV s^{-1} , in the presence (**B**) and in the absence (**C**) of $25 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ HEWL. (**A**) represents the potential waveform applied for the repetitive CVs study. (**B**) CVs 2 (light grey), 6, 10, 14, 18, 22, 26, 30, 35, 40 and 50 (black). (**C**) CVs 1, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60 and 70. Experimental setup as detailed in cell 2, with 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl) acting as the organic electrolyte salt.

It was initially observed that the HEWL pre-peak differed significantly between the 1st and the 2nd potentiodynamic scans (Figure 3.3.10). The pre-peak on the 1st scan was considerably more peak-shaped and occurred at a slightly lower potential than the pre-peak on the 2nd scan. This behaviour was reproducible and was first noticed when running preliminary CV experiments in triplicate.

The response to $25 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ HEWL was seen to change significantly over time (Figure 3.3.9(B)). A white precipitate was observed at the ITIES on completion of the 100 CVs. On the forward (positive) sweep the following changes were observed with successive scans:

- the peak currents of both the pre-peak and the main peak increased,
- the peak potential of the main peak remained constant,
- the peak potential of the pre-peak shifted to lower potentials,
- the pre-peak increased in magnitude (both in terms of peak current and broadness) at a greater rate than the main peak,
- after 45-50 scans both peaks on the forward sweep merged.

On the reverse (negative) sweep the following changes were observed with successive scans:

- the peak current and charge of the reverse peak increased,
- the peak potential of the reverse peak decreased,
- the peak became broader.

Figure 3.3.10: (A) Comparison of blank (light grey), CV 1 (black) and CV 2 (dark grey). (B) Expansion of the area in (A) highlighted in the dashed box. A change in behaviour of the HEWL pre-peak on the forward sweep is clearly evident with successive scans. Experimental setup as detailed in cell 2, with 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl) acting as the organic electrolyte salt. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

A control experiment was carried out consisting of 100 repetitive cycles, following the same procedure outlined in Figure 3.3.9(A), in the absence of HEWL (Figure 3.3.9(C)). This experiment was necessary in order to determine that the white

precipitate, (clearly visible in the picture of an electrochemical cell in Figure 3.3.11), was due to the presence of HEWL at the interface and not electrolyte ion interactions at the ITIES. Interestingly, despite the formation of a white precipitate at the interface the aqueous and organic phases remain clear throughout (Figure 3.3.11). This is in contrast to the studies of haemoglobin⁷⁸ and insulin⁷⁹ where the aqueous phases are red (due to the presence of iron in the heme groups) and cloudy white (due to the limited solubility of insulin), respectively. From the selected voltammograms shown in Figure 3.3.9(C) it is clear that the electrochemical processes that give rise to the evolving peak shapes with successive scans in Figure 3.3.9(B) were due to HEWL alone and no additional electrochemical processes occurred in its absence. The ITIES was also perfectly clear after 100 cycles in the absence of HEWL.

Figure 3.3.11: Picture of the interface after 100 CVs. **(A)** Aqueous phase containing 25 μM HEWL. **(B)** Liquid-Liquid interface with white HEWL film visible. **(C)** Organic phase.

Based on these results it is may be surmised that a time-dependent process (in a similar fashion to that observed with haemoglobin⁷⁸), such as adsorption or re-arrangement of HEWL molecules at the ITIES is taking place.

3.3.5 Proposed mechanism of HEWL electrochemical response

As previously mentioned, the mechanism of the HEWL electrochemical response on application of a triangular potential waveform with cyclic voltammetry may be thought of in terms of an *i*-C-*i* mechanism, see Reaction Scheme 3.3.1.

Reaction Scheme 3.3.1

On the forward (positive) sweep the positively charged HEWL molecule in the aqueous phase diffuses to the ITIES. The main HEWL peak on the forward scan may be due to the facilitated transfer of the organic electrolyte anion from o to w by HEWL and the subsequent formation of an ion-pair complex on the aqueous side of the ITIES (1). The rationale behind this thinking is two-fold. Firstly the peak current of the main HEWL peak on the forward sweep increases linearly with the square-root of the scan rate and has diffusional peak shaped features. The diffusion process in question here is the diffusion of the HEWL to the ITIES, the HEWL being present in considerably lower concentrations than the organic electrolyte anion. Secondly, we have clearly shown that the CV features in the presence of HEWL differ considerably depending on the nature of the organic electrolyte anion, in particular the fact that the more hydrophobic the anion the higher the formal transfer potential observed for the main HEWL peak on the forward sweep.

The protein/organic anion complex may then adsorb at the ITIES **(2)**. This “adsorption event” hypothesis is supported by the pre-peak on the forward sweep (the current of which increases linearly with the scan rate) and the visible formation of a white layer of adsorbed material at the ITIES with repetitive CV runs. The transfer of TEA⁺ across the ITIES was seen to be impeded by the presence of adsorbed HEWL at the ITIES, with the adsorbed layer reaching its maximum thickness at the pI of HEWL due to a combination of reduced HEWL solubility in the aqueous phase and reduced electrostatic repulsive forces within the adsorbed layer. The chemical step of this *i-C-i* mechanism may involve the denaturing of the HEWL molecule once the organic anion transfers across the ITIES and forms an ion-pair with it. Both ion-pair complexes, either adsorbed at the interface or in close proximity to the interface, denature to produce the same “denatured HEWL-organic anion complex” on the aqueous side of the ITIES **(3(a) & 3(b))**. Thus, a single peak is observed on the reverse (negative) sweep at a significantly lower peak potential than the forward sweep peaks. This peak has clear desorption features but the peak current increases linearly with the square-root of the scan rate (indicating a diffusion process is the rate limiting factor in this case). The diffusion-related features of this peak may be as a result of an as yet unknown kinetic feature of the proposed mechanism, which will form the basis of further studies. The desorption features are likely due to the stripping of TPBCl⁻, located at the ITIES as an ion-pair with denatured HEWL, into the organic phase **(4)**.

3.4 Conclusions

On investigation with cyclic voltammetry, hen-egg-white lysozyme (HEWL) was found to be electroactive at the polarised liquid-liquid interface. The shape of the HEWL CV, magnitude of the charge transfer, peak currents and transfer peak potentials were all dependent on the pH of the aqueous phase solution. In particular the current-pH behaviour of HEWL is dominated by the charge of the biomolecule at each pH, as indicated by the remarkably close relationship between the experimental peak currents and the theoretical curve for HEWL (calculated using the modified Randles-Sevcik equation). The adsorption of HEWL at the ITIES is suggested by the linear relationship of the peak current of the pre-peak on the forward (positive) sweep with the scan rate, the substantial variation of the voltammetric response with time and the formation of a white film of precipitate at the interface in the presence of HEWL. This white film was also seen to impede the transfer of TEA^+ across the ITIES, with maximum impedance occurring at the pI of HEWL where the adsorbed layer will be thickest. Increasing the ionic strength of the aqueous phase was seen to increase the solubility of the HEWL molecule in solution, ultimately causing the disappearance of the adsorption pre-peak. The facilitated transfer of the organic electrolyte anion by the adsorbed HEWL is implied by the diffusion-limited main peak on the forward sweep. In addition, the interaction of HEWL with the organic electrolyte anion was seen to increase with increasing hydrophobicity of the anion, in the order $\text{TPB}^- < \text{TPBCl}^- \approx \text{TFPB}^-$. As mentioned, the formation of an ion-pair at the ITIES between the adsorbed HEWL molecule and the transferred organic electrolyte anion may cause a conformational change or denaturing of the HEWL molecule. On the basis of these observations, the electrochemical behaviour of biological

macromolecules at immiscible liquid-liquid interfaces is complex and will require studies involving in situ optical methods and electrochemical simulation to further elucidate the details. Nevertheless, electrochemical techniques can still provide a basis for the label-free detection of protein molecules in a non-redox manner,³¹ together with characterising the effect of a host of experimental variables (i.e. pH, solution ionic strengths, time etc.) on the detection signal.

Chapter 4

Electrochemical characterisation of ion transfer at μ ITIES arrays under stationary and flowing conditions

4.1 Introduction

μ ITIES confined within the walls of solid-state silicon micropore arrays, developed at the Tyndall National Institute by Arrigan and co-workers,¹¹⁹ were electrochemically characterised by the voltammetric transfer of the model ion tetraethylammonium cation (TEA^+) across the interface under stationary and flowing conditions. Cyclic voltammetry experiments under stationary conditions were used to study the influence of different micropore array geometries on the shape of the $i - \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$ curves and limiting currents observed for ion transfer, with the organic phase present as an organogel. As noted in sections 1.3.4 and 1.3.5, the pore radii (r_a), pore centre-to-centre spacing (r_c), the number of pores in the array (N_p), diffusion coefficients of the transferring ion, j , in the aqueous and organic phases (D_j^{α} and D_j^{β} , respectively),

the position of the liquid-liquid interface within the micropore channel, and the timescale of the experiment (essentially, the voltammetric potential window chosen and scan rate, ν , applied) will all influence the cyclic voltammetric response. The specific micropore array geometries and experimental conditions implemented for TEA⁺ transfer under stationary conditions at the μ ITIES in this chapter have been computationally simulated by Dr. Jörg Strutwolf,²⁶⁴ and allow a comparison of experimental, calculated and simulated data.

The μ ITIES arrays were also characterised by amperometry under hydrodynamic conditions by their incorporation into a poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE) flow cell. The influence of volumetric flow rate on the amperometric response of TEA⁺ at the μ ITIES was investigated. Preliminary cyclic voltammetry experiments with this experimental setup by Dr. Alfonso Berduque²¹¹ have shown that, under flowing conditions, positively (TEA⁺) and negatively (4-ocylbenzenesulfonate anion, (4-OBSA⁻)) charged analyte species produce asymmetric diffusion profiles on either side of the μ ITIES.

For analytical applications of such flow injection analysis (FIA) systems, the mechanical instability of the liquid-liquid interface must be circumvented by gellification of the organic phase with poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) (see section 1.3.10) or insertion of solid porous membrane materials between the two immiscible solutions (see section 1.3.2). Inevitable reductions in diffusion coefficients of the analyte ions, associated with gellification of the organic phase, have not proven problematic when monitoring ion transfer by amperometric and voltammetric methods. Increases in

resistance in the cell due to gellification have been off-set by incorporating micropore or microhole arrays into the experimental setup.^{17, 19}

As noted by several authors,^{20, 182, 191} amperometric sensors as opposed to potentiometric, are more suitable for incorporation into FIA systems. Amperometric sensors have the ability to alter the selectivity of ion transfer across the interface by controlling the Galvani potential difference ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi = \phi^{\alpha} - \phi^{\beta}$) using a potentiostat. Essentially, this allows selective transfer (or extraction) of ions from one phase to the other by applying a potential difference across the interface ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$) that corresponds to the characteristic formal ion transfer potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{\circ}$) for that particular species. Thus, in this manner, a mixture of ions in solution may be selectively detected or separated. In contrast, potentiometric sensors lack the same degree of discrimination

4.2 Experimental details

4.2.1 Procedure for μ ITIES array experiments under stationary conditions

The composition of the electrochemical cell used under stationary and flowing conditions is illustrated in Figure 4.2.1. Five micropore array designs were used in these studies and the geometries of the individual arrays (r_a , r_c , and N_p) are shown in Table 4.2.1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the five designs are shown in Figure 4.2.2. Once the apparatus was set-up, as detailed in section 2.3.2, repetitive blank CVs (i.e. no TEA⁺ present in the liquid phase) were run, five in total at intervals of 180 s. The initial starting potential, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_i$, for each of these CVs was set at 0.05 V and the switching potential, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_{\lambda}$, at 1.05 V. A quiet time of 10 s was set

prior to each run and scan rates of 10 mV s^{-1} were applied, with the exception of the varying scan rate experiment. Subsequently an aliquot of TEA^+ solution (prepared in an aqueous 10 mM LiCl solution) was injected into the aqueous phase using a calibrated micropipette to produce a TEA^+ concentration of $100 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$, and five repetitive CVs were run, as for the blank CVs. Background subtracted CVs of $100 \text{ }\mu\text{M TEA}^+$ were obtained using the CH Instruments software. This background subtraction procedure produced artefacts at higher potentials, as shown in the experimental CVs.

Figure 4.2.1: The electrochemical cell utilised for the study of ion transfer of the model ion TEA^+ at the μITIES under stationary and flowing conditions.

4.2.2 Procedure for μITIES array experiments under flowing conditions

The composition of the electrochemical cell is identical to that used under stationary conditions (Figure 4.2.1), and micropore array design 2 (Figure 4.2.2) was selected for incorporation into the flowing μITIES setup. Specifically, the variation of the amperometric response of TEA^+ with flow rate at the μITIES array was investigated. The cell was setup as detailed in section 2.3.3 and filled with the aqueous phase (10 mM LiCl). The cell setup and parameters were verified prior to each experiment by attaining a stationary CV of the blank, as described in section 2.3.3.

Berduque et al.^{20, 21, 211} have shown that the magnitude of the TEA^+ transfer peak depends on the applied potential difference across the interface ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$). A cationic species will transfer from w to o on the application of an applied potential positive of the analyte's formal ion transfer potential, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{\circ}$. $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{\circ}$ for the specific analyte can

be determined prior to amperometric extraction by running a cyclic voltammogram under flowing conditions. This CV experiment, in the case of TEA⁺ transfer across the μ ITIES under flowing conditions, was carried out previously by Dr. Alfonso Berduque.²¹¹ A potential of 0.9 V was determined to be sufficiently positive of $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{\circ'}$ for TEA⁺ to ensure a maximum rate of extraction. A balance must be reached between a high enough value of $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ to ensure the maximum extraction of TEA⁺, but not too high a value of $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ that would result in the co-extraction of the background electrolyte ions.

Thus, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ was set to the sufficiently positive value, using amperometry, of 0.9 V so as to ensure a maximum rate at which TEA⁺ can be extracted into the organogel. Flow in the cell was set at the particular volumetric flow rate to be studied, one of 0.05, 0.15, 0.25, 0.35, 0.5, 0.65, 0.8 or 1.00 mL min⁻¹, and the background current allowed to stabilise. Subsequently an injection of 1 mM TEA⁺ in 10 mM LiCl was performed using the 100 μ L volume sample loop and the amperometric response recorded.

Table 4.2.1: Characteristics of the pores of the different solid-state membranes evaluated by SEM. Pore radius and pore centre-to-centre separation are values averaged over six pores (with the exception of design 1, where values were averaged over three pores).

Design	Pore radius, $r_a / \mu\text{m}$	Pore centre-to-centre separation, $r_c / \mu\text{m}$	Number of pores in the array, N_p
1	25.50 ± 0.09	985.73 ± 1.50	3
2	26.00 ± 0.01	491.27 ± 2.87	8
3	25.35 ± 0.02	246.15 ± 0.90	23
4	25.34 ± 0.11	99.06 ± 0.49	105
5	10.41 ± 0.04	99.38 ± 0.43	120

Design 1

Design 2

Design 3

Design 4

Design 5

Figure 4.2.2: SEM images of the five different micropore array designs used to support the μ TIES arrays. See table 4.2.1 for the geometric parameters of each array.

4.3 Results and discussion

4.3.1 Cyclic voltammetry of ion transfer at stationary μ ITIES arrays: the forward sweep

Using the theory developed by Compton and co-workers¹²³ and by Saito et al.,¹²⁵ outlined in detail in section 1.3.6, an estimation of whether each of the five μ ITIES array designs fulfill the conditions necessary for non-interacting diffusion zones, on transfer of a model ion from the aqueous to the organic phase under the voltammetric experimental conditions employed, is possible. These predictions are based on an assumption that the organogel is inlaid on the aqueous side of the micropore channel. Validation of this assumption is as follows:

- The organogel filling procedure is highly amenable to creating aqueous inlaid microinterfaces. The pore walls are hydrophobic in nature, a remnant feature arising from their fabrication process (see section 2.3.2). Consequently, the inner surface of the pore is easily wetted by an organogel introduced as a hot liquid into the borosilicate glass cylinder directly on top of the micropore array membrane.
- Previous ion transfer characterisation studies of these μ ITIES arrays by Zazpe et al.,¹¹⁹ using a non-gellified organic phase, estimated an interfacial recess depth of between 1 and 10 μm for the 100 μm deep pores by comparing experimental current densities to those calculated from the analytical expression developed by Bond et al.¹²⁰ (Equation 1.3.2) for recessed microdisc electrodes.

- Most importantly, however, simulations by Dr. Jörg Strutwolf,²⁶⁴ based on the CV experimental data at each μ ITIES array design to be outlined in this chapter, indicate a maximal interfacial recess of 2.5 μm for a pore with a depth of 100 μm and pore radius of ca. 25 μm . An inlaid liquid-liquid interface at the aqueous side of the micropore channel is therefore well within the experimental error limit. Strutwolf also notes that a hemisphere of organic phase (analogous to a hemisphere microelectrode geometry)^{97, 118} may protrude at the pore mouth on the aqueous side of the membrane due to the hydrophobic nature of the micropores. However; he concludes that, due to the limited resolution and reproducibility of the CV experiment, electrochemical characterisation by ion transfer of the μ ITIES does not allow differentiation between inlaid and hemisphere geometries. Thus within experimental error the interface should be considered aqueous inlaid.²⁶⁴

The four diffusion regime categories that may be established on transfer of TEA^+ from the aqueous to the organic phase are outlined in Figure 1.3.4 and discussed in detail in section 1.3.5. The methods of estimating the conditions necessary for non-interacting diffusion zones: (a) as a function of the pore radii, r_a , by Saito et al.,¹²⁵ and (b) by estimating the extension of the diffusion zone, δ , around individual micropores in a μ ITIES array as a function of the applied scan rate, ν , by Compton and co-workers,¹²³ are applied to μ ITES array designs 1 to 5 in Tables 4.3.1 and 4.3.2. Diffusion zone overlap between adjacent μ ITIES is predicted when $\delta > 0.5r_c$.

Table 4.3.1: The conditions for non-interacting diffusion zones at arrays of μ ITIES from theory developed by Saito et al.¹²⁵ are fulfilled when $r_c > 12r_a$. The calculation is based on the transfer of TEA⁺ from $w \rightarrow o$ at aqueous inlaid μ ITIES.

Design	$12r_a / \mu\text{m}$	$r_c / \mu\text{m}$	$0.5r_c / \mu\text{m}$
1	306.00	985.73 ± 1.50	492.87
2	312.00	491.27 ± 2.87	245.64
3	304.20	246.15 ± 0.90	123.08
4	304.08	99.06 ± 0.49	49.53
5	124.92	99.38 ± 0.43	49.69

Table 4.3.2: Estimation of the extension of the diffusion zone (δ), as a function of the applied scan rate (ν), around individual micropores in a μ ITIES array from theory developed by Compton and co-workers.¹²³ Diffusion zone overlap between adjacent μ ITIES is predicted when $\delta > 0.5r_c$. Values of $0.5r_c$ are summarised for each μ ITIES design in Table 4.3.1. The calculation is based on the transfer of TEA⁺ from $w \rightarrow o$ at aqueous inlaid μ ITIES, with $D_j^\alpha = 9.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (the diffusion coefficient of TEA⁺ in the aqueous phase).

ν / Vs^{-1}	$\delta \approx \sqrt{2D_j^\alpha \frac{\Delta(\Delta_{\beta}^\alpha \phi)}{\nu}} / \mu\text{m}$
0.0025	484.98
0.005	342.93
0.0075	280.00
0.01	242.49
0.0125	216.89
0.15	197.99

Category A type diffusion, where $\delta < r_a$ is highly unlikely as, in order to achieve such a diffusion profile, the applied scan rate would have to be significantly faster than the 10 mV s^{-1} implemented. Category B type diffusion, where spherical diffusion fields are established around each μ ITIES but remain mutually exclusive (ensuring the ideal situation from an analytical point of view where the limiting faradaic current/charging current ratio is maximised) will be observed when $\delta < 0.5r_c$ and $\delta > r_a$, and/or when $r_c > 12r_a$. Saito et al. (Table 4.3.1) predict a type B diffusion regime for μ ITIES arrays designs 1 and 2. Compton and co-workers (Table 4.3.2) predict a type B diffusion regime for μ ITIES array design 1 with $\nu \geq 2.5 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ and for μ ITIES design 2 with $\nu \geq 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$. In agreement with these predictions, on the timescale of

the experiments ($\nu = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$, potential range = 1 V), steady-state sigmoidal $i - \Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$ curves on the forward sweep for CV at μ ITIES array designs 1 and 2 on the transfer of TEA^+ from $w \rightarrow o$ were observed, see Figure 4.3.1.

Figure 4.3.1: Cyclic voltammetry of a blank system (grey) and $100 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ (black) using micropore array designs 1 (A) and 2 (B) to support arrays of μ ITIES. Experimental setup as detailed in Figure 4.2.1. Scan rate applied was 10 mV s^{-1} .

Category C type diffusion, where the individual diffusion zones overlap on the timescale of the voltammetric experiment, and category D type diffusion, where the individual diffusion zones interact to such a large extent that the μ ITIES array effectively operates as a macroITIES, will both be characterised by a peak-shaped

response on the forward sweep and can be difficult to distinguish between based on the voltammograms shape alone. As will be discussed in section 4.3.4, if category D type diffusion is present then the experimentally observed i_p will be in agreement with i_p calculated by the Randles-Sevcik equation for that particular μ ITIES array. However, if category C type diffusion is present then the experimentally observed i_p will exceed i_p calculated by the Randles-Sevcik equation due to enhancement by a spherical diffusion component.

Each of the micropore array designs 3, 4 and 5 fail to fulfill the conditions set by Saito et al. (Table 4.3.1) or by Compton and co-workers (Table 4.3.2) for non-interacting diffusion zones under the voltammetric experimental conditions employed, with all three expected to exhibit either category C or category D type diffusion regimes on transfer of TEA⁺ from w \rightarrow o. The values of r_c for designs 4 and 5 are approximately identical, the difference being the pore radius which is ca. 25 μ m for design 4 and ca. 10 μ m for design 5. Therefore, the current peak is expected to be more pronounced for design 4 due to greater overlap between the individual diffusion zones. Oncemore, in agreement with predictions, on the timescale of the experiments ($\nu = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$), peak-shaped $i - \Delta_\beta^\alpha \phi$ curves on the forward sweep for CV at μ ITIES array designs 3, 4 and 5 on the transfer of TEA⁺ from w \rightarrow o were observed, see Figure 4.3.2.

Figure 4.3.2: Cyclic voltammetry of a blank system (grey) and 100 μM TEA⁺ (black) using micropore array designs 3 (A), 4 (B) and 5 (C) to support arrays of μTIES . Experimental setup as detailed in Figure 4.2.1. Scan rate applied was 10 mV s^{-1} .

4.3.2 Cyclic voltammetry of ion transfer at stationary μ ITIES arrays: the reverse sweep

Each of the five μ ITIES arrays exhibit very prominent peak-shaped responses on the back-transfer of TEA⁺ from the organogel to the aqueous phase, as shown in Figures 4.3.1 and 4.3.2. Two separate diffusion regimes, categories E and H (outlined in Figure 1.3.4 and discussed in detail in section 1.3.5), may be responsible for these observations.

A linear diffusion profile is established in category E due to the confinement of the ion in the micropore channel after the initial transfer event. Thus, on back-transfer no spherical diffusion fields may be established. An ion will be confined within the micropore channel on the timescale of the voltammetric experiment under two conditions: (a) due to a very fast scan rate applied or (b) due to a very slow analyte diffusion coefficient in the organic phase, D_j^β . Clearly, the gellification of the organic phase will significantly reduce D_j^β .

Alternatively, a linear diffusion profile is established in category H due to two individual linear diffusion fields being established, and reinforcing each other, on transfer of the ion from o \rightarrow w. Linear diffusion occurs both within the confines of the micropore channel and also to the mouth of the micropore on the organic side (due to overlap of the individual spherical diffusion zones to such an extent that a linear diffusion profile, akin to a macroITIES, is established). This scenario is unlikely, however, due to the gellified nature of the organic phase. This means D_j^β is reduced, and at a minimum $D_j^\alpha > D_j^\beta$. As discussed in section 4.3.1, at μ ITIES array designs 1

and 2 the pores are separated at a sufficient distance to ensure non-interacting diffusion zones under the experimental conditions employed ($\nu = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$). Thus, since $D_j^\alpha > D_j^\beta$, the likelihood of overlapping spherical diffusion fields at the organic end of the micropore channel on the back-transfer, within the timescale of the voltammetric experiment, will be remote due to the magnitude of r_c for designs 1 and 2, and, also, the additional $100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ distance the ion will have to diffuse out of the pore. Yet, a linear diffusion profile was observed for designs 1 and 2 on the reverse sweep which suggests an alternative mechanism must be responsible.

By comparison of the experimental data presented in this chapter with simulation, Dr. Jörg Strutwolf has estimated that the diffusion coefficient of TEA^+ in the organogel, D_j^β , is $(1.13 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.²⁶⁴ This is a reduction by a factor of almost 9 compared with the diffusion coefficient of TEA^+ in the aqueous phase. It may therefore be concluded that the transferred species accumulates in the micropore channel prior to back transfer due to the slow diffusion coefficient in the organogel, and the resulting peak-shaped response on the reverse sweep is due to a category E type diffusion regime.

4.3.3 Resistance in the system

Pore resistance affects ion transport through the micropores. The cross-sectional area in direct electrical contact with either the aqueous or organic side is defined by the radius of the micropores. Reducing r_a increases the pore resistance. The first order approximation of the pore resistance is given by²⁶⁵

$$R_p = \frac{l}{\pi r_a^2 \kappa} \quad (\text{Eq. 4.3.1})$$

where R_p is the pore resistance and κ is the conductivity of the solution filling the pore, in this instance primarily the organic phase (see section 4.3.1). Katano and Senda⁶⁶ have reported the conductivity, κ , of 1,6-DCH as $49 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ in the presence of a tetraocylammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate as the organic electrolyte salt. In the experiments reported here (BTPPA)(TPBCl) was the organic electrolyte salt of choice (see Figure 4.2.1). However, conductivity studies by Kontturi et al.²⁶⁶ and Sawada and Chigira²⁶⁷ for a series of electrolytes in 1,2-DCE have shown that the conductivity of the organic phases is not substantially affected by the nature of the electrolyte. Thus, an assumption can be made that the conductivity measurements for 1,6-DCH by Katano and Senda⁶⁶ are similar in value to that of the gellified 1,6-DCH organogel, outlined in Figure 4.2.1.

The pores of the array act like resistors in parallel. The total inverse resistance is estimated by multiplying the inverse resistance of a single pore by N_p . Therefore a decrease in the resistance of the array, R_a , is expected with an increasing number of pores in the array. This effect is clearly evident in Table 4.3.3 for μITIES array designs 1 to 4, which each have an r_a value of ca. $25 \mu\text{m}$ but vary in N_p from 3 (design 1) to 105 (design 4). Other porous membranes used to support μITIES arrays have much greater numbers of pores, and thus lower reported resistances. PET track-etched membranes were used by Dryfe and co-workers,²⁶⁸ who report trans-membrane resistances three- to four-fold lower than those outlined in Table 4.3.3. Measurements of the limiting current on the forward sweeps, i_{lim} , for each of the μITIES arrays were made from the background subtracted CVs of $100 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer, shown in Figures 4.3.3 and 4.3.4, and are listed in Table 4.3.3. i_{lim} for designs 1 and 2 were

measured as a steady-state current (i_{ss}) from the sigmoidal forward sweeps, illustrated in Figure 4.3.3. i_{lim} for designs 3, 4 and 5 were measured as a peak current (i_p) from the peak-shaped forward sweeps, illustrated in Figure 4.3.4.

Table 4.3.3: The pore and array resistances (R_p and R_a , respectively) were calculated for each μ ITIES array design using Equation 4.3.1. r_a values were taken from SEM data listed in Table 4.2.1, and the conductivity, κ , of the 1,6-DCH organogel which fills the pores was assumed to be $49 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, as determined by Katano and Senda.⁶⁶ The iR drop was subsequently calculated for each μ ITIES array design using the experimentally derived limiting currents, i_{lim} , measured from the forward sweeps of the background subtracted CVs for TEA⁺ ion transfer.

Design	Pore resistance,		Array resistance, $R_a = R_p * N_p / \Omega$	i_{lim} / nA	$iR \text{ drop} / \text{mV}$
	$R_p = \frac{l}{\pi r_a^2 \kappa} / \Omega$				
1	100×10^5		33.30×10^5	3.51 ± 0.37	11.67 ± 1.25
2	96×10^5		12.00×10^5	11.87 ± 1.84	14.25 ± 2.22
3	101×10^5		4.40×10^5	15.01 ± 2.38	6.60 ± 1.05
4	101×10^5		0.96×10^5	50.96 ± 2.82	4.91 ± 0.27
5	599×10^5		4.99×10^5	36.96 ± 0.42	18.46 ± 0.21

Based on the experimentally determined limiting currents for each μ ITIES array design, which ranged from ca. 3 to 50 nA, iR drops of between ca. 5 and 19 mV were calculated across the membranes. During our experiments automatic positive feedback compensation was applied during the cyclic potential scans via the potentiostat, so as to minimise the effect of the resistance. In spite of this some Ohmic distortion of the background subtracted voltammograms was observed, in particular for design 1 which has the lowest number of pores and highest trans-membrane resistance of any array. This ohmic resistance is shown by a slight increasing positive slope of the current in the rising current region in Figure 4.3.3(A).

Figure 4.3.3: Background subtracted cyclic voltammograms of $100 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ using micropore array designs 1 (A) and 2 (B) to support arrays of μTIES . Experimental setup as detailed in Figure 4.2.1. Scan rate applied was 10 mV s^{-1} . The tailing off of the current at the higher potentials is an artefact of the background subtraction procedure.

Figure 4.3.4: Background subtracted cyclic voltammograms of $100 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ using micropore array designs 3 (A), 4 (B) and 5 (C) to support arrays of μTIES . Experimental setup as detailed in Figure 4.2.1. Scan rate applied was 10 mV s^{-1} . The tailing off of the current at the higher potentials is an artefact of the background subtraction procedure.

4.3.4 Comparison of experimental, simulated, and theoretically calculated i_{lim}

The experimentally derived limiting currents were measured from the background subtracted CVs, as detailed in section 4.3.3, and are listed in Table 4.3.3. For μ ITIES array designs 1 and 2 the theoretically calculated steady-state currents were determined by applying Equation 1.3.3, i.e. assuming an aqueous inlaid geometry at the μ ITIES array and a category B type diffusion regime, as explained in sections 1.3.5 and 4.3.1. For μ ITIES array designs 3, 4, and 5 the theoretically calculated peak currents were determined by applying the Randles-Sevcik equation (Equation 2.2.1), i.e. once more assuming an aqueous inlaid geometry at the μ ITIES array, a category D type diffusion regime, and assigning the area (A) as the total cross-section area of the pores in the array,

$$A = N_p \pi r_a^2 \quad (\text{Eq. 4.3.2})$$

The simulated limiting currents were taken from simulated CVs of each μ ITIES array for TEA⁺ transfer by Dr. Jörg Strutwolf,²⁶⁴ under identical experimental conditions to that outlined in section 4.2.1 and Figure 4.2.1. A comparison of the experimental, simulated, and theoretically calculated limiting currents at each μ ITIES array design is illustrated in Figure 4.3.5.

The experimentally derived limiting currents were in broad agreement with the simulated data within the experimental error limits for μ ITIES array designs 1 to 4. A slightly higher experimental i_{lim} was reported for design 5 in comparison to the simulated data.

Figure 4.3.5: Comparison of the experimental (solid red dots), simulated (solid blue triangles), calculated steady-state (for μ ITIES array designs 1 and 2; solid black diamonds), and calculated peak (for μ ITIES arrays 3, 4 and 5; hollow black squares) currents for 100 μ M TEA⁺ transfer across each μ ITIES array design.

The calculated steady-state currents (i_{ss}) for designs 1 and 2 were in relative agreement with the experimental and simulated data. The calculated peak currents from the Randles-Sevcik equation were considerably lower than the experimental and simulated data for μ ITIES array designs 3, 4, and 5. The diffusion regime that produces these peak-shaped responses was not strictly linear as the experimental and simulated peak currents were enhanced by a spherical component. This observation eliminates the possibility of category D type diffusion regimes being established but matches the behaviour expected from a category C type diffusion regime of moderately overlapping diffusion fields.

4.3.5 Scan rate studies at a μ ITIES array under stationary conditions

Scan rate studies were performed using μ ITIES array design 2. The electrochemical cell was setup as described in Figure 4.2.1, and ion transfer of $100\ \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ across the μ ITIES array was studied at scan rates of 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20, and $25\ \text{mV s}^{-1}$, as illustrated in Figure 4.3.6(A). As discussed in sections 4.3.1 and 4.3.2, TEA^+ transfer across μ ITIES array design 2 produces an asymmetric CV. On the forward sweep spherical diffusion (due to a category B type diffusion regime, see section 1.3.5) to the μ ITIES produces a sigmoidal steady-state response, which in theory should yield a scan rate independent steady-state current (i_{ss}) on transfer of TEA^+ from w \rightarrow o. For the back-transfer on the reverse sweep, linear diffusion (due to a category E type diffusion regime, see section 1.3.5) to the μ ITIES produces a peak-shaped response, with the magnitude of the peak current (i_p), in theory, dependent on the square root of the scan rate ($\nu^{1/2}$).

The currents, measured from the background subtracted CVs in Figure 4.3.6(B), for the forward and reverse sweeps were plotted versus $\nu^{1/2}$, and the expected trends were indeed observed (Figure 4.3.6(C)). A very slight increase in i_{ss} was observed on the forward sweep, but this may be attributed to slight discrepancies in the background subtraction process with increasing scan rate. A shift in the peak potential of the reverse peak to lower potentials may be attributed to the increase in iR drop across the μ ITIES with increasing scan rate.

Figure 4.3.6: (A) Cyclic voltammetry and (B) background subtracted cyclic voltammetry of $100 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer across μTIES array design 2 with increasing scan rates. Scan rates applied were 5 (black), 7.5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 (light grey) mV s^{-1} . (C) Determining scan rate dependence or independence of the measured currents by plotting the current (i / nA) versus the square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2} / (\text{V s}^{-1})^{1/2}$) for the forward and reverse sweeps.

4.3.6 Amperometry of ion transfer under flow conditions: the influence of volumetric flow rate

As outlined in sections 4.2.2 and 2.3.3, a sample injection of 1 mM TEA⁺ in 10 mM LiCl was carried out using a 100 μ L volume sample loop into a flowing 10 mM LiCl aqueous phase and the amperometric response recorded. The volumetric flow rates studied were 0.05, 0.15, 0.25, 0.35, 0.5, 0.65, 0.8 and 1.00 mL min⁻¹. Figure 4.3.7 shows the reproducibility attained at different flow rates tested. The percentage relative standard deviations (RSD), over 3 sample injections, at all flow rates varied in the range 2 – 4 %.

Figure 4.3.7: Amperometric response of TEA⁺ vs flow rate. Applied potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$) = 0.9 V. Sample injection of 100 μ L of 1 mM TEA⁺ in 10 mM LiCl. Three sample injections per flow rate test.

The rate of flow in a flow channel decreases near the surface of the channel walls, and thus near the surface of the μ ITIES array membrane, due to frictional forces until a thin layer of stagnant solution is present immediately adjacent to the μ ITIES array surface. This layer is considered as having a discrete thickness, δ_N , and is known as

the Nernst diffusion layer.⁸ At distances greater than δ_N the concentrations are maintained homogenous, due to the flowing solution, at the bulk analyte concentration, $C_j^{\alpha *}$. The application of a potential difference across the μ ITIES, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$, greater than or equal to the formal ion transfer potential of the analyte species in solution, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi_j^{o'}$, by amperometry such that the concentration of analyte at the surface of the μ ITIES, $C_j^{\alpha}, (x=0)$, is effectively zero, sets up a concentration gradient across the stagnant layer. The observed current is mass transport limited, as described by Equations 1.1.7 and 1.1.8. Under the experimental conditions outlined in this chapter (of a small electroactive area, i.e. the area of the μ ITIES array, relative to the solution volume and the relatively short experimental timescale), $C_j^{\alpha *}$ in the flowing layer will not be appreciably altered by the transfer of analyte across the μ ITIES to the organogel.

For the current at interfaces embedded in a flow channel two limiting behaviours can be encountered, corresponding to the limiting cases of diffusion or convection dominating the mass transport. When convection dominates, the limiting current (i_{lim}) follows the well known Levich equation,²⁶⁹ as explained by Dryfe and co-workers when studying ITIES electrochemistry under hydrodynamic conditions.^{270, 271} i_{lim} is proportional to $V_{av}^{1/3}$,

$$i_{\text{lim}} = 0.925 z_j^{\alpha} F C_j^{\alpha *} w \left(\frac{X_e^2 V_{av} D_j^{\alpha 2}}{h^2 d} \right)^{1/3} \quad (\text{Eq. 4.3.3})$$

where V_{av} is the average flow velocity of the liquid along the length of the channel, w and X_e are the width and length of the membrane-supported interface,

respectively, while d and h are the width and half-height of the channel. By increasing V_{av} the diffusion layer becomes more compressed and the concentration gradient at the ITIES increases, with the i_{lim} increasing correspondingly, as illustrated in Figure 4.3.8. δ_{Ha} and δ_{Hb} represent the thickness of hydrodynamic layers at higher and lower flow rates, respectively. In contrast, when diffusion is the main transport mode, the limiting current is not expected to show a dependence on the flow velocity.

Figure 4.3.8: Theoretical concentration profile on the aqueous side of the ITIES on transfer of TEA⁺ at varying flow rates where convection dominates the mass transport process. $C_j^{\alpha *}$ = concentration of TEA⁺ in the flowing bulk aqueous solution, δ_{Ha} = hydrodynamic boundary layer at fast flow rates, δ_{Hb} = hydrodynamic boundary layer at slow flow rates.

Figure 4.3.9 indicates diffusion dominated mass transport, since the height of the peak current does not increase with the cube root of the volumetric flow velocity, but remains constant. This behaviour can be explained in terms of diffusion and hydrodynamic layers, where the (steady-state) diffusion layer thickness perpendicular to the μ ITIES array does not exceed the thickness of the hydrodynamic layer for any volumetric flow rate used in this study. A qualitative description of this behaviour is

illustrated by the concentration profile shown in Figure 4.3.10, where the extension of the diffusion layer has been approximated by the Nernst diffusion layer thickness, δ_N .

Figure 4.3.9: Variation of TEA⁺ amperometric peak current with the cube root of the flow rate.

Figure 4.3.10: Theoretical concentration profile, on the aqueous side of the ITIES on transfer of TEA⁺ at varying flow rates, where diffusion dominates the mass transport process. $C_j^{\alpha*}$ = concentration of TEA⁺ in the flowing bulk aqueous solution, δ_{Ha} = hydrodynamic boundary layer at fast flow rates, δ_{Hb} = hydrodynamic boundary layer at slow flow rates, and δ_N = Nernst diffusion layer.

The dependence of the half peak width of the current-time peaks and of the charge flow on the volumetric flow rate is shown in Figures 4.3.11(A) & (B). With decreasing flow rate, both the half peak width and the charge increase. This is explained by the increased time period the μ ITIES are in contact with the analyte with decreasing volumetric flow rates. Consequently, at lower flow rates, the ion transfer can take place over a longer time and more ions (charge) can be transferred across the interfaces.

Figure 4.3.11: (A) Variation of the charge and (B) the half peak width (HPW) of the TEA⁺ amperometric peak with volumetric flow rate. Error bars indicate the standard deviation of the triplicate measurements.

4.4 Conclusions

Arrays of μ ITIES were formed by placing a silicon membrane containing micron-sized pores at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions. Five different silicon micropore array membrane designs were studied, each with a unique geometry with respect to pore radii (r_a), pore centre-to-centre separations (r_c), and numbers of pores in the array (N_p). The organic phase was gellified using poly(vinyl chloride). This increased the mechanical stability of the liquid-liquid interface to an extent that allowed the μ ITIES arrays to be incorporated into a flow injection analysis (FIA) system. Thus, voltammetric and amperometric characterisation of the μ ITIES arrays, under stationary and flowing conditions, respectively, was performed by transferring the model analyte ion, tetraethylammonium cation, across the μ ITIES.

Asymmetric cyclic voltammograms were observed for TEA^+ transfer under stationary conditions. This asymmetry of the CV response was described as a function of the geometry of the five individual micropore arrays, position of the liquid-liquid interface within the micropore channel, diffusion coefficients of the analyte in either phase, and timescale of the experiment (in other words the scan rate applied). Dr. Jörg Strutwolf elucidated that the liquid-liquid interface was inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel, and the diffusion coefficient of TEA^+ in the organic phase was reduced 9-fold compared to that in the aqueous phase by comparison of the experimental data described in this chapter with simulated CV's for TEA^+ transfer under identical experimental conditions.

On the forward sweep μ ITIES array designs 1 and 2 fulfilled the conditions for non-interacting diffusion zones described by Saito et al.¹²⁵ and Compton and co-workers,¹²³ based on the ratio of r_c to r_a , and whether the extension of the diffusion zone as a function of the applied scan rate (δ) exceeded $0.5r_c$, respectively. Thus, as expected, the forward sweeps for designs 1 and 2 were characterised by steady-state sigmoidal diffusion profiles or category B type diffusion (see section 1.3.5). μ ITIES array designs 3, 4, and 5 did not fulfill the aforementioned conditions for non-interacting diffusion zones and each was characterised by peak-shaped diffusion profiles. At each μ ITIES array design the experimentally determined limiting currents (i_{ss}) on the forward sweep (a steady-state current for designs 1 and 2, and a peak current for designs 3, 4 and 5) were in broad agreement with simulated i_{ss} values. In addition, calculated i_{ss} for μ ITIES array designs 1 and 2, based on spherical diffusion to inlaid μ ITIES, were also in agreement with the experimental and simulated data. However, the calculated peak currents for μ ITIES array designs 3, 4, and 5 from the Randles-Sevcik equation were considerably lower than the experimental and simulated values, an observation that suggests the experimental peak currents are enhanced by a spherical diffusion component. This eliminates the possibility of category D type diffusion regimes being established but matches the behaviour expected from a category C type diffusion regime of moderately overlapping diffusion fields.

The prominent peak-shaped responses on the reverse sweeps for each μ ITIES design were attributed to category E type diffusion regimes on transfer of TEA^+ from o \rightarrow w. The slow TEA^+ diffusion coefficient in the organogel prevented the ion diffusing out

of the pore on the timescale of the experiment after the initial transfer event, thus ensuring a linear diffusion regime on the back-transfer. Despite implementing automatic positive feedback compensation during the cyclic potential scans via the potentiostat, so as to minimise the effect of the resistance, some Ohmic distortion of the background subtracted voltammograms was observed. This was particularly the case for design 1 which has the lowest number of pores and highest trans-membrane resistance of any array.

The use of amperometry to study the effect of volumetric flow rate on TEA⁺ transfer across the μ ITIES indicated that the current is limited by diffusion dominated mass transport, as shown by the independence of the steady-state current from the flow velocity of the aqueous phase. This behaviour is due to the fact that the steady-state diffusion layer thickness perpendicular to the microinterfaces does not exceed the thickness of the hydrodynamic layer for any volumetric flow rate employed.

From an electroanalytical point of view, when designing a μ ITIES array, a trade-off is necessary in order to incorporate the maximum number of micropores into the array (thus increasing the current, which is the analytical signal, and reducing the resistance across the membrane) while ensuring the pores are sufficiently separated such that the condition for non-interacting diffusion zones is achieved (to ensure the maximum current density, or category B type diffusion regimes).

Chapter 5

Electrochemical detection of oligopeptides at μ ITIES arrays under stationary and flowing conditions

5.1 Introduction

Diverse strategies are used for the determinations of biomarkers such as peptides and proteins, including mass spectrometry and gel electrophoresis. Electrochemical methods often offer an elegant alternative to other analytical strategies for the detection and direct determination of amino acids, peptides and proteins of interest.^{200, 272} Electrochemical processes at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES) are especially interesting as they can be used as the basis for analytical responses for charged species in solution that are not easy to detect by oxidation or reduction processes.^{15, 16, 78, 247, 273-276} The objectives of the work reported in this chapter were to investigate the ability to electrochemically detect some model peptides at μ ITIES arrays under stationary and flowing conditions, and to assess the

analytical capability of miniaturised ITIES in combination with stripping voltammetry for the detection of these peptides.

Previous studies have investigated the electrochemical behaviour of oligopeptides at the ITIES, however, analytical detection performance was not investigated.^{231, 232} Osakai and colleagues^{231, 232} investigated the transfer of a range of peptides that were facilitated by the presence of the ionophore dibenzo-18-crown-6-ether (DB18C6) in the organic phase. As described in section 1.2.8, the potential window at the ITIES is limited by the Gibbs energy of transfer ($\Delta G_{transfer}^{o,\alpha \rightarrow \beta}$) of the aqueous and organic phase electrolyte salts. Using an approach pioneered by Koryta,²⁸ incorporation of ionophores into the organic phase allows detection of analyte ions (by lowering their $\Delta G_{transfer}^{o,\alpha \rightarrow \beta}$ on binding with the ionophore) that would otherwise be incapable of transferring within the available potential window. The studies by Osakai and colleagues^{231, 232} demonstrated that the formal ion transfer potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi_j^{o'}$) of the oligopeptide depended on both the hydrophobicity of the oligopeptides and the accessibility of the oligopeptide's protonated amine group to the ionophore. The transfers of these oligopeptides across the ITIES were diffusion-controlled processes.

Recently, preliminary differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) of a selection of oligopeptides in the presence of DB18C6 at the macroITIES was carried out in Dr. Damien W. M. Arrigan's group by Dr. Grégoire Herzog.²⁷⁷ Seven different oligopeptides were chosen for study (di-, tri-, and tetra-lysine, di- and tri-leucine, divaline, and diphenylalanine), each with a different α -side chain, charge, relative molecular mass, and hydrophobicity. Analogous to the finding by Osakai and

colleagues,^{231, 232} $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$ of an oligopeptide was dependant on the interplay of an oligopeptide side-chain's hydrophilicity and ability of the protonated amine function of the peptide (the experiments were carried out under acidic conditions) to complex the cavity of the crown ether. The trends in transfer potential for each individual oligopeptide are summarised in Table 5.1.1.

Table 5.1.1: Chemical and electrochemical parameters of the oligopeptides studied by Dr. Grégoire Herzog at the macroscopic interface. ^a: The hydrophathy index was calculated as shown by Kyte and Doolittle.²⁷⁸ The hydrophathy index of a substance is a number representing its hydrophilic or hydrophobic properties. The larger the number, the more hydrophobic the substance is. ^b: Charge at pH 2 was calculated using the pK_a values of the different functional groups, and is outlined in appendix E.

Oligopeptide	Mol. wt. g mol ⁻¹	Hydrophathy index ^a	z_j^{α} ^b	$\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$ mV
Dilysine	247	- 7.8	2.60	134
Trilysine	402	- 11.7	3.60	118
Tetralysine	530	- 15.6	4.60	156
Dileucine	244	7.6	0.69	60
Trileucine	357	11.4	0.69	2
Divaline	216	8.4	0.67	177
Diphenylalanine	294	5.6	0.40	17

Lysine is a strongly hydrophilic amino acid. However, oligopeptides consisting of two, three, or four lysine units were transferred across the ITIES at potentials between 118 and 156 mV (on the Galvani scale). The strong hydrophilicity of these oligopeptides was overcome by the protonated amine groups of the side chain of lysine which offer additional possibilities of interaction with DB18C6. On the other hand, valine is a highly hydrophobic amino acid. However, divaline transferred at a potential of 177 mV. Such a high transfer potential indicated that the side chain of valine hindered the interactions of the protonated amine moiety with the cavity of DB18C6. Similarly, diphenylalanine, less hydrophobic than dileucine, transferred at a less positive potential. This again can be explained by stronger interactions between

diphenylalanine and DB18C6 than between dileucine and DB18C6. Trileucine is more hydrophobic than the dileucine, and the transfer potential of trileucine was less positive, as expected.²⁷⁷

Electrochemistry at the μ ITIES has been used for the detection of urea,²⁷⁹ creatinine,²⁸⁰ nitrates,²⁸¹ and adenosine phosphates.²⁸² More recently, μ ITIES arrays supported in microporous silicon membranes, as characterised in chapter 4 of this thesis, were also applied to the detection of dopamine by facilitated ion transfer.²⁸³

Stripping voltammetry (SV) is used to improve detection capability.²⁰⁹ This is a two-step method, the first step of which involves potential-controlled pre-concentration at the working electrode. As applied to voltammetry at the ITIES, the pre-concentration step involves selective extraction of the analyte from the aqueous phase into the organic phase, and the second (detection) step is the back-extraction into the aqueous phase under suitable voltammetric conditions. The peak current or charge resulting from the (back-extractive) stripping process is the analytical response and is proportional to the concentration of analyte. The limits of detection achieved can be lowered by increasing the pre-concentration time. The modification of the liquid-liquid interface to form a gel-liquid interface allows the implementation of SV techniques at the μ ITIES.

We present here investigations into the analytical possibilities offered by electrochemistry at gellified μ ITIES arrays for peptide detection. Four of the seven oligopeptides originally studied by Dr. Grégoire Herzog were chosen for further study, namely di- and trilysine, dileucine and diphenylalanine. The impact of their

relative molecular masses, charges, and α -side chains on their analytical properties was assessed. Strategies to improve the limits of detection that entailed combining the use of gellified μ ITIES arrays, which bring the benefits of miniaturisation, and stripping techniques, widely used at solid-liquid interfaces, were adapted to liquid-liquid interfaces. Attempts to improve the selectivity of the analytical responses for mixtures of oligopeptides using background subtraction techniques are detailed. The ability to construct hydrodynamic voltammograms (HDVs) of two oligopeptides, diphenylalanine and dilysine, via amperometry at μ ITIES arrays under flowing conditions by the incorporation of DB18C6 into the organogel and controlling the applied potential difference across the μ ITIES is presented.

5.2 Experimental details

5.2.1 Stationary and flowing μ ITIES array setups tailored for oligopeptide detection

The composition of the electrochemical cell used under stationary and flowing conditions, incorporating the ionophore DB18C6 into the organogel phase, is illustrated in Figure 5.2.1. The μ ITIES array apparatus, either under stationary or flowing conditions, was setup as detailed in sections 2.3.2 and 2.3.3, respectively. Micropore array design 2 (see figure 4.2.2 for SEM images and Table 4.2.1 for details of the membranes geometric features) was chosen for incorporation into both experimental setups. The aqueous electrolyte solution selected was 10 mM HCl, ensuring a pH at which the oligopeptides studied were positively charged (i.e. pH's less than the oligopeptide pKa's). Stock solutions of the oligopeptides were prepared in 10 mM HCl and stored at +4 °C. The oligopeptides studied were diphenylalanine

(Phe-Phe), dileucine (Leu-Leu), dilysine (Lys-Lys), and trilycine (Lys-Lys-Lys). The chemical structures of the amino acids that form the building blocks of these four oligopeptides, and also the structure of DB18C6, are illustrated in Figure 5.2.2.

Background subtracted DPSVs were obtained using the CH Instruments software.

Figure 5.2.1: The electrochemical cell utilised for the study of oligopeptide transfer at μITIES array design 2 under stationary and flowing conditions.

Figure 5.2.2: Chemical structures of the amino acids that form the building blocks for the oligopeptides studied, and the ionophore incorporated into the organogel: (A) Phenylalanine, (B) Lysine, (C) Leucine, and (D) Di-benzo-18-crown-6 ether.

5.2.2 Voltammetry at the μITIES arrays under stationary conditions

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) experiments were used for the electrochemical characterisation of the oligopeptide ion transfer processes. For differential pulse stripping voltammetry (DPSV) at the μITIES, the amplitude of the pulse and sampling

widths were varied to obtain the optimal combination of these parameters providing the best signal reproducibility, the highest signal-to-noise ratio, and maximize the trade-off between the analyte signal and background signal. Three different pulse amplitudes (0.025, 0.05 and 0.075 V) and three different sampling widths (0.02, 0.05 and 0.075 s) were investigated. This gave a total of nine different possible combinations and the optimum was found to be at an amplitude of 0.05 V and a sampling width of 0.05 s.

5.2.3 Preconditioning of the organogel

Preconditioning of the gel was implemented prior to each voltammetric experiment. This involved applying a more negative potential than the transfer potential of the species being studied for a period of time. The preconditioning potential for the set of oligopeptides studied was 0.3 V. At this potential any un-extracted positively charged oligopeptides from a previous run still remaining in the organogel will be back-extracted to the aqueous phase, essentially “cleaning” the gel. A series of preconditioning times between 0 and 120 s for the DPV of 50 μM Phe-Phe were investigated and the optimal was found to be 15 s. This preconditioning time showed the lowest standard deviation in the peak current signal and the second highest peak current observed.

5.2.4 Amperometry at the μITIES arrays under flowing conditions

The influence of the applied potential difference across the interface ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$) on the amperometric response of both Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys at the μITIES array was investigated. The cell was filled with the aqueous phase (10 mM HCl) and a stationary CV of the blank attained, as described in section 2.3.3. $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ was set to a specific

value (in the studied range 0.3-0.75 V) and the flow was initiated at a volumetric flow rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹. On stabilization of the background current a 100 µL injection of either 1 mM Phe-Phe or Lys-Lys in 10 mM HCl was carried out. For both oligopeptides, multiple sample injections (n = 3) at each applied potential were performed.

5.3 Results and discussion

5.3.1 CV behaviour at the µITIES

Four of the original seven oligopeptides investigated at the macroITIES were chosen as suitable candidates for further study at gellified µITIES arrays via CV and DPSV. The oligopeptides chosen (Phe-Phe, Leu-Leu, Lys-Lys and Lys-Lys-Lys) exhibited sufficient separation in their transfer potentials at the macroITIES such that resolution of their individual stripping peaks in a mixture via DPSV, or by combining DPSV with further signal processing, would be a realistic goal.

Initially, each oligopeptide was studied individually to ensure that the trends in transfer potential observed at the macroITIES were repeated at the miniaturised interface. CVs of increasing concentrations Phe-Phe, Leu-Leu, Lys-Lys and Lys-Lys-Lys at the gellified µITIES are presented in Figure 5.3.1.

Figure 5.3.1: Cyclic voltammetry of increasing concentrations (A) Phe-Phe, (B) Leu-Leu, (C) Lys-Lys, and (D) Lys-Lys-Lys at the μ TIES: For Phe-Phe and Leu-Leu CV responses of blank (black), 1 (light grey), 10, 20, 30, 50, 75, 100, 150 and 200 (μ M) oligopeptide were obtained. For Lys-Lys and Lys-Lys-Lys CV responses of blank (black), 1 (light grey), 2, 5, 10, 20, 40, 60 and 100 (μ M) oligopeptide were obtained. The scan rate used was 10 mV s⁻¹. The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

The CV profiles for each of the four oligopeptides are broadly similar. On the forward scan the current increases with the concentration of oligopeptide suggesting that transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase occurs. On the reverse scan, a peak-shaped voltammetric response is observed indicating transfer of the oligopeptides back to the aqueous phase. The transfer of oligopeptides across the μ ITIES is facilitated by the presence of DB18C6 in the organogel. The transfer potentials of the oligopeptides follow the same trend as observed at the macro-ITIES. A trade-off between the hydrophilicity of the side chain and the ability of the side chain to interact with the crown ether cavity of DB18C6 determines the transfer potential of each oligopeptide. Lys-Lys and Lys-Lys-Lys transferred at the highest potentials due to the greater hydrophilicity of their side-chains, followed by Leu-Leu and Phe-Phe. As previously mentioned, Leu-Leu, a more hydrophobic dipeptide than Phe-Phe, transfers at a more positive potential than Phe-Phe. This may be due to stronger interactions between Phe-Phe and DB18C6 than Leu-Leu and DB18C6.

Background subtracted CVs of each oligopeptide at a concentration of 100 μ M are shown in Figure 5.3.2. On the forward sweep steady-state voltammetry is observed for each oligopeptide, indicating spherical diffusion as the dominant process on transfer of analyte from the aqueous to the organic phase. The tailing-off seen at higher potentials for Phe-Phe and Leu-Leu is an artifact of the background subtraction process. The lysine oligopeptides transfer at the upper limit of the potential window such that the plateau region of the steady-state voltammogram is interrupted by transfer of the background electrolyte. The reverse sweep is peak-shaped for each oligopeptide, indicative of linear diffusion dominating on the back transfer.

Figure 5.3.2: Background subtracted CVs of 100 μM (A) Phe-Phe, (B) Leu-Leu, (C) Lys-Lys, and (D) Lys-Lys-Lys at the μITIES . The scan rate used was 10 mVs^{-1} . The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

Each oligopeptide undergoes assisted or facilitated ion transfer (FIT) across the interface on the forward and reverse sweeps. Specifically transfer by interfacial complexation (TIC) on the forward sweep and transfer by interfacial dissociation (TID) on the reverse sweep (as outlined in detail in section 1.2.8). The limiting factor in the transfer process is the oligopeptide, present at a micromolar concentration level in the aqueous phase, as opposed to the millimolar concentration of the ionophore DB18C6 in the organogel. The organogel fills the hydrophobic pores of the micropore array (as discussed in sections 2.3.2 and 4.3.1) such that the interface is inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel. A steady-state diffusion profile is therefore established on the forward sweep. As discussed in section 4.3.1, the pore centre-centre separation, r_c , of micropore design 2 is such that at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} minimal or no overlap of the adjacent diffusion zones occurs allowing spherical diffusion to dominate at the inlaid μITIES (i.e. category B type diffusion regime, see section 1.3.5). The oligopeptide complexes with DB18C6 at the ITIES and is transferred into

the organogel (TIC). The diffusion coefficient of the oligopeptide/DB18C6 complex is significantly reduced by the viscosity of the organogel such that the complex will remain close to the ITIES on the time-scale of the voltammetric experiment, thus staying confined within the micropore channel structure. As a result, on the reverse sweep the oligopeptide/DB18C6 complex can only diffuse linearly to the ITIES (category E type diffusion regime, see section 1.3.5) whereupon the complex dissociates and the oligopeptide is transferred back into the aqueous phase (TID).

5.3.2 Stripping voltammetry: influence of the preconcentration time

The experimental protocol employed for the DPSV experiments at the μ ITIES is illustrated in Figure 5.3.3. This consisted of a preconditioning step, a preconcentration step, and a voltammetric analysis step. The preconditioning step was employed for 15 s at the potential of 0.3 V. The influence of the preconcentration time was investigated at the preconcentration potential of 0.75 V (this was also the initial potential of the voltammetric analysis). In this step, accumulation of the oligopeptide occurs in the organogel via its assisted transfer across the μ ITIES in the presence of DB18C6. Finally, the preconcentrated oligopeptide was stripped out of the organic phase using DPSV.

The stripping peak current increases with the preconcentration time before reaching a plateau, as shown in Figure 5.3.4. These experiments were carried out at a concentration of 75 μ M which constitutes the upper concentration limit employed. A preconcentration time of 60 s was selected as an optimum, in terms of both transfer peak currents and time of experiments. This preconcentration time was used in all

subsequent experiments, which were carried out in triplicate with an interval of 75 s between each run.

Figure 5.3.3: Schematic of the differential pulse stripping voltammetry (DPSV) experimental protocol at the gellified μ TIES.

Figure 5.3.4: Influence of the deposition time on the background subtracted DPSV of 75 μ M Phe-Phe at the μ TIES: $DPSV_{bg}$ response of 0 (light grey), 5, 15, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120 and 180 s (black) deposition times. The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

5.3.3 Analytical characterisation

In an effort to maximise the analytical performance of the gellified μ ITIES system two different methods of signal processing were applied to the experimental DPSVs. Firstly, background subtraction of the DPSVs (DPSV_{bg}) was attempted whereby the blank signal, attained under identical experimental conditions to the analyte signal, was subtracted using the CH instruments software from the analyte signal. This method produced substantial and broad stripping peaks improving the limits of detection (LOD). A comparison of a typical oligopeptide DPSV and DPSV_{bg} response is highlighted in Figures 5.3.5(A) and (B) for Leu-Leu. Whereas the substantial nature of the peak in Figure 5.3.5(B) was encouraging from an analytical point of view in terms of sensitivity and LOD improvements, the broadness of the peak raised serious doubts whether two or more oligopeptides in a mixture can be resolved based solely on their unique transfer potentials.

In an attempt to further reduce these limits of detection and improve the resolution of the oligopeptide stripping signal, an alternative signal generation method was assessed. Kirowa-Eisner's group has previously used subtractive stripping voltammetry to improve the detection limits of metals at solid electrodes. In papers by Bonfil et al. a subtractive anodic stripping voltammetry (SASV) technique at gold and rotating gold disc electrodes was used for the pM detection of Hg in sample matrices.²⁸⁴⁻²⁸⁷ This technique involves carrying out an initial voltammetric scan at a preconcentration time, t , followed by a second scan at a preconcentration time, $t = 0$. The second scan is then subtracted from the first one using the CH instruments software. In the present study, we carried out subtractive DPSV (DPSV_{sub}) on each of the individual oligopeptides and then on mixtures of the oligopeptides. This consisted

of carrying out initial scans in triplicate for each oligopeptide concentration at a preconcentration time $t = 0$ s, followed by scans in triplicate of the same oligopeptide concentration at $t = 60$ s. The scan at $t = 0$ s was then subtracted from the signal at $t = 60$ s. In real sample matrices a blank may not always be possible due to the presence of trace concentrations of the analyte in the media. $DPSV_{\text{sub}}$ circumvents these difficulties. Although no further improvements in LOD were achieved using $DPSV_{\text{sub}}$, the resolution of the individual $DPSV_{\text{sub}}$ peaks for each oligopeptide were markedly improved, as illustrated for Leu-Leu in Figure 5.3.5(C). This has a major impact on the ability to resolve multiple oligopeptides in a mixture, as will be outlined in section 5.3.5.

Calibration curves of the peak currents versus concentration for each oligopeptide studied were constructed from their respective $DPSV_{\text{bg}}$ signals. $DPSV_{\text{bg}}$ responses of increasing concentrations Phe-Phe, Lys-Lys and Lys-Lys-Lys are presented in Figures 5.3.6(A), (B) and (C), respectively, and the resultant calibration curves are illustrated in Figure 5.3.7.

Figure 5.3.5: DPSV of Leu-Leu at the μ ITIES: **(A)** without background subtraction for blank (black), 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μ M (black) Leu-Leu, **(B)** Background subtracted DPSV ($DPSV_{bg}$), and **(C)** subtractive DPSV ($DPSV_{sub}$) responses of 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μ M (black) Leu-Leu at the μ ITIES. The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

Figure 5.3.6: Background subtracted DPSV ($DPSV_{bg}$) responses of 1 (light grey), 2, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50, 75 and 100 μM (A) Phe-Phe, (B) Lys-Lys and (C) Lys-Lys-Lys, respectively, at the μTIES . The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

Figure 5.3.7: Comparison of the four calibration curves for each oligopeptide constructed from their respective background subtracted DPSV experiments. Each point on the graph was repeated in triplicate. The standard deviation error bars are smaller than the size of the symbols.

The ionic charges of the oligopeptides at pH 2 were calculated using the pKa values of the different functional groups (Table 5.1.1, and Appendix E). Based on these values we would expect Lys-Lys-Lys, with a charge of 3.60, to have the highest peak current, followed by Lys-Lys, with a charge of 2.60. Leu-Leu and Phe-Phe have charges of 0.69 and 0.40, respectively, and would be expected to have lower peak currents than the lysine oligopeptides. At low μM concentrations ($\leq 10 \mu\text{M}$) the expected trends were observed, with the lysine oligopeptides having higher peak currents than those observed for the leucine and phenylalanine dipeptides. Phe-Phe has a higher peak current than Leu-Leu, despite the fact they have Phe-Phe has a slightly smaller charge. As mentioned earlier, Leu-Leu transfers at a higher potential than Phe-Phe. In order to preconcentrate the analyte into the gel, the preconcentration potential was held at 0.75 V for all analytes. Since Phe-Phe transfers more readily than Leu-Leu, the outcome is a greater preconcentration of Phe-Phe in the organic

phase prior to stripping. As a result, the stripping peak current (which is directly proportional to the concentration) is greater for Phe-Phe than Leu-Leu.

5.3.4 Saturation of the $DPSV_{bg}$ response

A saturation effect was observed with all oligopeptides studied, as is evident in Figure 5.3.7. This effect is more pronounced with the lysine oligopeptides, which saturate at lower concentrations than do Leu-Leu or Phe-Phe. Two possible explanations are proposed for this saturation effect both of which centre on the availability of DB18C6 molecules to complex the oligopeptides, and thus transfer them into the organic phase prior to the stripping step, as the limiting factor.

The initial proposed explanation focuses on the varying number of free amino groups present on each oligopeptide capable of complexing with the cavity of the crown ether ionophore, DB18C6. Phenylalanine and leucine both contain one amino group. The formation of a dipeptide requires one amino group of the two present to be occupied forming a peptide bond whereas the other will remain “free” and capable of complexation with a single DB18C6 molecule. Each lysine peptide contains two amino groups. Thus, after the formation of peptide bonds, Lys-Lys will have three “free” amino groups and Lys-Lys-Lys will have four “free” amino groups. Each oligopeptide will be capable of complexing three and four DB18C6 molecules, respectively. The availability of DB18C6 molecules to complex the oligopeptides and transfer them into the organic phase prior to stripping step may thus be a limiting factor. A concentration of oligopeptide at which the ionophore becomes saturated and can no longer facilitate oligopeptide transfer into the organic phase will be reached

more quickly for the lysine oligopeptides which complex multiple DB18C6 molecules per oligopeptide.

An alternative explanation focuses on the significantly reduced mobility of the ionophore and the ionophore-oligopeptide complex in the organogel. As discussed in section 4.3.2, it has been shown that the viscosity of the organogel reduces the diffusion coefficient of the tetraethylammonium cation (TEA^+) 9-fold compared to that observed in the aqueous phase. An analogous reduction in the free and complexed DB18C6 diffusion coefficient in the organogel would therefore be expected. Immediately after complex formation, and transfer of the oligopeptide across the μITIES into the organogel via a TIC mechanism, the minimised mobility of the complex prevents its diffusion out of the pore. In fact, on the time-scale of the voltammetric experiment, all transferred species remain within a thin concentrated layer at the interface. Collins and Arrigan have shown that only 50% of a species present in the organogel will be back transferred into the aqueous phase.²⁸⁸ Thus, with each subsequent addition this non-back transferred element in the organogel increases in concentration, and causes the resultant concentration saturation effect. This is particularly the case when using high preconcentration times.²⁸⁸

An additional consideration that needs to be taken into account when an ionophore is involved in the transfer process, as is the case here, would be depletion of the uncomplexed or free DB18C6 at the ITIES. With each subsequent DPSV fewer and fewer free DB18C6 molecules remain in the crucial analyte saturated region in close proximity to the ITIES. The slow diffusion coefficient of DB18C6 in the organogel prevents new DB18C6 from diffusing to the ITIES quickly enough in order to replace

complexed DB18C6. Thus, despite the fact an excess of 10 mM DB18C6 is present in the organogel it will become the limiting factor in the experiment due to local depletion at the ITIES. This also explains why the lysine oligopeptides saturate more quickly as they complex multiple DB18C6 molecules per oligopeptide.

5.3.5 Analytical parameters for oligopeptide detection at the μ ITIES array

For the dipeptides, the analytical sensitivities (the slopes of the linear regions of the calibration graph) were $-3205 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Phe-Phe and $-1791 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Leu-Leu over a concentration range $0.5\text{-}10 \text{ } \mu\text{M}$. The sensitivity improved for Lys-Lys and Lys-Lys-Lys, to $-6014 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ and $-9611 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ respectively, over the narrower concentration ranges of $0.5\text{-}5 \text{ } \mu\text{M}$ and $0.5\text{-}3 \text{ } \mu\text{M}$ (Table 5.3.1). The limits of detection (LODs) achieved at the μ ITIES using CV_{bg} and DPSV_{bg} for each of the oligopeptides are illustrated in Table 5.3.1. The well known beneficial effects of miniaturising the interface, such as increased mass transport rates and increased current densities, in combination with the preconcentration allowed by stripping techniques resulted in LODs which were 100-fold improvements on those achieved using DPV at the macroITIES. The use of DPSV_{sub} did not significantly improve the LODs compared with those achieved using conventional DPSV_{bg} (Table 5.3.1).

Table 5.3.1: Analytical parameters for the detection of oligopeptides. CV_{bg} : Background subtracted cyclic voltammetry. $DPSV_{bg}$: Background subtracted differential pulse stripping voltammetry. $DPSV_{sub}$: Subtractive differential pulse stripping voltammetry. LOD: limit of detection, calculated as the concentration of analyte producing a signal equal to the blank signal plus three times the standard deviation of the blank signal. N is the no. of analytical measurements taken within the dynamic range.

Analyte	Detection technique	Deposition time s	Sensitivity $nA \mu M^{-1} cm^{-2}$	LOD μM	Dynamic range μM	N	R
Phe-Phe	CV_{bg}	0	-456	48.2	10-200	7	0.997
	$DPSV_{bg}$	60	-3205	0.9	0.5-10	7	0.993
	$DPSV_{sub}$	60	-1593	1.3	0.5-10	7	0.994
Leu-Leu	CV_{bg}	0	-686	66.1	10-250	10	0.975
	$DPSV_{bg}$	60	-1791	0.6	0.5-10	7	0.999
	$DPSV_{sub}$	60	-1029	1.2	0.5-10	7	0.995
Lys-Lys	CV_{bg}	0	-3150	2.5	1-10	6	0.969
	$DPSV_{bg}$	60	-6014	1.4	0.5-5	5	0.975
	$DPSV_{sub}$	60	-5148	1.4	0.5-5	5	0.974
Lys-Lys-Lys	CV_{bg}	0	-5547	1.3	1-7.5	5	0.990
	$DPSV_{bg}$	60	-9611	0.4	0.5-3	4	0.995
	$DPSV_{sub}$	60	-8512	0.7	0.5-3	4	0.988
Mixture: Phe-Phe	$DPSV_{sub}$	60	-1697	9.7	2-10	5	0.992
Mixture: Lys-Lys	$DPSV_{sub}$	60	-5885	1.0	0.5-3	4	0.969

5.3.6 Mixtures of oligopeptides

Encouraged by the significantly improved resolution of the individual $DPSV_{sub}$ peaks for each oligopeptide, in comparison to the substantial but broad peaks achieved using convention $DPSV_{bg}$, we applied both background subtraction techniques when detecting a variety of different oligopeptide mixtures at the μ ITIES. The non-background subtracted $DPSVs$ for increasing concentrations of the Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys mixture at both 0 s and 60 s preconcentration times are illustrated in Figures 5.3.8(A) and (B). Clearly, with increasing preconcentration times the analytical signal increases in magnitude, as expected, and the Lys-Lys stripping peak saturates much quicker than that of Phe-Phe at both preconcentration times studied.

Figure 5.3.8: DPSV of a mixture of Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys at the μ ITIES: DPSV responses of blank (black), 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μ M (black) Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys at (A) 0s deposition time and (B) 60s deposition time. The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

As expected, the use of DPSV_{sub} greatly improved the resolution of the individual oligopeptide voltammetric peaks. This phenomenon is illustrated by the mixture of Lys-Lys and Phe-Phe in Figures 5.3.9(A) and (B). The peak-to-peak separations of Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys are significantly more resolved in the case of DPSV_{sub} .

Figure 5.3.9: Background subtracted DPSV of a mixture of Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys at the μ ITIES: DPSV_{bg} responses of 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μ M (black) Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys at (A) 0s deposition time and (B) 60s deposition time. (C) Subtractive DPSV (DPSV_{sub}) responses of 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μ M (black) Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys at the μ ITIES. The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

Similar results were achieved with a mixture of Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys-Lys, since Lys-Lys-Lys transfers at a potential only slightly higher than that of Lys-Lys. A mixture of Leu-Leu and Lys-Lys was less resolved, see Figure 5.3.10. Leu-Leu transfers at a higher potential relative to Phe-Phe, and thus greater overlap with the Lys-Lys signal results. Using the $DPSV_{\text{sub}}$ voltammetric data the sensitivities for the two oligopeptides, Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys, when they are in a mixture were calculated and compared with the $DPSV_{\text{sub}}$ sensitivities of the individual oligopeptides, summarised in Table 5.3.1. When present in a mixture, slight increases in sensitivity were noted for both dipeptides: from -1593 to -1697 $\text{nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Phe-Phe and from -5148 to -5885 $\text{nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Lys-Lys. At low concentrations ($\leq 2 \mu\text{M}$) the Lys-Lys peak is much larger than that of Phe-Phe and inhibits measurement of Phe-Phe peak currents. Thus, the dynamic range of Phe-Phe in the mixture (2-10 μM) is lessened somewhat compared to that achieved when solely detecting Phe-Phe (0.5-10 μM). The LODs of Lys-Lys in the absence and presence of Phe-Phe are relatively close, 1.4 and 1.0 μM respectively. However, a much higher LOD is noted for Phe-Phe in the presence of Lys-Lys, 9.7 μM , as opposed to 1.3 μM in the absence of Lys-Lys. This again can be attributed to the Lys-Lys signal dominating at lower concentrations.

Figure 5.3.10: (A) Background subtracted DPSV of a mixture of Leu-Leu and Lys-Lys at the ITIES: $DPSV_{bg}$ responses 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, and 10 μM (black) Leu-Leu and Lys-Lys at 60s deposition time. (B) Subtractive DPSV ($DPSV_{sub}$) responses of 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7.5, and 10 μM (black) Leu-Leu and Lys-Lys at the μITIES . The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

5.3.7 Influence of applied potential on the amperometric response under flowing conditions

The flowing μITIES experimental apparatus was setup as discusses in sections 2.3.3 and 5.2.4. Once the electrochemical cell was filled with the aqueous phase (0.2 mM of

either Phe-Phe or Lys-Lys in 10 mM HCl), the flow was halted and a stationary CV carried out, as described in the methodology in section 2.3.3. Based on the properties of the individual oligopeptides at pH 2 (ionic charge, hydrophilicity, ability of the side chain to complex the crown ether DB18C6), as described in detail in sections 5.1 and 5.3.1, one would expect Phe-Phe to transfer at a lower potential than Lys-Lys, and that Lys-Lys would produce the greater transfer peak currents.

Figure 5.3.11: Cyclic voltammetry of oligopeptides in a stationary aqueous phase at the μ ITIES. CV response of (A) blank (black), (B) 0.2 mM Phe-Phe (blue) and (C) 0.2 mM Lys-Lys (red). Scan rate: 10 mV s^{-1} . The transfer potentials are relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes used.

The expected trends were indeed observed (Figure 5.3.11) and the CVs act as a good indicator of the applied potentials necessary to electrochemically modulate the transfer from w to o of either oligopeptide in subsequent FIA studies. Finally, the expected steady-state signal on transfer from w to o was observed for Phe-Phe but not Lys-Lys. This may be due to the forward transfer peak of Lys-Lys being masked by the background electrolyte transfer at higher potentials or simply the steady-state

response may occur outside the available potential window. Both oligopeptides generated the expected peak shaped responses for the reverse, o to w, transfer process.

The influence of the applied potential across the ITIES ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$) on the amperometric response of both Phe-Phe and Lys-Lys at the μ ITIES array was investigated. The cell was filled with the aqueous phase (10 mM HCl) and a stationary CV of the blank attained, as described in the methodology in section 2.3.3. The potential was set to a specific value (in the studied range 0.3-0.75 V) and the flow was initiated at a volumetric flow rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹. On stabilisation of the background current a 100 μ L injection of either 1 mM Phe-Phe or Lys-Lys in 10 mM HCl was carried out. For both oligopeptides, multiple sample injections (n = 3) at each applied potential were performed.

Analogous to previous potentiostatic extraction studies on cations at a macroITIES,^{20, 21} on injection of Phe-Phe or Lys-Lys into the flow cell positive current peaks were observed, indicative of the transfer of a cation from w to o. Figure 5.3.12 is representative of typical peak current responses of an oligopeptide at different applied potentials, in this case Phe-Phe. The time axis is normalised with respect to the time at which the sample injections were made. The magnitude of these peaks was dependent on the applied potential across the interface. The percentage relative standard deviations (RSD), over 3 sample injections for the applied potentials studied, varied in the range 2 – 10 % with both oligopeptides.

Figure 5.3.12: Amperometric response of Phe-Phe as a function of the applied potential difference across the ITIES ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$). The applied potentials were, in the order of increasing peak height, 0.6 (light grey), 0.625, 0.65, 0.665, 0.675 and 0.7 (black) V. The amperometric peak currents were normalised with respect to the time at which each injection was performed. Flow rate: 0.5 mL min⁻¹. Sample injection of 100 μ L of 1 mM Phe-Phe in 10 mM HCl. Three sample injections per applied potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$).

At $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi \geq 0.675$ V for Phe-Phe and $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi \geq 0.725$ V for Lys-Lys, the amperometric peak current stabilizes and reached a plateau. CV analysis in Figure 5.3.11 revealed that the steady-state conditions had been attained for Phe-Phe by 0.675 V and the maximum current reached by Lys-Lys occurred at the upper limits of the available potential window. Therefore, the applied potential independent currents are indicative of the maximum rate of transfer for the particular oligopeptides into the organogel.

5.3.8 Detection of oligopeptides: hydrodynamic voltammograms

Hydrodynamic voltammograms (HDVs) are constructed by plotting the average amperometric peak currents at each applied potential for a given transferring species versus the applied potential across the ITIES ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$). HDV curves for Phe-Phe and

Lys-Lys are illustrated in figure 5.3.13. HDV curves are of particular benefit when carrying out a comparative study into the magnitude of the applied potential necessary to electrochemically transfer (or extract) an analyte from one phase to another. If these analytes are in a mixture they may be selectively extracted or co-extracted depending on the applied potential.

Berduque et al.^{20, 21} have established that for cationic species increased levels of transfer from w to o occur moving to more positive potentials, eventually reaching a maximum at $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi \geq$ the peak potential of the ion. For anionic species the opposite is true with the maximum rate of extraction observed at values of $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi \leq$ the peak potential of the ion. A hydrodynamic voltammogram for a specific analyte can be broken down into 3 distinct regions:

- (1) a range of applied potentials over which no amperometric peaks are observed,
- (2) a range of applied potentials where successively higher peak currents are observed, and
- (3) a range of applied potentials where potential independent behaviour of the amperometric peak current is observed.

Figure 5.3.13: Hydrodynamic voltammograms for Phe-Phe (blue circles) and Lys-Lys (red diamonds). Flow rate: 0.5 mL min^{-1} . Sample injection of $100 \mu\text{L}$ of either 1 mM Phe-Phe or 1 mM Lys-Lys in 10 mM HCl . Three sample injections per applied potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha} \phi$).

In agreement with the CV data in Figure 5.3.11, the electrochemically modulated transfer of Phe-Phe is seen to begin at lower applied potentials than is the case for Lys-Lys. The magnitude of the maximum Phe-Phe peak current response is less than that of Lys-Lys, and the maximum rate of transfer is also attained at a lower applied potential for Phe-Phe. Based on the HDV results in Figure 5.3.13 selective extraction of Phe-Phe from Lys-Lys would be possible at an applied potential of $\sim 0.525 \text{ V}$.

5.4 Conclusions

In this chapter the label-free detection of oligopeptides based on their voltammetric behaviour at gellified and miniaturised liquid-liquid interfaces is outlined. The detection of peptides is an important bioanalytical challenge, as they are a generic class of potent molecules of biomedical and biopharmaceutical significance. The use

of a gellified organic phase allowed the implementation of voltammetric stripping techniques at the liquid-organogel interface. The incorporation of the ionophore DB18C6 into the organogel facilitated the transfer of oligopeptides across the μ ITIES array under stationary and flowing conditions. The ion transfer potentials of these oligopeptides were dependent on their hydrophobicities and their interaction with DB18C6. The combination of using silicon-fabricated micropores with stripping voltammetry techniques enabled enhanced detection limits to be obtained. The sensitivities (calibration graph slopes) were $-3205 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Phe-Phe, $-1791 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Leu-Leu, $-6014 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Lys-Lys, and $-9611 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}$ for Lys-Lys-Lys. Furthermore, simple signal processing such as subtractive stripping voltammetry was shown to produce well-separated peaks for a mixture of two oligopeptides, illustrating the possibility to detect certain mixture combinations. The methods reported are expected to be of benefit to label-free bioanalytical detection schemes.

The magnitude of the amperometric peak currents for each oligopeptide under flowing conditions were shown to be dependent on the applied potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$) and hydrodynamic voltammograms constructed from the amperometric peak currents at each applied potential show that Phe-Phe may be selectively extracted from a mixture containing Lys-Lys at $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi \approx 0.525 \text{ V}$. These data demonstrate that hydrodynamic μ ITIES arrays engineered within microporous silicon membranes may be usefully employed as detectors for flow analytical methods such as liquid chromatography, capillary electrophoresis, or flow-injection analysis.

Chapter 6

The electrochemical behaviour of biological macromolecules at μ ITIES arrays

6.1 Introduction

Large biological macromolecules have been studied at the macroITIES by Arrigan and co-workers, namely haemoglobin,⁷⁸ insulin,⁷⁹ and hen-egg-white lysozyme (HEWL, as discussed in detail in Chapter 3). This chapter reports an investigation into improvement of the analytical responses for insulin and HEWL by miniaturising the liquid-liquid interface using silicon micropore arrays, as discussed in chapters 4 and 5, and also using the asymmetric diffusion fields established at μ ITIES array design 2 (see table 4.2.1, and Figure 4.2.2) to reveal further mechanistic details of the insulin and HEWL charge transfer process.

The enhanced mass transport at the μ ITIES array, formed within the confines of the solid-state micropore array (see section 1.3.4), is expected to yield significant

improvements in both the LOD and sensitivity of the analytical response for both biological macromolecules compared with those achieved at the macroITIES under otherwise identical experimental conditions.

The characteristics of HEWL have been summarised in the introduction to Chapter 3. Insulin is a peptide hormone whose primary function is to signal that blood glucose levels in the body are higher than necessary.¹⁰ This leads to the excess glucose present being taken up by cells and converted into storage compounds, such as glycogen and triacylglycerols.¹⁰ Another hormone, glucagon, signals that blood glucose levels are too low. This causes the release of glucose by breaking down the aforementioned storage compound glycogen, and oxidation of fats to reduce the use of glucose.¹⁰ Together, insulin and glucagon help regulate the blood glucose level in the body on a minute-by-minute basis.¹⁰ Insulin is synthesised in the pancreatic β -cells as preproinsulin, stored in the pancreatic β -cells as the inactive proinsulin, and finally released into the blood stream in the presence of elevated glucose levels as active insulin.¹⁰ Specifically, bovine pancreatic insulin was investigated in this study. Insulin (bovine) contains 51 amino acid residues²⁸⁹ shared between two polypeptide chains, designated A and B, and possesses three cysteine disulphide bonds.^{289, 290} Two of these bonds are interchain between A and B, and the third is intrachain on chain A.^{289, 290} Bovine and human insulin differ in only three amino acids.²⁹¹ Insulin (bovine) has an isoelectric point (pI) of ~ 5.5 ,²⁹² a hydrodynamic radius of $\sim 20 \text{ \AA}$,²⁹³ and a molecular weight (Mol. wt.) of 5733 g mol^{-1} .²⁹⁴ The common disease *diabetes mellitus* is caused by a deficiency in the secretion (type 1 diabetes) or action of (type 2 diabetes) of insulin.¹⁰

Gellified μ ITIES arrays, created using micropore array design 2 (see table 4.2.1, and Figure 4.2.2), were shown in Chapter 4 to exhibit asymmetric diffusion regimes for simple ion transfer. As discussed in section 1.3.7, Zazpe et al.¹¹⁹ have applied this particular μ ITIES array geometry to study the facilitated ion transfer of K^+ across the ITIES, in the presence of the ionophore dibenzo-18-crown-6 ether (DB18C6), via the TIC/TID mechanism. In a manner analogous to studies of TIC/TID at a micropipette supported ITIES,^{80, 126} the diffusion regimes observed at this solid-state μ ITIES array are determined by the limiting factor in the transport process (i.e. either the ionophore or the analyte). Therefore, by varying the experimental conditions such that the ionophore or analyte is in excess, mechanistic information on whether the transport process is being controlled by diffusion of a species either in the organogel-filled micropores or the aqueous phase to the ITIES may be obtained, as illustrated in Figures 1.3.5(C) & (D).

In the proposed mechanisms for the HEWL (see reaction scheme 3.3.1) and insulin⁷⁹ electrochemical responses, the organic phase anion, usually $TPBCl^-$, is believed to play a significant role. In principle, the HEWL or insulin adsorbed on the aqueous side of the ITIES essentially facilitates the transfer of $TPBCl^-$ across the ITIES. If the HEWL molecule is equated to an “ionophore” that facilitates the transfer of the “analyte” $TPBCl^-$, then the asymmetric diffusion regimes established using μ ITIES array design 2 can be used to elucidate further the transfer mechanism by having an excess of “analyte” or “ionophore” present.

As reported in Chapter 3 and in studies by Kivlehan et al.,⁷⁹ HEWL and insulin both adsorb at the ITIES during a CV cycle. Further evidence of macromolecular

adsorption at the μ ITIES was expected. Comparisons were made to the electrochemical response of a much smaller synthetic macromolecule that was not expected to adsorb at the μ ITIES, polypropylenimine tetraamine dendrimer, generation 1.0 (DAB-AM-4), under identical experimental conditions to those implemented for HEWL and insulin.

6.2 Experimental details

The compositions of the electrochemical cells used in this study are illustrated in Figure 6.2.1. The macroITIES apparatus was setup as detailed in section 2.3.1. The μ ITIES apparatus was setup as detailed in section 2.3.2, with micropore array design 2 (see Figure 4.2.2 and Table 4.2.1 for SEM images and details of the membranes geometric features, respectively) chosen due to the optimal steady-state conditions established for transfer of analyte from $w \rightarrow o$ on the timescale of the voltammetric experiment, and the asymmetric diffusion regime observed on application of a triangular potential waveform with cyclic voltammetry (see Chapter 4 for details). From previous studies of the HEWL (Chapter 3) and bovine pancreatic insulin (Kivlehan et al.)⁷⁹ electrochemical responses it was noted that maximum peak currents on the forward sweep were observed under acidic aqueous phase conditions, with the pH being considerably lower than the isoelectric points (pI) of either molecule (the pIs are 11.35 and \sim 5.5 for HEWL²¹⁷ and insulin,^{292, 295, 296} respectively). Thus, the aqueous phase chosen was 10 mM HCl, with a pH of \sim 2, for both the macro- and μ ITIES experimental setups. Stock solutions of HEWL and insulin from

bovine pancreas were prepared in 10 mM HCl daily and stored at +4 °C. Background subtracted CVs were obtained using the CH Instruments software.

Cell 1:

Cell 2:

Cell 3:

Figure 6.2.1: Electrochemical cells utilised in this study. Cell 1 is the composition at the macroITIES, and cells 2 & 3 are the compositions at particular gellified μ ITIES array experiments.

6.3 Results and discussion

6.3.1 CV of HEWL and bovine pancreatic insulin at a μ ITIES array at pH ~2

The CV profiles of increasing concentration insulin, in the range 1-15 μ M, at the gellified μ ITIES array design 2 are presented in Figure 6.3.1(A). The experiment was carried out under acidic conditions at pH ~2, as described in cell 2 of Figure 6.2.1 and in section 6.2. An increase in the current on the forward sweep, associated with an increasing concentration of insulin in the aqueous phase solution, is observed at a very

positive applied potential difference across the ITIES ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$). This current response occurs at almost the same $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ as the background electrolyte transfer, and, consequently, the shape of the resulting wave is difficult to ascertain. The transfer profile seems to be approaching steady-state until it is swamped by the background electrolyte transfer current. On the reverse sweep a very broad peak with adsorption or desorption features is observed.

Background subtraction of the insulin CVs was carried out, as illustrated in Figure 6.3.1(B). Care needs to be taken when analysing background subtracted CVs of insulin and HEWL. This is because both of these molecules adsorb at the macroITIES during the transfer process, and it is reasonable to assume that this is also the case at the gellified μ ITIES arrays. Previously, in Figures 3.3.10(A) & (B), it has been shown that the first CV run in the presence of HEWL is different from all subsequent CVs carried out in terms of the magnitude and shape of the prepeak on the forward sweep. For the initial CV the HEWL transfer process occurs at a “neat” or clean interface, however; for all subsequent CVs the HEWL transfer process is occurring at an ITIES that has a layer, or at the very least patches, of adsorbed HEWL present from the previous CV scan. This layer of adsorbed HEWL is expected to change the capacity at the interface and may induce a local electric field.

Adsorbed HEWL or insulin is seen at the ITIES in the form of a white layer of precipitate. This layer remains between CV scans meaning if adsorption occurs on the forward sweep then the adsorbed molecules are not fully desorbed on the reverse sweep. Therefore, the blank CV used for background subtraction is not a true reflection of the actual initial conditions at the ITIES (once insulin or HEWL has

previously adsorbed during the first CV). In addition, the background subtraction process is known to show artifacts in the potential regions where the background electrolyte ions transfer (as was the case for TEA⁺ transfer in Chapter 4). Since, the insulin response (and HEWL response as will be shown later) occurs in this region, the background subtraction process may distort its shape. Thus, whereas the background subtraction process will enhance the clarity of the increases in current between subsequent CV runs for increasing insulin or HEWL concentrations in the aqueous phase, the shape of the background subtracted voltammogram is unreliable if used to interpret the diffusion processes taking place during ion transfer. The shape of the non-background subtracted CVs are a more reliable guide to the possible transfer processes occurring.

The currents on the forward and reverse sweeps are measured from the background subtracted CVs of insulin in Figure 6.3.1(B). The current of the apparent sigmoidal curve on the forward sweep increases linearly with the concentration of insulin in the aqueous phase (Figure 6.3.1(C)), whereas the reverse sweep saturates after the addition of 9 μM insulin to the aqueous phase (Figure 6.3.1(D)). This saturation event is similar to that observed for the extraction of oligopeptides from the o \rightarrow w phase using DPSV and CV, as discussed in section 5.3.4. This saturation event will be discussed in more detail later in section 6.3.3.

Figure 6.3.1: (A) Cyclic voltammetry of blank (black), 1 (light grey), 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, and 15 (black) μM insulin, and (B) background subtracted cyclic voltammetry of 1 (light grey), 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, and 15 (black) μM insulin at the gellified μTIES array design 2. Electrochemical cell as detailed in cell 2 (Figure 6.2.1). Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} . The steady-state and peak currents, measured from the background subtracted CVs, of the forward and reverse sweeps for each concentration are illustrated in (C) and (D), respectively.

The CV profiles of increasing concentrations of HEWL, in the range 0.5-13 μM , at the gellified μITIES array design 2 are illustrated in Figure 6.3.2(A). An increase in the current on the forward sweep, associated with an increasing concentration of HEWL in the aqueous phase solution, is observed at a very positive $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$, even more so than the case of insulin. Again, the transfer profile seems to be approaching steady-state until it is swamped by the background electrolyte transfer current. On the reverse sweep an adsorption or desorption feature is clearly observed. In comparison to insulin, this HEWL adsorption/desorption peak is more compact and well defined.

The currents on the forward and reverse sweeps are measured from the background subtracted CVs of HEWL in Figure 6.3.2(B). The current of the apparent peak on the forward sweep increases linearly with the concentration of HEWL in the aqueous phase (Figure 6.3.2(C)), whereas the reverse sweep saturates after the addition of 7 μM HEWL to the aqueous phase (Figure 6.3.2(D)). This saturation event will be discussed in more detail later in section 6.3.3.

Figure 6.3.2: (A) Cyclic voltammetry of blank (black), 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, and 13 (black) μ M HEWL, and (B) background subtracted cyclic voltammetry of 0.5 (light grey), 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, and 13 (black) μ M HEWL at the gellified μ ITIES array design 2. Electrochemical cell as detailed in cell 2 (Figure 6.2.1). Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} . The peak currents, measured from the background subtracted CVs, of the forward and reverse sweeps for each concentration are illustrated in (C) and (D), respectively.

6.3.2 Comparison of the current responses on the forward sweep for insulin and HEWL

A higher current is observed on the forward sweep for HEWL than with insulin for equivalent concentrations in the aqueous phase. From studies of HEWL transfer at the macroITIES in Chapter 3 (specifically section 3.3.1.3) it is known that under more acidic conditions, as the HEWL molecule becomes progressively more positively charged, the peak current observed increases in magnitude.

The current on the forward sweep at an inlaid μ ITIES array is determined by Equation 1.3.3, as discussed in section 1.3.5. The variables between HEWL and insulin are the diffusion coefficient (D_j^α), and the charge (z_j^α) of the macromolecule in the aqueous phase at pH 2. HEWL has a charge of 17+,²⁵⁵ whereas insulin has a charge of 6+ at pH 2.⁷⁹ Insulin and HEWL have similar diffusion coefficients in the aqueous phase. Values of $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ have been reported for both insulin²⁹⁷ and HEWL,²⁶⁰ although the HEWL diffusion coefficient was calculated as $2.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ via a scan rate experiment in section 3.3.1.2. Therefore, based on its significantly larger charge, one would expect HEWL to produce the greater charge transfer or current at the μ ITIES.

Two distinct sources of this charge transfer event are possible: (A) the macromolecules themselves are transferred across the ITIES on the forward sweep. The greater charge on the HEWL molecule causes the greater observed current on the forward sweep (as expected from Equation 1.3.3). Alternatively, in explanation (B): as discussed in reaction scheme 3.3.1 for the proposed HEWL transfer mechanism, it is suggested that the HEWL molecule acts as an ionophore at the ITIES and facilitates

the transfer of TPBCl⁻ into the aqueous phase. Since TPBCl⁻ is in excess in the organic phase, HEWL is the limiting factor, and consequently determines the current observed on the forward sweep. Because HEWL is the larger molecule with the greater charge it has an increased ability to transfer single or multiple organic anions, via an electrostatic attraction, across the interface, and subsequently complex these anions perhaps in a hydrophobic pocket.

6.3.3 The saturation of the adsorption/desorption peaks on the reverse sweep

Both insulin and HEWL show adsorption/desorption features on the reverse sweep, and the peak currents are seen to saturate with increasing macromolecule concentrations in the aqueous phase. The more positively charged HEWL saturates at a slightly lower aqueous phase concentration than insulin. HEWL does, however, saturate at a more gradual rate than insulin. Similar saturation curves for the reverse sweep were observed for the facilitated ion transfer of oligopeptides across the μ ITIES array via DPSV and CV, as discussed in section 5.3.4.

Two possible explanations of the peak current saturation on the reverse sweep are now outlined. (A) As discussed by Strutwolf et al.,²⁶⁴ due to the lower diffusion coefficients of all species in the organogel, only species in a thin strip of gel adjacent to the aqueous phase are transferred across the μ ITIES. Subsequently, with each successive CV scan, in the presence of an increased concentration of HEWL or insulin, more and more TPBCl⁻ is transferred into the aqueous phase from this region of the organogel only. This may lead to the TPBCl⁻ becoming depleted in the organogel region immediately adjacent the aqueous phase. On the timescale of the voltammetric experiments TPBCl⁻ cannot be replaced due to its low diffusion

coefficient in the gel. As mentioned already in section 6.3.2, HEWL may transfer a larger number of TPBCl⁻ anions per molecule than insulin (as suggested by the increased HEWL current in comparison to insulin on the forward sweep) across the ITIES explaining why it saturates at a lower concentration. In addition it seems that not all of the TPBCl⁻ molecules transferred into the aqueous phase transfer back, as indicated by the total charges measured for HEWL and insulin on the forward and reverse sweeps (see Tables 6.3.1 and 6.3.2).

Table 6.3.1: Total charge transfer (nC) measured on the forward and reverse sweeps for insulin at μ ITIES array design 2.

[Insulin] μ M	Total charge on the forward sweep nC	Total charge on the reverse sweep nC
1	3.9 \pm 0.1	2.9 \pm 0.3
2	7.1 \pm 0.2	5.8 \pm 0.3
3	9.2 \pm 0.4	7.9 \pm 0.5
5	13.3 \pm 0.1	13.7 \pm 0.9
7	16.7 \pm 1.0	15.7 \pm 0.9
9	21.3 \pm 0.4	19.4 \pm 0.4
11	25.2 \pm 1.1	21.8 \pm 0.3
13	30.4 \pm 1.5	22.6 \pm 1.1
15	37.7 \pm 2.1	22.6 \pm 0.6

Table 6.3.2: Total charge transfer (nC) measured on the forward and reverse sweeps for HEWL at μ ITIES array design 2.

[HEWL] μ M	Total charge on the forward sweep nC	Total charge on the reverse sweep nC
0.5	9.3 \pm 1.7	5.0 \pm 0.8
1	15.6 \pm 0.7	7.0 \pm 0.7
2	22.8 \pm 1.0	11.6 \pm 0.6
3	32.7 \pm 0.9	16.6 \pm 0.3
5	43.1 \pm 1.8	23.2 \pm 1.1
7	55.6 \pm 1.0	29.9 \pm 0.6
9	71.2 \pm 1.8	34.7 \pm 0.9
11	88.7 \pm 2.1	39.9 \pm 0.2
13	110.2 \pm 3.2	45.8 \pm 0.5

In the proposed mechanism of the HEWL electrochemical response in section 3.3.5 it was suggested that the HEWL molecule denatures at the ITIES on complexation with TPBCl⁻ (as implied by the white precipitate formed at the ITIES and the very large HEWL peak-to-peak separation, $\Delta E_{(HEWL)}$). Thus the back transfer (desorption) event is a chemically distinct process to that discussed for the forward sweep. The denatured HEWL-TPBCl complex may not dissociate readily on the reverse sweep, and as a result a reduced quantity of TPBCl⁻ is back-transferred. The current on the reverse sweep therefore saturates due to the continuous depletion of the thin layer of organogel closest to the μ ITIES, and the incomplete back-transfer of TPBCl⁻ with successive CV scans. One caveat of this mechanism, however, is that on depletion of TPBCl⁻ in the organogel the current on the forward sweep should also saturate. This does not prove to be the case, and as a result an alternative explanation of the saturation event on the reverse sweep is put forward.

(B) An alternative explanation suggests that while TPBCl⁻ is depleted in the thin region adjacent to the aqueous phase, and TPBCl⁻ undergoes incomplete back-transfer, the 10 mM concentration present means this effect is negligible with successive voltammograms. Instead with each successive run more and more denatured HEWL or denatured HEWL-TPBCl remains adsorbed at the ITIES. This view is supported by the fact that with repetitive run experiments (as discussed in section 3.3.4), and with increasing concentration experiments (as discussed in section 3.3.1.2) the layer of precipitate at the ITIES is seen to become more substantial. The desorption peak current of TPBCl⁻ will continue to increase in a linear fashion at least until a monolayer is formed at the ITIES. Once a monolayer has adsorbed, multilayer formation of adsorbed precipitate occurs, as shown by the increase in charge on the

forward and reverse sweeps for repetitive run experiments in section 3.3.4. As the thickness of the adsorbed denatured HEWL or denatured HEWL-TPBCl multilayer increases, a point is reached where the newly transferred and complexed TPBCl⁻ is not close enough to the ITIES to be desorbed back into the aqueous phase (i.e. TPBCl⁻ present in the multilayer, furthest away from the ITIES will not back-transfer). Thus, once the thickness of the adsorbed denatured HEWL or denatured HEWL-TPBCl complex reaches a critical dimension the reverse peak current is seen to saturate. In this mechanism it must be assumed that the layer of adsorbed material at the ITIES does not impede TPBCl⁻ transfer across the interface from $w \rightarrow o$.

6.3.4 Improving the sensitivity and LODs for macromolecule detection using miniaturised ITIES

From solid microelectrode theory, as the area of the electrode is reduced to micrometer dimensions the rate of mass transport to the surface increases due to the creation of spherical diffusion zones around the electrode, as discussed in sections 1.3.1 and 1.3.5. Improved limits of detection (LODs) and sensitivity of the analytical response are expected. The sensitivity is the slope of a plot of current density versus the concentration of the analyte species. The current signal must be normalised for different electrode areas in order to make direct comparisons. The greater (steeper) the slope of the resulting line of best fit to the experimental data, the greater the sensitivity. An increased slope means that with a small increase in concentration a large increase in current is observed, in comparison to an electrode that produces a smaller (less steep) slope. The slope and intercept of the line of best fit for a plot of current versus concentration are used to calculate the LOD, as discussed in appendix

D. All of this theory is equally applicable when comparing macroITIES and μ ITIES array current responses to changes in the analyte concentration in solution.

In Figures 6.3.1 and 6.3.2 the current responses for μ ITIES array design 2 with increasing insulin and HEWL concentrations, respectively, have been reported. In Chapter 3 (Figure 3.3.4) the current response at the macroITIES with increasing concentration HEWL has been reported. The experimental conditions at the macroITIES and μ ITIES array design 2 in terms of the pH of the aqueous phase solution, which has been shown to dramatically affect the peak currents for both HEWL and insulin, were identical with 10 mM HCl at pH 2 chosen to give the maximum current responses. Thus, in order to fill a gap in the data an experiment of increasing concentration insulin was undertaken at the macroITIES at pH 2, the experimental setup of which is outlined in cell 1 of Figure 6.2.1. The resulting voltammograms are illustrated in Figure 6.3.3(A).

The CVs of insulin at the macroITIES at pH 2, outlined in Figure 6.3.3, are identical to the electrochemical response reported and explained in detail by Kivlehan et al.⁷⁹ for insulin at the macroITIES at pH 1. In a similar trend to that noted with HEWL (see Table 3.3.1), as the pH of the aqueous phase solution becomes more acidic the peak-to-peak separation ($\Delta E_{(insulin)}$) of the insulin peaks on the forward and reverse sweeps decrease in magnitude. For a 50 μ M concentration of insulin at pH 2, in Figure 6.3.3, $\Delta E_{(insulin)}$ is 217 mV, while a 50 μ M concentration of insulin at pH 1, as reported by Kivlehan et al.,⁷⁹ produces a $\Delta E_{(insulin)}$ of 115 mV. Plots of the current density versus

the macromolecule concentration for HEWL and insulin at the macro- and μ ITIES array design 2 are compared in Figure 6.3.4.

Figure 6.3.3: (A) Cyclic voltammetry of blank (black), 10 (light grey), 15, 20, 30, 40, 50, 75 and 100 (black) μ M insulin at the macroITIES. Electrochemical cell as detailed in cell 1 (Figure 6.2.1). Scan rate used was 10 mV s^{-1} . (B) Calibration graph of peak current (μ A) versus concentration of insulin (μ M) for the peak on the forward sweep at $\sim 0.75 \text{ V}$.

Figure 6.3.4: Current density ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$) versus **(A)** [insulin] or **(B)** [HEWL], under the experimental conditions outlined in cells 1 & 2 (Figure 6.2.1) and cell 2 (Figure 3.2.1) at the macroITIES and gellified μ -ITIES array design 2, respectively.

It can be seen that the sensitivities at the μ ITIES array do not increase significantly with interfacial miniaturisation when detecting insulin and HEWL under otherwise identical experimental conditions, although it must be noted that the experiments at the μ ITIES array were carried out at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} , whereas the experiments at the macroITIES were carried out at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} . The peak current data

was measured from the CVs of insulin and HEWL at the macroITIES, and from the background subtracted CVs of insulin and HEWL at the μ ITIES array design 2. This data was then normalised with regard to the geometric area of the interface. At the macroITIES the interfacial area was 1.1 cm^2 . At μ ITIES array design 2 the area of each individual pore was $2.12 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2$, and this was multiplied by the number of pores in the array, $N_p = 8$, to give the overall geometric area of $1.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$. As discussed in Chapter 4, no overlap of the individual diffusion zones is expected at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} , as used in this study, at μ ITIES array design 2.

From a mechanistic point-of-view, steady-state diffusion on the forward sweep was anticipated. The limiting factor proposed is the behaviour of HEWL or insulin (since TPBCl⁻ is significantly in excess, as outlined in the experimental setup illustrated in cell 2 of Figure 6.2.1), both of which diffuse to the μ ITIES, and facilitate the transfer of TPBCl⁻ across the interface. Thus, in this scenario spherical diffusion fields established at the μ ITIES array were expected to give an increase in the current density of approximately one order of magnitude due to enhanced mass transport (as discussed in detail for TEA⁺ transfer at the macro-, micro-, and nanoITIES in section 7.3.4 of Chapter 7), and reduce the limits of detection for the macromolecules. Clearly, as regards improving the sensitivities this did not prove to be the case, as presented for insulin and HEWL in Figure 6.3.4. However, on miniaturisation of the ITIES, the LOD for insulin was reduced somewhat from 6.8 to 1.6 μM , and the LOD for HEWL was reduced from 6.0 to 1.4 μM . The sensitivities and LODs are summarised in Table 6.3.3. The sensitivities were further normalised with regard to the square root of the scan rate, $(\nu)^{1/2}$, as detailed in Table 6.3.4.

Table 6.3.3: Comparison of analytical parameters for the detection of insulin and hen-egg-white lysozyme (HEWL) at the macroITIES or μ ITIES via cyclic voltammetry (CV) and background subtracted cyclic voltammetry (CV_{bg}), respectively. ^a: the experiments at the macroITIES were carried out at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} , and ^b: the experiments at the μ ITIES were carried out at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . LOD is the limit of detection (as described in Appendix D).

Analyte	Technique	Sensitivity $\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	LOD μM	Dynamic range μM	N	R
Insulin	CV (macroITIES) ^a	0.6290	6.8	10-100	8	0.998
	CV_{bg} (μ ITIES) ^b	0.8624	1.6	1-15	9	0.995
Hen-egg-white lysozyme	CV (macroITIES) ^a	2.3838	6.0	5-40	7	0.989
	CV_{bg} (μ ITIES) ^b	1.9108	1.4	0.5-13	9	0.995

Table 6.3.4: Comparison of the normalised sensitivities with regard to the square root of the applied scan rate, $(\nu)^{1/2}$, for the detection of insulin and HEWL, as described in Table 6.3.3.

Analyte	Technique	Sensitivity $\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	Scan rate, ν V s^{-1}	Normalised sensitivity w.r.t. $(\nu)^{1/2}$ $\frac{\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M cm}^{-2}}{\sqrt{\text{Vs}^{-1}}}$
Insulin	CV (macroITIES) ^a	0.6290	0.01	6.3
	CV_{bg} (μ ITIES) ^b	0.8624	0.005	12.2
Hen-egg-white lysozyme	CV (macroITIES) ^a	2.3838	0.01	23.8
	CV_{bg} (μ ITIES) ^b	1.9108	0.005	27.0

After normalising the sensitivities with regard to $(\nu)^{1/2}$ a very minor increase in sensitivity was observed for HEWL and the sensitivity for insulin doubles. These modest increases in sensitivity in comparison to those expected suggest that the diffusion of HEWL or insulin to the μ ITIES is not in fact the rate determining step as predicted. Two other potential rate determining steps are now outlined.

(A) The linear diffusion of $TPBCl^-$ in the organogel, within the confines of the micropore, to the μ ITIES, where it undergoes association and transfer by adsorbed HEWL or insulin, may be the mechanistic rate determining step. In this case $TPBCl^-$ undergoes category E type diffusion to the μ ITIES, as discussed in section 1.3.5, on

the forward sweep. Thus, no edge effect is possible and as a result no increase in the mass transport in comparison with the macroITIES is likely. (B) On the forward sweep two processes are occurring: the diffusion of HEWL or insulin to the μ ITIES and then the adsorption of HEWL or insulin at the interface. Perhaps, this adsorption process is the rate determining step and negates the influence of the enhanced mass transport to the μ ITIES.

6.3.5 Scan rate studies of HEWL at a gellified μ ITIES array

A scan rate experiment involving 10 μ M HEWL at μ ITIES array design 2 was carried out at pH 2, as illustrated in Figure 6.3.5(A). At each scan rate chosen, in the range 5-50 mV s^{-1} , a blank CV was attained in the absence of HEWL. The blank response was background subtracted from the HEWL response at each scan rate using the CH instruments software, as illustrated in Figure 6.3.5(B). A plot of the peak current (i_p) versus the square root of the scan rate, $(\nu)^{1/2}$, for the forward and reverse peaks, as measured from the background subtracted CVs, is presented in Figure 6.3.5(C).

Figure 6.3.5: (A) Cyclic voltammetry of blank (black) and 10 μM HEWL at 5 (light grey), 10, 15, 20, 25, 35, and 50 (black) mV s^{-1} , and (B) background subtracted cyclic voltammetry of 10 μM HEWL at 5 (light grey), 10, 15, 20, 25, 35, and 50 (black) mV s^{-1} at the gellified μTIES array design 2. Electrochemical cell as detailed in cell 2 (Figure 6.2.1). (C) Peak current (nA), measured from the background subtracted CV's, versus the square root of the scan rate, $(v)^{1/2} / (\text{Vs}^{-1})^{1/2}$ for each concentration.

If, as originally anticipated, the steady-state diffusion of HEWL to the μ ITIES was the rate determining mechanistic step, then the HEWL peak current on the forward sweep would have been expected to show scan rate independence. A scan rate independent response on the forward sweep has already been highlighted for simple TEA⁺ ion transfer at μ ITIES array design 2 in Chapter 4 (Figure 4.3.6). As is clear from Figure 6.3.5(C), however, the forward sweep seems to show a linear dependence on $(\nu)^{1/2}$. This observation is consistent with a linear diffusion process dominating the charge transfer and re-enforces the notion that the diffusion of TPBCl⁻ in the organogel to the μ ITIES is the rate determining step on the forward sweep.

One possible alternative explanation of this observation is that the background subtraction process is inadequate, as described in section 6.3.1. The close proximity of the HEWL peak on the forward sweep to the background electrolyte transfer complicates the background subtraction process further. On the forward sweep HEWL is expected to adsorb at the ITIES as it facilitates the transfer of TPBCl⁻. It is this adsorption component of the response on the forward sweep that may cause a scan rate dependence of the peak current. The reverse peak current ($i_{p,rev}$) was also plotted versus the scan rate (ν / Vs^{-1}) (not shown) and seen to increase linearly. On the reverse sweep the scan rate range is too limited to make a judgement on whether the peak current is due to a desorption process as $i_{p,rev}$ increases linearly with both ν and $(\nu)^{1/2}$ within the limits of the experimentally accessible scan rates.

6.3.6 Comparison of the electrochemical behaviour of insulin and HEWL with that of a dendrimer, DAB-AM-4, at a gellified μ ITIES array

HEWL and insulin are large macromolecules with molecular weights of 14,600 and 5,733 g mol⁻¹, respectively, and both are seen to form thick layers of white precipitate at the interface after CV experiments. In this section, the electrochemical response of a much smaller molecule, polypropylenimine tetraamine dendrimer, generation 1.0, also known as DAB-AM-4, with a molecular weight of 316.53 g mol⁻¹ was investigated at pH 2 (i.e. under identical experimental conditions to HEWL and insulin as described in cell 2 of Figure 6.2.1).

The electrochemistry of DAB-AM-4 was previously investigated by Berduque et al.²⁴⁷ at the macroITIES at a pH of 5.5. A peak on the forward sweep was observed at the upper limit of the transfer window at ~0.85 V (the aqueous background electrolyte used was 10 mM LiCl) and a single peak was observed on the reverse sweep, also at a high transfer potential of ~0.75 V.

A scan rate study of the DAB-AM-4 electrochemical response at pH 2 was initially carried out at the macroITIES (described in cell 1 of Figure 6.2.1). As illustrated in Figures 6.3.6(A) & (B), the potential window where only non-faradaic currents flow was reduced in size due to transfer of the acidic background aqueous phase electrolyte. As a result, the forward peak, just visible at CVs carried out using a bigger window at pH 5.5, was hidden by the background electrolyte transfer. The peak on the reverse sweep was seen at a high $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ of ~0.75 V, in agreement with Berduque et al.²⁴⁷ The absence of a forward peak eliminated the possibility of creating a current versus increasing concentration DAB-AM-4 calibration graph.

Figure 6.3.6: (A) Cyclic voltammetry of blank (black) and 150 μM DAB-AM-4 at scan rates of 5 (light grey), 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15, 20, 30, 40, and 50 (black) mV s^{-1} . Electrochemical cell as detailed in cell 1 (Figure 6.2.1). (B) Cyclic voltammetry of blank (black), 150 μM DAB-AM-4 (dark grey), and 150 μM DAB-AM-4 plus 150 μM TEA⁺ (light grey). Electrochemical cell as detailed in cell 1 (Figure 6.2.1). Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

The electrochemical detection of DAB-AM-4 at the gellified μITIES array design 2 produced a sigmoidal response on the forward sweep at the absolute upper limit of the available potential window. Thus, an experiment that involved increasing the concentration of DAB-AM-4, in the range 3-20 μM , in the aqueous phase was

performed; see Figure 6.3.7(A). A peak-shaped response, indicative of linear diffusion and identical in shape to the reverse peak observed for the back-transfer of TEA⁺ in Chapter 4, is seen on the reverse sweep at a high $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$ of ~0.925V. After background subtraction a peak was observed at a potential of ~0.975 V on the forward sweep, see Figure 6.3.7(B). It is likely that the peaked shape of the CV is an artifact of the background subtraction process, as discussed for HEWL and insulin, when the molecule of interest transfers at an applied potential difference across the ITIES, $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$, similar to the background electrolyte transfer.

The familiar trends of a linear increase in peak current (as measured from the background subtracted voltammograms) with concentration on the forward sweep (Figure 6.3.7(C)), and a saturation of the peak current on the reverse sweep (Figure 6.3.7(D)) were observed. The sensitivity of the analytical response to DAB-AM-4 at the gellified μ ITIES array ($1.3457 \mu\text{A } \mu\text{M cm}^{-2}$), determined from the slope of a plot of the current density versus the DAB-AM-4 concentration (Figure 6.3.7(D)), was found to be quite comparable to those found for HEWL and insulin, as summarised in Table 6.3.3.

Figure 6.3.7: (A) Cyclic voltammetry of blank (black), 3 (light grey), 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 17.5 and 20 (black) μM DAB-AM-4, and (B) background subtracted cyclic voltammetry of 3 (light grey), 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 17.5 and 20 (black) μM DAB-AM-4 at the gellified μTIES . Electrochemical cell as detailed in cell 2 (Figure 6.2.1). Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} . The peak currents, measured from the background subtracted CVs, of the forward and reverse sweeps for each concentration are illustrated in (C) and (D), respectively. The current density ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$) versus the [DAM-AM-4] (μM) is illustrated in (E).

The complete absence of a precipitate at the interface during the scan rate experiment detailed in Figure 6.3.6(A), and the absence of any adsorption/desorption features in the voltammetric responses at the macro- and μ ITIES seem to indicate that DAB-AM-4 undergoes simple ion transfer at the ITIES (in an identical manner to TEA^+). The forward sweep undergoes a category B type diffusion regime, and the reverse sweep a category E type diffusion regime, as discussed in section 1.3.5. The DAB-AM-4 molecule may simply be too small and not have the requisite charge to facilitate the transfer of TPBCl^- molecules, and subsequently form the characteristic insoluble dendrimer-TPBCl precipitate at the interface.

Interestingly, further evidence of the presence or absence of any adsorbed macromolecules at the μ ITIES was found on comparison of the background subtracted voltammetric responses of insulin, HEWL, and DAB-AM-4 after the addition of $15\ \mu\text{M}$ TEA^+ to the aqueous phase (Figures 6.3.8(A), (B) & (C)). On transfer of the TEA^+ from $w \rightarrow o$ in the presence of insulin or HEWL the expected steady-state response is distorted, seemingly amalgamating with the insulin or HEWL peaks on the forward sweep. A perfectly formed TEA^+ steady-state response, indicating an absence of any interfering adsorbed material at the interface, is observed on the forward sweep in the presence of DAB-AM-4. The reverse sweep for TEA^+ in the presence of all three molecules is unaffected, perhaps indicating that the interfering adsorbed layers are present on the aqueous side of the ITIES.

Figure 6.3.8: Background subtracted cyclic voltammetry of **(A)** 15 μM insulin (black) plus 5 (dark grey) and 10 (light grey) μM TEA⁺, **(B)** 15 μM HEWL (black) plus 5 (dark grey) and 15 (light grey) μM TEA⁺, and **(C)** 20 μM DAB-AM-4 (black) plus 15 μM TEA⁺ (light grey) at a gellified μITIES . Electrochemical cell as detailed in cell 2 (Figure 6.2.1). Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

6.3.7 Mechanistic study of the HEWL and insulin electrochemical response: the use of asymmetric diffusion regimes established at the μ ITIES array

As discussed in sections 1.3.7 and 6.1, by equating the HEWL (or insulin) molecule to an “ionophore” that facilitates the transfer of the “analyte” TPBCl⁻, the asymmetric diffusion regimes established using μ ITIES array design 2 may be used to further elucidate the transfer mechanism by having an excess of “analyte” or “ionophore” present. This concept is illustrated in Figure 6.3.9.

Figure 6.3.9: Summary of the expected diffusion regimes, based on the mechanism of the HEWL electrochemical response outlined in reaction scheme 3.3.1, at the solid-state μ ITIES array under conditions where (A) TPBCl⁻ is in excess or (B) HEWL is in excess.

Figure 6.3.9(A) illustrates the scenario when TPBCl⁻ is in excess in comparison to the HEWL aqueous phase concentration. Initially when designing these experiments the electrochemical response on the forward sweep was assumed to be limited by the diffusion of HEWL (or insulin) to the μITIES and, thus, non-interacting spherical diffusion fields would be established at each μITIES in the array with steady-state voltammetry expected on the forward scan. This assumption was based on the voltammetry observed at the same μITIES array design 2 when studying simple diffusion controlled ion transfer of TEA⁺, as detailed in Chapter 4. However, as discussed in sections 6.3.4 and 6.3.5, on further analysis of increasing concentration and scan rates studies of insulin and HEWL transfer at the μITIES, this assumption did not prove valid. The diffusion of TPBCl⁻ in the organogel to the μITIES, or the adsorption step, are now the most likely rate determining steps.

On the reverse sweep the adsorbed denatured HEWL-TPBCl complex dissociates, the TPBCl⁻ is back-transferred across the μITIES, and the denatured HEWL molecule desorbs. A desorption peak is thus expected on the reverse sweep.

The thought process described in this section will still, however, be outlined with the assumption that the current response on the forward sweep for the macromolecule is limited by the diffusion of HEWL to the μITIES. This thought process can be applied to any ionophore (or macromolecule) that may be present in the aqueous phase, is capable of facilitating the transfer of TPBCl⁻ (which is in excess), and the rate determining step on the forward sweep is the diffusion of that ionophore to the μITIES.

Under the experimental conditions outlined in Figures 6.3.1 and 6.3.2, TPBCl⁻ (10 mM concentration) is at least 665 times in excess of insulin and HEWL, respectively, at all aqueous phase concentrations. Figure 6.3.9(B) illustrates the scenario when the HEWL aqueous phase concentration is in excess in comparison to the TPBCl⁻ concentration. The electrochemical response on the forward sweep is now assumed to be limited by the diffusion of TPBCl⁻ in the organogel to the interface where it undergoes complexation with HEWL and transfer. The linear diffusion of TPBCl⁻ to the interface would be expected to produce a peak-shaped response on the forward sweep. The reverse sweep will remain identical in nature to the situation described in Figure 6.3.9(A), where, once more, the limiting factor is the adsorbed denatured HEWL-TPBCl complex.

Ideally, the HEWL and insulin aqueous phase concentrations should be at least 50 times in excess. Unfortunately, simply increasing the aqueous phase concentration to ~500 mM was not possible in practice due to the limited solubility of the HEWL and insulin molecules at such a high aqueous phase concentration. Thus, a compromise was investigated where the (BTPPA)(TPBCl) concentration in the organogel was reduced to a minimal level (i.e. less than 0.5 mM) that, in theory, would allow the use of reduced HEWL and insulin aqueous phase concentrations when attempting to achieve excess conditions.

Clearly, the use of a reduced organic phase electrolyte concentration would introduce increased resistance to the experimental setup that was unlikely to be compensated even with the use of a miniaturised ITIES.¹⁷⁸ The effects of (BTPPA)(TPBCl) concentration on the TEA⁺ transfer peak shape, transfer potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$), and steady-

state current on the forward sweep were thus initially investigated. These experiments allow the feasibility of using such low organic electrolyte concentrations, in terms of the extent of voltammetric distortion that occurs with decreasing [(BTTPPA)(TPBCl)], to be investigated. Cyclic voltammetry of 50 μM TEA⁺ transfer was carried out at μITIES array design 2 using organogels with 10, 1, 0.5, and 0.1 mM (BTTPPA)(TPBCl) concentrations, respectively, as shown in Figures 6.3.10 and 6.3.11.

As the organogel [(BTTPPA)(TPBCl)] decreased the following trends were observed:

- the resistance in the system increased as signified by the progressively shallower slope of the rising part of the TEA⁺ steady-state response (Figure 6.3.10 & 6.3.11 (A)),
- the TEA⁺ steady-state current (i_{ss}) on the forward sweep decreased in magnitude somewhat in comparison with the 10 mM [(BTTPPA)(TPBCl)] (Figure 6.3.11(B)),
- the TEA⁺ half-wave transfer potential ($E^{1/2}$) increased in magnitude, a clear resistance effect (Figure 6.3.11(C)),
- a [(BTTPPA)(TPBCl)] of 0.1 mM caused “crossing-over” on the reverse sweep of the cyclic voltammogram due to the effect of increased resistance, and
- the blank system electrochemical response was also heavily distorted with significantly reduced background electrolyte transfer.

The heavy distortion of the blank and TEA⁺ cyclic voltammograms with increasing resistance in the system prevents reliable analysis of the CV data based solely on the shape of the voltammograms. Thus, experiments with excess HEWL or insulin concentrations in the aqueous phase, in comparison to the TPBCl⁻ concentration in the organogel, were not possible.

Figure 6.3.10: Cyclic voltammetry of blank (grey) and 50 μM TEA⁺ (black) at μTIES array design 2 under experimental conditions where the (BTPPA)(TPBCl) concentration in the organogel is either (A) 10 mM, (B) 1 mM, (C) 0.5 mM, or (D) 0.1 mM. The experimental setup is outlined in cell 3 of Figure 6.2.1. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

Figure 6.3.11: (A) Cyclic Voltammetry of 50 μM TEA⁺ in the presence of 0.1 (grey), 0.5 (blue), 1 (red) and 10 (black) mM organic phase electrolyte (BTPPA)(TPBCl) in the organogel at μITIES array design 2. The experimental setup is outlined in cell 3 of Figure 6.2.1. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} . (B) TEA⁺ steady-state current (i_{ss}) versus [BTPPA)(TPBCl)], and (C) TEA⁺ half wave potential on the forward sweep ($E_{1/2}$) versus [BTPPA)(TPBCl)].

6.4 Conclusions

Insulin from bovine pancreas and hen-egg-white lysozyme (HEWL) were both found to induce an electrochemical response within the potential window limits available under the experimental conditions investigated using μ ITIES array design 2. The CVs for both macromolecules consisted of apparent steady-state responses on the forward sweeps (albeit somewhat swamped by the background electrolyte transfer) and adsorption/desorption features on the reverse sweep (the HEWL adsorption/desorption peak being noticeably more compact and well defined).

The use of miniaturised ITIES and the subsequent increases in the rate of insulin and HEWL mass transport to the interface did not bring about significant improvements in the sensitivities of the analytical responses, although the limits of detection (LOD) were somewhat enhanced. The LOD improved from 6.8 to 1.6 μ M for insulin and from 6.0 to 1.4 μ M for HEWL, while the sensitivities, normalised with respect to $(\nu)^{1/2}$, increased from 6.3 to 12.2 μ A μ M⁻¹ cm⁻² V⁻¹ s for insulin and from 23.8 to 27.0 μ A μ M⁻¹ cm⁻² V⁻¹ s for HEWL. The modest increases in the sensitivities for HEWL and insulin (in comparison to the one order of magnitude improvements for simple diffusion controlled ion transfer processes, as outlined later in Chapter 7) suggest that the diffusion of the macromolecule to the μ ITIES is not the rate determining step in the mechanism. The linear (category E type diffusion as outlined in section 1.3.5) diffusion of TPBCl⁻ from the organogel to the μ ITIES would not enhance the mass transport since an edge effect cannot be established within the confines of a micropore. Thus, this step in the mechanism is the most likely candidate to act as the

rate determining step. This hypothesis is further corroborated by the linear dependence of the peak current on the forward sweep with $(\nu)^{1/2}$, again suggesting linear diffusion as the rate determining step. This is in stark contrast to the scan rate independence shown at the same μ ITIES array design for simple diffusion controlled TEA⁺ charge transfer. An alternative rate determining step may be the adsorption of the macromolecule at the μ ITIES prior to transferring the organic phase electrolyte anion, TPBCl⁻.

Comparison of the electrochemical responses of the large bio-macromolecules insulin and HEWL with that of the much smaller dendrimer DAB-AM-4 in the presence of TEA⁺ provided further evidence for adsorption of these large bio-macromolecules at the interface. The expected TEA⁺ steady-state response is distorted in the presence of insulin or HEWL on transfer from w \rightarrow o, seemingly amalgamating with the insulin or HEWL peaks on the forward sweep. A perfectly formed TEA⁺ steady-state response, indicating an absence of any interfering adsorbed material at the interface, is observed on the forward sweep in the presence of DAB-AM-4. In addition, the reverse sweep for TEA⁺ in the presence of all three molecules is unaffected, perhaps indicating that the interfering adsorbed layers are present on the aqueous side of the ITIES.

Further attempts were made to confirm the proposed insulin and HEWL mechanisms by employing the asymmetric diffusion regimes established at μ ITIES array design 2 to investigate if the transport process is being controlled by diffusion of a species either in the organogel-filled micropores or the aqueous phase to the ITIES. However, experiments with excess HEWL or insulin concentrations in the aqueous phase, in

comparison to the TPBCl⁻ concentration in the organogel, were not possible due to (A) the low solubility of the large biological macromolecules in the aqueous phase, and (B) the increase in resistance and subsequent distortion of the cyclic voltammetric features that occurs on reduction of the [(BTPPA)(TPBCl)] in the organogel, and (C) the revelation that the diffusion of the macromolecule to the μ ITIES array may not in fact be the rate determining step.

Chapter 7

Ion-transfer electrochemistry at arrays of nano-interfaces between immiscible electrolyte solutions confined within silicon nitride nanopore membranes

7.1 Introduction

The development of arrays of nanoscale interfaces between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (nanoITIES) will offer benefits at the liquid-liquid interface similar to those experienced at the solid-liquid interface on introduction of solid nanoelectrode arrays.^{97, 117, 298} From an experimental viewpoint, nanoscale miniaturisation of the liquid-liquid interface minimises difficulties associated with the high iR -drop effect across the interface (owing to the use of highly resistive non-aqueous solvents) and allows separation of the faradaic current from double-layer charging current.⁹⁸ Significantly enhanced mass transport⁹⁸ and voltammetric measurements in low polarity media or even in media with no supporting electrolytes are possible.⁹⁹⁻¹⁰¹ Additional benefits of supporting the nanoITIES in a nanoporous

solid-state membrane include improved control over nanopore size, array geometry, and higher mechanical stability at the interface.

As discussed in section 1.3.8, to date two categories of nanoITIES have been reported, those supported at the tip of a nanopipette^{98-101, 127-133} or a double-barreled nanopipette,^{100, 134, 135} producing single or double nano-interfaces, and those created by immobilising nanoporous materials, containing geometrically irregular pore arrays with extremely high pore densities (up to ca. 10^9 pores per cm), such as “track etched” polyester^{136, 268} and γ -alumina ultrafiltration membranes¹¹² at the ITIES.

In the past decade, as discussed in section 1.3.9, a series of solid-state nanopore membranes have been fabricated in a variety of materials to act as sensors for DNA and other biological molecules such as peptides and proteins.^{102, 139, 140} In this work, arrays of geometrically regular solid-state nanopores, fabricated in 100 nm thick Si_3N_4 membranes, are presented. These were used to support arrays of nanoscale liquid-liquid interfaces, or nanoITIES. The development of nanoITIES, and especially arrays of these, opens up the possibility to investigate the opportunities for enhanced bioanalytical detection based on biomolecular interactions at the ITIES.^{31, 78, 79, 264, 288} The geometric parameters were evaluated by analysis of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of each nanopore array design. The transfer of the ion tetraethylammonium cation (TEA^+) across the water | 1,6-dichlorohexane interface was chosen as a model system to investigate the voltammetric responses of the nanopore array designs in terms of varying pore radius (r_a), pore centre-to-centre separation (r_c), and total number of pores in the array (N_p).

7.2 Experimental details

7.2.1 Membrane fabrication

Two materials were investigated, namely silicon-on-insulator (SOI) and silicon nitride (Si_3N_4), as suitable candidates to create membranes capable of (a) surviving the fabrication process itself and (b) surviving repeated immersions in liquids whilst being only tens of nanometers in thickness. These SOI and Si_3N_4 membranes are supported by a silicon (Si) frame 525 μm in thickness. Additionally, two membrane designs were attempted for each membrane material: in the first design the ultrathin membrane is situated planar with the surface, whereas in the second design the ultrathin membrane is supported in a recess or “trough” etched into the surface. Different trough areas were investigated with a view to determining the optimal trough dimensions that allow maximum stability or strength in the membrane. Thus, in total four fabrication process flows were attempted.

Each of the four process flows are outlined in extensive detail in Appendix F, section F.2. The fabrication survival statistics are outlined for each process flow in section F.3. Briefly, the SOI membrane chips (both with and without an etched trough) were fabricated seemingly intact but were revealed as extensively damaged when viewed using SEM. On the other hand the Si_3N_4 membrane chips were successfully fabricated as intended with very low percentages broken; 10.7% and 6.4% for the chips with and without an etched trough, respectively. In this chapter only Si_3N_4 membrane chips without the etched trough have been electrochemically characterised. The fabrication process flow for these particular membranes is illustrated in Figure 7.2.1.

Figure 7.2.1: Nanopore array patterned Si₃N₄ membrane (without an etched trough) fabrication process flow. Note: this flow is NOT to scale. The bulk silicon layer is 525 μm thick, the pad-oxide layer is 35 nm thick, the proTEK® B3 layer is 8 μm thick, and, finally, the patterned Si₃N₄ layer is 100 nm thick.

The key steps in the fabrication flow outlined in Figure 7.2.1 involve the deposition of oxide (thermally) and nitride (low pressure chemical vapour deposition (LPCVD))

layers onto the $\langle 100 \rangle$ silicon wafer, the patterning of the nanopore array into the front-side nitride layer by e-beam lithography, the etching of the back-side oxide and nitride layers photolithographically using deep reactive ion etching (DRIE), the removal of the bulk silicon from the back of the wafer by wet-etching, and the protection of the fragile 100 nm thick Si_3N_4 membrane using a patented polymer (proTEK[®]B3) during the final fabrication and dicing steps. From a single 4-inch $\langle 100 \rangle$ silicon wafer up to two hundred 5×5 mm nanopore array patterned chips may be attained. The membrane thickness, 100 nm for all array designs, was confirmed by analysis using a Nanospec 3000 system (Nanometrics incorporated, California). For an in-depth discussion of each technique and fabrication step see Appendix F.

Contact angle measurements were made with an OCA contact angle system (Dataphysics Instruments GmbH, Germany). The drop volume dispensed on the surface was 1 μL . The contact angle between the drop and the substrate was measured immediately after the contact was made.

Figure 7.2.2: Image of the drop of de-ionised water dispensed on the surface of the nanopore array patterned Si_3N_4 membrane.

The hydrophobicity of the thinned Si₃N₄ membranes was assessed by measurement of its contact angle with de-ionised water, as depicted in Figure 7.2.2. The contact angle was $97 \pm 3^\circ$, indicating that the surface of the membrane was hydrophobic. An assumption must be made that the nanopore walls were also of a similar hydrophobicity, although this is not necessarily the case. The high surface-to-volume ratio may make the nanopores difficult to permeate with water, and thus even more hydrophobic in nature.²⁹⁹

7.2.2 Nanopore array designs

The nanopore arrays consisted of patterns which were a combination of pores with varying pore radii (r_a) (in the range $25 \text{ nm} \geq r_a \leq 250 \text{ nm}$ for process run X-3858, and in the range $10 \text{ nm} \geq r \leq 50 \text{ nm}$ for process run X-4093), pore centre-to-centre separations (r_c) as a multiple of the radius of either $5r_a$ or $20r_a$, and total pore numbers (N_p) of either 0, 1, 8, 23, 95, or 390 pores. All of the nanopore arrays were patterned using a hexagonal closed packing (HCP) arrangement. In total 82 different e-beam designs (between process runs X-3858 and X-4093) were written and are summarised in Appendix F, section F.4.

7.2.3 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) characterisation of the nanopore arrays

SEM images were obtained using a field emission scanning electron microscope (6700F SEM, JEOL U.K., Ltd.) operated at beam voltages of between 3 kV and 7.5 kV. Figure 7.2.3 shows SEM images of typical membranes portraying their pore geometry and pore-to-pore relationships. The geometric parameters (in terms of $r_a, r_c,$

and N_p) of each nanopore array characterised electrochemically by ion transfer in this chapter are listed in Table 7.2.1. A full summary of all SEM images, and the subsequent geometric parameter data, for a host of nanopore array membrane designs (i.e. not just those electrochemically characterised in this chapter) is available in Appendix F, section F.5.

Figure 7.2.3: SEM images (a), (c), and (d) depict nanopore array designs 5, 35, and 45 which contain 1, 95, and 390 nanopores, respectively, each with pore radii of ~ 125 nm. SEM images (b), (e), and (f) are close-up images of nanopore designs 32, 31, and 35 that contain pores with radii of ~ 25 , ~ 225 , and ~ 125 nm, respectively. SEM images (e) and (f) of nanopore array designs 31 and 35, also highlight examples of arrays with pore centre-to-centre separations of 5 or 20 times the radius, respectively.

Table 7.2.1: Characteristics of the pore arrays of the different solid-state Si_3N_4 membranes evaluated by SEM. Pore radius and pore centre-to-centre separation are values averaged over six pores (with the exception of designs 1, 5 and 55, which contain zero or a single pore in the array). The resolution of the SEM measurements are within ± 5 nm.

Design	Pore radius, r_a / nm	Pore centre-to-centre separation,		Number of pores in the array, N_p
		r_c / nm	as a multiple of r_a	
1	-	-	-	0
5	120 ± 5	-	-	1
27	25 ± 5	125 ± 5	$5 r_a$	95
28	45 ± 5	250 ± 5	$5 r_a$	95
29	75 ± 5	375 ± 5	$5 r_a$	95
30	120 ± 5	630 ± 10	$5 r_a$	95
31	225 ± 5	1240 ± 25	$5 r_a$	95
32	25 ± 5	495 ± 5	$20 r_a$	95
34	65 ± 5	1455 ± 10	$20 r_a$	95
35	125 ± 5	2445 ± 20	$20 r_a$	95
36	230 ± 5	4905 ± 20	$20 r_a$	95
44	70 ± 5	1460 ± 20	$20 r_a$	390
45	115 ± 5	2475 ± 15	$20 r_a$	390
55	65 ± 5	-	-	1
64	45 ± 5	915 ± 15	$20 r_a$	23
73	50 ± 5	1040 ± 10	$20 r_a$	95
82	55 ± 5	1090 ± 5	$20 r_a$	390

7.2.4 Procedure for voltammetric experiments at nanoITIES arrays

The experimental apparatus was setup as detailed in section 2.3.2 and depicted in Figure 2.3.2. This experimental setup is essentially identical to that used when characterising ion transfer (Chapter 4) or detecting biological molecules (Chapters 5 & 6) at a μ ITIES array with the exception that the 4 x 4 mm microporous chip is replaced with a 5 x 5 mm nanoporous chip.

The nanoITIES arrays were electrochemically characterised by ion transfer of the model ion tetraethylammonium cation (TEA^+) across the membrane voltammetrically via cyclic voltammetry, linear sweep voltammetry, and differential pulse voltammetry. The composition of the electrochemical cell used is illustrated in Figure 7.2.4.

Figure 7.2.4: Electrochemical cell configuration utilised in this study.

Once the cell was set-up, repetitive blank CVs (i.e. no TEA⁺ present in the aqueous phase) were run, three in total, at intervals of 180 s. The starting potential, $\Delta_o^w \phi_{st}$, for each of these CVs was set at 0.35 V and the switching potential, $\Delta_o^w \phi_{sw}$, at 1.00 V. A quiet time of 5 s was set prior to each CV and the scan rates applied varied between 5 and 200 mV s⁻¹. Subsequently, an aliquot of TEA⁺ stock solution was injected into the aqueous phase using a calibrated micropipette to produce a TEA⁺ concentration of 150 μM and three repetitive CVs were run, as per the blank CVs. Background subtracted CVs of 150 μM TEA⁺ were obtained using the CH Instruments software.

A calibration curve of increasing TEA⁺ concentration was prepared using LSV. Analogous to the CV experiments, blank LSVs were run, three in total at intervals of 180 s. The starting potential, $\Delta_o^w \phi_{st}$, for each of these LSVs was set at 0.35 V and the end potential, $\Delta_o^w \phi_{end}$, at 0.85 V. A quiet time of 5 s was set prior to each LSV run and the scan rate applied was 10 mV s⁻¹. Aliquots of TEA⁺ solution were injected into the aqueous phase, as described, producing a TEA⁺ bulk solution concentration range from 50 to 400 μM. Three repetitive LSVs were run after each addition, as per the blank LSVs.

Preliminary experiments using DPV were attempted. The parameters used were those previously optimised for use at μITIES arrays (see section 5.2.2: amplitude of 0.05 V, sampling width of 0.05 s) and no further optimisation of these parameters was

attempted in this chapter. Analogous to the CV experiments blank DPVs were run, three in total, at intervals of 180 s. The starting potential, $\Delta_o^w\phi_{st}$, for each of these DPVs was set at 0.35 V and the end potential, $\Delta_o^w\phi_{end}$, at 1.00 V. A quiet time of 10 s was set prior to each DPV run. Aliquots of TEA⁺ solution were injected into the aqueous phase, as described, producing a TEA⁺ concentration of 150 μ M and three repetitive DPVs were run, as per the blank DPVs. Background subtracted DPVs of 150 μ M TEA⁺ were obtained using the CH Instruments software.

7.3 Results and discussion

7.3.1 Electrochemical ion transfer across the nanoITIES arrays

Ion transfer across arrays of nanoscopic liquid-liquid interfaces localised within 100 nm thick Si₃N₄ membranes was characterised using cyclic voltammetry. The transfer of TEA⁺ across the ITIES is known to be reversible on the time scale of voltammetric experiments at macro-interfaces^{300, 301} and micro-interfaces,¹⁰⁶ and was chosen as the model analyte ion for the present studies. As discussed in sections 1.3.4 and 1.3.5, a variety of parameters inherent to the experimental setup influence the general shape of the observed CVs. These include:

- (i) the geometric properties of the pores, such as r_a , r_c , N_p , and the thickness of the membrane or pore depth, l ;
- (ii) the properties of the transferring ion species and the electrolyte solutions employed, such as the diffusion coefficients of TEA⁺ in the aqueous and organic phases, D_{aq} and D_{org} , respectively, and the bulk concentration of TEA⁺, C_i , in the aqueous phase;

(iii) the location of the liquid-liquid interface within the pore, which depends mainly on the hydrophobicity and wetting properties of the nanoporous membrane material;

(iv) the Debye length (λ_D), which corresponds to the distance from the nanopore walls where the surplus charge at the surface (i.e. by ion adsorption or charged surface groups) no longer has an effect on a particle (or ion) in proximity to the nanopore walls. The Debye length (λ_D , SI units are metres) at the nanopore-electrolyte interface depends on the ionic strength of the electrolyte, the dielectric constant of the solvent, and the temperature, as shown in Equation 7.3.1,^{7, 302}

$$\lambda_D = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_o \varepsilon_r k_B T}{N_A e^2 \sum_j^n C_j^* z_j^2} \right)^{1/2} = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_o \varepsilon_r k_B T}{2 N_A e^2 I_c} \right)^{1/2} = 6.2881 \times 10^{-11} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_r T}{I_c} \right)^{1/2} \quad (\text{Eq. 7.3.1})$$

where ε_o is the dielectric constant of free space (F m^{-1}), ε_r is the relative dielectric constant of the solvent, k_B is Boltzmann's constant ($1.38 \times 10^{-12} \text{ J K}^{-1}$), T is the temperature (K), N_A is Avagadro's constant ($6.022 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$), e is the elementary charge ($1.062 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$), C_j^* and z_j are the bulk concentration and charge of the electrolyte ion j (mol m^{-3}), and I_c is the ionic strength of the electrolyte solution (mol m^{-3}). At high ionic strengths the EDL is thin but at low ionic strengths the EDL increases in thickness, reducing the effective cross-section through which ions of the same charge as the pore walls (co-ions) may be transported. At a sufficiently small pore size, the nanopore will selectively only allow the transfer of counter-ions. The Debye length (λ_D) for a 10 mM LiCl aqueous electrolyte at 25 °C is approximately 10 nm.⁷ The relative

dielectric constant (ϵ_r) of 1,6-DCH is 8.6.⁶⁶ Using Equation 7.3.1, λ_D for an organic phase electrolyte of 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl) in 1,6-DCH at 25 °C was approximately 1 nm. Consequently, all ions irrespective of charge are capable of undergoing ion transfer across the smallest diameter pores (ca. 50 nm) studied here and the charge selectivity observed in dilute electrolyte solutions will not influence the experimental results.

CVs at a nanoITIES array, the geometric parameters of which are defined by nanopore array design 45, both in the presence and absence of 150 μM TEA⁺ in the aqueous phase are shown in Figure 7.3.1. Steady-state voltammograms were observed at all scan rates investigated for both the forward transfer of TEA⁺, from the aqueous to the organic phase, and the back transfer. This indicates that spherical diffusion is dominant on both the forward and reverse ion transfer processes. However, after background subtraction it became clear that only the forward sweep truly exhibits a steady-state behaviour and that the reverse sweep exhibits a peak-shaped voltammogram (Figure 7.3.2).

Figure 7.3.1: Cyclic voltammetry (CV) of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer as a function of scan rate at nanoITIES arrays formed using nanopore array design 45. CV responses are shown at scan rates of (a) 5 mV s^{-1} and (b) 50 mV s^{-1} for blank (grey) and $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ (black) transfer. (c) CV responses at scan rates of 5 (light grey), 10, 15, 20, 25, 35 and 50 (black) mV s^{-1} for $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer.

Figure 7.3.2: Background subtracted cyclic voltammetry (BS CV) of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer as a function of scan rate at nanoITIES arrays formed using membrane design 45. **(a)** BS CV response at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} for $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer. The crossing observed at the lower potentials is an artifact associated with the background subtraction procedure used. **(b)** BS CV responses at scan rates of 5 (light grey), 10, 20, 35, 50 and 100 (black) mV s^{-1} for the back transfer of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer.

Steady-state behaviour was observed on the forward sweep at all scan rates (not shown) after background subtraction. This was an expected observation as r_c for nanopore array design 45 was 20-times the pore radius such that the nanopores were sufficiently separated as to avoid diffusion zone overlap at adjacent pores. However, as will be discussed in subsequent paragraphs, we will show that in fact diffusion zone overlap does occur at an r_c value of $20r_a$ and that the absence of a peak on the

forward sweep may be attributed to a combination of distortion by resistance and masking by capacitance in the system.

Closer examination of the as-recorded CVs of TEA⁺ transfer across the nanoITIES array revealed that they did not display a true limiting current plateau on the forward sweep (Figure 7.3.1). Instead, the current in the diffusion-limited region was seen to steadily rise with applied potential up to $\Delta_o^w \phi_{sw}$. This phenomenon has previously been noted in CVs of ion transfer across μ ITIES^{103, 104} and may be attributable to movement of the aqueous-organogel nano-interfaces under potential stimulation. Dale and Unwin demonstrated recently that the polarised liquid-liquid micro-interface moves during charge transfer³⁰³ by imaging the interface with confocal laser scanning microscopy during CV measurements. They noted that on the forward sweep the liquid-liquid interface had a slight oblate hemispheroidal shape, but in the diffusion limited region approaching $\Delta_o^w \phi_{sw}$ the interface gradually expanded outwards and thus caused an increase in the limiting current. The movement of the interface was completely reversible, contracting on the reverse sweep and adopting its initial configuration at the start of the next scan. Such movement of the nanoITIES may be occurring to some extent, despite the organic electrolyte phase being gellified and thus more viscous than an organic liquid electrolyte phase.

The back transfer sweeps (Figure 7.3.1) display steady-state voltammograms, indicative of rapid, radial diffusion, unlike the case obtained with silicon-membrane-based μ ITIES arrays, as discussed in Chapter 4, which displayed peak-shaped reverse voltammetric peaks due to linear diffusion within those micropores. The voltammetric sweep rate (Figure 7.3.1(c)) had no influence on the limiting current, indicating radial

diffusion to the pore mouth on the forward scan. However, one of the major features of the CVs in Figure 7.3.1 is the large capacitive component, as shown by the large separation between currents on the forward and reverse sweeps at all rates employed. For this reason, background-subtracted CVs were examined (Figure 7.3.2) in order to eliminate this capacitance effect.

After background subtraction the reverse scan response became progressively more peak-shaped with increasing scan rates (Figure 7.3.2(b)). At slower scan rates, the transferring ion TEA^+ had a longer time period in which to diffuse out of/away from the pore. Upon reaching $\Delta_o^w \phi_{\text{sw}}$, a quantity of the transferred TEA^+ was present in the bulk organogel. Therefore on back transfer a significant spherical component to the diffusion was present and a steady-state response observed, as was the case at 5 mV s^{-1} . Faster scan rates allow less time for TEA^+ to diffuse out of the pore. Therefore, when $\Delta_o^w \phi_{\text{sw}}$ was reached, the majority of the TEA^+ ions remained confined within the pore and linear diffusion dominated the back-transfer process. In Figure 7.3.2(b) this effect is already perceptible at 10 mV s^{-1} and linear diffusion is the dominant process at and above 20 mV s^{-1} .

Some analysis of the resistance and capacitance of the nanoITIES membrane system may be beneficial in developing an understanding of its properties. Pore resistance influences ion transport through the nanopores. The cross-sectional area in direct electrical contact with either the aqueous or organic side is defined by the diameter of the nanopores. The first order approximation of the pore resistance is given by Equation 4.3.1, as discussed with regard to the μITIES arrays in section 4.3.3. The conductivity (κ) of the solution filling the pore, in this instance primarily the organic

phase (see section 7.3.3), is $49 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ as discussed in section 4.3.3, and the pore depth, l , is 100 nm for all nanopore array designs.

From Equation 4.3.1, it is clear that increasing r_a reduces the pore resistance. Also, the pores of the array act like resistors in parallel so that the total inverse resistance is estimated by multiplying the inverse resistance of a single pore by N_p . Therefore a decrease in the resistance of an array is also expected with an increasing number of pores. Both these effects are exemplified in Table 7.3.1, in terms of increasing N_p for nanoITIES array designs 5, 35, and 45 (which each have an r_a value of ca. 125 nm but vary in N_p from 1 to 390 pores) and increasing r_a for nanoITIES array designs 27 to 31 (which each have 95 pores in the array but vary in r_a from ca. 25 to ca. 250 nm). Measurements of the steady-state current on the forward sweeps, i_{ss} , for each of the nanoITIES array designs were attained from the background subtracted CVs of 150 $\mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer, discussed later in section 7.3.2 with the as-recorded CVs shown in Figures 7.3.9 and 7.3.10, and are listed in Table 7.3.1. The calculated iR drops followed the trends in array resistance, decreasing with increasing N_p or increasing r_a . A very large iR drop was observed for nanoITIES array design 5, which contains a single pore, of ~ 47 mV. All other iR drops, however, occurred in the range ~ 1 to ~ 11 mV.

Table 7.3.1: The pore and array resistances (R_p and R_a , respectively) were calculated for each nanoITIES array design using Equation 4.3.1. r_a values were taken from SEM data listed in Table 7.2.1, and the conductivity, κ , of the 1,6-DCH organogel which fills the pores was assumed to be $49 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, as determined by Katano and Senda.⁶⁶ The iR drop was subsequently calculated for each nanoITIES array design using the experimentally derived steady-state currents, i_{ss} , measured from the forward sweeps of the background subtracted CVs for TEA⁺ ion transfer.

Design	Pore resistance,		Array resistance,	i_{ss} / nA	iR drop / mV
	$R_p = \frac{l}{\pi r_a^2 \kappa}$ / Ω	$R_a = R_p * N_p$ / Ω			
5	451×10^6	451×10^6		0.104 ± 0.002	46.80 ± 0.93
35	422×10^6	4.4×10^6		0.483 ± 0.029	2.15 ± 0.13
45	491×10^6	1.3×10^6		0.920 ± 0.074	1.16 ± 0.09
27	11278×10^6	118×10^6		0.097 ± 0.003	11.50 ± 0.36
28	3070×10^6	32.3×10^6		0.125 ± 0.014	4.05 ± 0.45
29	1253×10^6	13.2×10^6		0.215 ± 0.020	2.84 ± 0.27
30	459×10^6	4.8×10^6		0.300 ± 0.007	1.45 ± 0.03
31	128×10^6	1.4×10^6		0.785 ± 0.026	1.06 ± 0.04

In the present experiments, automatic positive feedback compensation was applied during the CV scans via the potentiostat, so as to minimise the effect of the resistance. However, Ohmic distortion of the background subtracted CV at 50 mVs^{-1} is still evident at nanopore array design 45 (Figure 7.3.2(a)). This Ohmic resistance effect is encapsulated in the rising part of the voltammogram, where the slope is lower than expected for a reversible ion-transfer process. This would limit the applicability of these nanoITIES arrays to study the kinetics of fast heterogenous processes such as simple (unassisted)^{100, 130, 133} and facilitated (assisted)^{98, 127-129, 131} ion transfer (IT) and electron transfer (ET)¹³² at the liquid-liquid interface.

From the CVs shown in Figures 7.3.1 and 7.3.2, it may be surmised that linear diffusion is the dominant mode of diffusion at the nanoITIES array on the back transfer of TEA⁺ from the organogel into the aqueous phase, but the peak-shaped voltammetric response is masked by the non-faradaic current. The capacitance at the

nanoITIES array produced using nanopore array design 45 was calculated from the slope of a plot of current versus scan rate for a blank system, i.e. no ion transfer, see Figures 7.3.3(a) & (b).

Figure 7.3.3: (a) Cyclic voltammetry (CV) of a blank system as a function of scan rate at nanoITIES arrays formed using membrane design 45. Scan rates used: 5 (light grey), 10, 15, 20, 25, 35, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150 and 200 (black) mV s⁻¹. (b) Currents (nA) of the forward and reverse sweeps versus the scan rate (Vs⁻¹) of a blank system at nanoITIES arrays formed using membrane design 45.

This analysis assumes that the capacitance is independent of the applied potential. The current measurements were taken at an applied potential of 0.55 V and the capacitance determined was 17.8 nF. By normalising this to the geometric area of the pores, we obtain a specific capacitance of 110,000 $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$; by normalising it to the geometric area of the 100 nm thick Si₃N₄ membrane exposed to liquid contact on

either side we obtain $7 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$. The former is three-to-four orders of magnitude greater than typical literature values for an ITIES, while the latter is equivalent to the typical values of $10\text{-}100 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ in the literature.^{38, 207, 304, 305} The total capacitance of the aqueous-membrane-organogel setup may be considered to have as components the capacitance of the water-organogel nano-interface and the capacitance of the aqueous-silicon nitride-organogel three-phase structure. Thus this can be considered as two capacitances in parallel, that of the nanoITIES (in reality many identical interfaces in parallel) and that of the three-phase (liquid-solid-liquid) structure.

The CV responses of a blank system (i.e. in the absence of TEA^+) obtained at a nanoITIES array with no pores present (design 1) and a nanoITIES array containing 23 pores, each with r_a of ~ 44 nm (design 64), are compared in Figure 7.3.4(a). The blank CVs in both cases are virtually identical. Si_3N_4 is an electronic insulating material. However, the establishment of such a large capacitance across the aqueous-silicon nitride-organogel three-phase structure suggests that the Si_3N_4 membrane is somehow conductive to ion transport. One proposition is that the Si_3N_4 membrane is not acting as an effective ionic insulator between the organic and aqueous phases and, perhaps, on a sub-nanometer scale may be porous. Also, the capacitance of the aqueous-silicon nitride-organogel three-phase structure seems to be dominant over any capacitive contribution from the water-organogel nano-interface array.

Figure 7.3.4: (a) Comparison of the CV response for a blank system at nanoITIES array design 1 (black), which contains no pores, and nanoITIES array design 64 (grey), which contains 23 pores with pore radii (r_a) of 44 ± 2 nm. (b) Comparison of the CV response for a blank system at nanoITIES array design 1 (black) and the CV response after replacing the nanoporous membrane chip in the experimental setup (see section 2.3.2) with an unpatterned (i.e. by e-beam lithography, photolithography, or wet-etching) 5 x 5 mm diameter chip of uniform ~ 525 μm thickness (grey). This chip consisted of a 525 μm thick Si layer, 35 nm pad-oxide layer, and 100 nm Si_3N_4 layer.

A control experiment was carried out to ensure that no leakage of electrolyte was taking place from one phase to the other, i.e. to ensure that the only water-organogel interfaces present were those to be found within the confines of the nanopore arrays. The nanoporous membrane chip in the experimental setup (see section 2.3.2) was replaced with an unpatterned (i.e. by e-beam lithography, photolithography, or wet-etching) 5 x 5 mm diameter chip of uniform ~ 525 μm thickness. This chip consisted

of a 525 μm thick Si layer, 35 nm pad-oxide layer, and 100 nm Si_3N_4 layer. The CV responses for a blank system at nanopore array design 1 are compared with those attained for the unpatterned $\sim 525 \mu\text{m}$ chip in Figure 7.3.4(b). The only difference between the experimental setups is that nanopore array design 1 contains the 100 nm thick Si_3N_4 membrane, whereas the unpatterned 5 x 5 mm chip is uniformly $\sim 525 \mu\text{m}$ thick over its entire area. The CV response observed for the uniformly $\sim 525 \mu\text{m}$ thick chip is featureless, compared with that for nanopore array design 1, as (a) it acts as an effective electronic and ionic insulator and (b) no additional water-organogel interfaces, due to electrolyte leakage, are present in the system.

The detailed analysis of the capacitance of these nanopore membrane-based ITIES arrays will be studied further in due course. It can be surmised that the dominance of the capacitance in the CV measurements may be a limiting factor in analytical applications since the background current influences the detection limits. In this case it appears the three-phase aqueous-silicon nitride-organogel structure controls the overall capacitance but that the analytical signal, based on diffusion-controlled faradaic current, is controlled by the e-beam defined pore area.

7.3.2 Influence of nanopore array geometry

The electrochemical behaviour of the nanoITIES arrays was examined in terms of the number of pores in the array (N_p), the size of the pores defining the interfaces (r_a), and the pore center-to-center separation (r_c).

The greater steady-state current density, J_{ss} , generated at the nanoITIES is gained only at the expense of a much smaller measurable analytical signal in the form of the

absolute steady-state current, i_{ss} . This is due to the significant reduction in the area of the interface, A , defined with regard to an array of pores by Equation 4.3.2 (see section 4.3.4). Generally, the preferred strategy when dealing with this conundrum is to create arrays of nanopores (increase N_p), ideally with non-interacting diffusion zones on the timescale of the voltammetric experiment (equivalent to category B type diffusion as discussed with regard to μ ITIES arrays in section 1.3.5), in order to provide a useful electroanalytical signal. The absolute current is then simply the sum of the steady-state currents of the individual pores in the array, as described by Equation 1.3.3 (or Equation 1.3.4 depending on the position of the liquid-liquid interface within the pore).

A study of the effect of increasing N_p , while maintaining a constant r_a of ca. 125 nm and r_c of $20r_a$, on the CV response was undertaken (Figure 7.3.5).

Figure 7.3.5: CV of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer at nanoITIES arrays formed using nanopore array designs 5 (a), 35 (b), and 45 (c) with increasing N_p of 1, 95 and 390 pores, respectively, at a constant r_a of ca. 125 nm and r_c of $20r_a$. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

The expectation here was that as N_p increases, i_{ss} increases, and the resistance across the membrane decreases (Equation 4.3.1). These effects were observed, as shown by the increased current and shift of $E^{1/2}$ to less positive potentials with increasing N_p . Table 7.3.2 summarises i_{ss} , J_{ss} , and $E^{1/2}$ values obtained after background subtraction of the CVs illustrated in Figure 7.3.5.

Table 7.3.2: Summary of the experimental steady-state currents (i_{ss}), steady-state current densities (J_{ss}) and half-wave potential ($E^{1/2}$) for 150 μM TEA⁺ transfer at nanoITIES arrays with increasing N_p (at a constant r_a of ca. 125 nm and r_c of $20r_a$). Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} . The standard deviation of J_{ss} was calculated using the method of propagation of random errors.

Design	N_p	i_{ss} / nA	$J_{ss} / \text{mA cm}^{-2}$	$E^{1/2} / \text{V}$
5	1	0.104 ± 0.002	228.54 ± 19.54	0.764
35	95	0.483 ± 0.029	10.55 ± 1.05	0.701
45	390	0.920 ± 0.074	5.68 ± 0.67	0.651

For an array of non-interacting diffusion zones, as mentioned, i_{ss} at each array design is simply $N_p \times i_{ss(\text{single pore})}$ (the steady-state current for a single pore). This latter value was obtained experimentally from the current for nanopore array design 5. In addition, if the diffusion zones are non-interacting, J_{ss} should be independent of N_p because the pore radii in each array are identical. The data in Table 7.3.2 does not satisfy these criteria: the currents at the nanoITIES arrays are not 95- and 390-times that obtained at the single nanopore ITIES, which indicates the presence of overlapping diffusion zones at an r_c value of $20r_a$.

Typically at values of $r_c > 12r_a$, as discussed in section 1.3.6, one would expect that the overlap of adjacent diffusion zones would not occur under the voltammetric

conditions implemented.¹²⁵ Therefore in an effort to validate the experimental results observed in Figure 7.3.5 and Table 7.3.2 a new set of nanopores were fabricated using an identical fabrication process (as outlined in Appendix F.2). From this second set of membranes four new nanopore array designs were chosen for study with r_a of ~ 50 nm, r_c values of $20 r_a$, and N_p of either 1, 23, 95, or 390 pores, respectively (designs 55, 64, 73, and 82 in Table 7.2.1). The CV responses for the reversible ion transfer of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ and a blank electrolyte system were obtained for three individual chips at each nanopore array design. These CVs and the background subtracted CVs at each nanopore array design are presented in Figure 7.3.6. In addition, nanopore array design 1, with no pores patterned in the 100 nm thick Si_3N_4 membrane, was investigated to see if TEA^+ ions could permeate the membrane and cause a resultant steady-state current to be observed (Figure 7.3.6(a)). This experiment is based on the proposition that the large capacitance observed at nanopore array design 1 in section 7.3.1 may be due to a sub-nanometer porosity of the membrane not visible from the SEM images obtained of each nanopore array design.

As is evident from the background subtracted CV for nanopore array design 1 in Figure 7.3.6(a) some TEA^+ molecules seem to be capable of diffusing across the membrane with a steady-state current of (0.067 ± 0.010) nA measured. In contrast to the other nanopore array designs with e-beam fabricated pores, however, the steady-state current at nanopore array design 1 showed poor reproducibility.

Figure 7.3.6: CVs and background subtracted CVs of blank (grey) and $150 \mu\text{M}$ TEA⁺ transfer (black) at nanolTIES arrays formed using nanopore array designs 1 (a), 55 (b), 64 (c), 73 (d), and 82 (e) with increasing N_p of 0, 1, 23, 95, and 390 pores, respectively, at a constant r_a of ca. 50 nm and r_c of $20r_a$. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

The forward sweeps for the background subtracted CVs of each nanopore array design depicted in Figure 7.3.6 (with N_p values of 0, 1, 23, 95, and 390) are compared in Figure 7.3.7. The same trends observed with increasing N_p for the 1st set of nanopore array designs, shown in Figure 7.3.5 and Table 7.3.2, are replicated. Oncemore, a shift of $E^{1/2}$ to less positive potentials occurs with increasing N_p as the array resistance decreases. i_{ss} increases with N_p , but not in a linear fashion as illustrated in Figure 7.3.8, suggesting diffusion zone overlap at r_c values of $20r_a$. Each nanopore array design was investigated using three different nanopore array membranes and good reproducibility of the electrochemical signal between fabricated membranes was evident.

Figure 7.3.7: Comparison of background subtracted CVs (forward sweep depicted only) of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer at nanoITIES arrays formed using nanopore array designs 1 (a), 55 (b), 64 (c), 73 (d), and 82 (e) with increasing N_p of 0, 1, 23, 95, and 390 pores, respectively, at a constant r_a of ca. 50 nm and r_c of $20r_a$. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

Figure 7.3.8: The variation of i_{ss} (nA) with N_p measured from the background subtracted forward sweeps of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer at nanoITIES arrays formed using nanopore array designs 1 (a), 55 (b), 64 (c), 73 (d), and 82 (e) (see Figure 7.3.7). Three separate membranes were characterised for each nanopore array design.

Diffusion to a single nanoITIES occurs in two-dimensions at sufficiently long times: normal to the plane of the interface (linear diffusion) and radially with respect to the axis of symmetry (spherical diffusion).³⁰⁶ Consequently, the current density is not uniform across the surface of the nanoITIES but is greater at the edge of the pore. This is commonly known as the “edge effect”,¹¹⁷ as discussed in section 1.3.4. As the dimensions of the nanopore are reduced the edge effect (and therefore current density) increases in magnitude. This is because the area of the pore decreases linearly with r_a^2 (see Equation 4.3.2) but the circumference (C_p , or edge) of the pore decreases linearly with r_a , see Equation 7.3.2:

$$C_p = 2\pi r_a \quad (\text{Eq. 7.3.2})$$

In order to investigate the effects of r_a and r_c on ion transfer at nanoITIES arrays, CV of the transfer of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ and of blank electrolyte systems were undertaken

using membrane designs with an identical N_p value of 95 but increasing r_a values in the range $25 \text{ nm} \leq r_a \leq 250 \text{ nm}$. These increasing pore radii experiments were performed using two distinct sets of membranes with constant pore centre-centre separation, as a function of the pore radius, of either $20r_a$ (Figure 7.3.9) or $5r_a$ (Figure 7.3.10).

Figure 7.3.9: Highlighting the effect of increasing pore radii (r_a) on the electrochemical ion transfer response. CVs of blank (grey) and $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ transfer (black) at nanoITIES arrays formed using nanopore array designs 32 (a), 34 (b), 35 (c), and 36 (d) with increasing r_a of ca. 25, 75, 125, and 250 nm, respectively, at a constant N_p of 95 and r_c of $5r_a$. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

Figure 7.3.10: Highlighting the effect of increasing pore radii (r_a) on the electrochemical ion transfer response. CVs of blank (grey) and 150 μM TEA⁺ transfer (black) at nanoITIES arrays formed using nanopore array designs 27 (a), 28 (b), 29 (c), 30 (d), and 31 (e) with increasing r_a of ca. 25, 50, 75, 125, and 250 nm, respectively, at a constant N_p of 95 and r_c of $5r_a$. Scan rate used was 5 mV s^{-1} .

The CV responses produced sigmoidal waves on both the forward and reverse sweep at all r_a and both r_c values investigated in Figures 7.3.9 and 7.3.10. As outlined, for both of these data sets two trends are expected: an increase in the absolute steady-state current (i_{ss}) and a decrease in the steady-state current density (J_{ss}) with increasing r_a . Both of these trends were observed, as shown in Figure 7.3.11.

Figure 7.3.11: (a) Experimental steady-state currents (i_{ss}) and (b) steady-state current densities (J_{ss}) for ion transfer of 150 μM TEA⁺ through pores of the indicated pore radii (r_a) with r_c as a multiple of either 5 (hollow circles) or 20 (solid squares) times r_a . Scan rate used: 5 mV s⁻¹.

The enhancement in J_{ss} obtained with a decrease in pore size (interface size) is the result of the beneficial enhanced mass transport, due to dominance of the edge effect. This enhanced J_{ss} at small interfaces will be of benefit in bioanalytical detection methods as long as the effects of resistance, capacitance, and low absolute current can be circumvented. The latter, of course, is achieved through use of pore (interface) arrays. This in turn is influenced by the possibility of diffusion zone overlap at adjacent pores. From the data presented (Figure 7.3.11), it can be seen that an important feature of these experiments is that J_{ss} and i_{ss} are greater for the data set with the larger pore center-to-center separation, r_c , of $20 r_a$. This is indicative of less diffusion zone overlap between adjacent pores at the arrays with greater pore centre-to-centre separations.

The extension of the diffusion zone around an individual nanoITIES under potential scanning conditions, and hence the degree of diffusion zone overlap for an array of nanoITIES, can only be accurately estimated by inclusively considering the influences of the pore radius (r_a), the applied scan rate (ν), and the diffusion coefficients of the transferring species in both phases ($D_{aq.}$ and $D_{org.}$). This concept was discussed in detail when considering diffusion zone overlap at μ ITIES arrays in section 1.3.5. Whether this is a reasonable approach depends on whether the ion transfer at the nanoITIES is described by classical mass transport theory. White and co-workers have reported that voltammetric behaviour of nanometer-sized electrodes with $r_a > 10$ nm is consistent with mass transport by Fickian diffusion.^{307, 308} However, for $r_a < 10$ nm deviations of the electrochemical response from that predicted by classical theories occur.^{307,308} Therefore, classically derived theories of mass transport will

suffice to describe mass transport at the nanoITIES arrays studied here, all of which have pores with radii ≥ 25 nm.

Although attempts have been made to quantify the degree of diffusion zone overlap at μ ITIES arrays (simulation by Strutwolf et al.²⁶⁴) and at microelectrode arrays,^{123, 125, 309} as yet no universal equation exists that allows accurate estimation of overlap of diffusion zones when $r_a < 1$ μ m. Therefore, a qualitative approach towards describing the diffusion zone overlap at nanoITIES arrays is applied here. As discussed above, J_{ss} and i_{ss} are greater for the data set with the larger r_c spacing of $20 r_a$ (Figure 7.3.11). When $\delta > 0.5 r_c$ the diffusion zones around adjacent nanoITIES overlap. Within these overlapping areas the individual nanoITIES compete with each other for incoming analyte species, effectively depleting the same area, referred to as the depletion or exclusion zone. The presence of these exclusion zones leads to a drop in J_{ss} and i_{ss} for an array compared to the situation where $\delta < 0.5 r_c$. As the nanoITIES move progressively closer together, to a situation where $\delta \gg 0.5 r_c$, complete overlap of diffusion zones will occur and a linear concentration profile will be established. The data in Figure 7.3.11 indicate a greater degree of overlap of diffusion zones, with the corresponding drop in J_{ss} and i_{ss} , as we move from an r_c value of $20 r_a$ to $5 r_a$. Nevertheless, linear concentration profiles were not observed in either data set for the forward sweep, as illustrated by the steady-state voltammograms (Figures 7.3.9 and 7.3.10). Regardless, we know from the influence of N_p on the ion transfer current that overlap does occur at an r_c value of $20 r_a$, and logically this overlap is greater at an r_c of $5 r_a$. It is possible that the peak-shaped response expected for overlapped

diffusion zones is masked by the capacitive current, and not visible even after background subtraction, or may be distorted by resistance in the system.

A very recent report by Compton and co-workers³¹⁰ has commented on the aforementioned issue with regard to studies of mass transport to arrays of nanoelectrodes. They conclude that, while microelectrode arrays with small electrode centre-to-centre distances behave as a macroelectrode (category D type diffusion in section 1.3.5), nanoelectrode arrays that occupy an overall area of micrometer dimensions and exhibit either overlapping or non-overlapping diffusion zones between adjacent nanoelectrodes behave as a microelectrode. Simulated and experimental data highlighted sigmoidal CVs that reach steady-state for nanoelectrode arrays that have electrode centre-to-centre separations and diffusion zones that are definitely overlapping. Essentially the contribution of radial diffusion to nanoelectrode arrays is more important than at microelectrode arrays.

The experiments by Compton and co-workers³¹⁰ at nanoelectrode arrays provided a number of other experimental and simulated results that are complimentary to the results outlined in this chapter with regard to arrays of nanoITIES, namely:

- (a) overlap of diffusion zones between individual nanoelectrodes occurred at very large electrode centre-to-centre separations (even at very fast scan rates) up to 60 times the radius i.e. much greater than the maximum pore separation used in this chapter (20 times the radius),
- (b) greater diffusion zone overlap, as indicated by a decrease in the steady-state current, was observed as the electrode centre-to-centre separation decreased,

- (c) as the number of nanoelectrodes in the array increased the average current per nanoelectrode decreased,
- (d) the sigmoidal voltammograms at the nanoelectrode arrays seemed to exhibit a near scan rate independence in the experimentally accessible range available at nanoITIES arrays (i.e. $\nu \leq 200 \text{ mVs}^{-1}$).

7.3.3 Determination of the interface location

At a gellified nanoITIES the location of the interface within the pore structure significantly affects the voltammetric response for the initial transfer of TEA^+ . The Si_3N_4 membrane is hydrophobic at the macroscale, as determined by contact angle experiments detailed in section 7.2.1, and we assume retains this hydrophobicity at the nanoscale. As a result, there is a high probability that the pores are filled with the organogel and that the interfaces are inlaid or shallow-recessed at the aqueous side of the membrane. A comparison of the experimental steady-state currents with the theoretical steady-state currents at inlaid and shallow recessed nanoITIES will determine the extent of the recess. The following discussion assumes, however, that no overlap of diffusion zones occurs under the experimental conditions employed. The overlapping of individual diffusion zones discussed in section 7.3.2 will lead to an overestimation of the recess depths (from the aqueous side) but is unavoidable in this analysis.

Equations describing the steady-state current (i_{ss}) at inlaid¹¹⁸ (Equation 1.3.3) and recessed¹²⁰ (Equation 1.3.4) disc microelectrodes have been reported, and are discussed in sections 1.3.4 and 1.3.5. These models may also be applied to the μITIES and nanoITIES. Equation 1.3.4 is accurate provided that the recess is not too shallow.

Bartlett and Taylor³¹¹ have compared simulated chronoamperometric responses at disc microelectrodes with Equation 1.3.4 and confirmed significant discrepancies for recessed microdiscs with dimensionless depths, d (Equation 7.3.3), less than 2 (i.e. at shallow recessed microelectrodes),

$$d = \frac{L}{r_a} \quad (\text{Eq. 7.3.3})$$

where L , when discussing experiments at μ - and nanoITIES arrays, is the recessed depth of the interface in the pore from the aqueous side of the membrane. For clarity the different symbols L , l , and d for a micro- or nanopore based recessed liquid-liquid interface are schematically represented in Figure 7.3.12.

Figure 7.3.12: Schematic of a micropore or a nanopore partially filled with an organogel electrolyte phase. The ITIES is recessed from the aqueous side of the membrane to a depth, L , and the pore depth is defined as l (this is 100 μm for the microporous membranes discussed in this thesis and 100 nm for the nanoporous membranes discussed in this chapter). The dimensionless depth, d , is defined as in Equation 7.3.3.

A 4th order polynomial expression (Equation 7.3.4) was fitted by Bartlett and Taylor to the simulated steady-state flux data, over the range $0 < d < 1$, to within 0.2 and 0.25 %, respectively,

$$i_{ss} = \left(\frac{4z_j F D_j C_j^* r_a}{1 + A_1 d + A_2 d^2 + A_3 d^3 + A_4 d^4} \right) N_p \quad (\text{Eq. 7.3.4})$$

where $A_1 = 1.6843$, $A_2 = -1.3237$, $A_3 = 1.7116$, and $A_4 = -0.7585$ are all dimensionless coefficients for $0 < d < 1$. In this study the nanopore radii, r_a , are

relatively large in comparison to their depth, l . Nanopore array designs 35 and 36 will have a d value < 1 even if $L = 100$ nm and the ITIES are inlaid on the organic side of the membrane. Membrane designs 32 and 34 have d values ≤ 1 when the interfaces are recessed up to 25 % and 75%, respectively. Taking this information into consideration with the likelihood of organogel filling a considerable portion of the volume of the hydrophobic nanopores, the correct expression to use when determining i_{ss} at inlaid and recessed nanoITIES is clearly that derived by Bartlett and Taylor for shallow recessed interfaces.

A comparison of experimental steady-state currents for pore designs with r_c values of $20 r_a$ (Figure 7.3.11(a)) and calculated steady-state currents (using Equation 7.3.4, for inlaid and recessed nano-interfaces, $L = 10, 20, 30$ and 40 nm, respectively) as a function of r_a are illustrated in the Figure 7.3.13.

Figure 7.3.13: Comparison of experimental steady-state currents (for nanopore array designs 32, 34, 35, and 36; see Figure 7.3.11(a)) and calculated steady-state currents (using Equation 7.3.4) for the ion transfer of $150 \mu\text{M TEA}^+$ at inlaid and recessed nano-interfaces, $L = 10, 20, 30$ and 40 nm, respectively, as a function of r_a .

The higher aspect ratio pores (r_a of ca. 25 and ca. 75 nm, respectively) are almost entirely filled with organogel, i.e. < 10 % interface recess was observed. The lower aspect pores (r_a of 125 and ca. 250 nm, respectively) were slightly more recessed between 10-30%.

7.3.4 Improving the sensitivity of the analytical response with nanoITIES arrays

As discussed extensively in this thesis (see sections 1.3.1, 1.3.5, 6.3.4, or 7.3.2), by reducing the dimensions of the pore that geometrically defines an individual liquid-liquid interface, the mass transport to that interface is substantially enhanced (the “edge effect”), the current density increases, and the sensitivity (the slope of a plot of current density versus the concentration of the analyte species) of the analytical response is also expected to increase. In this section the improvements in the sensitivity of the analytical response for the reversible transfer of TEA⁺ across the interface was investigated. Calibration graphs of the recorded current responses (peak currents (i_p) at the macroITIES, steady-state currents (i_{ss}) at the μ - and nanoITIES arrays), and current densities (J) from CV or LSV experiments with increasing concentrations of TEA⁺ in the aqueous phase were prepared at the macroITIES (Figure 7.3.14), μ ITIES array design 2 (Figure 7.3.15), and nanoITIES array design 44 (Figure 7.3.16). The experimental setups at the μ - and nanoITIES were identical except for the membranes used to define the ITIES arrays. The experiment at the macroITIES is setup as described in section 2.3.1. The geometric area of the macroITIES was 0.92 cm² and the only variation from the electrochemical cell described in Figure 7.2.4 is that the organogel is replaced with a 1,2-DCE liquid phase containing 10 mM (BTPPA)(TPBCl).

Figure 7.3.14: CV of increasing concentrations TEA⁺ at the macroITIES. **(a)** CVs of blank (black), 50 (light grey), 100, 150, 200, 600, 1000, and 1500 (black) μM TEA⁺. **(b)** CVs of 50 (light grey), 100, 150, and 200 (dark grey) μM TEA⁺. **(c)** Plot of the peak current (i_p) versus the [TEA⁺]. **(d)** Plot of the current density (J) versus the [TEA⁺]. The geometric area of the macroITIES was 0.92 cm². Scan rate used was 5 mV s⁻¹.

Figure 7.3.15: CV of increasing concentrations TEA^+ at μTIES array design 2 (see table 4.2.1 for the geometric parameters). **(a)** CVs of blank (black) and, in order of increasing i_{ss} response, 5 (light grey), 7.5, 10, 15, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 (black) μM TEA^+ . **(b)** CVs (forward sweep only) of blank (black), 5 (light grey), 7.5, 10, 15, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 (black) μM TEA^+ . **(c)** Plot of the steady-state current (i_{ss}) versus the $[\text{TEA}^+]$. **(d)** Plot of the steady-state current density (J_{ss}) versus the $[\text{TEA}^+]$. The geometric area of μTIES array design 2 was $1.70 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$. Scan rate used was 10 mV s^{-1} .

Figure 7.3.16: (a) LSV of blank (black) and, in order of increasing i_{ss} response, 50 (light grey), 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 350 and 400 (black) μM TEA⁺ transfer at a nanoITIES array formed using nanopore array design 44. Lower inset: * expansion of base line current response between 0.32 V and 0.58 V for the blank and at all TEA⁺ additions. (b) Plot of the steady-state current (i_{ss}) versus [TEA⁺]. (c) Plot of the steady-state current density (J_{ss}) versus [TEA⁺]. The geometric area of nanopore array design 44 was $5.62 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2$. Scan rate used was 10 mV s^{-1} .

The experiment at the macroITIES (Figure 7.3.14) was carried out using a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} , while the experiments at the μ - and nanoITIES (Figures 7.3.15 and 7.3.16, respectively) were carried out using a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} . From scan rate studies of TEA^+ ion transfer at both the μ ITIES array (Figure 4.3.6) and nanoITIES array (Figure 7.3.1(c)) we see that i_{ss} is scan rate independent in both cases and can therefore be directly compared with the i_p obtained at the macroITIES. The sensitivities of the analytical response are normalised in each case with respect to the area of the ITIES and summarised in Table 7.3.3.

Table 7.3.3: Improvements in the sensitivity of the analytical response to the detection of TEA^+ ion transfer across the ITIES with interfacial miniaturisation.

ITIES type	Geometric area cm^2	Dynamic range μM	n	R	Sensitivity $\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$
Macro	0.92	50-1500	7	0.998	0.0345
Micro (array design 2)	1.70×10^{-4}	5-100	9	0.999	0.7432
Nano (array design 44)	5.62×10^{-8}	50-400	8	0.998	53.433

The sensitivity of the analytical response to TEA^+ ion transfer increases one order of magnitude on miniaturisation of the interface from the macroscale to the microscale and a further two-orders of magnitude on miniaturisation from the microscale to the nanoscale. The characteristic increased slope of the plot of current density versus concentration due to enhanced mass transport at the μ ITIES array in comparison to that at the macroITIES is depicted in Figure 7.3.17(a). The sheer magnitude of the increase in current density with the nanoITIES array required the use of Log scales to compare the macro, micro, and nano-scale ITIES data directly (Figure 7.3.17(b)). The use of Log scales, however, precludes direct visual comparisons of the increasing slope with miniaturisation.

Figure 7.3.17: (a) Comparison of the calibration plots of the current density (J) versus increasing concentration TEA^+ obtained at the macroITIES and μ ITIES array design 2. (b) Plot of $\text{Log}(J)$ versus $\text{Log}([TEA^+])$ at the macroITIES, μ ITIES array design 2, and nanoITIES array design 44. Note that the experiment at the macroITIES was carried out using a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} and the experiment at the μ ITIES array was carried out at 10 mV s^{-1} .

During the successive voltammograms used for construction of Figure 7.3.16 it was noticed that the voltammetric baseline between 0.32 V and 0.58 V shifted in slope and

to more negative current values (see lower inset, Figure 7.3.16) with increasing analyte concentration. This may be a change in the capacitive current at the ITIES as the experiment progresses. As mentioned in section 7.3.1, the ITIES moves during charge transfer processes.³⁰³ With each successive charge transfer event some aqueous phase may creep up the inside walls of the nanopore becoming trapped between the organogel and the wall, leading to an increase of the organogel's interfacial area in contact with the aqueous phase, thus altering the capacitance current observed.

Finally, some preliminary differential pulse voltammetry experiments at nanoITIES arrays formed using membrane design 36 were performed. As discussed in Chapter 5, the use of differential pulse voltammetry as a stripping technique after preconcentration of the organogel with an analyte (the rate of preconcentration being considerably increased by the enhanced mass transport at the miniaturised ITIES) proved highly successful with low limits of detection for analytes such as oligopeptides achieved. As discussed in section 7.2.4 no further optimisation of the experimental parameters used at the μ ITIES arrays was attempted in this chapter. In any event the parameters implemented at the μ ITIES arrays also seem adequate for use at the nanoITIES arrays with well-shaped pulse voltammograms recorded, as illustrated in Figure 7.3.18.

Figure 7.3.18: Use of pulse techniques at nanoITIES arrays formed using membrane design 36. **(a)** Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV) of 150 μM TEA⁺ transfer for blank (grey) and 150 μM TEA⁺ (black) transfer. **(b)** Background subtracted differential pulse voltammetry (BS DPV) of 150 μM TEA⁺ transfer.

7.4 Conclusions

The miniaturisation of electrified interfaces can bring improved sensitivity in electroanalytical detection methods. Presented here is the first use of geometrically regular solid-state nanopore arrays in Si_3N_4 membranes to support nanoscale liquid-liquid interfaces. The membranes were fabricated by a combination of photolithographic patterning, wet-etching, e-beam lithographic patterning, and gas-

phase reactive ion etching. The geometric parameters of the individual arrays were thoroughly characterised by analysis of SEM images.

The voltammetric behaviour of the resultant organogel-liquid nanoITIES arrays in the presence of a transferring ion was characterised via CV, LSV, and DPV. From CV analysis we were able to determine that the interface is $\leq 30\%$ recessed from the aqueous side for all pore sizes, with smaller recesses for pores with higher aspect ratios. This was achieved by comparison of experimental steady-state currents and calculated steady-state currents.

Apparent steady-state behaviour was observed on the forward and reverse sweeps at all nanoITIES array geometries irrespective of the pore centre-to-centre separations. However, it appeared that diffusion zone overlap between adjacent pores occurred on the transfer of TEA⁺ from the aqueous to organogel phase at all array geometries, i.e. with r_c values of either $5r_a$ or $20r_a$, at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . The expected peak-shaped response on the forward sweep is absent even after CV background subtraction and may be attributed to possible distortion by resistance in the system. Interestingly, a recent report by Compton and co-workers³¹⁰ also reported these seemingly unusual observations for mass transport at arrays of nanoelectrodes both experimentally and with simulation. They conclude that microelectrodes arrays with small electrode centre-to-centre distances and extensive diffusion zone overlap behave as a macroelectrode while nanoelectrode arrays, that occupy an overall area of micrometer dimensions and exhibit either overlapping or non-overlapping diffusion zones between adjacent nanoelectrodes, behave as a microelectrode. Thus, the deviation of the nanoelectrode array behaviour from that typical of a microelectrode

array is attributed to the greater contribution of radial diffusion to nanoelectrode arrays than to microelectrode arrays.³¹⁰

NanoITIES arrays with the smaller pore centre-centre separation, at $5 r_a$, exhibited the greater apparent diffusion zone overlap as indicated by a reduced i_{ss} and J_{ss} . Background subtracted CVs confirmed the evolution of a peak-shaped response, otherwise masked by the non-faradaic current, on the reverse sweep with increasing scan rate, indicating that linear diffusion dominates the reverse transfer. The significantly reduced diffusion coefficient of TEA⁺ in the organogel means that it cannot diffuse out of the pore prior to back transfer on the timescale of a voltammetric experiment at higher scan rates.

The presence of a larger than expected capacitance in the CV measurements may be a limiting factor in analytical applications since the background current influences the detection limits. The total capacitance of the aqueous-membrane-organogel setup may be considered to have as components the capacitance of the water-organogel nano-interfaces and the capacitance of the aqueous-silicon nitride-organogel three-phase structure. The 100 nm thick Si₃N₄ membrane may contain sub-nanometer diameter pores, not seen under SEM imaging, leading to an ionic conductivity over the entire $500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}^2$ thinned portion of the membrane that gives rise to the capacitance across the three-phase structure. It appears that this three-phase aqueous-silicon nitride-organogel structure controls the overall capacitance but that the analytical signal, based on diffusion-controlled faradaic current, is controlled by the e-beam defined pore area.

Nevertheless, the sensitivity of the analytical response to TEA⁺ ion transfer was seen to increase one order of magnitude on miniaturisation of the interface from the macroscale to the microscale and a further two-orders of magnitude on miniaturisation from the microscale to the nanoscale.

The electrochemical characterisation reported here provides the basis for development of nanoanalytical detection methods, including those aimed at the detection of biochemical substances, toward which this present work is aimed.

Chapter 8

General conclusions and suggestions for further progress

The body of work presented in this thesis is concerned with the electrochemical processes that occur at a polarised liquid-liquid interface, also known as the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES), or an array of polarised liquid-liquid interfaces. The ITIES may be used to electrochemically detect species of bio-analytical importance in a non-redox active manner. Three categories of ITIES are discussed in this thesis: (a) ITIES created on a macro-scale i.e. with an interfacial areas of approximately 1 cm², (b) a variety of micron-scale ITIES arrays confined within micro-machined pores in silicon membranes, and (c) a variety of nano-scale ITIES arrays confined within e-beam patterned and chemically etched pores in 100 nm thick silicon nitride membranes.

The macroITIES were used to study the electrochemical behaviour of a bio-macromolecule, hen-egg-white lysozyme (HEWL). The μ ITIES arrays were: (a)

characterised by electrochemical transfer of the model ion tetraethylammonium cation (TEA^+), (b) investigated as a useful analytical tool for the detection of a selection of bio-molecules, either relatively small (i.e. oligopeptides and a low generation dendrimer) or quite large (HEWL and insulin from bovine pancreas) in size, in a non-redox active manner, and (c) analysed under hydrodynamic conditions. The nanoITIES arrays were characterised by electrochemical transfer of the model ion TEA^+ .

An investigation of the electrochemical behaviour of the large bio-macromolecule HEWL at the macroITIES, carried out by means of cyclic voltammetry, proved quite complicated. In general it was found that:

- (a) the electrochemical response of HEWL at the ITIES was dominated by the charge of the HEWL molecule in the aqueous phase and the nature of the anion in the organic phase, and
- (b) HEWL does not transfer across the ITIES itself but instead absorbs on the aqueous side of the ITIES facilitating the transfer of the organic anion.

Studying the electrochemical behaviour of a large bio-macromolecule such as HEWL (or insulin⁷⁹ or haemoglobin⁷⁸) at the ITIES is still an emerging topic of interest within the liquid-liquid electrochemistry field and, as such, a considerable amount of further research is necessary in order to answer some fundamental questions. In particular more evidence needs to be gathered to prove conclusively that HEWL does not in fact transfer across the ITIES itself but instead produces an electrochemical response by facilitating the transfer of the organic electrolyte anion.

Recently, Girault and co-workers have reported the coupling of liquid-liquid electrochemistry with biphasic electrospray ionisation mass spectrometry (BESI-MS).^{312, 313} BESI-MS can provide extremely useful data to compliment voltammetric data obtained at the polarised liquid-liquid interface. The mass spectra have been shown to (a) identify complexes that are capable of forming at the liquid-liquid interface and (b) give data on the stoichiometry of complexation reactions between an aqueous based ion (such as metal ions or peptides) and an ionophore present in the organic phase. The identification of a HEWL-TPBCl⁻ complex by BESI-MS would provide crucial corroborative evidence that the electrochemical response observed in the presence of HEWL is a result of the facilitated transfer of the organic electrolyte anion by adsorbed HEWL (or denatured HEWL) at the ITIES.

Sagara and co-workers have reported the coupling of liquid-liquid electrochemistry with potential modulated fluorescence (PMF) spectroscopy.²⁴⁸ PMF spectroscopy was used to analyse the interfacial transfer mechanism of a fourth generation (G4) PAMAM dendrimer.²⁴⁸ Comparing the voltammetric data for the varying HEWL electrochemical response with pH at the ITIES and PMF data obtained under the same conditions would provide additional useful information on the interfacial transfer mechanism. Potential obstacles include selecting a suitable fluorescent probe, as was necessary in the case of the dendrimer study mentioned above, that binds stably to HEWL and does not interfere with the transfer mechanism. If this is achieved then a PMF spectroscopic study would be expected to show the adsorption of HEWL on the aqueous side of the ITIES and a transfer event associated with the facilitated transfer of TPBCl⁻ from o → w at all pHs below HEWL's *pI* of 11.35. At and above pH 11.35 no evidence of adsorption or ion transfer processes is expected.

Finally, the electrochemical response of HEWL should be investigated using a series of buffered aqueous phase solutions at different pHs and compared with the experiments carried out with a 10 mM LiCl aqueous phase (pH adjusted using either aqueous HCl or aqueous LiOH). These experiments will ensure that the measured bulk aqueous phase pH and the local pH at the ITIES are identical and remain constant during the CV experiment. The absence of buffered aqueous phases in the experiments outlined in Chapter 3 leave open the possibility of local pH changes at the ITIES.

Five different μ ITIES array designs were characterised by ion transfer of the model ion TEA⁺ using CV. The organic phase was gellified with poly (vinyl chloride) to increase the mechanical stability of the ITIES. The experimental data, in terms of the shapes of the CVs and the steady-state (i_{ss}) or peak (i_p) currents obtained on the forward sweeps, was compared with calculated data and simulated data (from simulated CVs of TEA⁺ transfer by Dr. Jörg Strutwolf under identical experimental conditions to those employed). The following conclusions were made from analysis of the forward sweeps:

- (a) the liquid-organogel interface was essentially inlaid at the aqueous side of the micropore channel with a maximal recess of 2.5 μm for a pore with a depth of 100 μm and pore radius of ca. 25 μm ,
- (b) steady-state voltammetry on the forward sweep was observed for μ ITIES array designs that fulfilled the conditions for non-interacting diffusion zones described by Saito et al.¹²⁵ and Compton and co-workers,¹²³ based on the ratio of r_c to r_a , and whether the extension of the diffusion zone (δ) as a function of the applied scan rate exceeded $0.5r_c$, respectively,

- (c) experimental i_{ss} for these μ ITIES arrays designs were in agreement with the calculated, based on spherical diffusion to inlaid μ ITIES, and simulated data (category B type diffusion regimes, see section 1.3.5),
- (d) peaked-shaped voltammetry on the forward sweep was observed for μ ITIES array designs that did not fulfill the aforementioned conditions for non-interacting diffusion zones,
- (e) the calculated i_p for these μ ITIES array designs using the Randles-Sevcik equation were considerably lower than the experimental and simulated values suggesting the experimental peak currents are enhanced by a spherical diffusion component,
- (f) thus, the diffusion regimes established were indicative of moderately overlapping diffusion fields (see category C type diffusion regimes in section 1.3.5).

The slow TEA⁺ diffusion coefficient in the organogel prevented the ion diffusing out of the 100 μ m deep pore on the timescale of the experiment after the initial transfer event, thus ensuring a linear diffusion regime on the back-transfer and the resulting prominent peak-shaped responses on the reverse sweeps for each μ ITIES array design. From an electroanalytical point of view, when designing a μ ITIES array, a trade-off is necessary in order to incorporate the maximum number of micropores into the array (thus increasing the current, which is the analytical signal, and reducing the resistance across the membrane) while ensuring the pores are sufficiently separated such that the condition for non-interacting diffusion zones is achieved (to ensure the maximum current density). The sensitivity for cyclic voltammetry of a simple diffusion controlled ion transfer process (i.e. TEA⁺ transfer) increased one order of

magnitude using μ ITIES array design 2 in comparison to that achieved at the macroITIES.

Once the behaviour of the μ ITIES array system was characterised and understood, a suitable μ ITIES array design was chosen (design 2; exhibiting non-interacting diffusion zones) and investigated as a useful analytical tool for the detection of a selection of bio-molecules, either relatively small (i.e. oligopeptides and a low generation dendrimer) or quite large (HEWL and insulin from bovine pancreas) in size, in a non-redox active manner. The use of a gellified organic phase was amenable to the implementation of voltammetric stripping techniques at the liquid-organogel interface. Thus, by combining:

- (a) the ability to preconcentrate the organogel with the analyte of interest,
- (b) the enhanced mass transport available at the μ ITIES array,
- (c) the use of the sensitive differential pulse voltammetry stripping technique, and
- (d) some simple signal processing

greatly improved detection limits and sensitivities were achieved for a selection of oligopeptides in comparison to those at the macroITIES. Furthermore, the signal processing technique described as “subtractive stripping voltammetry” in Chapter 5 was shown to produce well-separated peaks for a mixture of two oligopeptides, illustrating the possibility to detect certain mixture combinations depending on individual oligopeptide formal ion transfer potentials ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi_j^{o'}$).

Expected increases in the rate of insulin and HEWL mass transport to the interface at μ ITIES array 2 did not bring about significant improvements in the sensitivities of the

analytical responses in comparison to those achieved at the macroITIES, suggesting that:

- (a) diffusion of the bio-macromolecules in the aqueous phase to the μ ITIES was not the rate determining step in the mechanism, and
- (b) linear diffusion of TPBCl⁻ from the organogel to the μ ITIES was the most likely candidate to act as the rate determining step since
 - I. no enhancement of the mass transport would occur in this scenario as an edge effect cannot be established within the confines of a micropore, and
 - II. a linear dependence of the peak current on the forward sweep for HEWL with $(\nu)^{1/2}$ suggests linear diffusion occurs during the rate determining step. This is in contrast to the scan rate independence shown at the same μ ITIES array design for simple diffusion controlled TEA⁺ charge transfer.

The distorted electrochemical responses of TEA⁺ in the presence of insulin and HEWL on the forward sweep at μ ITIES array design 2, in comparison with the perfectly formed TEA⁺ steady-state response in the presence of the smaller dendrimer DAB-AM-4, provided further evidence for adsorption of the larger bio-macromolecules at the interface. In addition, the reverse sweep for TEA⁺ in the presence of all three molecules is unaffected, perhaps indicating that the interfering adsorbed layers are present on the aqueous side of the ITIES.

Hydrodynamic analysis of the μ ITIES arrays using amperometry revealed:

- (a) the independence of the steady-state current for TEA⁺ on the flow velocity of the aqueous phase, which indicated the current is limited by diffusion

dominated mass transport. This behaviour is due to the fact that the steady-state diffusion layer thickness perpendicular to the microinterfaces does not exceed the thickness of the hydrodynamic layer for any volumetric flow rate employed.

- (b) a dependence of the magnitude of the amperometric peak currents for each oligopeptide studied under flowing conditions on the applied potential ($\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$). Hydrodynamic voltammograms constructed from the amperometric peak currents at each applied potential show that an individual oligopeptide may be selectively extracted from a mixture of oligopeptides at a specific $\Delta_{\beta}^{\alpha}\phi$.

These data demonstrate that hydrodynamic μ ITIES arrays engineered within microporous silicon membranes may be usefully employed as detectors for flow analytical methods such as liquid chromatography, capillary electrophoresis, or flow-injection analysis.

A variety of nanopore array designs were fabricated in 100 nm thick Si_3N_4 membranes, 5 x 5 mm in area, and supported by a 525 μm thick silicon chip. Subsequently, an assortment of nano-liquid-liquid interface arrays were created by immobilising these Si_3N_4 pores between two immiscible electrolyte solutions. This is the first reported use of geometrically regular solid-state nanopore arrays to support nanoscale liquid-liquid interfaces. The nanoITIES arrays, in a similar manner to the μ ITIES arrays discussed earlier, were characterised by ion transfer of TEA^+ using CV.

The following conclusions were made:

- (a) the liquid-organogel interface is $\leq 30\%$ recessed from the aqueous side for all pore sizes, with smaller recesses for pores with higher aspect ratios,

- (b) apparent steady-state voltammetry is observed on the forward and reverse sweeps irrespective of the pore centre-to-centre separations, r_c , (i.e of either 5 or 20 times the pore radius, r_a) and at all scan rates applied in the range $5 \geq \nu \geq 50 \text{ mVs}^{-1}$,
- (c) despite this observation, the i_{ss} on the forward sweep did not increase linearly with the number of pores in the array, N_p , indicating diffusion zone overlap at the greater r_c value of $20 r_a$,
- (d) the i_{ss} on the forward sweep increased linearly with increasing r_a ,
- (e) the steady-state current density (J_{ss}) on the forward sweep increased with decreasing r_a ,
- (f) arrays with the smaller r_c value of $5 r_a$ exhibited the greater apparent diffusion zone overlap as indicated by a reduced i_{ss} and J_{ss} ,
- (g) background subtracted CVs confirmed the evolution of a peak-shaped response, otherwise masked by the non-faradaic current, on the reverse sweep with increasing scan rate indicating linear diffusion dominates the back transfer,
- (h) the significantly reduced diffusion coefficient of TEA^+ in the organogel means that it cannot diffuse out of the pore prior to back transfer on the timescale of a voltammetric experiment at higher scan rates,
- (i) a larger than expected capacitance in the CVs was observed and attributed to a three phase aqueous- Si_3N_4 -aqueous structure that may be due to sub-nanometer porosity of the Si_3N_4 membrane not visible when viewed with SEM,

- (j) this sub-nanometer porosity may also explain the large capacitance at a Si_3N_4 membrane that has no nanopores etched through it,
- (k) nevertheless the sensitivity of the analytical response to TEA^+ ion transfer was seen to increase two-orders of magnitude on miniaturisation from the microscale to the nanoscale.
- (l) observations (b), (c), and (f) above have also been observed in a recent report by Compton and co-workers³¹⁰ when studying mass transport to nanoelectrode arrays.

The electrochemical characterisation reported here provides the basis for development of nanoanalytical detection methods, including those aimed at the detection of biochemical substances, toward which this present work is aimed.

Further study of the capacitance observed at all nanoITIES arrays is required. Perhaps the sub-nanometer porosity proposed may be due to the very thin nature of the Si_3N_4 membrane. It is known that the thinner the membrane the smaller the pores that may be fabricated in that membrane. Nevertheless, it may be useful to fabricate nanoporous Si_3N_4 membranes of 200, 300, 400, or 500 nm thicknesses to see if the observed capacitance with CV is reduced. Also impedance measurements of the capacitance at the current 100 nm thick Si_3N_4 membranes will be carried out in due course.

The Si_3N_4 surface of the nanopore array membranes and the nanopore walls themselves may be functionalised with a probe (for example an antibody³¹⁴ or a specific substrate) and used to create a selective on/off type sensor response³¹⁵ for the corresponding analyte (for example an antigen or enzyme). The on response would be

an ionic current flowing across the open functionalised nanopores in the array and the off response would be the disappearance (or at least dramatic reduction) of this ionic current due to blockage of the nanopores on, for example, binding of an antibody to its corresponding antigen.

Fabrication of nanopore arrays with pore radii in the range of 1 to 10 nm will allow selective transfer of ions based on their charge by varying the ionic strength of the solution. At low ionic strengths the electrical double layer increases in thickness, reducing the effective cross-section through which ions of the same charge as the pore walls (co-ions) may be transported. At a sufficiently small pore size, the nanopore will selectively only allow the transfer of counter-ions.

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Appendix A

List of chemicals

- Chemicals used for this study are classified in alphabetical order and listed below.
- All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Ireland Ltd.
- All aqueous phase solutions were prepared in ultrapure water with a resistivity of 18 M Ω cm from an Elgastat maxima-HPLC (Elga, UK).

Reagent	Acronym	Mol. wt. g mol ⁻¹	Purity/comment	Product number
Acetone	-	58.80	≥99% (GC)	24201
Activated aluminium oxide	Al ₂ O ₃	101.96	-	199974
Bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene) ammonium chloride	(BTPPA)(Cl)	574.03	97%	223832

Reagent	Acronym	Mol. wt. g mol ⁻¹	Purity/comment	Product number
Dibenzo-18-crown-6 ether	DB18C6	360.40	≥98.0% (UV)	33531
1,2-dichloroethane	1,2-DCE	98.96	≥ 99% (GC)	15428
1,6-dichlorohexane	1,6-DCH	155.07	≥ 97.0% (GC)*	35860
			98%	D63809
Dileucine	Leu-Leu	244.33	-	L2752
Dilysine dihydrochloride	Lys-Lys	347.28	-	L5502
Diphenylalanine	Phe-Phe	312.36	-	P4126
Hydrochloric Acid	HCl	36.46	36.5-38%	07102
Insulin from bovine pancreas	-	5733.49	HPLC grade, powder	I5500
Iron (III) chloride hexahydrate	FeCl ₃ , ferric chloride	270.30	≥99%	31232
Lithium chloride, anhydrous	LiCl	42.39	≥99.0% (AT)	62478
Lithium hydroxide monohydrate	LiOH	41.96	≥99.0%	62531
Lysozyme from chicken egg white	HEWL	~14,600	dialyzed, lyophilized, powder	62970
Magnesium chloride, anhydrous	MgCl ₂	95.21	≥98%	M8266
Methanol	MeOH	32.04	≥99.9%, CHROMASOLV [®] , for HPLC	34860
Nitric acid	HNO ₃	63.01	≥69%	30702

Reagent	Acronym	Mol. wt. g mol⁻¹	Purity/comment	Product number
Polypropylenimine tetraamine dendrimer, generation 1.0	DAB-AM-4	316.53	-	460699
Poly(vinyl chloride), low molecular weight	PVC	~48,000	-	81388
Potassium chloride	KCl	74.55	99.0-100.5%	P3911
Potassium tetrakis (4- chlorophenyl) borate	(K)(TPBCl)	496.11	≥98.0% (AT), Selectophore®	60591
Potassium tetraphenylborate	(K)(TPB)	358.32	97%	466689
1-Propanol	-	60.10	≥99% (GC)	24135
Sodium hydroxide, anhydrous pellets	NaOH	40.00	≥98%	S8045
Sodium tetrakis(4- fluorophenyl)borate dihydrate	(Na)(TFPB)	450.21	≥97.0% (NT), Selectophore®	72014
Sulphuric acid	H ₂ SO ₄	98.08	95.0-98.0%	320501
Tetraethylammonium chloride	(TEA)(Cl)	165.70	≥99.0% (AT) electrochemical grade	86616
Trilysine	Lys-Lys-Lys	402.53	≥97% (TLC)	L8901
Tween® 80	-	~1310	viscous liquid	P1754

*This product number has been discontinued by Sigma-Aldrich Ireland Ltd.

Appendix B

Preparation of the organic

electrolyte salts: (BTPPA)(TPBCl),

(BTTPA)(TPFB), and

(BTPPA)(TPB)

B.1: (BTPPA)(TPBCl)

Chemicals: Potassium tetrakis(4-chlorophenylborate), (K)(TPBCl)

Bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium chloride, (BTPPA)(Cl)

H₂O/MeOH solution (1:2 v/v)

H₂O/acetone solution (1:1 v/v)

Metathesis reaction:

The reaction between (BTPPA⁺)(Cl⁻) and (K⁺)(TPBCl⁻) is 1:1, i.e. 1 mole (BTPPA⁺)(Cl⁻): 1 mole (K⁺)(TPBCl⁻).

Protocol:

- 1.157 g of (BTPPA)(Cl) was dissolved in 10 mL of H₂O/MeOH (1:2 v/v) solution and added drop-wise to a 20 mL stirring solution containing 1g of (K)(TPBCl) (also dissolved in the H₂O/MeOH (1:2 v/v) solution).

- The (BTTPA)(TPBCl) product formed is filtered under vacuum using a Buchner funnel and covered with Parafilm®. Holes are pierced in the Parafilm® to allow drying under vacuum for ca. 2 hours. The product was then placed in the dessicator overnight.
- The product was re-crystallised by its dissolution in acetone. The acetone solution was then filtered under gravity through filter paper soaked in acetone into a clean dry beaker.
- The beaker containing the electrolyte was covered with Parafilm®, holes were pierced in the Parafilm®, and the container placed in the fume-hood to allow the acetone to evaporate (generally 1 day).
- The resulting precipitate washed with the H₂O/acetone (1:1 v/v) solution, and allowed to dry overnight in the dessicator.
- The final pure (BTTPA)(TPBCl) product must be stored in the refrigerator (the electrolyte is sensitive to temperature) and covered in aluminium foil, to prevent exposure to light.

B.2: (BTTPA)(TPFB)

This electrolyte salt was prepared using the protocol outlined above for (BTTPA)(TPBCl) preparation, using potassium tetrakis(4-fluorophenylborate) as the starting material for the following metathesis reaction:

The reaction between (BTTPA⁺)(Cl⁻) and (K⁺)(TPFB⁻) is 1:1, i.e. 1 mole (BTTPA⁺)(Cl⁻): 1 mole (K⁺)(TPFB⁻). Therefore, the first step of this protocol is:

- 1.275 g of (BTPPA)(Cl) was dissolved in 10 mL of H₂O/MeOH (1:2 v/v) solution and added drop-wise to a 20 mL stirring solution containing 1g of (K)(TPFB) (also dissolved in the H₂O/MeOH (1:2 v/v) solution).

B.3: (BTPPA)(TPB)

This electrolyte salt was prepared using the protocol outlined above for (BTPPA)(TPBCl) and (BTPPA)(TPB) preparation, using sodium tetraphenylborate as the starting material for the following metathesis reaction:

The reaction between (BTPPA⁺)(Cl⁻) and (Na⁺)(TPB⁻) is 1:1, i.e. 1 mole (BTPPA⁺)(Cl⁻): 1 mole (Na⁺)(TPB⁻). Therefore, the first step of this protocol is:

- 1.602 g of (BTPPA)(Cl) was dissolved in 10 mL of H₂O/MeOH (1:2 v/v) solution and added drop-wise to a 20 mL stirring solution containing 1g of (K)(TPB) (also dissolved in the H₂O/MeOH (1:2 v/v) solution).

Appendix C

Purification of 1,6-dichlorohexane⁶⁷

Protocol

- Add 4 mL of H₂SO₄ (95.0-98.0%) to 40mL of 1,6-dichlorohexane in a 50 mL separation funnel and shake the mixture. Allow the mixture to stand overnight in the fume-hood until two distinct layers are formed. The top layer is clear in colour and the bottom layer (which contains any impurities removed by the H₂SO₄ and the H₂SO₄ itself) is brown. The interface between these two layers is dark brown and extremely obvious.
- Transfer the upper organic layer into a clean dry beaker. Discard the lower layer.
- Add 0.5g of activated aluminium oxide powder to the organic phase and swirl the beaker. The alumina soaks up a large portion of the H₂SO₄ present and most will change from white to yellow in colour. The suspension is filtered under gravity into a new clean dry beaker.

- Shake the filtrate with 5mL of 10 M NaOH. Leave the mixture to stand for a day at least, two days may be necessary. Two different phases are formed: an upper phase that is the 1,6-DCH, and a lower phase that is more organic, viscous and cloudy in appearance. The lower phase is discarded.
- The upper phase is taken and a few mL of DI water added. The mixture is shaken and allowed stand overnight. The bottom layer is the purified 1,6-DCH solvent which is collected.

Appendix D

Procedure for calculating the limits of detection (LOD)³¹⁶

A typical experiment carried out during the course of this thesis was the preparation of a calibration graph of increasing analyte concentration in the aqueous phase (x -axis) versus the resultant current observed (y -axis) via cyclic voltammetry, linear voltammetry, or differential pulse stripping voltammetry at the macro-, μ -, or nano-ITIES. A correct statistical analysis of this data was crucial and will now be outlined.

Initially it is important to estimate how well the experimental points fit on a straight line, i.e. is there a true linear relationship present between the observed current and the concentration of analyte present. This is represented by the product-moment correlation coefficient or more commonly termed **the correlation coefficient**, R , as calculated from Equation D.1,

$$R = \frac{\sum_j \{(x_j - \bar{x})(y_j - \bar{y})\}}{\left\{ \left[\sum_j (x_j - \bar{x})^2 \right] \left[\sum_n (y_j - \bar{y})^2 \right] \right\}^{1/2}} \quad (\text{Eq. D.1})$$

where (x_j, y_j) are the experimentally observed individual points on the line, and there are n points altogether. The mean of the x and y values are \bar{x} and \bar{y} , respectively. R values are possible in the range $-1 \leq R \leq +1$, with -1 and $+1$ representing perfect negative and positive correlation.

Once it is established that a linear relationship does indeed exist between the analytical current signal (x -axis) and the concentration of analyte present (y -axis) the line of best fit that passes through the calibration points, each of which are subject to error, must now be calculated. These errors or deviations (some positive and others negative) are assumed to only occur in the y -direction, and the **fitted line of regression of y on x** seeks to minimise the deviations in the y -direction between the experimental points and the calculated line. The slope, b (Equation D.2), and intercept, a (Equation D.3), of the line are calculated using the **method of least squares**:

$$b = \frac{\sum_j \{(x_j - \bar{x})(y_j - \bar{y})\}}{\sum_j (x_j - \bar{x})^2} \quad (\text{Eq. D.2})$$

$$a = \bar{y} - b\bar{x} \quad (\text{Eq. D.3})$$

The fitted line of regression of y on x is used to calculate the limit of detection (LOD) and, thus, the random errors in the slope and intercept of this line need to be evaluated. The statistic $S_{y/x}$ is calculated (Equation D.4) and represents the standard

deviation of each point on the calibration graph (including the point representing the blank or background) that has a normally distributed variation in the y-direction only:

$$S_{y/x} = \left\{ \frac{\sum_j (y_j - \hat{y}_j)^2}{n - 2} \right\} \quad (\text{Eq. D.4})$$

where y_j are the y values obtained from the experimental data at each x value and \hat{y}_j are the y values calculated using Equation D.3.

The **limit of detection (LOD)** can now be calculated. The LOD is the analyte concentration that gives a signal (current response in this case) equal to the blank signal, y_B , plus three standard deviations of the blank, S_B .

$$y_{LOD} = 3S_B + y_B \quad (\text{Eq. D.5})$$

where y_{LOD} is the current signal equivalent to the current signal of the blank plus three times the deviation of the blank. The assumption that each point on the calibration graph (including the point representing the blank or background) has a normally distributed variation (in the y-direction only) with a standard deviation of $S_{y/x}$ allows S_B to be replaced with $S_{y/x}$. The value of the calculated intercept, a , from Equation D.3, can be used as an estimate for y_B . Therefore, the equation for y_{LOD} can be re-written (Equation D.6) and the LOD calculated from the line of best fit (Equation D.7) or read of the graph, as illustrated in Figure D.1.

$$y_{LOD} = 3S_{y/x} + a \quad (\text{Eq. D.6})$$

$$LOD = \frac{y_{LOD} - a}{b} \quad (\text{Eq. D.7})$$

Figure D.1: Determination of the limit of detection from a calibration graph of increasing concentration analyte versus the resultant current response.

Appendix E

Calculation of the net charge of an oligopeptide at a given pH

E.1 The Henderson-Hasselbalch equation is used:

For an acidic situation:

$$pH = pK_a + \log \frac{[A^-]}{[HA]} \quad (\text{Eq. E.1})$$

where $[A^-]$ is the proton acceptor, and $[HA]$ is the proton donor.

For a basic situation:

$$pH = pK_a + \log \frac{[B]}{[BH^+]} \quad (\text{Eq. E.2})$$

where $[B]$ is the proton acceptor, and $[BH^+]$ is the proton donor.

Table E.1: The following is a table, adapted from the textbook *Principles of biochemistry* (2nd Ed.)¹⁰ by Lehninger, Nelson, and Cox, of pK_a values for the functional groups that constitute the amino acids leucine, phenylalanine and lysine.

Amino acid	$pK_1(-COOH)$	$pK_2(-NH_3^+)$	$pK_R(R \text{ group})$
Leucine	2.36	9.60	-
Phenylalanine	1.83	9.13	-
Valine	2.32	9.62	-
Lysine	2.18	8.95	10.53

The charge for each oligopeptide at the given pH consists of the summation of the charge contribution from each ionisable group present in the molecule. Leucine and phenylalanine have two ionisable groups (the terminal amino and carboxyl groups), whereas lysine has three ionisable groups (the terminal amino and carboxyl groups, and the R group, which is unique to each amino acid, that contains a further amino functionality in lysine's case). When determining the overall charge of an oligopeptide it is important to remember that each dipeptide bond formed will remove one amino group and one carboxyl group capable of undergoing ionisation i.e. accepting or donating an H⁺.

Table E.2: The numbers of each ionisable functional group present, after dipeptide bond formation, in each oligopeptide.

Oligopeptide	Ionisable (-COOH) functionalities	Ionisable (-NH ₃ ⁺) functionalities	Ionisable R group functionalities
Dilysine	1	1	2
Trilysine	1	1	3
Tetralysine	1	1	4
Dileucine	1	1	0
Trileucine	1	1	0
Divaline	1	1	0
Diphenylalanine	1	1	0

All experiments involving oligopeptides in chapter 4 were carried out at pH 2.

E.2 Calculation of the charge of dileucine and trileucine at pH 2

Contribution from the -COOH functionality:

$$pH = pK_a + \log \frac{[A^-]}{[HA]} = pK_a + \log \frac{[COO^-]}{[COOH]}$$

$$2 = 2.36 + \log \frac{[COO^-]}{[COOH]}$$

$$10^{(2-2.36)} = \frac{[COO^-]}{[COOH]}$$

$$0.44 = \frac{[COO^-]}{[COOH]}$$

This is a ratio of 1 part $[HA]$ to 0.44 $[A^-]$; therefore the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[A^-]}{[HA]+[A^-]} = \frac{[COO^-]}{[COOH]+[COO^-]} = \frac{0.44}{1+0.44} = 0.31$$

Therefore at pH 2 the $-COOH$ functionality of leucine has a charge, $z_{(-COO^-)}$ of -0.31.

Contribution from the $-NH_3^+$ functionality:

$$pH = pK_a + \log \frac{[B]}{[BH^+]} = pK_a + \log \frac{[NH_2]}{[NH_3^+]}$$

$$2 = 9.60 + \log \frac{[NH_2]}{[NH_3^+]}$$

$$10^{(2-9.60)} = \frac{[NH_2]}{[NH_3^+]}$$

$$2.5 \times 10^{-8} = \frac{[NH_2]}{[NH_3^+]}$$

This is a ratio of 1 part $[BH^+]$ to 2.5×10^{-8} $[B]$; therefore the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{1}{1+2.5 \times 10^{-8}} \approx 1$$

Therefore at pH 2 the $-NH_3^+$ functionality of leucine has a charge, $z_{(-NH_3^+)}$, of +1.

The total charge, Z_j^α , of dileucine at pH 2:

$$z_j^\alpha = \sum (nz_{(-COO^-)} + nz_{(-NH_3^+)} + nz_{(R)}) \quad (\text{Eq. E.3})$$

$$z_j^\alpha = \sum ((1 \times -0.31) + (1 \times 1) + (1 \times 0)) = 0.69$$

Where n is the number of a particular ionisable group present (and not involved in the formation of dipeptide bonds) in the oligopeptide, and $z_{(R)}$ is the charge of the R group functionality.

The total charge, z_j^α , of trileucine at pH 2:

$$z_j^\alpha = \sum ((1 \times -0.31) + (1 \times 1) + (1 \times 0)) = 0.69$$

E.3 Calculation of the charge of diphenylalanine at pH 2

Contribution from the $-COOH$ functionality:

$pK_1(-COOH) = 1.83$ for phenylalanine (Table E.1). Using Equation E.1 the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[A^-]}{[HA]+[A^-]} = \frac{[COO^-]}{[COOH]+[COO^-]} = \frac{1.48}{1+1.48} = 0.60$$

Therefore at pH 2 the $-COOH$ functionality of phenylalanine has a charge, $z_{(-COO^-)}$ of -0.60.

Contribution from the $-NH_3^+$ functionality:

$pK_2(-NH_3^+) = 9.13$ for phenylalanine (Table E.1). Using Equation E.2 the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{1}{1+7.4 \times 10^{-8}} \approx 1$$

Therefore at pH 2 the $-NH_3^+$ functionality of phenylalanine has a charge, $z_{(-NH_3^+)}$, of +1.

The total charge, z_j^α , of diphenylalanine at pH 2 calculated using Equation E.3:

$$z_j^\alpha = \sum((1x - 0.6) + (1x1) + (1x0)) = 0.40$$

E.4 Calculation of the charge of divaline at pH 2

Contribution from the $-COOH$ functionality:

$pK_1(-COOH) = 2.32$ for valine (Table E.1). Using Equation E.1 the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[A^-]}{[HA]+[A^-]} = \frac{[COO^-]}{[COOH]+[COO^-]} = \frac{0.48}{1+0.48} = 0.32$$

Therefore at pH 2 the $-COOH$ functionality of valine has a charge, $z_{(-COO^-)}$ of -0.32.

Contribution from the $-NH_3^+$ functionality:

$pK_2(-NH_3^+) = 9.62$ for valine (Table E.1). Using Equation E.2 the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{1}{1+2.3 \times 10^{-8}} \approx 1$$

Therefore at pH 2 the $-NH_3^+$ functionality of valine has a charge, $z_{(-NH_3^+)}$, of +1.

The total charge, z_j^α , of divaline at pH 2 calculated using Equation E.3:

$$z_j^\alpha = \sum((1x - 0.32) + (1x1) + (1x0)) = 0.67$$

E.5 Calculation of the charge of dilysine, trilysine and tetralysine at pH 2

Contribution from the $-COOH$ functionality:

$pK_1(-COOH) = 2.18$ for lysine (Table E.1). Using Equation E.1 the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[A^-]}{[HA]+[A^-]} = \frac{[COO^-]}{[COOH]+[COO^-]} = \frac{0.66}{1+0.66} = 0.40$$

Therefore at pH 2 the $-COOH$ functionality of lysine has a charge, $z_{(-COO^-)}$ of -0.40.

Contribution from the $-NH_3^+$ functionality:

$pK_2(-NH_3^+) = 8.95$ for lysine (Table E.1). Using Equation E.2 the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{1}{1+11.2 \times 10^{-8}} \approx 1$$

Therefore at pH 2 the $-NH_3^+$ functionality of lysine has a charge, $z_{(-NH_3^+)}$, of +1.

Contribution from the R group, which is another $-NH_3^+$ functionality in lysine's case: $pK_R(R \text{ group}) = 10.53$ for lysine (Table E.1). Using Equation E.2 the concentration of the charged elements as a percentage of the total is:

$$\frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{[BH^+]}{[B]+[BH^+]} = \frac{1}{1+0.2 \times 10^{-8}} \approx 1$$

Therefore at pH 2 the R group ($-NH_3^+$) functionality of lysine has a charge, $z_{(R)}$, of +1.

The total charge, z_j^α , of dilysine at pH 2 calculated using Equation E.3:

$$z_j^\alpha = \sum((1x - 0.4) + (1x1) + (2x1)) = 2.60$$

The total charge, z_j^α , of trilysine at pH 2 calculated using Equation E.3:

$$z_j^\alpha = \sum((1x - 0.4) + (1x1) + (3x1)) = 3.60$$

The total charge, z_j^α , of tetralysine at pH 2 calculated using Equation E.3:

$$z_j^\alpha = \sum((1x - 0.4) + (1x1) + (4x1)) = 4.60$$

E.6 Summary

Table E.3: Summary of the total charge, z_j^α , of each oligopeptide

Oligopeptide	z_j^α
Dilysine	2.60
Trilysine	3.60
Tetralysine	4.60
Dileucine	0.69
Trileucine	0.69
Divaline	0.67
Diphenylalanine	0.40

Appendix F

Fabrication of e-beam patterned solid-state nanopore arrays in Si_3N_4 and SOI membranes

F.1 Introduction to micro- and nano-fabrication processes

F.1.1 Overview of fabrication steps and techniques

The fabrication flow chart, illustrated in Figure F.1, is an outline of all the techniques required to fabricate supported solid-state nanoporous membranes, described in detail later in section F.2. It is not, however; an exhaustive list of potential nano- and micro-machining techniques, for these a variety of excellent textbooks are available.³¹⁷⁻³²⁰ Only the techniques utilised to fabricate the supported nanopore arrays are described in detail here.

Figure F.1: Overview of the general fabrication steps and techniques utilised to fabricate supported solid-state nanoporous membranes in this thesis.

F.1.2 The silicon substrate

The most common starting material for all micro- and nano-fabrication processes, as is the case in this thesis, is a wafer of silicon (Si). The silicon wafer's ability to conduct electrically is modified by doping, and will produce either n-type Si or p-type Si. Silicon has four valence electrons and doping is achieved by implanting ions with one valence electron more, known as donors (group V elements such as phosphorous or arsenic), or less, known as acceptors (group III elements such as boron or gallium). The implantation of donors produces positive or p-type Si, due to "holes" that are now present in the Si lattice and free to move, while implantation of acceptors produces negative or n-type Si, due to the presence of extra valence electrons free to conduct in the Si lattice.³²¹

F.1.3 Thermal oxidation of silicon

When silicon is exposed to oxygen in air under ambient conditions its surface will be oxidised forming what is known as a "native oxide". This silicon dioxide (SiO₂) layer

will only be $\sim 20 \text{ \AA}$ in thickness. Silicon dioxide formed by thermal oxidation of silicon is an extremely useful material in micromachining being used as an insulating layer, a mask, or a sacrificial layer. As illustrated in Figure F.2, SiO_2 can be grown in a “wet” manner by steam oxidation at 1 atm or in a “dry” manner by dry oxidation at high temperatures (900-1500°C) in pure oxygen. A SiO_2 layer is grown more quickly by wet oxidation but produces a poorer quality oxide, much more prone to impurities, than with dry oxidation. Dry oxidation produces a stoichiometric oxide during which the silicon substrate is consumed.³²² The thickness of the layer of silicon replaced by the dioxide (X_s) is 44% of the thickness of the silicon dioxide layer (X_{ox}) produced, as depicted in Figure F.2.

Figure F.2: “Wet” and “dry” thermal of oxidation of silicon. Dry oxidation produces the stoichiometric oxide.

F.1.4 Chemical vapour deposition (CVD)

Deposition can be defined, in the semiconductor industry, as any process whereby a material is physically deposited on the wafer surface forming a new layer. This is in contrast to the thermal oxidation process described in section F.1.3 where the new oxide film is “grown” from the material in the wafer surface. Therefore chemical vapour deposition can be described succinctly as follows: chemicals (C) that contain the constituent elements of the desired film are mixed and reacted together in a

deposition chamber where they form a vapour (V). Subsequently, the atoms or molecules deposit (D) on the wafer surface eventually leading to film formation. It is important to note that, in general, in order to ensure the stoichiometrically correct film is deposited on the substrate a “deposition” energy needs to be provided (for example thermally or via a plasma).

The basic steps of the CVD process are firstly loading the wafer into the chamber, which should contain an inert atmosphere. Then the wafers are heated to the desired temperature. The chemical gases (vapours) are introduced into the chamber for the expected length of time it should take to create a new deposited layer and finally these chemical vapours are flushed out of the chamber and the wafer removed.

Initially, a few atoms or molecules will deposit on the surface of the substrate by a process known as nucleation. These initial atoms will form islands, and eventually these islands of material will coalesce to form a thin continuous film known as the “transition region” film. Finally the transition region film continues its growth becoming thicker until the “bulk” film is attained. Structurally, the film formed by CVD may be amorphous, polycrystalline or a single crystal depending on the experiment conditions employed.

Low pressure chemical vapour deposition (LPCVD) systems were introduced in an effort to improve the uniformity of the deposited film. This is achieved by using lower operating pressures that allow an increase in the mean free path of a molecule (how far on average a molecule moves before it undergoes a collision with another molecule) in the deposition chamber. Other advantages of this system stemming from

the use of low pressures include a lowering of the deposition temperatures (or deposition energy) required and a lessened dependence on the gas flow dynamics in the deposition chamber.

Plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD) generates a higher deposition energy and thus allows a significantly reduced deposition temperature to be used. As with LPCVD low pressures are also used with PECVD allowing good film uniformity.³²³⁻³²⁵ A more detailed discussion of plasmas will follow in section F.1.9.

F.1.5 Photolithography

Photolithography (also known as optical lithography) is the most common type of lithography. Lithography involves transferring a pattern from a mask, via a resist, onto a thin film grown or deposited on a substrate.

A mask is a stencil that can be used repeatedly to generate a specific pattern or design on a resist-coated wafer. A photomask consists of either a glass or quartz plate with an absorber pattern metal (often an 800 Å thick layer of chromium) generated on it by e-beam lithography (discussed later in section F.1.6). This mask can be placed either in direct contact with (contact mask), or be elevated slightly above (proximity or soft contact mask), the wafer. The wafer is then exposed to ultraviolet (UV) light. The glass and quartz are optically transparent (in the near UV and deep UV, respectively) but the absorber pattern is opaque to UV radiation.

Photoresists are photoreactive materials that are sensitive to radiation such that their chemical properties are altered in the presence of UV light. They can be broadly

categorised as either negative or positive photoresists, as illustrated in figure F.3. Negative photoresists are initially soluble but on exposure to light become hardened and more difficult to remove by solvents. Thus, the image formed by the resist on the substrate is the inverse of the mask pattern, Figure F.3(A). Positive photoresists are initially insoluble but on exposure to light degrade, allowing ease of removal by chemical solvents, and thus an exact image of the mask pattern is transferred into the substrate by the resist, Figure F.3(B). Positive photoresists are the preferred option for many micro- and nano-fabrication schemes due to their capabilities to resolve smaller features and be used in much thicker coatings than negative photoresists. Positive photoresists are thus much more reliable and capable of surviving fabrication steps, for example chemical ashings, which lead to significant resist thinning.³²⁶⁻³²⁸

Figure F.3: Schematic of pattern transfer for (A) a negative photoresist and (B) a positive photoresist.

The basic steps when patterning a deposited layer on a substrate using a positive photoresist are illustrated in figure F.1.4. Initially a uniform and highly adherent layer of resist is spun on the substrate free from dust or pinholes. The mask is aligned automatically to the wafer and unmasked photoresist is exposed to UV light. The wafer is now sprayed with the appropriate developer chemical for the specific resist and causes the dissolution and removal of the exposed resist only. The pattern in the resist is now transferred into the underlying deposited layer by dry etching (see section F.1.9). Finally the unexposed resist is stripped off revealing the patterned deposited layer. The stripping of a resist can be done via a wet etch in sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) or solvent-based chemicals, or can be achieved via an O_2 plasma etch at high temperatures, known as O_2 ashing.³²⁶⁻³²⁸

Photolithography also has certain disadvantages. It is exclusively a 2-D process and has a limited capability to pattern a non-planar topography. Photoresist has only a limited resistance to the more aggressive etchants. As a result in these situations the photoresist needs to be substituted with a “hard-mask” (usually an oxide),³²⁶⁻³²⁸ see steps 14 and 15 of the process flow in Figure F.9.

Figure F.4: Steps required when patterning a deposited layer on a substrate by photolithography using a positive photoresist.

F.1.6 Electron beam (e-beam) lithography

The ultimate resolution, necessary when patterning nano-features, is achieved using e-beam lithography. The energy imparted by a directed stream of electrons chemically and structurally modifies a film on the surface of the substrate. With this technique no mask is required and the pattern is “written” directly into the resist. The big disadvantage of this approach however is the long times required and low throughput when patterning each substrate. The root of this problem is that the individual features of the overall pattern are written into the resist in a sequential manner.

The resolution limits on the patterned feature are dependent on a variety of factors, some of the most important being the creation of as narrow and bright an e-beam as possible, the choice of electron beam resists, and how the pattern is transferred to the substrate. The diameter of the beam at the substrate surface is a fraction of the diameter at the emission source and hence a bright source is essential. The resist is chosen with optimal sensitivity (increased sensitivity means reduced exposure times to the e-beam and higher throughputs), resolution and dry-etch resistance. ZEP-520 polymer (Nippon Zeon), a photoresist with sub-100 nm resolution, was chosen in the fabrication of the nanopore arrays outlined in section F.2. Pattern transfer is achieved by deep reactive ion etching (DRIE),³²⁹⁻³³¹ see section F.1.12.

F.1.7 Wet etching

Wet etching is an extremely useful microfabrication technique capable of cleaning, polishing, removing surface damage and, most importantly from the point of view of this thesis, shaping 3-D structures.³³² This technique is purely chemical in nature and uses corrosive liquids (either acidic or basic in nature) to remove material from the wafer surface. A variety of materials can be etched in this manner whether they are semiconductors, conductors or insulators. A specific material can be targeted for etching by tailoring the chemical mix of the etchants. This feature makes wet etching a highly material selective technique. Commonly used wet etches include hydrofluoric acid (HF) for oxides, phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄) for nitride, nitric acid (HNO₃) in combination with HF for silicon, KOH and alcohols for silicon, and polysilicon and a combination of acetic acid (CH₃COOH), H₃PO₄ and HNO₃ for aluminium.

The etching process can be summarised broadly in four key steps: (1) transport of the reactant to the surface, (2) surface reaction, (3) transport of the reaction product away from the surface and, finally, (4) rinsing the wafer with DI water to remove any etchants followed by spin drying in a nitrogen gas atmosphere. The etch process is diffusion limited if steps (1) or (3) are the rate-determining steps, whereas the etch process is reaction rate limited if step (2) is the rate determining step. In the diffusion limited process the rate of reaction can be increased by controllably agitating the solution (either mechanically or ultrasonically). In the reaction rate limited case the rate of reaction is dependent on temperature, etching material and solution composition. Therefore when designing a wet etching apparatus control over the bath temperature and the solution agitation rate, pH and concentration are essential features.^{333, 334}

F.1.8 Isotropic versus anisotropic wet etching

An isotropic etch involves etching in all crystallographic directions simultaneously, in other words the vertical and lateral etch rates are identical. This type of etch is clearly illustrated in Figure F.5(A). The etchants are usually acidic in nature and lead to rounded isotropic features in single-crystalline silicon. This type of etching has significant limitations in terms of the feature sizes that can be incorporated on a wafer. This is due to the sideways encroachment between adjacent features during which the resist or mask is undercut, as illustrated in Figure F.5(B). In general, isotropic etches are diffusion limited and require the use of agitated baths. This is due to the difficulties experienced by the reactant in reaching the bottom of the etch pits and in removal of the reaction products.^{333, 334}

Figure F.5: (A) An isotropic wet etch, (B) sideways encroachment between adjacent isotropic wet etches, and (C) an anisotropic wet etch.

An anisotropic etch involves etching along one particular crystallographic plane in preference to the others. Essentially the etch rates for each of the crystallographic planes are different and the geometric shape of the etched feature will be perfectly defined by the slowest etching plane. The etchants are usually alkaline in nature and wet etchings key advantage is the ability to control the lateral as well as the vertical etch rate. No undercutting of the resist or mask occurs ensuring the mask geometry is patterned into the substrate with minimal variation in the lateral geometry, as illustrated in Figure F.5(C) for a preferential KOH wet etch of single-crystalline silicon along the (111) crystal plane. In general, anisotropic etches are reaction rate limited and quite slow. In order to decrease the etch times high temperatures are required in the etch baths and this often precludes the use of a variety of resists. Although very temperature sensitive, anisotropic etches are relatively unaffected by agitation. This is a distinct advantage because typically it is much easier to maintain and monitor the temperature of an etch bath than its rate of agitation.^{333, 334}

F.1.9 Dry (plasma) etching

Dry etching is a micromachining technology that combines physical (through ion bombardment of the surface) as well as chemical (through reaction of a reactive species at the surface) removal of material. Dry etching allows the isotropy of an etch to be controlled precisely and eliminates the undercutting/encroachment effects inherent to wet etching. As a result, small geometric features ($< 3 \mu\text{m}$) can be packed much more closely together (vastly increasing the circuit density) by controlling their profiles (slopes).

All dry etch systems expose the wafer substrate to a plasma. A plasma is a gas (eg. SF_6 , C_2F_2 , HBr) that has been ionized by high energy electric and magnetic fields resulting in the creation of highly reactive chemical species (neutral gas atoms, ions and electrons) that attack the surface. Any material not protected by a photoresist will be removed. The free electrons in the gas are accelerated by the electrical energy applied to the gas (which creates an electric potential between the two electrodes) and “collide” with the gas molecules. This leads to the release of other electrons, thus ionizing the gas molecules. The net charge of the plasma is neutral due to the presence of equal numbers of positive and negative charges.

Currently, plasmas are usually generated using an R.F. (radio-frequency) electrical supply. This AC electrical power source operates at a high frequency (13.56 MHz) and has a very short cycle time. This means the potential on the electrodes switches rapidly from positive to negative. Initially the electrode is positively biased attracting electrons and building up a negative potential on the electrode. On switching to a negative bias, ions become attracted to the electrode and begin to cancel out the

negative potential. However, the ions will never completely cancel out the negative potential on the electrode because (a) the cycle time is too short and (b) the ions cannot move as quickly through the plasma as the electrons. With each cycle a larger and larger negative potential is built up on the electrode so that eventually a constant negative potential is achieved. This is the mechanism by which the ions are accelerated towards the electrode since in effect a DC potential difference (DC bias) has been established between the plasma and the electrode.³³⁵

F.1.10 Reactive plasma etching

The experimental configuration for reactive plasma etching is illustrated in Figure F.6(A). The wafer is placed on the grounded electrode (the “chuck”) and the “showerhead” is the powered electrode. The gas used to form the plasma should be highly chemically reactive. Neutral chemical species (e.g. radicals such as F^0 or Cl^0) diffuse to the substrate where they react to form volatile gaseous products (removed from the system by a vacuum pump) with the specific layer to be etched. Radicals have no charge, but are highly chemically unstable and thus highly reactive. As they react at the surface, a type of pressure gradient forms which draws in more radicals allowing the etch to continue. Therefore, in this variation of dry etching the only role of the plasma is to supply gaseous, reactive etchant species. By operating at low voltages (DC bias is 10 V-100 V) the impingement of high-energy ions on the sample is avoided. At the high pressures applied (100 mTorr-1 Torr), the neutral species strike the surface at random angles producing a largely isotropic etch profile,³³⁶ as illustrated in figure F.6(A).

Figure F.6: The experimental configurations and etch profiles for (A) reactive plasma etching and (B) reactive ion etching (RIE).

F.1.11 Reactive ion etching (RIE)

The experimental configuration for RIE is illustrated in Figure F.6(B). The wafer is placed on the powered electrode (the “chuck”) while the other electrode (the “showerhead”) and the chamber body are grounded. In this manner higher DC biases (100 V-700 V) are achieved at the wafer surface. As with reactive plasma etching the gas used to form the plasma is highly chemically reactive. The substrates are both normal to the gas flow and R.F. field which makes the movement of the ionized gas both directional and rapid. The higher operating voltages allow ions to impact the surface areas not protected by a photoresist. When an unreactive substrate is bombarded in such a manner this produces defects such as dangling bonds and dislocations in the substrate. Subsequently the substrate is much more reactive and susceptible to etching by the reactive chemical species in the plasma. This produces an energy-driven anisotropic etch profile, as illustrated in Figure F.6(B). By using lower operating pressures (10 mTorr-100 mTorr) in the system the mean free path of the impacting ions (how far on average a molecule moves before it undergoes another

collision) typically grows larger than the depth to be etched. As a result the horizontal surfaces are hit by the ions, and subsequently etched by the reactive radicals, more frequently than the sidewalls.^{336, 337}

F.1.12 High density plasmas: deep reactive ion etching (DRIE)

DRIE delivers an improvement on RIE by providing higher density plasmas for etching while operating at even lower pressures. A higher density plasma (ions per unit volume) is more reactive with a greater flux of ions and reactants at the substrates surface, and thus allows much faster etch rates. Just as important, the ability to operate at lower pressures (1 mTorr-10 m Torr) prevents any etching of the sidewalls by keeping the scattering of ions at an absolute minimum and also allows the reactants and reaction products to enter and exit the often high aspect ratio features much more readily. DRIE is therefore the most attractive etching technology when creating high aspect ratio micro-features.^{338, 339} A variety of systems for producing high density plasmas are available with the most common being inductively coupled plasma (ICP), electron cyclotron resonance (ECR), and magnetic zero resonance induction (MORI). The gas mixtures used to produce plasmas for DRIE of the nanopore structures fabricated and characterised in this thesis are summarised in Table F.1 Finally, a summary of the etch system trends is illustrated in Figure F.7.

Table F.1: The gas mixtures used to produce DRIE plasmas used in the fabrication of the nanopore structures characterised in this thesis.

Material being etched	Plasma chemistry
Si	Cl ₂ /HBr/O ₂
	CH ₂ F ₂ /CHF ₃
SiO ₂	CF ₄ /CHF ₃
	SF ₆ /HBr/O ₂
	5:1 buffered oxide etch (BOE) [5 NH ₄ F:1 HF]
Si ₃ N ₄	CH ₂ F ₂ /CHF ₃
	SF ₆ /HBr/O ₂

Figure F.7: Summary of the etch system trends.

F.2 Summary and discussion of the individual fabrication process steps

F.2.1 Master process flow for nanopore array fabrication (process run X-3858)

Legend

Silicon	Buried Oxide	P-type SOI
Isolation oxide	Resist	Pad-Oxide
Si_3N_4	PECVD-oxide hard mask	proTEK®B3

Figure F.8: Legend for each constituent layer deposited during the membrane fabrication process.

Flow (A): Si_3N_4 membrane with no trough

Flow (B): Si_3N_4 membrane with a trough

Flow (C): SOI membrane with no trough

Flow (D): SOI membrane with a trough

Figure F.9: Master process flow for nanopore array fabrication run X-3858.

F.2.2 Discussion of each step in the nanopore array fabrication

process flow

Four separate nanopore array membranes were fabricated, two in silicon nitride (flows (A) and (B)), and two in silicon-on-insulator (SOI) (flows (C) and (D)), for process run X-3858. Note that this X-(four digit code) is a system used by the Central Fabrication Facility (CFF) at the Tyndall National Institute to record and track each process flow they carry out. Of the two silicon nitride membranes one has the nanopore arrays patterned into a planar membrane (flow (A)) and the other has the nanopore arrays patterned into a recessed membrane, also known as an etched “trough” (flow (B)). Similarly, of the two SOI membranes one has the nanopore arrays patterned into a planar membrane (flow (C)) and the other has the nanopore arrays patterned into a recessed membrane (flow (D)). The four process flows are illustrated in Figure F.9 and described in detail below. Process run X-4093 was carried out in an identical manner to flow (A) of process run X-3858 when fabricating a second silicon nitride membrane with additional unique nanopore arrays patterned into the planar membrane.

The nanopore fabrication process required a number of key individuals at the Tyndall National Institute in order to be successfully realised. The input of each person is detailed below:

Micheál D. Scanlon & Damien W. M. Arrigan (Molecular Microsystems Group):

responsible for the design of each nanopore array in terms of the suitable geometric parameters (N_p , r_a , r_c , and r_r) required to support a variety of nanoITIES arrays that could be used to systematically study the effects of N_p , r_a , and r_c on the electrochemical responses for simple ion transfer.

Alan Blake & Ann-Marie Kelleher (CFF): Alan Blake was coordinator for the processes carried out in the CFF during process runs X-3858 and X-4093. In addition, Alan Blake & Ann-Marie Kelleher were responsible for all photolithographic steps (i.e. DRIE etching the nanopores, scribe lines, e-beam alignment marks, and troughs) and deposition steps (i.e. of oxides, nitrides, and resists) except of the proTEK[®]B3 layer.

Joe O' Brien (CFF): responsible for all wet etch processes and the deposition and removal of the proTEK[®]B3 layer.

Richard Murphy (CFF): responsible for using Computer Aided Design (CAD) to write all the necessary instructions for the positions of the scribe lines, identifier numbers, e-beam alignment marks, and the nanopore array patterns on the device wafers.

Brendan McCarthy (CFF): responsible for the exposure of the device wafers to the e-beam in order to write the nanopore array patterns in the resist.

Kenneth Rodgers (Microelectronics Applications Integration (MAI) group): responsible for the wafer dicing process.

F.2.2.1 Starting materials

- 1) The starting material for the silicon nitride membranes in flows (A) and (B) is a 525 μm thick p-type $\langle 100 \rangle$ silicon wafer. The starting material for the SOI membranes in flows (C) and (D) is a standard p-type SOI wafer consisting of a 525 μm thick p-type $\langle 100 \rangle$ silicon bulk “handle” layer, a 4000 Å buried oxide layer and a 3400 Å top silicon “device” or SOI layer.
- 2) A 5000 Å layer of oxide, known as an isolation oxide, is grown on the front and the back of the silicon wafer in flow (B) by thermal oxidation in the

furnace. This is the layer within which the trough will be etched on the front of the wafer. A 2850 Å layer of isolation oxide (X_{ox}) is grown on the front and the back of both SOI wafers (flows (c) and (d)) by thermal oxidation in the furnace. This causes the SOI layer to be thinned from 3400 Å to ~2150 Å. The ~1250 Å of Si consumed (X_s) corresponds to 44% of the thickness of the oxide formed, as per the equation $X_s = 0.44X_{ox}$ outlined in section F.1.3 and Figure F.2. Oncemore, the isolation oxide is the layer within which the trough will be etched on the front of the wafer in flow (D).

- 3) A 5:1 BOE (buffered oxide etch), which consists of ammonium fluoride / HF in a 5:1 ratio, is subsequently used to remove the front layer of isolation oxide, exposing the SOI layer, in flow (C). The isolation oxide has no purpose in flow (C) but will be the layer within which the trough will be etched in flow (D). Both SOI flows are fabricated concurrently. Therefore during the overlapping steps in the fabrication process (of which there are many) it is important that all the individual layers are of the same thickness to ensure uniform etching for both flows. In the case of flow (C) the SOI layer at 3400 Å would be considerably thicker than the ~2150 Å SOI layer in flow (D) and, thus, required thinning. An advantage of a BOE etch is a negligible silicon etch rate which prevents surface damage to the underlying SOI layer.

F.2.2.2 Photolithographic definition of scribe lines and e-beam alignment marks

- 4) A standard photoresist is spun on the front of each of the four wafers to a depth of 1.1 to 1.2 µm.
- 5) Individually, a mask is aligned with each wafer in order to pattern scribe lines and e-beam alignment marks in the resist via optical lithography.

- 6) In flow (A) the pattern for the scribe lines and e-beam alignment marks are transferred into the silicon wafer to a depth of $> 1.2 \mu\text{m}$ by plasma (dry) etching with a $\text{Cl}_2/\text{HBr}/\text{O}_2$ high density ICP (inductively coupled plasma), also known as a MORI etch. Multi-plasma etches are required in flows (B), (C), and (D) to pattern the scribe lines and e-beam alignment marks into the underlying layers. In flow (B) the entire 5000 \AA of isolation oxide is etched through using a $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2/\text{CHF}_3$ plasma etch and the bulk silicon layer is etched to a depth of 7000 \AA by switching to a $\text{Cl}_2/\text{HBr}/\text{O}_2$ high density ICP. In flow (C) the entirety of the $\sim 2150 \text{ \AA}$ SOI and 4000 \AA buried oxide layers are etched through with a $\text{Cl}_2/\text{HBr}/\text{O}_2$ high density ICP and a $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2/\text{CHF}_3$ plasma, respectively. The underlying bulk silicon is etched to a depth of 6000 \AA also with a $\text{Cl}_2/\text{HBr}/\text{O}_2$ high density ICP. Finally, in flow (D) the entirety of the 2850 \AA isolation oxide, $\sim 2150 \text{ \AA}$ SOI and 4000 \AA buried oxide layers are etched through with a $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2/\text{CHF}_3$ plasma followed by a $\text{Cl}_2/\text{HBr}/\text{O}_2$ high density ICP, and a $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2/\text{CHF}_3$ plasma etch, respectively. The underlying bulk silicon is etched to a depth of 3000 \AA also with a $\text{Cl}_2/\text{HBr}/\text{O}_2$ high density ICP.
- 7) The resist is removed on each wafer with a 100:1 HF clean (required after a MORI etch), followed by an O_2 plasma etch (known as “ashing”) and finally a sulphuric/peroxide wet etch.

F.2.2.3 Photolithographic definition of “troughs”

- 8) The next four steps of the fabrication process involve etching troughs in the isolation oxides of flows (B) and (D). In the first step of this process a

standard photoresist is spun on the front of the wafers in flows (B) and (D) to a depth of 1.1 to 1.2 μm .

- 9) A mask is aligned with the front of the wafers in flows (B) and (D) in order to pattern the resist with a square window, which will later be used to define the area of the “trough” on the front side of the wafers, by optical lithography.
- 10) The resist pattern is transferred into the underlying isolation oxide layer by plasma etching with CF_4/CHF_3 , the etch stopping with a “soft landing” on reaching the underlying silicon layer in flows (B) and (D). This is known as a MORI contact-etch and is based on using an etchant plasma with a higher proportion of fluorine present and a lower RF applied. Both of these factors result in a significant reduction in the etch rate allowing greater control over the process. The square windows on the front of the wafer have diameters of 20, 50, 100, 200, 350, and 500 μm and after etching through the isolation oxide will lead to corresponding troughs with 20, 50, 100, 200, 350, and 500 μm , respectively, diameters, as illustrated in Figure F.10.
- 11) The resist on the front of the wafers in flows (B) and (D) is removed with an O_2 plasma etch followed by a wet etch in sulphuric/peroxide.

Figure F.10: Optical micrographs of SiN nanoporous membranes, as designed in flow (B), with trough radii of 10, 25, 50, 100, 175 and 250 μm . The 100nm thick SiN membrane patterned with the nanopore arrays is yellow in colour, while the trough itself is purple. The surrounding orange colour is the SiN surface of the supporting Si/pad-oxide/SiN membrane.

F.2.2.4 Deposition of oxide and nitride functional layers

- 12) In each process flow a layer of pad-oxide is grown on the front and the back of the wafer to a thickness of 350 Å by thermal oxidation in the furnace. This layer of pad-oxide acts as a stress relief and is necessary to prevent cracking in the wafer.
- 13) The source of the stress in the wafer is the film of Si_3N_4 deposited with a thickness of 1000 Å by Low Pressure Chemical Vapour Deposition (LPCVD) on the front and the back of the wafer in each process flow. It is known that Si_3N_4 films deposited directly onto silicon substrates contain large intrinsic stresses.³⁴⁰⁻³⁴² When the structure undergoes selective oxidation (oxidation of the area of the silicon substrate that is not masked by the LPCVD layer of Si_3N_4) high density dislocations are induced in the silicon substrate along the edge of the oxidised area. This phenomenon arises when the high tensile stress

of the nitride film produces a force along the periphery of the local oxide that exceeds the yield stress for silicon.^{342, 343} The density of these dislocations (which are damaging to the substrate) can be reduced considerably by inserting a layer of so called “pad-oxide” between the silicon and Si₃N₄ layers. In essence the pad-oxide acts as a buffer reducing the force transmitted to the silicon by relieving the stress through the viscous flow of the oxide. The thicker this layer the less force transmitted to the silicon.^{342, 344, 345} However, the pad-oxide layer can also cause problems due the diffusion of oxygen and growth of SiO₂ under the edge of the Si₃N₄ film during thermal oxidation. This effect is known as the “bird’s beak” effect and is more prevalent at higher pad-oxide thicknesses but can be minimised by a thicker Si₃N₄ film. Therefore, optimization of the pad-oxide and nitride thicknesses are required in order to firstly minimise the effect of the “bird’s beak” while at the same time not creating dislocations in the silicon substrate.^{342, 344, 345}

14) At this stage of the fabrication process the Si₃N₄ layer on the front of the wafer is removed in a two step process from the SOI wafers (flows (C) and (D)). The nanopores will eventually be etched in the pad-oxide and SOI layers. A Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapour Deposition (PECVD) hard oxide mask is deposited on the back of the SOI wafers in flows (C) and (D) to a thickness of ~ 1 μm. This hard mask will provide protection to the layers on the back side of the wafer when the Si₃N₄ layer on the front side is wet etched.

15) A wet etch is carried out in hot phosphoric acid to remove the Si₃N₄ from the front side of the wafer in flows (C) and (D). When carrying out a wet etch it is extremely important to carefully select the masking material such that it is able to withstand the etch and protect the areas underneath. This is due to the

highly corrosive nature of the chemicals used for wet etching, for example hydrofluoric acid, nitric acid and in this case hot phosphoric acid, which would dissolve the majority of photoresists, see section F.1.5. Thus, in our fabrication process the “hard-mask” layer of PECVD deposited oxide ($\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ in thickness) is essential to protect the Si_3N_4 layer on the back of the wafer while the front Si_3N_4 is wet etched using highly corrosive hot phosphoric acid.

F.2.2.5 E-beam lithography followed by dry and wet etching to define nanopore arrays

- 16) A new layer of resist is spun on the front of the each of the four wafers to a depth of 2000 \AA . This resist is diluted 1:1 which ensures a thinner resist is deposited, a requirement when patterning nano-features. In essence the thinner the resist used, the smaller the features that can be defined using photolithography.
- 17) The nanopore array is patterned into this resist photolithographically on each of the four wafers using a JEOL e-beam. The e-beam was aligned to each wafer using e-beam alignment marks previously etched. The nanopore arrays consisted of patterns which were a combination of pores with varying pore radii (r_a) (in the range $25 \text{ nm} \geq r \leq 250 \text{ nm}$ for process run X-3858, and in the range $10 \text{ nm} \geq r \leq 50 \text{ nm}$ for process run X-4093), pore centre-to-centre separations (r_c) of either $5 r_a$ or $20 r_a$, and total pore numbers (N_p) of either 0, 1, 8, 23, 95, or 390 pores, see section F.4 for more details.
- 18) The nanopore patterns are transferred into the underlying Si_3N_4 layer in flows (A) and (B) using a $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2/\text{CHF}_3$ MORI plasma etch. The etch stops on the pad-oxide layer. However, some of the pad-oxide is also etched to a certain

extent. For the SOI wafers in flows (C) and (D) the nanopore patterns are transferred into the underlying pad oxide layer using a $\text{CH}_2\text{F}_2/\text{CHF}_3$ plasma, and then into the SOI layer using a $\text{Cl}_2/\text{HBr}/\text{O}_2$ etch, with the etch stopping on the buried oxide layer.

19) The resist on the SOI wafer in flows (C) and (D) is subsequently removed by a 100:1 HF clean (after MORI); followed by a short ash with O_2 plasma and a sulphuric/peroxide wet etch. The resist on the wafers in flows (A) and (B) is removed in an identical manner with the exception of using the 100:1 HF clean at the start.

F.2.2.6 Photolithographic etching of back opening

20) For each process flow a thick non-standard resist, up to 3 times thicker than normal at $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$, is spun on the front of the wafer and a standard resist, with a thickness of 1.1 to 1.2 μm , is spun on the back of the wafer.

21) Individually, the back of each wafer is aligned with a mask via double-sided alignment. Optical lithography is then used to pattern the back resist with a $1243 \mu\text{m}^2$ square window as defined by the mask, see Figure F.11 for an outline of the geometric parameters of the free-standing membrane arising from bulk etching the Si with this mask.

Figure F.11: Geometric parameters of a SiN nanoporous membrane, as fabricated in flow

(A).

22) This square window is etched into the immediate layers underneath the resist on each wafer. A PERIE nitride-on-oxide plasma etch is undertaken on each of the four wafers. This plasma consists of a SF₆/HBr/O₂ mixture with the etch stopping on the underlying pad-oxide layer in each case. This means for the wafers in flows (A) and (B) the Si₃N₄ layer is etched with the etch stopping on the underlying pad-oxide layer, while in flows (C) and (D) the underlying ~ 1 μm PECVD hard mask and Si₃N₄ underlayers are etched, stopping once more on the pad-oxide layer.

- 23) Both resists, on the front and the back of each wafer, are removed by ashing with O₂ plasma. Multiple ashes are required on the front side of the wafer owing to the thickness of the non-standard resist. A wet etch in sulphuric/peroxide follows the ashing.
- 24) The square window etched on the back of each wafer, in the Si₃N₄ layer for flows (A) and (B) and the ~ 1 μm PECVD hard mask and Si₃N₄ layers in flows (C) and (D), acts as a mask and the pattern is transferred into the underlying pad-oxide layer using a 10:1 HF wet etch.

F.2.2.7 proTEK[®]B3 coating

- 25) A layer of protective polymer, known as proTEK[®]B3, is spun on the front side of each wafer to a depth of 8 μm. This polymer, as its name suggests, protects the integrity of the fragile Si₃N₄ or SOI membrane during the dicing step towards the end of the fabrication procedure.

F.2.2.8 Wet etching of bulk Si and dry etching of buried oxide

- 26) By using the square window defined on the back of each wafer as a mask the bulk 525 μm <100> silicon layer is wet etched along the <100> crystal planes using KOH. In flows (A) and (B) the remaining exposed pad-oxide on the front of the wafer (having been previously thinned by the plasma etch that created the nanopores in step 18) is fully consumed at this point by the KOH wet etch. As a result in flow (A) this produces a 500 μm x 500 μm area of Si₃N₄ on the front of the wafer that is 1000 Å thick and contains the nanopore array. In flow (B) the area of the Si₃N₄ that is 1000 Å thick is determined by the size of the trough in the isolation oxide and varies from 20 x 20 μm² to 500

$x 500 \mu\text{m}^2$ in area. For the SOI wafers in flows (C) and (D) the etch stops on the buried oxide layer.

27) For flows (C) and (D) the exposed buried oxide on the front side of the wafer and the PECVD oxide hard mask are both removed with a 5:1 BOE etch. As a result in flow (C) this produces a $500 \mu\text{m} x 500 \mu\text{m}$ area of SOI ($\sim 2150 \text{ \AA}$ thick) and pad oxide on the front of the wafer that contains the nanopore array. The pad oxide layer will be considerably thinner than the original 350 \AA due to thinning by both the etch in hot phosphoric acid (in step 15) and the 5:1 BOE etch (in this step). In flow (D) the area of the SOI and pad oxide that is thinned to contain the nanopore arrays is determined by the size of the trough in the isolation oxide and varies from $20 x 20 \mu\text{m}^2$ to $500 x 500 \mu\text{m}^2$ in area.

F.2.2.9 Dicing and proTEK[®]B3 removal

28) Each of the four wafers is diced along the defined scribe lines using a DISCO Automatic Dicing Saw DAD 3350. The water pressure is reduced to ensure the fragile membranes survive. A tradeoff is achieved between a low enough water pressure such that the membranes remain intact, yet a high enough pressure to ensure that the dicing blade remains sufficiently cool so as not to shatter. The sticky blue film used during the dicing process and attached to the back of the wafer was removed immediately on completing the dicing process. This was to ensure that the blue film did not become permanently attached to the fragile membrane. The blue film was removed using a hot plate that also had the functionality of a weak vacuum. The heat from the hot-plate loosened the adhesive attaching the blue film to the wafer, while the weak vacuum

applied held the blue film in place and made lifting off the individual chips easy to achieve.

- 29) The 4 inch wafers are now successfully diced into individual 5 x 5 mm chips, each with a thinned nanoporous membrane in the centre.
- 30) The final step of the fabrication process is to remove the proTEK[®]B3 polymer from each chip. The 5 x 5 mm chip is first dipped in a beaker of patented proTEK[®]B3 Remover 100 solution at room temperature for 5 minutes. The chip is then transferred to a second beaker also containing proTEK[®]B3 Remover 100 solution and left for a further 5 minutes at room temperature. The proTEK[®]B3 will become detached from the surface of the chip in this time and float away. Then the chip is transferred to a beaker of isopropanol (IPA) for 5 minutes to remove any proTEK[®]B3, proTEK[®]B3 Remover 100, or other debris still clinging to the surface. Finally, the chip is dipped in a fresh beaker of IPA (free of any proTEK[®]B3 or proTEK[®]B3 Remover 100) and remains until the IPA evaporates fully. The chips are cleaned in O₂ plasma prior to use.

F.3 Fabrication survival statistics of the nanoporous membranes for process flow X-3858

The percentage membrane survival for each of the four fabrication process flows in run X-3858 is listed in Table F.2, and the percentage membrane survival based on the square “trough” diameter for the SiN and SOI (in flows (B) and (D), respectively) membranes with “troughs” is listed in Table F.3.

Table F.2: Overall statistics of membrane survival for each of the four fabrication process flows.

Membrane material	With “trough”	Without “trough”	Total no. of membranes fabricated	% broken
SiN		X	188	(12/188) = 6.4%
	X		196	(21/196) = 10.7%
SOI		X	188	(188/188) = 100 %-
	X		196	(196/196) = 100 %-

Table F.3: Comparison of the membrane survival percentages based on the square “trough” diameter for SiN and SOI membranes with “troughs”.

Membrane material	Square trough diameter (μm)	Total no. of membranes fabricated	% broken
SiN (with “trough”)	20	25	(1/25) = 4.0%
	50	34	(1/34) = 2.9%
	100	36	(4/36) = 11.1%
	200	37	(2/37) = 5.4%
	350	37	(5/37) = 13.5%
	500	27	(8/27) = 29.6%
SOI (with “trough”)	20	25	(25/25) = 100 %
	50	34	(34/34) = 100 %
	100	36	(36/36) = 100 %
	200	37	(37/37) = 100 %
	350	37	(37/37) = 100 %
	500	27	(27/27) = 100 %

Clearly, based on the data presented in Tables F.2 and F.3, it is clear that silicon nitride is the more suitable material for extremely thin membranes, while silicon-on-insulator membranes, while technically intact, are shattered and damaged in the extreme. An SEM of the thinned SOI-based membrane is shown in Figure F.12. The surface is damaged to the extent that the nanopore arrays could not be located and identified.

Overall the SiN membrane with no troughs seems to have a slightly greater survival rate than the SiN membrane with troughs. The SiN membranes with the smallest 100 nm thick membranes at the bottom of the etched troughs (i.e. 20 x 20 and 50 x 50 μm^2

in area) also had high survival rates in comparison with the larger 100 nm thick membranes at the bottom of the etched troughs (i.e. 350×350 and $500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}^2$ in area). SEM images and the geometric data acquired from the SEM images for a broad selection of nanopore array designs created in the SiN membranes with no troughs (flow (A) in Figure F.9) are presented in section F.5.

Figure F.12: SEM images of the thinned SOI membrane that theoretically was to contain the nanopore arrays.

F.4 Summary of the nanopore array designs patterned by e-beam lithography

The nanopore arrays consisted of patterns which were a combination of pores with varying pore radii (r_a) (in the range $25 \text{ nm} \geq r_a \leq 250 \text{ nm}$ for process run X-3858, and in the range $10 \text{ nm} \geq r_a \leq 50 \text{ nm}$ for process run X-4093), pore centre-to-centre separations (r_c) of either $5r_a$ or $20r_a$, and total pore numbers (N_p) of either 0, 1, 8, 23, 95, or 390 pores. In total 82 different e-beam designs (between process runs X-3858 and X-4093) were written and are summarised in Table F.4 and F.5. All of the nanopore arrays were patterned using a hexagonal closed packing (HCP) arrangement, as illustrated in Figure F.13.

Figure F.13: Hexagonal close packing (HCP) arrangement of the nanopore arrays patterned using e-beam lithography.

For process run X-3858 the area of membrane available for patterning was greatest for flows (A) and (C), with no troughs, at $500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}^2$. This maximum area was also available in flows (B) and (D) for those arrays containing the maximum trough area. Therefore, some nanopore array patterns, with the larger pores and the greater pore centre-to-centre distances cover an area in excess of the total membrane area available to be patterned. This applies in particular to the “troughed” membrane designs with the smallest ($20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$ and $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$) thinned SiN or SOI areas. An added limitation when choosing which e-beam designs to pattern on the SiN and SOI membranes with troughs (flows (B) and (C)) was the fact that only 200 chips can fit on a single 4 inch wafer. Therefore it was decided that array designs 7 through to the 16 would be omitted. These arrays contained 8 pores with varying pore sizes and pore centre-to-centre spacing. The chosen e-beam designs patterned on the SiN and SOI membranes with troughs (flows (B) and (D)) are summarised in Table F.6.

Table F.4: Summary of nanopore array e-beam designs for process run X-3858.

Design no.	Pore radius, r_a / nm	Pore centre-to-centre separation, (as a multiple of the radius)	Pore centre-to-centre separation, r_c / nm	Distance between 2 consecutive rows, r_r / nm	No. of rows	No. of columns	Total no. of pores, N_p
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	25	0	0	0	1	1	1
3	50	0	0	0	1	1	1
4	75	0	0	0	1	1	1
5	125	0	0	0	1	1	1
6	250	0	0	0	1	1	1
7	25	$5r_a$	125	108	3	3	8
8	50	$5r_a$	250	216	3	3	8
9	75	$5r_a$	375	325	3	3	8
10	125	$5r_a$	625	541	3	3	8
11	250	$5r_a$	1250	1082	3	3	8
12	25	$20r_a$	500	433	3	3	8
13	50	$20r_a$	1000	866	3	3	8
14	75	$20r_a$	1500	1299	3	3	8
15	125	$20r_a$	2500	2165	3	3	8
16	250	$20r_a$	5000	4330	3	3	8
17	25	$5r_a$	125	108	5	5	23
18	50	$5r_a$	250	216	5	5	23
19	75	$5r_a$	375	325	5	5	23
20	125	$5r_a$	625	541	5	5	23
21	250	$5r_a$	1250	1082	5	5	23
22	25	$20r_a$	500	433	5	5	23
23	50	$20r_a$	1000	866	5	5	23
24	75	$20r_a$	1500	1299	5	5	23
25	125	$20r_a$	2500	2165	5	5	23
26	250	$20r_a$	5000	4330	5	5	23
27	25	$5r_a$	125	108	10	10	95
28	50	$5r_a$	250	216	10	10	95
29	75	$5r_a$	375	325	10	10	95
30	125	$5r_a$	625	541	10	10	95
31	250	$5r_a$	1250	1082	10	10	95
32	25	$20r_a$	500	433	10	10	95
33	50	$20r_a$	1000	866	10	10	95
34	75	$20r_a$	1500	1299	10	10	95
35	125	$20r_a$	2500	2165	10	10	95
36	250	$20r_a$	5000	4330	10	10	95
37	25	$5r_a$	125	108	20	20	390
38	50	$5r_a$	250	216	20	20	390
39	75	$5r_a$	375	325	20	20	390
40	125	$5r_a$	625	541	20	20	390
41	250	$5r_a$	1250	1082	20	20	390
42	25	$20r_a$	500	433	20	20	390
43	50	$20r_a$	1000	866	20	20	390
44	75	$20r_a$	1500	1299	20	20	390
45	125	$20r_a$	2500	2.65	20	20	390
46	250	$20r_a$	5000	4330	20	20	390

Table F.5: Summary of nanopore array e-beam designs for process run X-4093.

Design no.	Pore radius, r_a / nm	Pore centre-to-centre separation, (as a multiple of the radius)	Pore centre-to-centre separation, r_c / nm	Distance between 2 consecutive rows, r_r / nm	No. of rows	No. of columns	Total no. of pores, N_p
47	10	0	0	0	1	1	1
48	15	0	0	0	1	1	1
49	20	0	0	0	1	1	1
50	25	0	0	0	1	1	1
51	30	0	0	0	1	1	1
52	35	0	0	0	1	1	1
53	40	0	0	0	1	1	1
54	45	0	0	0	1	1	1
55	50	0	0	0	1	1	1
56	10	$20r_a$	200	173	5	5	23
57	15	$20r_a$	300	260	5	5	23
58	20	$20r_a$	400	346	5	5	23
59	25	$20r_a$	500	433	5	5	23
60	30	$20r_a$	600	520	5	5	23
61	35	$20r_a$	700	606	5	5	23
62	40	$20r_a$	800	693	5	5	23
63	45	$20r_a$	900	779	5	5	23
64	50	$20r_a$	1000	866	5	5	23
65	10	$20r_a$	200	173	10	10	95
66	15	$20r_a$	300	260	10	10	95
67	20	$20r_a$	400	346	10	10	95
68	25	$20r_a$	500	433	10	10	95
69	30	$20r_a$	600	520	10	10	95
70	35	$20r_a$	700	606	10	10	95
71	40	$20r_a$	800	693	10	10	95
72	45	$20r_a$	900	779	10	10	95
73	50	$20r_a$	1000	866	10	10	95
74	10	$20r_a$	200	173	20	20	390
75	15	$20r_a$	300	260	20	20	390
76	20	$20r_a$	400	346	20	20	390
77	25	$20r_a$	500	433	20	20	390
78	30	$20r_a$	600	520	20	20	390
79	35	$20r_a$	700	606	20	20	390
80	40	$20r_a$	800	693	20	20	390
81	45	$20r_a$	900	779	20	20	390
82	50	$20r_a$	1000	866	20	20	390

Table F.6: Appropriate nanopore array designs chosen for each trough area in process run X-3858.

Design no.	20 x 20 μm trough area	50 x 50 μm trough area	100 x 100 μm trough area	200 x 200 μm trough area	350 x 350 μm trough area	500 x 500 μm trough area
1	X	X	X	X	X	X
2	X	X	X	X	X	X
3	X	X	X	X	X	X
4	X	X	X	X	X	X
5	X	X	X	X	X	X
6	X	X	X	X	X	X
7						
8						
9						
10						
11						
12						
13						
14						
15						
16						
17	X	X	X	X	X	
18	X	X	X	X	X	
19	X	X	X	X	X	
20	X	X	X	X	X	
21	X	X	X	X	X	
22	X	X	X	X	X	
23	X	X	X	X	X	
24	X	X	X	X	X	
25	X	X	X	X	X	
26		X	X	X	X	
27	X	X	X	X	X	X
28	X	X	X	X	X	X
29	X	X	X	X	X	X
30	X	X	X	X	X	X
31		X	X	X	X	X
32	X	X	X	X	X	X
33	X	X	X	X	X	X
34		X	X	X	X	X
35		X	X	X	X	X
36			X	X	X	X
37	X	X	X	X	X	X
38	X	X	X	X	X	X
39	X	X	X	X	X	X
40		X	X	X	X	X
41		X	X	X	X	X
42		X	X	X	X	X
43		X	X	X	X	X
44		X	X	X	X	X
45			X	X	X	X
46				X	X	X

F.5 SEM characterisation of the nanopore arrays

The SEM images were taken by Daniela Iacopino and Aidan Quinn (Nanotechnology group (NTG)) using a field emission scanning electron microscope (6700F SEM, JEOL U.K., Ltd.) operated at beam voltages of between 3 kV and 7.5 kV. The complete set of geometric parameters (measured using ImageJ software) for each nanopore array design SEM-ed are summarised in Table F.7 and the SEM images are shown in Figures F.14 to F.18.

Table F.7: Summary of the geometric parameters measured from SEM data for a selection of nanopore array designs. n = no. of separate measurements acquired for each of the parameters in a nanopore array in order to determine the SEM data average values. The resolution of the SEM images is ± 5 nm.

Design no.	Total no. pores, N_p	n	Pore diameter, D_p / nm		Pore centre-to-centre distance r_c / nm		Distance between 2 consecutive rows r_r / nm	
			SEM data average	Theory	SEM data average	Theory	SEM data average	Theory
5	1	1	240 (± 5)	250	-	-	-	-
15	8	6	245 (± 5)	250	2420 (± 25)	2500	2155 (± 30)	2165
25	23	6	245 (± 5)	250	2445 (± 0)	2500	2150 (± 10)	2165
27	95	6	50 (± 5)	50	125 (± 5)	125	110 (± 5)	108
28	95	6	90 (± 5)	100	250 (± 5)	250	215 (± 5)	216
29	95	6	145 (± 5)	150	375 (± 5)	375	325 (± 5)	325
30	95	6	240 (± 5)	250	630 (± 10)	625	540 (± 10)	541
31	95	6	450 (± 10)	500	1240 (± 25)	1250	1050 (± 20)	1082
32	95	6	50 (± 5)	50	495 (± 5)	500	430 (± 5)	433
34	95	6	130 (± 5)	150	1455 (± 10)	1500	1275 (± 15)	1299
35	95	6	250 (± 5)	250	2445 (± 20)	2500	2160 (± 20)	2165
36	95	6	460 (± 10)	500	4905 (± 20)	5000	4335 (± 45)	4330
37	390	6	55 (± 5)	50	135 (± 5)	125	110 (± 5)	108
38	390	6	80 (± 5)	100	245 (± 5)	250	215 (± 5)	216
40	390	6	240 (± 5)	250	625 (± 5)	625	545 (± 5)	541
41	390	6	475 (± 10)	500	1240 (± 5)	1250	1070 (± 25)	1082
44	390	6	135 (± 5)	150	1460 (± 15)	1500	1300 (± 5)	1299
45	390	6	230 (± 5)	250	2475 (± 15)	2500	2160 (± 25)	2165
46	390	6	485 (± 10)	500	4805 (± 20)	5000	4275 (± 45)	4330
55	1	1	130 (± 5)	100	-	-	-	-
64	23	6	90 (± 5)	100	915 (± 15)	1000	795 (± 10)	866
73	95	6	100 (± 5)	100	1040 (± 10)	1000	860 (± 10)	866
82	390	6	105 (± 5)	100	1090 (± 5)	1000	865 (± 5)	866

Design 5

Design 15

Design 25

Design 27

Design 28

Figure F.14: SEM images of nanopore array designs 5, 15, 25, 27, and 28.

Design 29

Design 30

Design 31

Design 32

Design 34

Figure F.15: SEM images of nanopore array designs 29, 30, 31, 32, and 34.

Design 35

Design 36

Design 37

Design 38

Design 40

Figure F.16: SEM images of nanopore array designs 35, 36, 37, 38, and 40.

Design 41

Design 44

Design 45

Design 46

Design 55

Figure F.17: SEM images of nanopore array designs 41, 44, 45, 46, and 55.

Design 64

Design 73

Design 82

Figure F.18: SEM images of nanopore array designs 64, 73, and 82.

Curriculum Vitae

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DOB: February 9th, 1984

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Education

PhD: Electrochemical processes of bio-analytical importance at micro- and nano- liquid | liquid interfaces, (2005-2009).

Molecular microsystems, Life Sciences Interface (LSI) group, Tyndall National Institute, University College Cork (U.C.C.), Cork, Ireland.

Awarded EMBARK Postgraduate Scholarship by the Irish Research Council for Science, Engineering and Technology, 2005-2009.

Awarded the Ronald-Belcher lectureship award from the Royal Society of Chemistry, 2009.

Bachelor of Science in Chemistry (BSc. Chem.) (2001-2005).

University College Cork (U.C.C.), Cork, Ireland.

- Awarded **1st class honours**, position 1 of 28 in my graduation year.
- Awarded “The Reilly Prize, 2006”. This award is presented to the candidate who obtains first place in the final year chemistry examinations and has obtained 1st class honours.
- Awarded “Title of College Scholar” in each of my 4 years as an undergraduate based on end-of-term examination results.
- This undergraduate course provided me with extensive theoretical and laboratory-based practical knowledge of organic & pharmaceutical chemistry, inorganic chemistry, analytical chemistry, physical chemistry and spectroscopy. As elective courses I primarily chose modules detailing peptide/protein structure & function and pharmaceutical toxicology.
- **Final year projects 2004/2005:** The first was an organic synthesis project. The synthesis and application of the Burgess reagent was explored. The second was an electrochemistry project, carried out under the supervision of Dr. Damien W. M. Arrigan, involving the voltammetric characterisation of dendrimers and chromium (VI) at the polarised liquid | liquid interface.
- **Summer internship project June – September 2004:** The voltammetric study of silver electro-deposition at bare and modified gold electrodes. Completed under the supervision of Dr. Grégoire Herzog and Dr. Damien W. M. Arrigan in the Life Sciences Interface (LSI) group, the Tyndall National Institute..

Other professional collaborations:

National Access Project (NAP) 136: Improving the attachment efficiency and stability of DNA probes on gold electrodes.

Collaboration between the Life Sciences Interface (LSI) group, Tyndall National Institute and the CAMbio research group, Letterkenny Institute of Technology (LYIT), 2008-2009.

This project aimed to develop immobilised electrochemical hairpin DNA sensors with improved standards in probe attachment stability and reproducibility than currently available. Reductive desorption techniques were utilised to determine the attachment stability and surface coverages of thiolated probes on gold disc electrodes. Comparative data was compiled at commercial and in-house Tyndall fabricated gold electrodes for probe attachment using thiolated, 1-disulphide, 2-disulphide and 3-disulphide modified DNA probes.

Proof-of-concept experiments: integrating nanopore arrays into a microfluidic chip setup.

Collaboration between the Life Sciences Interface (LSI) group, Tyndall National Institute and the Bohn research group, Notre Dame University, Indiana, 2008.

As part of this collaboration I traveled to Notre Dame University in late October – early November 2008 to complete some early proof of concept work on incorporating a Tyndall fabricated silicon nitride nanopore array onto PDMS microchannels. Fluroscein dye was successfully injected through the nanopores and imaged moving down the microchannel.

Teaching Experience

Undergraduate Project Supervision

2007: An SFI UREKA (Science Foundation Ireland Undergraduate Research Experience & Knowledge Award) (UPCRO site) student, University College Cork, Ireland. 12 week project titled: Electrochemical protein diagnostic devices.

2008: A 4th year Chemistry student, University College Cork. Undergraduate 14 week final year project titled: Biomolecular detection at soft interfaces.

Publications

1. **M.D. Scanlon**, A. Berduque, J. Strutwolf, D.W.M. Arrigan, Flow-injection amperometry at microfabricated silicon-based μ -liquid-liquid interface arrays, *Electrochimica Acta*, **2009**, in press. DOI: 10.1016/j.electacta.2008.12.014
2. **M.D. Scanlon**, E. Jennings, D.W.M. Arrigan, Electrochemical behaviour of hen-egg-white lysozyme at the polarized water | 1,2-dichloroethane interface. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, **2009**, 11, 2272-2280.
3. J. Strutwolf, **M.D. Scanlon**, D.W.M. Arrigan, Electrochemical ion transfer across liquid/liquid interfaces confined within solid-state micropore arrays – simulations and experiments. *Analyst*, **2009**, 134, 148-158.

4. **M.D. Scanlon**, G. Herzog, D.W.M. Arrigan, Electrochemical detection of oligopeptides at silicon-fabricated micro-liquid | liquid interfaces. *Analytical Chemistry*, **2008**, 80, 5743-5749.
5. A. Berduque, **M.D. Scanlon**, C.J. Collins, D.W.M. Arrigan, Electrochemistry of non-redox-active poly(propylenimine) and poly(amidoamine) dendrimers at liquid-liquid interfaces. *Langmuir*, **2007**, 23, 7356-7364.
6. A.M. O'Mahony, **M.D. Scanlon**, A. Berduque, V. Beni, D.W.M. Arrigan, E. Faggi, A. Bencini, Voltammetry of chromium (VI) at the liquid | liquid interface. *Electrochemistry Communications*, **2005**, 7, 976-982.

Oral Presentations

1. **M.D. Scanlon**. Electrochemical detection of lysozyme at the polarised water | 1,2-dichloroethane interface. Electrochem '08, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, U.K., 15-17 September 2008.

Poster Presentations

1. J. Strutwolf, **M. D. Scanlon**, D. W. M. Arrigan. Liquid/liquid electrochemistry at microinterfaces: Charge transfer through solid-state micro- and nanopore arrays. Electrochem '08, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, U.K., 15-17 September 2008.
2. J. Strutwolf, **M.D. Scanlon**, G. Herzog, C.J. Collins, D.W.M. Arrigan. An electrochemical approach to investigate interfacial transfer phenomena at microscopic liquid-liquid interfaces. Nano2Life Scientific Meeting, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, 25-27 June 2008.
3. **M.D. Scanlon**, D.W.M. Arrigan. Towards nanoscale interfaces for biomolecular detection, Conference in honour of Philip N. Bartlett, University of Southampton, Southampton, U.K., 5-6 April 2008.
4. F. Kivlehan, Y.H. Lanyon, **M.D. Scanlon**, G. Herzog, D.W.M. Arrigan. Study of biomolecules at the liquid-liquid interface. Nano2Life Scientific Meeting, Le Palladium de Champéry, Switzerland, 9-11 January 2008.
5. **M.D. Scanlon**, D.W.M. Arrigan. Towards nanoscale interfaces for biomolecular detection. Nano2Life Scientific Meeting, University of Lund, Lund, Sweden, 22-24 October 2007. (**Awarded 2nd prize in the poster competition**)
6. **M.D. Scanlon**, G. Herzog, D.W.M. Arrigan. Detection of model ions and oligopeptides at a gellified micro-liquid | liquid interface. Royal Society of Chemistry Analytical Research Forum, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, U.K., 16-18 July 2007.
7. **M.D. Scanlon**, G. Herzog, D.W.M. Arrigan. Electrodeposition of silver at disorganised monolayer modified gold electrodes. 57th Annual Meeting of the International Society of Electrochemistry, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, U.K., 2006, 27 August-1 September 2006.
8. **M.D. Scanlon**, G. Herzog, D.W.M. Arrigan. Silver electrodeposition at disorganised monolayer modified gold electrodes. Royal Society of Chemistry Analytical Research Forum, University College Cork, Cork, Ireland, 17-19 July 2006.

9. **M.D. Scanlon**, G. Herzog, D.W.M. Arrigan. Silver electrodeposition at disorganised monolayer modified gold electrodes. 4th Biennial Conference of Analytical Sciences, Dublin Institute of Technology, Dublin, Ireland, 11-12 April 2006.
10. **M.D. Scanlon**, G. Herzog, D.W.M. Arrigan. Study of silver electrodeposition at bare and modified gold electrodes. 3rd Biennial Conference of Analytical Sciences, University College Cork, Cork, Ireland, 9-10 September 2004.

Professional Skills

Chemistry skills:

Electrochemistry (CV, LSV, DPV, SWV, stripping techniques, chronoamperometry), organic synthesis, NMR, IR, surface contact angle measurements, microfabrication technologies.

Training Courses:

May 2007: Labs-on-Chip Technologies: Basics and Applications, Fondation Suisse de la Recherche en Microtechnique, Neuchâtel, Switzerland.

Society Membership:

Member of the Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC).

Member of the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland (ICI).

Member of the International Society of Electrochemistry (ISE).

References

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